

Single Digit Representations of Natural Numbers From 1 to 5000

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Abstract

*There are different ways of representing natural numbers, such as writing in terms of 1 to 9 or 9 to 1, writing in terms of single letter, single digit, flexible power, etc. These types of representations we call as **crazy representations**. This paper extends the authors previous work [8] on representation of natural numbers in terms of **single digit**. The previous work is upto 1000. This paper bring numbers 1 to 5000 in terms of each digit. The total work up to 20000 numbers divided in four parts. For other parts refer [9, 10, 11].*

Contents

1 Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers	1
1.1 First Type: Increasing and Decreasing	2
1.2 Second Type: Flexible Power Representations	2
1.2.1 Unequal String Lengths	2
1.2.2 Equal String Lengths	3
1.3 Third Way: Single Digit Representations	4
1.4 Forth Way: Single Letter Representations	5
1.5 Running Expressions	6
1.5.1 Running Expressions with Fibonacci Sequence	7
1.5.2 Running Expressions with Triangular Numbers	8
2 Single Digit Representations From 1 to 20000	9
2.1 Single Digit Representation: 1-5000	10

1 Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers

In this section, we shall write different ways of writing natural numbers. These representations are divided in four different types.

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1.1 First Type: Increasing and Decreasing

In 2014, author [1] wrote natural numbers in increasing and decreasing orders of 1 to 9 and 9 to 1. See examples below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{100} &:= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 \times 9 = 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{101} &:= 1 + 2 + 34 + 5 + 6 \times 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{102} &:= 12 + 3 \times 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4^3 + 2 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{103} &:= 1 \times 2 \times 34 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5 \times 4 + 3 + 21 \\
 \mathbf{104} &:= 1 + 23 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 65 + 4 \times 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{105} &:= 1 + 2 \times 3 \times 4 + 56 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{106} &:= 12 + 3 + 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{107} &:= 1 \times 23 + 4 + 56 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 76 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{108} &:= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 78 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 76 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1.
 \end{aligned}$$

See more examples,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{999} &:= 12 \times 3 \times (4 + 5) + (67 + 8) \times 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 654 + 321. \\
 \mathbf{2535} &:= 1 + 2345 + (6 + 7 + 8) \times 9 = 9 + 87 \times (6 + 5 \times 4 + 3) + 2 + 1. \\
 \mathbf{2607} &:= 123 \times 4 \times 5 + 6 + (7 + 8) \times 9 = 987 + 6 \times 54 \times (3 + 2) \times 1. \\
 \mathbf{10958} &:= 12 \times 3 + \sqrt{4} + 5! \times (67 + 8 \times \sqrt{9}) = (9 + 8 \times 7 \times 65 + 4) \times 3 - 2 + 1. \\
 \mathbf{11807} &:= 1 \times 234 \times (5 + 6 \times 7) + 89 = -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3)^2 \times 1.
 \end{aligned}$$

We observe that the number 10958 is the only number among 0 to 11111, where we need extra operations, such as **square-root**, **factorial**, etc. to write in increasing case. For more details refer author's web-site link [5]. Extension of numbers from 11112 to 30000 refer [2, 3, 4].

1.2 Second Type: Flexible Power Representations

Let us consider two numbers, 1 and 2. Using the idea of power and the operations of *addition* and *subtraction*, we can write following 3 numbers in terms of 1 and 2, as $1 = -1^2 + 2^1$, $3 = 1^2 + 2^1$ and $5 = 1^1 + 2^2$. In this situation, we observe that *bases* and *exponents* are of same digits. Permutations of exponent values helps in bringing different numbers. In case of repeated values, for example, $3 = 1^2 + 2^1 = -1^1 + 2^2$, only possibilities is considered. There is only one number having single digit, i.e., $1 = 1^1$. For simplicity, let us represent the above procedure as $(1, 2)^{(1, 2)}$, resulting in three possible values. The above procedure is with two digits. Instead having two digits, we can work with two letters, such as,

$$(a, b)^{(a, b)}, \dots, (a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i)^{(a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i)},$$

where $a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}$, all distinct.

1.2.1 Unequal String Lengths

$$100 := 2^6 + 6^2$$

$$101 := 1^1 + 2^6 + 6^2$$

$$102 := -2^5 + 3^2 + 5^3$$

$$103 := 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^3$$

$$104 := -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^2$$

$$105 := 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^2$$

$$106 := 2^7 + 3^3 - 7^2$$

$$107 := -1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 7^1$$

$$108 := 1^7 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 7^1$$

$$109 := 1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 7^1$$

$$110 := 1^9 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 9^1$$

$$111 := -1^3 + 2^7 - 3^2 - 7^1$$

$$112 := 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^3$$

$$113 := -1^5 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^3$$

$$114 := -2^2 + 3^5 - 5^3$$

$$115 := 1^5 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^3$$

$$116 := 2^2 + 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^3$$

$$117 := -1^1 + 3^5 - 5^3$$

$$118 := 3^5 - 5^3$$

$$119 := 1^1 + 3^5 - 5^3.$$

See more examples,

$$638 := -1^5 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^4$$

$$666 := -2^5 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4$$

$$786 := -1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1$$

$$1933 := -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 7^1$$

$$1934 := 2^9 + 3^6 - 6^2 + 9^3$$

$$3098 := -3^3 + 5^5$$

$$2280 := -1^1 - 2^6 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 6^4$$

$$6922 := -3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5$$

$$9711 := 1^3 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 8^1$$

$$9777 := 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$$

$$11110 := 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^3$$

$$11111 := -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 8^4.$$

The whole work is from 1 to 11111. For details refer [6].

1.2.2 Equal String Lengths

Based on second type still we can write natural numbers in a sequential way with uniform representations. Instead working with unequal strings as of previous section, here we worked with equal string using the digits 0 to 9, i.e., using all the 10 digits, {0,1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9}. The results obtained are symmetric, i.e., writing in 0 to 9 or 9 to 0, the resulting number is same. See some examples below,

$$201 := 0^3 + 1^9 + 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^8 + 5^1 + 6^6 + 7^5 + 8^2 + 9^0$$

$$202 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^7 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 7^2 + 8^1 + 9^4$$

$$203 := 0^3 - 1^9 + 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^8 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 7^5 + 8^2 + 9^1$$

$$204 := 0^8 + 1^9 + 2^5 + 3^7 - 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^4 + 7^2 + 8^0 + 9^3$$

$$205 := 0^3 + 1^9 + 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^8 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 7^5 + 8^2 + 9^1$$

$$206 := 0^7 - 1^9 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^4 + 8^0 + 9^2$$

$$207 := 0^8 + 1^9 + 2^5 + 3^7 - 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^4 + 7^2 + 8^1 + 9^3$$

$$208 := 0^7 + 1^9 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^4 + 8^0 + 9^2$$

$$209 := 0^7 - 1^9 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^3 + 7^4 + 8^1 + 9^2$$

$$210 := 0^5 - 1^7 - 2^8 - 3^9 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^3 + 8^4 + 9^2$$

$$211 := 0^7 + 1^9 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^3 + 7^4 + 8^1 + 9^2$$

$$212 := 0^5 + 1^7 - 2^8 - 3^9 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^3 + 8^4 + 9^2$$

$$213 := 0^5 + 1^8 - 2^7 - 3^9 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^0 + 8^4 + 9^2$$

$$214 := 0^5 + 1^7 - 2^8 - 3^9 + 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 + 8^4 + 9^2$$

$$215 := 0^5 + 1^9 + 2^8 + 3^7 - 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^4 + 7^2 + 8^3 + 9^1$$

$$216 := 0^1 - 1^7 + 2^8 - 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^4 + 8^3 + 9^2$$

$$217 := 0^7 - 1^9 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^3 + 7^4 + 8^1 + 9^0$$

$$218 := 0^1 + 1^7 + 2^8 - 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^4 + 8^3 + 9^2$$

$$219 := 0^7 + 1^9 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^3 + 7^4 + 8^1 + 9^0$$

$$220 := 0^7 + 1^9 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^3 + 7^4 + 8^0 + 9^1.$$

Below are more examples,

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{11080} &:= 0^8 + 1^9 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^0 + 7^1 + 8^3 + 9^4 \\
\mathbf{11081} &:= 0^8 - 1^9 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^0 + 8^2 + 9^3 \\
\mathbf{11082} &:= 0^8 + 1^9 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^3 + 8^0 + 9^2 \\
\mathbf{11083} &:= 0^8 + 1^9 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^0 + 8^2 + 9^3 \\
\mathbf{11084} &:= 0^7 + 1^9 + 2^8 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^0 + 7^3 + 8^2 + 9^4 \\
\mathbf{11085} &:= 0^8 + 1^9 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^1 + 8^2 + 9^3 \\
\mathbf{11086} &:= 0^7 + 1^9 + 2^8 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 7^3 + 8^2 + 9^4 \\
\mathbf{11087} &:= 0^6 + 1^9 - 2^8 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^0 + 8^1 + 9^3.
\end{aligned}$$

The whole work is from 1 to 11111. For details refer [7].

Analysing the procedures given in sections 1.1 and 1.2, we observe that in section 1.1, all the 9 digits are used in increasing and decreasing ways to bring natural numbers, where each digit appears only once. In this case, the operations used are, **addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, potentiation, factorial** and **square-root**. The section 1.2 works with representations of natural numbers written in a way that we use each digit twice, where **bases** and **exponents** are of same digits with different permutations. Subsection 1.2.1 choose the digits from 1 to 9, according to necessity, while subsection 1.2.2 works with all the 10 digits, i.e., 0 to 9, along with the operations of **addition** and **subtraction**.

1.3 Third Way: Single Digit Representations

In [1], author wrote natural numbers 1 to 1000 using single digit in each case. For example,

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{717} &:= (1+1)^{11} - 11^{(1+1+1)} \\
&:= 22^2 + 222 + 22/2 \\
&:= 3^{(3+3)} - 3 - 3 \times 3 \\
&:= 4 \times (4 \times 44 + 4) - 4 + 4/4 \\
&:= (55 \times (55 + 5 + 5) + 5 + 5)/5 \\
&:= (6 \times 6 / (6 + 6))^6 - 6 - 6 \\
&:= 777 - 7 \times 7 - 77/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 88 + (88 + 8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - (99 + 9)/9.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{786} &:= ((1+1+1)^{(1+1+1)} + 1)^{(1+1)} + 1 + 1 \\
&:= (22 + 2 + 2 + 2)^2 + 2 \\
&:= 33 \times (3^3 - 3) - 3 - 3 \\
&:= 4 \times (4 \times (44 + 4) + 4) + (4 + 4)/4 \\
&:= 5 + (5^5 - 5/5)/(5 - 5/5) \\
&:= 66 \times (6 + 6) - 6 \\
&:= 777 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 \times (88 + 8) + 8 + (88 - 8)/8 \\
&:= 9 \times 99 - 99 - 9 + (9 + 9 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{995} &:= (11 - 1)^{(1+1+1)} - (11 - 1)/(1 + 1) \\
&:= 22 + 2 \times (22^2 + 2) + 2/2 \\
&:= 3 \times 333 - 3 - 3/3 \\
&:= 4 \times (4^4 - 4 - 4) + 4 - 4/4 \\
&:= 5 \times (5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5 \\
&:= 666 + 6 \times 66 - 66 - 6/6 \\
&:= (7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) + 7 + 7 + 7/7 \\
&:= 888 + 88 + 8 + 88/8 \\
&:= 999 - (9 + 9 + 9 + 9)/9.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{1000} &:= (11 - 1)^{(1+1+1)} \\
&:= 2 \times (22^2 + 2^{(2+2)}) \\
&:= (3 \times 3 + 3/3)^3 \\
&:= 4 \times (4^4 - 4) - 4 - 4 \\
&:= 5 \times (5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5) \\
&:= ((66 - 6)/6)^{(6 \times 6 / (6+6))} \\
&:= (7 + 7 + 7 - 7/7) \times (7 \times 7 + 7/7) \\
&:= 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 \\
&:= 999 + 9/9.
\end{aligned}$$

Values are calculated up to 1.000.000 (.txt file), but the work is written only from 0 to 1000. For details, refer Taneja [8]. Recent extension to 20000 in four parts refer Taneja [9, 10, 11]

1.4 Forth Way: Single Letter Representations

We observe that the numbers written in previous section 1.3 are in terms of each digit, not necessarily symmetric. But there are numbers, that can be written in a symmetric way, see examples below:

$$5 = \frac{11-1}{1+1} = \frac{22-2}{2+2} = \frac{33-3}{3+3} = \frac{44-4}{4+4} = \frac{55-5}{5+5} = \frac{66-6}{6+6} = \frac{77-7}{7+7} = \frac{88-8}{8+8} = \frac{99-9}{9+9}.$$

$$6 = \frac{11+1}{1+1} = \frac{22+2}{2+2} = \frac{33+3}{3+3} = \frac{44+4}{4+4} = \frac{55+5}{5+5} = \frac{66+6}{6+6} = \frac{77+7}{7+7} = \frac{88+8}{8+8} = \frac{99+9}{9+9}.$$

$$55 = \frac{111-1}{1+1} = \frac{222-2}{2+2} = \frac{333-3}{3+3} = \frac{444-4}{4+4} = \frac{555-5}{5+5} = \frac{666-6}{6+6} = \frac{777-7}{7+7} = \frac{888-8}{8+8} = \frac{999-9}{9+9}.$$

$$56 = \frac{111+1}{1+1} = \frac{222+2}{2+2} = \frac{333+3}{3+3} = \frac{444+4}{4+4} = \frac{555+5}{5+5} = \frac{666+6}{6+6} = \frac{777+7}{7+7} = \frac{888+8}{8+8} = \frac{999+9}{9+9}.$$

Motivated by this idea, instead working for each digit separately, we can work with a **single letter "a"**, for example,

• Running-Type

$$5 := (aa - a)/(a + a)$$

$$6 := (aa + a)/(a + a)$$

$$55 := (aaa - a)/(a + a)$$

$$56 := (aaa + a)/(a + a)$$

$$561 := (aaaa + aa)/(a + a)$$

$$666 := aaa \times (aa + a)/((a + a) \times a)$$

$$925 := (aaaaa - aa)/(aa + a)$$

$$1089 := (aaaa - aa - aa)/a$$

$$1991 := (aaaaaa/aaa \times (a + a) - aa)/a$$

$$2020 := (aaaaa - a)/aa \times (a + a)/a$$

$$2035 := (aaaa - a)/(a + a + a) \times aa/(a + a)$$

$$4477 := (aaa/(a + a + a) \times aa \times aa)/(a \times a)$$

$$4999 := (aaaaa - aaaa - a - a)/(a + a)$$

$$5000 := (aaaaa - aaaa)/(a + a).$$

• Fraction-Type

$$5 := \frac{aa - a}{a + a}$$

$$6 := \frac{aa + a}{a + a}$$

$$55 := \frac{aaa - a}{a + a}$$

$$56 := \frac{aaa + a}{a + a}$$

$$561 := \frac{aaaa + aa}{a + a}$$

$$666 := \frac{aaa \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$786 := \frac{(\frac{(aa + a) \times aa}{a} - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$925 := \frac{aaaaa - aa}{aa + a}$$

$$1089 := \frac{aaaa - aa - aa}{a}$$

$$1991 := \frac{\frac{aaaaaa}{aaa} \times (a + a) - aa}{a}$$

$$2020 := \frac{\frac{aaaaa - a}{aa} \times (a + a)}{\frac{aaaa - a}{a + a + a} \times aa}$$

$$2035 := \frac{\frac{aaaa - a}{a + a + a} \times aa}{\frac{a + a}{aaa} \times aa \times aa}$$

$$4477 := \frac{\frac{aaaa - a}{a + a + a} \times aa \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$4999 := \frac{(aaaaa - aaaa - a - a)}{(a + a)}$$

$$5000 := \frac{(aaaaa - aaaa)}{(a + a)}$$

$$122988 := \frac{(aaaa - a - a - a) \times aaa}{a \times a}$$

where $a \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}$, and $aa = 10 \times a + a$, $aaa = 10^2 \times a + 10 \times a + a$, etc.

The full work is from 1 to 11111 numbers, written in two different ways. One running type [15] and another in fraction-type way [16]. For previous work refer [12, 13]. The summary of author's work on recreation of numbers in different situations refer [22].

1.5 Running Expressions

Previous subsections, works with natural numbers in different situations using 9 or 10 digits. In this section also we shall do similar kind of work, but in little different way. It is based on the idea of subsection 1.1. We divide the numbers in equal parts, two or three in such a way that the results are increasing and decreasing orders 1 to 9 or 9 to 1 or 9 to 0 separated by equalities, for example,

$$1^{234} = (5 + 67) / (8 \times 9)$$

$$98/7 + 6 = 54/3 + 2 \times 1.$$

Below are more examples, written in increasing and decreasing ways:

- **Increasing Order**

$$12 = 3 + 4 + (5 \times 6 + 7 + 8) / 9 \quad (1)$$

$$123 = 4 + 5 + 6 \times 7 + 8 \times 9$$

$$1234 = -5 + 6! + 7 + 8^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$12 + 3 \times 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7) = 89$$

$$1 + 23 + 45 + 6! = 789$$

- **Decreasing Order**

$$\begin{aligned}
 98 - 7 \times (6 + 5) \times (4 - 3) &= \mathbf{21} \\
 \sqrt{9} \times 87 + 6 + 54 &= \mathbf{321} \\
 9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5! &= \mathbf{4321}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9 - 8 + 7 - 6 + 5 + 4 - 3 + 2 &= \mathbf{10} \\
 9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 + 5 + 4^3 &= \mathbf{210} \\
 (9 - 87 + 6!) \times 5! / 4! &= \mathbf{3210}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{98} &= (7 + 6) \times 5 + 4 \times 3 + 21 \\
 \mathbf{987} &= 6! + 5! + (4 + 3) \times 21
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{98} &= 7 + 65 + 4 + 32 - 10 \\
 \mathbf{987} &= 6! + 54 + 3 + 210
 \end{aligned}$$

Above examples give representations separated by equality sign having the digits in either increasing and/or decreasing orders. There are numbers that can be written in increasing as well as decreasing orders at the same time with single or double equality signs, such as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{16} &:= 12/3 \times 4 = 5 + 6 + (7 + 8)/\sqrt{9} \\
 &:= (9 + 87)/6 = 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{18} &= 12 + 3! = \sqrt{4 + 5} \times 6 = 7 + 8 + \sqrt{9} \\
 &= \sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 = \sqrt{6 \times 54} = -3 + 21 = 3! + 2 + 10
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{120} &:= (1 \times 2 + 3)! = 4 \times 5 \times 6 = ((7 + 8)/\sqrt{9})! \\
 &:= ((\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7)! = 6 \times 5 \times 4 = (3 \times 2 - 1)! = 3! \times 2 \times 10
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

The above three examples divide the numbers in two and three parts respectively with equality signs using the numbers in increasing as well as decreasing orders. From the examples (1), (2) and (3), we observe that the operations used are **addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, potentiation, factorial** and **square-root**. More details can be seen in [22, 18, 19]. In this work, our interest is to found examples similar to (1), (2) and (3), using **Fibonacci sequence** values.

1.5.1 Running Expressions with Fibonacci Sequence

Fibonacci sequence numbers are well known in literature. This sequence is defined as

$$F(0) = 0, \quad F(1) = 1, \quad F(n+1) = F(n) + F(n-1), \quad n \geq 1.$$

Similar to (1) and (2), given above, below are examples of running expressions using **Fibonacci sequence** numbers. Most of the results uses basic operations, except numbers 21 and 9876, where extra operation, such as factorial is used.

- **Increasing Order**

$$12 = F(3) \times F(4) \times F(5) + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \quad (4)$$

$$123 = -4 \times 5 \times (6 - F(7)) - 8 - 9$$

$$1234 = 5 \times F(6) \times F(7) + F(8) \times F(9)$$

$$1 + F(2^3 + F(4)) + (5 - 6)^7 = 89$$

$$1 \times 2 \times 3^4 \times 5 - F(F(6)) = 789$$

$$1 + 23 + F(4 \times 5) = 6789.$$

- **Decreasing Order**

$$9 + (-F(8)/7 + 6) \times 5 - F(4)! + 3 = 21 \quad (5)$$

$$-98 - F(7) + F(6) \times 54 = 321$$

$$(F(9) \times F(8) + 7) \times 6 - 5 = 4321$$

$$98 = (7 - 6) \times 5 + F(4) \times (32 - 1)$$

$$987 = (6 - 5) \times F(4 \times (3 + 2 - 1))$$

$$98 = -5 - 4 - 3 + 2 \times F(10)$$

$$987 = (6 - 5)^4 \times F(3 \times 2 + 10)$$

$$9876 = (\sqrt{5+4})! + F(F(3!) \times 2) \times 10$$

More details can be seen in Taneja [20].

1.5.2 Running Expressions with Triangular Numbers

Triangular numbers are very much famous in the literature of mathematics. These are given by

$$1, 3, 6, 10, 15, 21, \dots$$

The general formula to write these numbers is given by

$$T(n) = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots = \frac{n+1}{2} = C(n+1, 2)$$

The letter "C" represents as "**binomial coefficient**".

In this paper our aim is to bring **running expressions** by use of **triangle numbers**. This we have done in subsequent sections. Due to high quantity of numbers, we the work is limited to 3 digits in case of single equality. As a part of results, see below some interesting examples,

- **Increasing Order**

$$12 = T(3) - 4 - 5 + 6 - (7 - 8) \times 9 \quad (6)$$

$$123 = (-4 + 5) \times 6 + T(7) + 89$$

$$1234 = T(56 \times 7/8) + 9$$

$$1 + 2 + T(3) \times 4 - 5 + 67 = 89$$

$$1 + 2 + T(3) + T(45 - 6) = 789$$

$$-1 - 2 + T(3) + T(-4 + T(T(5))) = 6789.$$

- **Decreasing Order**

$$9 \times 8 - T(7) - T(6) + 5 - 4 - 3 = 21 \quad (7)$$

$$T(9 + 8) - 7 \times 6 + T(5 \times 4) = 321$$

$$(-T(9) + T(T(8))) \times 7 - T(6) - 5 = 4321$$

$$98 = (7 - 6) \times 5^4 - T(32) + 1$$

$$987 = T(6) \times (5 \times T(4) - 3) \times (2 - 1)$$

$$9876 = T(5 \times T(4 + 3)) + T(2 + 1)$$

$$98 = (7 - 6) \times T(5) - 4 + 32 + T(10) \quad (8)$$

$$987 = (6 - 5) \times 4 \times (T(T(T(3))) + 2) + T(10)$$

$$9876 = (-5 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(3) + T(T(-2 + 10))$$

$$9 \times 8 - T(7) - T(6) - T(5) - 4 + 3 \times 2 = 10$$

$$T(9) + 87 \times (6 - 5) + T(4 \times 3) = 210$$

$$T(9) + 8 + 7 + T(6) \times T(5) \times T(4) = 3210$$

More details can be seen in Taneja [21].

2 Single Digit Representations From 1 to 20000

The whole work brings numbers 1 to 10000 written in terms of single digits. Since, it is not possible to put all the numbers in single work, we divided it in four parts as given below:

- Part I: From 0001 to 5000;
- Part II: From 5001 to 10000 [9];
- Part III: From 10001 to 15000 [10];
- Part IV: From 15000 to 20000 [11].

This paper brings first part giving **single digit representations** of natural numbers from 1 to 5000. For other parts refer [9, 10, 11].

Remark 2.1. *Due to high quantity of numbers there are so many extra brackets. After simplifications, these unnecessary brackets can be removed easily.*

2.1 Single Digit Representation: 1-5000

This subsection brings the first part of the whole project. Here, the numbers are represented from 1 to 5000 in terms of different digits. The work done previously up to 1000 [6] is also repeated here.

- | | | |
|---|---|--|
| ▶ 1 := 1
:= 2/2
:= 3/3
:= 4/4
:= 5/5
:= 6/6
:= 7/7
:= 8/8
:= 9/9 | ▶ 5 := 1+1+1+1+1
:= 2+2/2+2
:= 3+3-3/3
:= 4+4/4
:= 5
:= 6-6/6
:= 7-(7+7)/7
:= 8+8-88/8
:= (9×9+9)/(9+9) | ▶ 9 := 11-1-1
:= (2/2+2) ²
:= 3×3
:= 4+4+4/4
:= 5+5-5/5
:= 6+6×6/(6+6)
:= 7+(7+7)/7
:= 8+8/8
:= 9 |
| ▶ 2 := 1+1
:= 2
:= 3-3/3
:= (4+4)/4
:= (5+5)/5
:= (6+6)/6
:= (7+7)/7
:= (8+8)/8
:= (9+9)/9 | ▶ 6 := (1+1)×(1+1+1)
:= 2+2+2
:= 3+3
:= 4+(4+4)/4
:= 5+5/5
:= 6
:= 7-7/7
:= 8-(8+8)/8
:= 9-(9+9+9)/9 | ▶ 10 := 11-1
:= 2+2×(2+2)
:= 3×3+3/3
:= (44-4)/4
:= 5+5
:= (66-6)/6
:= (77-7)/7
:= 8+(8+8)/8
:= 9+9/9 |
| ▶ 3 := 1+1+1
:= 2+2/2
:= 3
:= 4-4/4
:= 5-(5+5)/5
:= 6×6/(6+6)
:= (7+7+7)/7
:= 88/8-8
:= (9+9+9)/9 | ▶ 7 := 1+(1+1)×(1+1+1)
:= 2+2+2+2/2
:= 3+3+3/3
:= 4+4-4/4
:= 5+(5+5)/5
:= 6+6/6
:= 7
:= 8-8/8
:= 9-(9+9)/9 | ▶ 11 := 11
:= 22/2
:= 33/3
:= 44/4
:= 55/5
:= 66/6
:= 77/7
:= 88/8
:= 99/9 |
| ▶ 4 := 1+1+1+1
:= 2+2
:= 3+3/3
:= 4
:= 5-5/5
:= 6-(6+6)/6
:= 77/7-7
:= 8×8/(8+8)
:= (9×9-9)/(9+9) | ▶ 8 := (1+1) ¹⁺¹⁺¹
:= 2×(2+2)
:= 3×3-3/3
:= 4+4
:= 5+5-(5+5)/5
:= 6+(6+6)/6
:= 7+7/7
:= 8
:= 9-9/9 | ▶ 12 := 1+11
:= 2×(2+2+2)
:= 3+3×3
:= 4+4+4
:= (55+5)/5
:= 6+6
:= (77+7)/7
:= (88+8)/8
:= (99+9)/9 |

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 13 &:= 1+1+11 \\ &:= 2+22/2 \\ &:= 3+3 \times 3+3/3 \\ &:= 4+4/4+4+4 \\ &:= (55+5+5)/5 \\ &:= 6+6/6+6 \\ &:= 7+7-7/7 \\ &:= (88+8+8)/8 \\ &:= (99+9+9)/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 14 &:= 1+1+1+11 \\ &:= 2^{2+2}-2 \\ &:= 3+33/3 \\ &:= 4+(44-4)/4 \\ &:= 5+5-5/5+5 \\ &:= 6+6+(6+6)/6 \\ &:= 7+7 \\ &:= 8+8-(8+8)/8 \\ &:= 9+(9 \times 9+9)/(9+9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 15 &:= 1+1+1+1+11 \\ &:= 2+2+22/2 \\ &:= 3+3+3 \times 3 \\ &:= 4+44/4 \\ &:= 5+5+5 \\ &:= 6+6+6 \times 6/(6+6) \\ &:= 7+7+7/7 \\ &:= 8+8-8/8 \\ &:= 9+9-(9+9+9)/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 16 &:= (1+1)^{1+1+1+1} \\ &:= 2^{2+2} \\ &:= 3^3-33/3 \\ &:= 4 \times 4 \\ &:= 5+55/5 \\ &:= 6+(66-6)/6 \\ &:= 7+7+(7+7)/7 \\ &:= 8+8 \\ &:= 9+9-(9+9)/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 17 &:= 1+(1+1)^{1+1+1+1} \\ &:= 2/2+2^{2+2} \\ &:= 3+33/3+3 \\ &:= 4 \times 4+4/4 \\ &:= 5+(55+5)/5 \\ &:= 6+66/6 \\ &:= 7+(77-7)/7 \\ &:= 8+8+8/8 \\ &:= 9+9-9/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 18 &:= (1+1) \times (11-1-1) \\ &:= 2+2^{2+2} \\ &:= 3 \times (3+3) \\ &:= 4 \times 4+(4+4)/4 \\ &:= 5+(55+5+5)/5 \\ &:= 6+6+6 \\ &:= 7+77/7 \\ &:= 8+8+(8+8)/8 \\ &:= 9+9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 19 &:= (1+1) \times (11-1)-1 \\ &:= 22-2/2-2 \\ &:= 3/3+3 \times (3+3) \\ &:= 4+4+44/4 \\ &:= 5 \times 5-5-5/5 \\ &:= 6+6/6+6+6 \\ &:= 7+(7+77)/7 \\ &:= 8+88/8 \\ &:= 9+9/9+9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 20 &:= (1+1) \times (11-1) \\ &:= 22-2 \\ &:= 3 \times 3+33/3 \\ &:= 4+4 \times 4 \\ &:= 5 \times 5-5 \\ &:= 6+((6+6)/6+6+6) \\ &:= 7+7+7-7/7 \\ &:= 8+(88+8)/8 \\ &:= 9+99/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 21 &:= 11+11-1 \\ &:= 22-2/2 \\ &:= 3+3 \times (3+3) \\ &:= 4+4 \times 4+4/4 \\ &:= 5+55/5+5 \\ &:= 6 \times (6 \times 6+6)/(6+6) \\ &:= 7+7+7 \\ &:= 8+(88+8+8)/8 \\ &:= 9+(99+9)/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 22 &:= 11+11 \\ &:= 22 \\ &:= 33-33/3 \\ &:= 44 \times 4/(4+4) \\ &:= (55+55)/5 \\ &:= (66+66)/6 \\ &:= 7+7+7+7/7 \\ &:= (88+88)/8 \\ &:= (99+99)/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 23 &:= 1+11+11 \\ &:= 22+2/2 \\ &:= 3^3-3-3/3 \\ &:= 4+4+4+44/4 \\ &:= 5 \times 5-(5+5)/5 \\ &:= 6+6+66/6 \\ &:= 7+7+7+(7+7)/7 \\ &:= 8+8+8-8/8 \\ &:= (99+99+9)/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 24 &:= (1+1) \times (1+11) \\ &:= 2+22 \\ &:= 3^3-3 \\ &:= 4+(4 \times 4+4) \\ &:= 5 \times 5-5/5 \\ &:= 6+(6+6+6) \\ &:= 7+((77-7)/7+7) \\ &:= 8+(8+8) \\ &:= 9+((9-((9+9+9)/9))+9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 25 &:= 1+(1+1) \times (1+11) \\ &:= 2+22+2/2 \\ &:= 3^3-3+3/3 \\ &:= 4+4+4 \times 4+4/4 \\ &:= 5 \times 5 \\ &:= 6 \times 6-66/6 \\ &:= 7+7+77/7 \\ &:= 8+8+8+8/8 \\ &:= 9+9+9-(9+9)/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 26 &:= (1+1) \times (1+1+11) \\ &:= 2+22+2 \\ &:= 3^3-3/3 \\ &:= 4+44 \times 4/(4+4) \\ &:= 5 \times 5+5/5 \\ &:= 6 \times 6+(6-66)/6 \\ &:= 7+7+(77+7)/7 \\ &:= 8+8+8+(8+8)/8 \\ &:= 9+9+9-9/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 27 &:= (1+1+1)^{1+1+1} \\ &:= 2+22+2/2+2 \\ &:= 3^3 \\ &:= 4 \times 4+44/4 \\ &:= 5 \times 5+(5+5)/5 \\ &:= 66 \times 6/(6+6)-6 \\ &:= 7+7+7+7-7/7 \\ &:= 8+8+88/8 \\ &:= 9+9+9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 28 &:= 1 + (1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1} \\
 &:= 2 + 22 + 2 + 2 \\
 &:= 3^3 + 3/3 \\
 &:= 44 - 4 \times 4 \\
 &:= 5 + 5 \times 5 - (5 + 5)/5 \\
 &:= 6 + (66 + 66)/6 \\
 &:= 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 \\
 &:= 8 + 8 + (88 + 8)/8 \\
 &:= 9 + 9 + 9 + 9/9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 29 &:= (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \\
 &:= 2 + 2 + 2 + 22 + 2/2 \\
 &:= 3 + 3^3 - 3/3 \\
 &:= 44 + 4/4 - 4 \times 4 \\
 &:= 5 + 5 \times 5 - 5/5 \\
 &:= 6 \times 6 - 6 - 6/6 \\
 &:= 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7/7 \\
 &:= 8 + 8 + (88 + 8 + 8)/8 \\
 &:= 9 + 9 + 99/9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 30 &:= (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) \\
 &:= 22 + 2 \times (2 + 2) \\
 &:= 3 + 3^3 \\
 &:= 4 \times (4 + 4) - (4 + 4)/4 \\
 &:= 5 + 5 \times 5 \\
 &:= 6 \times 6 - 6 \\
 &:= 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7 \\
 &:= 8 + (88 + 88)/8 \\
 &:= 9 + 9 + (99 + 9)/9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 31 &:= 1 + (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) \\
 &:= 22 + (2/2 + 2)^2 \\
 &:= 3 + 3^3 + 3/3 \\
 &:= 4 \times (4 + 4) - 4/4 \\
 &:= 5 + 5 \times 5 + 5/5 \\
 &:= 6 \times 6 + 6/6 - 6 \\
 &:= 7 \times 7 - 7 - 77/7 \\
 &:= 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8 \\
 &:= 9 + (99 + 99)/9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 32 &:= 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \\
 &:= 2 \times 2^{2+2} \\
 &:= 33 - 3/3 \\
 &:= 4 \times (4 + 4) \\
 &:= ((5 + 5)/5)^5 \\
 &:= 6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6 - 6 \\
 &:= 7 + 77/7 + 7 + 7 \\
 &:= 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 \\
 &:= 9 + (99 + 99 + 9)/9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 33 &:= 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) \\
 &:= 22 + 22/2 \\
 &:= 33 \\
 &:= 4/4 + 4 \times (4 + 4) \\
 &:= 5/5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5 \\
 &:= 66 \times 6/(6 + 6) \\
 &:= 7 + 7 + 7 + (77 + 7)/7 \\
 &:= 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8 \\
 &:= 99 \times 9/(9 + 9 + 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 34 &:= 1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) \\
 &:= 2 + 2 \times 2^{2+2} \\
 &:= 3/3 + 33 \\
 &:= 44 + (4 - 44)/4 \\
 &:= 5 + 5 + 5 \times 5 - 5/5 \\
 &:= 6 \times 6 - (6 + 6)/6 \\
 &:= 7 \times 7 - 7 - 7 - 7/7 \\
 &:= 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8 \\
 &:= 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 35 &:= 1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) \\
 &:= 2 + 22/2 + 22 \\
 &:= 3 + 33 - 3/3 \\
 &:= 4 + 4 \times (4 + 4) - 4/4 \\
 &:= 5 + 5 + 5 \times 5 \\
 &:= 6 \times 6 - 6/6 \\
 &:= 7 \times 7 - 7 - 7 \\
 &:= 8 + 8 + 8 + 88/8 \\
 &:= 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - 9/9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 36 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11) \\
 &:= (2 + 2 + 2)^2 \\
 &:= 3 + 33 \\
 &:= 4 + 4 \times (4 + 4) \\
 &:= 5 \times 5 + 55/5 \\
 &:= 6 \times 6 \\
 &:= 7/7 + (7 \times 7 - (7 + 7)) \\
 &:= (8 \times 8 + 8) \times 8/(8 + 8) \\
 &:= 9 + 9 + 9 + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 37 &:= 111/(1 + 1 + 1) \\
 &:= 2/2 + (2 + 2 + 2)^2 \\
 &:= 3 + 33 + 3/3 \\
 &:= 4 + 4 \times (4 + 4) + 4/4 \\
 &:= 5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5 \\
 &:= 6 \times 6 + 6/6 \\
 &:= 7 \times 7 - (77 + 7)/7 \\
 &:= 888/(8 + 8 + 8) \\
 &:= 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9/9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 38 &:= 1 + 111/(1 + 1 + 1) \\
 &:= 2 + (2 + 2 + 2)^2 \\
 &:= 3^3 + 33/3 \\
 &:= 44 - 4 - (4 + 4)/4 \\
 &:= 5 + 5/5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5 \\
 &:= 6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6 \\
 &:= 7 \times 7 - 77/7 \\
 &:= 8 + 8 + (88 + 88)/8 \\
 &:= 9 + 9 + 9 + 99/9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 39 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11) \\
 &:= 2 \times (22 - 2) - 2/2 \\
 &:= 3 + 3 + 33 \\
 &:= 44 - 4 - 4/4 \\
 &:= 55 - 5 - 55/5 \\
 &:= 6 + 66 \times 6/(6 + 6) \\
 &:= 7 \times 7 + (7 - 77)/7 \\
 &:= 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8 \\
 &:= 9 + 9 + 9 + (99 + 9)/9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 40 &:= (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times (11 - 1) \\
 &:= 2 \times (22 - 2) \\
 &:= 3 + 3 + 33 + 3/3 \\
 &:= 44 - 4 \\
 &:= 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 \times 5 \\
 &:= 6 + 6 \times 6 - (6 + 6)/6 \\
 &:= 7 \times 7 - 7 - (7 + 7)/7 \\
 &:= 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 \\
 &:= (9 \times 9 \times 9 - 9)/(9 + 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 41 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times (11 - 1) \\
 &:= 2/2 + 2 \times (22 - 2) \\
 &:= 3 + 33/3 + 3^3 \\
 &:= 44 - 4 + 4/4 \\
 &:= 5 + 5 \times 5 + 55/5 \\
 &:= 6 + 6 \times 6 - 6/6 \\
 &:= 7 \times 7 - 7 - 7/7 \\
 &:= 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8 \\
 &:= (9 \times 9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 42 &:= (1 + 1) \times (11 + 11 - 1) \\
 &:= 2 \times 22 - 2 \\
 &:= 3 \times 3 + 33 \\
 &:= 44 - (4 + 4)/4 \\
 &:= 5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5 + 5 \\
 &:= 6 + 6 \times 6 \\
 &:= 7 \times 7 - 7 \\
 &:= 8 \times 8 - (88 + 88)/8 \\
 &:= 9 + 99 \times 9/(9 + 9 + 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 43 &:= (1+1) \times (11+11) - 1 \\
&:= 2 \times 22 - 2/2 \\
&:= 3 \times 3 + 3/3 + 33 \\
&:= 44 - 4/4 \\
&:= 55 - (55+5)/5 \\
&:= 6 + 6 \times 6 + 6/6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7 + 7/7 - 7 \\
&:= 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 88/8 \\
&:= 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - (9+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 44 &:= (1+1) \times (11+11) \\
&:= 2 \times 22 \\
&:= 33 + 33/3 \\
&:= 44 \\
&:= 55 - 55/5 \\
&:= 6 + 6 \times 6 + (6+6)/6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7 - 7 + (7+7)/7 \\
&:= 88 \times 8 / (8+8) \\
&:= 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 45 &:= 1 + (1+1) \times (11+11) \\
&:= 2 \times 22 + 2/2 \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times 3 + 33 \\
&:= 44 + 4/4 \\
&:= 55 - 5 - 5 \\
&:= 666/6 - 66 \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times 7 - 77/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 - 8 - 88/8 \\
&:= 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 46 &:= (1+1) \times (1+11+11) \\
&:= 2 + 2 \times 22 \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times 3 + 33 + 3/3 \\
&:= 44 + (4+4)/4 \\
&:= 55 + 5/5 - 5 - 5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + (66-6)/6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7 - (7+7+7)/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 - 8 - (88-8)/8 \\
&:= 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 47 &:= 1 + (1+1) \times (1+11+11) \\
&:= 2 + 2 \times 22 + 2/2 \\
&:= 3 + 33/3 + 33 \\
&:= 4 + 44 - 4/4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 + 5 + ((5+5)/5)^5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + 66/6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7 - (7+7)/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 - 8 - 8 - 8/8 \\
&:= 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 99/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 48 &:= (1+1) \times (1+1) \times (1+11) \\
&:= 2 \times (22+2) \\
&:= 3 \times 3^3 - 33 \\
&:= 4 + 44 \\
&:= 55 + 5 - (5+5)/5 \\
&:= 6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7 - 7/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 - 8 - 8 \\
&:= 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + (99+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 49 &:= 1 + (1+1) \times (1+1) \times (1+11) \\
&:= 2/2 + 2 \times (22+2) \\
&:= 3^3 + 33 - 33/3 \\
&:= 4 + 44 + 4/4 \\
&:= 55 - 5 - 5/5 \\
&:= 6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 + 6/6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 - 8 - 8 + 8/8 \\
&:= (9 \times 99 - 9) / (9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 50 &:= (11-1)^{1+1} / (1+1) \\
&:= 2 + 2 \times (22+2) \\
&:= 3 + 3 + 33 + 33/3 \\
&:= 4 + 44 + (4+4)/4 \\
&:= 5 \times (5+5) \\
&:= 6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 + (6+6)/6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7 + 7/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 - 8 - 8 + (8+8)/8 \\
&:= (9 \times 99 + 9) / (9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 51 &:= 1 + (11-1)^{1+1} / (1+1) \\
&:= 2 + 2 \times (22+2) + 2/2 \\
&:= 3^3 + 3^3 - 3 \\
&:= 4 + 4 + 44 - 4/4 \\
&:= 55 + 5/5 - 5 \\
&:= 6 - 66 + 666/6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7 + (7+7)/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 - (88+8+8)/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9) - 999/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 52 &:= (1+1) \times (1+1) \times (1+1+11) \\
&:= 2 \times (22+2+2) \\
&:= 3^3 + 3/3 - 3 + 3^3 \\
&:= 4 + 4 + 44 \\
&:= 55 - 5 + (5+5)/5 \\
&:= ((6+6)/6)^6 - 6 - 6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7 + (7+7+7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + 88 \times 8 / (8+8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 99/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 53 &:= (111-1)/(1+1) - 1 - 1 \\
&:= 2/2 + 2 \times (22+2+2) \\
&:= 3^3 + 3^3 - 3/3 \\
&:= (4^4 - 44)/4 \\
&:= 55 - (5+5)/5 \\
&:= 6 + 6 \times 6 + 66/6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7 - 7 + 77/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 - 88/8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 54 &:= (111-1)/(1+1) - 1 \\
&:= 2 + 2 \times (22+2+2) \\
&:= 3 \times 3 \times (3+3) \\
&:= 44 + (44-4)/4 \\
&:= 55 - 5/5 \\
&:= 66 - 6 - 6 \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times 7 - (7+7)/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 + (8-88)/8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 55 &:= (111-1)/(1+1) \\
&:= 22/2 + 2 \times 22 \\
&:= 3^3 + 3^3 + 3/3 \\
&:= 44 + 44/4 \\
&:= 55 \\
&:= 66 - 66/6 \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times 7 - 7/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 - 8 - 8/8 \\
&:= (999-9)/(9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 56 &:= (1+111)/(1+1) \\
&:= 2 \times (22+2+2+2) \\
&:= (333+3)/(3+3) \\
&:= 4 + 4 + 4 + 44 \\
&:= 55 + 5/5 \\
&:= 66 + (6-66)/6 \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times 7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 - 8 \\
&:= (999+9)/(9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 57 &:= 1 + (1+111)/(1+1) \\
&:= 2 + 22/2 + 2 \times 22 \\
&:= 3 + 3^3 + 3^3 \\
&:= 4 + (4^4 - 44)/4 \\
&:= 55 + (5+5)/5 \\
&:= 66 + (6+6-66)/6 \\
&:= 7 + 7/7 + 7 \times 7 \\
&:= 8/8 + 8 \times 8 - 8 \\
&:= (((9+9)/9)^9 + 9/9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 58 &:= 1 + 1 + (1 + 111)/(1 + 1) \\
&:= 22 + (2 + 2 + 2)^2 \\
&:= (3/3 + 3)^3 - 3 - 3 \\
&:= (4^4 - 4 - 4)/4 - 4 \\
&:= 5 + 55 - (5 + 5)/5 \\
&:= ((6 + 6)/6)^6 - 6 \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times 7 + (7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 - 8 + (8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times 99 - 9)/(9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 59 &:= (11^{1+1} - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1 \\
&:= 22/2 + 2 \times (22 + 2) \\
&:= 3^3 + 33 - 3/3 \\
&:= (4^4 - 4)/4 - 4 \\
&:= 5 + 55 - 5/5 \\
&:= 66 - 6/6 - 6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7 + (77 - 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 + 88/8 - 8 - 8 \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times 99 + 9)/(9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 60 &:= (11^{1+1} - 1)/(1 + 1) \\
&:= 2 \times (2 \times (2 + 2) + 22) \\
&:= 3^3 + 33 \\
&:= 4 \times 4 + 44 \\
&:= 5 + 55 \\
&:= 66 - 6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7 + 77/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 - 8 \times 8/(8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 - 9 - (99 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 61 &:= (1 + 11^{1+1})/(1 + 1) \\
&:= 2^{2+2+2} - 2/2 - 2 \\
&:= (3/3 + 3)^3 - 3 \\
&:= (4^4 + 4)/4 - 4 \\
&:= 5 + 55 + 5/5 \\
&:= 66 + 6/6 - 6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7 + (77 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + 8 \times 8 - 88/8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 - 9 - 99/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 62 &:= 1 + (1 + 11^{1+1})/(1 + 1) \\
&:= 2^{2+2+2} - 2 \\
&:= 3 + 33 - 3/3 + 3^3 \\
&:= (4^4 - 4 - 4)/4 \\
&:= 5 + 55 + (5 + 5)/5 \\
&:= 66 - 6 + (6 + 6)/6 \\
&:= 7 + 7 + 7 \times 7 - 7/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 - (8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 63 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 + 11 - 1) \\
&:= 2^{2+2+2} - 2/2 \\
&:= 3 + 33 + 3^3 \\
&:= (4^4 - 4)/4 \\
&:= (5^5/5 + 5)/(5 + 5) \\
&:= 66 - 6 \times 6/(6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + 7 + 7 \times 7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 - 8/8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 - 9 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 64 &:= (1 + 1)^{(1+1) \times (1+1+1)} \\
&:= 2^{2+2+2} \\
&:= (3/3 + 3)^3 \\
&:= 4 \times 4 \times 4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 + 55 - 5/5 \\
&:= ((6 + 6)/6)^6 \\
&:= 7 + 7 + 7 \times 7 + 7/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \\
&:= 9/9 + 9 \times 9 - 9 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 65 &:= 1 + (1 + 1)^{(1+1) \times (1+1+1)} \\
&:= 2/2 + 2^{2+2+2} \\
&:= (3/3 + 3)^3 + 3/3 \\
&:= (4^4 + 4)/4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 + 55 \\
&:= 66 - 6/6 \\
&:= 77 - (77 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8/8 + 8 \times 8 \\
&:= 9 + (999 + 9)/(9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 66 &:= (1 + 1) \times 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) \\
&:= 2 + 2^{2+2+2} \\
&:= 33 + 33 \\
&:= (4^4 + 4 + 4)/4 \\
&:= 55 + 55/5 \\
&:= 66 \\
&:= 77 - 77/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 + (8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= (9 + 9) \times 99/(9 + 9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 67 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) \\
&:= 2 + 2^{2+2+2} + 2/2 \\
&:= 3 + (3/3 + 3)^3 \\
&:= 4 + (4^4 - 4)/4 \\
&:= 55 + (55 + 5)/5 \\
&:= 66 + 6/6 \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times 7 + 77/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 - 8 + 88/8 \\
&:= 9 + 9 + (9 \times 99 - 9)/(9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 68 &:= (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)) \\
&:= 2 + 2 + 2^{2+2+2} \\
&:= ((3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3 - 3 \\
&:= 4 + 4 \times 4 \times 4 \\
&:= 5 + (5^5/5 + 5)/(5 + 5) \\
&:= 66 + (6 + 6)/6 \\
&:= 77 - 7 - (7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 + 8 \times 8/(8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 - (99 + 9 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 69 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11 + 11) \\
&:= (2/2 + 2) \times (22 + 2/2) \\
&:= 3 + 33 + 33 \\
&:= 4 + (4^4 + 4)/4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 + 5 + 55 - 5/5 \\
&:= 66 + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6) \\
&:= 77 - 7 - 7/7 \\
&:= 88 - 8 - 88/8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 - (99 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 70 &:= (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1} - 11 \\
&:= 22 + 2 \times (22 + 2) \\
&:= 3 + (((3/3 + 3)^3) + 3) \\
&:= 4 + (((4^4 + 4) + 4)/4) \\
&:= 5 + (55 + 5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^6 \\
&:= 77 - 7 \\
&:= 8 + 8 \times 8 - (8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 - 99/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 71 &:= (1 + 11)^{1+1}/(1 + 1) - 1 \\
&:= 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2 - 2/2 \\
&:= ((3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3 \\
&:= 4 + (4^4 - 4)/4 + 4 \\
&:= 5 + 55 + 55/5 \\
&:= 6 + 66 - 6/6 \\
&:= 7/7 + 77 - 7 \\
&:= 8 + 8 \times 8 - 8/8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 - 9/9 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 72 &:= (1 + 11)^{1+1}/(1 + 1) \\
&:= 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2 \\
&:= 3 \times (3^3 - 3) \\
&:= 4 + 4 + 4 \times 4 \times 4 \\
&:= 5 + 55 + (55 + 5)/5 \\
&:= 6 + 66 \\
&:= 77 + (7 + 7)/7 - 7 \\
&:= 8 + 8 \times 8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 73 &:= 1 + (1 + 11)^{1+1} / (1 + 1) \\
&:= 2/2 + 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2 \\
&:= ((3 + 3)^3 + 3) / 3 \\
&:= 4 + (4^4 + 4) / 4 + 4 \\
&:= 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5) - (5 + 5) / 5 \\
&:= 6 + 66 + 6 / 6 \\
&:= 7 + 77 - 77 / 7 \\
&:= 8 + 8 / 8 + 8 \times 8 \\
&:= 9 / 9 + 9 \times 9 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 74 &:= (1 + 1) \times 111 / (1 + 1 + 1) \\
&:= 2 + 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2 \\
&:= 3 + ((3 + 3)^3 - 3) / 3 \\
&:= (4^4 + 44 - 4) / 4 \\
&:= 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 / 5 \\
&:= 6 + 66 + (6 + 6) / 6 \\
&:= 77 - (7 + 7 + 7) / 7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 + 8 + (8 + 8) / 8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 - 9 + (9 + 9) / 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 75 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times 111 / (1 + 1 + 1) \\
&:= 22 / 2 + 2^{2+2+2} \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times (3^3 - 3) \\
&:= (44 + 4^4) / 4 \\
&:= 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5) \\
&:= 666 / 6 - 6 \times 6 \\
&:= 77 - (7 + 7) / 7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 + 88 / 8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + (9 + 9 + 9) / 9 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 76 &:= (1 + 1) \times (1 + 111 / (1 + 1 + 1)) \\
&:= 2 \times ((2 + 2 + 2)^2 + 2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3 + 3)^3 + 3) / 3 \\
&:= 44 + 4 \times (4 + 4) \\
&:= 5 / 5 + 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 + 6 + ((6 + 6) / 6)^6 \\
&:= 77 - 7 / 7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 + (88 + 8) / 8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + (9 - 99) / (9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 77 &:= 11 \times (1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)) \\
&:= 2 \times 2 \times 22 - 22 / 2 \\
&:= 3 \times 3^3 - 3 / 3 - 3 \\
&:= (4 - 4 / 4)^4 - 4 \\
&:= 55 + (55 + 55) / 5 \\
&:= 66 + 66 / 6 \\
&:= 77 \\
&:= 88 - 88 / 8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + (9 - 9 \times 9) / (9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 78 &:= 111 - 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) \\
&:= 2 \times 2 \times (22 - 2) - 2 \\
&:= 3 \times 3^3 - 3 \\
&:= 4 + (4^4 - 4 + 44) / 4 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + 55 - (5 + 5) / 5 \\
&:= 6 + 66 + 6 \\
&:= 7 / 7 + 77 \\
&:= 88 + (8 - 88) / 8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 - (9 + 9 + 9) / 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 79 &:= (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1} - 1 - 1 \\
&:= (2 / 2 + 2)^{2+2} - 2 \\
&:= 3 \times 3^3 + 3 / 3 - 3 \\
&:= 4 + (44 + 4^4) / 4 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + 55 - 5 / 5 \\
&:= 6 + 6 + 66 + 6 / 6 \\
&:= 77 + (7 + 7) / 7 \\
&:= 88 - 8 - 8 / 8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 - (9 + 9) / 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 80 &:= (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1} - 1 \\
&:= 2 \times 2 \times (22 - 2) \\
&:= 3 \times 3^3 - 3 / 3 \\
&:= 4 \times (4 \times 4 + 4) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + 55 \\
&:= 6 + 6 + 66 + (6 + 6) / 6 \\
&:= 77 + (7 + 7 + 7) / 7 \\
&:= 88 - 8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 - 9 / 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 81 &:= (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1} \\
&:= (2 / 2 + 2)^{2+2} \\
&:= 3 \times 3^3 \\
&:= (4 - 4 / 4)^4 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + 55 + 5 / 5 \\
&:= 6 + 666 / 6 - 6 \times 6 \\
&:= 77 - 7 + 77 / 7 \\
&:= 8 / 8 + 88 - 8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 82 &:= 1 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 + 2 \times 2 \times (22 - 2) \\
&:= 3 / 3 + 3 \times 3^3 \\
&:= 4 / 4 + (4 - 4 / 4)^4 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + 55 + (5 + 5) / 5 \\
&:= 6 + 6 + 6 + ((6 + 6) / 6)^6 \\
&:= 7 + 77 - (7 + 7) / 7 \\
&:= 88 - 8 + (8 + 8) / 8 \\
&:= 9 / 9 + 9 \times 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 83 &:= 1 + 1 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 + (2 / 2 + 2)^{2+2} \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times 3^3 - 3 / 3 \\
&:= 4 + (44 + 4^4) / 4 + 4 \\
&:= 5 + 55 + 5 \times 5 - (5 + 5) / 5 \\
&:= 6 + 66 / 6 + 66 \\
&:= 7 + 77 - 7 / 7 \\
&:= 8 + 8 \times 8 + 88 / 8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + (9 + 9) / 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 84 &:= 1 + 1 + 1 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 \times (2 \times 22 - 2) \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times 3^3 \\
&:= 4 + 4 \times (4 \times 4 + 4) \\
&:= 5 + (55 - 5 / 5) + 5 \times 5 \\
&:= 6 + 66 + 6 + 6 \\
&:= 7 + 77 \\
&:= 88 - 8 \times 8 / (8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + (9 + 9 + 9) / 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 85 &:= 111 - (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11) \\
&:= 2 + 2 + (2 / 2 + 2)^{2+2} \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times 3^3 + 3 / 3 \\
&:= 4 + (4 - 4 / 4)^4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 \times 5 + 55 \\
&:= 6 + 6 + 6 + 66 + 6 / 6 \\
&:= 7 + 77 + 7 / 7 \\
&:= 8 + 88 - 88 / 8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + (9 \times 9 - 9) / (9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 86 &:= (1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1) \times (11 + 11) - 1) \\
&:= 2 \times 2 \times 22 - 2 \\
&:= 3 + 3 + 3 \times 3^3 - 3 / 3 \\
&:= 4 + (4 - 4 / 4)^4 + 4 / 4 \\
&:= 555 / 5 - 5 \times 5 \\
&:= 6 + 6 + 6 + 66 + (6 + 6) / 6 \\
&:= 7 + (7 + 7) / 7 + 77 \\
&:= 88 - (8 + 8) / 8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + (9 \times 9 + 9) / (9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 87 &:= 111 - (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11) \\
&:= 2 \times 2 \times 22 - 2 / 2 \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times 3^3 + 3 \\
&:= 44 + 44 - 4 / 4 \\
&:= 55 + ((5 + 5) / 5)^5 \\
&:= 6 + 666 / 6 - 6 \times 6 + 6 \\
&:= 77 + (77 - 7) / 7 \\
&:= 88 - 8 / 8 \\
&:= 99 - (99 + 9) / 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 88 &:= 11 \times (1+1)^{1+1+1} \\
&:= 2 \times 2 \times 22 \\
&:= 3 \times 33 - 33/3 \\
&:= 44 + 44 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + (5^5/5+5)/(5+5) \\
&:= 66 + (66+66)/6 \\
&:= 77 + 77/7 \\
&:= 88 \\
&:= 99 - 99/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 89 &:= 111 - 11 - 11 \\
&:= 2/2 + 2 \times 2 \times 22 \\
&:= 3 \times (3^3 + 3) - 3/3 \\
&:= 4 + 4 + (4 - 4/4)^4 \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 55/5 \\
&:= 6 + 66 + 6 + 66/6 \\
&:= 77 + (77 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8/8 + 88 \\
&:= 9 + 9 \times 9 - 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 90 &:= (11 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) \\
&:= 2 + 2 \times 2 \times 22 \\
&:= 3 \times (3^3 + 3) \\
&:= 44 + ((4 + 4)/4 + 44) \\
&:= 5 + (5 \times 5 + 55 + 5) \\
&:= 6 + ((66 + 6 + 6) + 6) \\
&:= 7 + (77 - 7/7 + 7) \\
&:= 88 + (8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= 9 + 9 \times 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 91 &:= 1 + (11 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) \\
&:= 2 + 2 \times 2 \times 22 + 2/2 \\
&:= 3^3 + (3/3 + 3)^3 \\
&:= 4 + 44 + 44 - 4/4 \\
&:= 5 - 5 \times 5 + 555/5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + 66 - 66/6 \\
&:= 7 + 77 + 7 \\
&:= 88 + (88/8 - 8) \\
&:= 9 + 9 \times 9 + 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 92 &:= 11 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 \times (2 \times 22 + 2) \\
&:= 3 \times 3^3 + 33/3 \\
&:= 4 + 44 + 44 \\
&:= 5 + 55 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + 66 + (6 - 66)/6 \\
&:= 7 + 7 + 77 + 7/7 \\
&:= 88 + 8 \times 8/(8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + 99/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 93 &:= ((1 + 1)^{11-1} - 1)/11 \\
&:= 2/2 + 2 \times (2 \times 22 + 2) \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times (3^3 + 3) \\
&:= ((4 + 4)^4 - 4)/44 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 \times 5 - ((5 + 5)/5)^5 \\
&:= 666/6 - 6 - 6 - 6 \\
&:= 7 + 77 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + 88 + 8 - 88/8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + (99 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 94 &:= 1 + ((1 + 1)^{11-1} - 1)/11 \\
&:= 2 + 2 \times (2 \times 22 + 2) \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times (3^3 + 3) + 3/3 \\
&:= (444 - 4)/4 - 4 \times 4 \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5 - 5/5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^6 - 6 \\
&:= 7 + 77 + (77 - 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + 88 - (8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= 99 + (9 - 99)/(9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 95 &:= 111 - (1 + 1)^{1+1+1+1} \\
&:= 222/2 - 2^{2+2} \\
&:= 3 \times 33 - 3 - 3/3 \\
&:= 444/4 - 4 \times 4 \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + 66 - 6 - 6/6 \\
&:= 7 + 77 + 77/7 \\
&:= 8 + 88 - 8/8 \\
&:= 99 + (9 - 9 \times 9)/(9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 96 &:= (1 + 11) \times (1 + 1)^{1+1+1} \\
&:= 2 \times 2 \times (22 + 2) \\
&:= 3 \times 33 - 3 \\
&:= 4 \times (4 \times 4 + 4 + 4) \\
&:= 5/5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + 66 - 6 \\
&:= 7 \times (7 + 7) - (7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + 88 \\
&:= 99 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 97 &:= 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 \\
&:= 2/2 + 2 \times 2 \times (22 + 2) \\
&:= 3/3 + 3 \times 33 - 3 \\
&:= 4 \times 4 + (4 - 4/4)^4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 + 55 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + 66 - 6 + 6/6 \\
&:= 7 \times (7 + 7) - 7/7 \\
&:= 8 + 88 + 8/8 \\
&:= 99 - (9 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 98 &:= 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 \\
&:= 2 + 2 \times 2 \times (22 + 2) \\
&:= 3 \times 33 - 3/3 \\
&:= 4 + (444 - 4)/4 - 4 \times 4 \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - (5 + 5)/5 \\
&:= (666 - 6)/6 - 6 - 6 \\
&:= 7 \times (7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 + 88 + (8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= 99 - 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 99 &:= 11 \times (11 - 1 - 1) \\
&:= (22/2)^2 - 22 \\
&:= 3 \times 33 \\
&:= 4 - 4 \times 4 + 444/4 \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5/5 \\
&:= 666/6 - 6 - 6 \\
&:= 7/7 + 7 \times (7 + 7) \\
&:= 88 + 88/8 \\
&:= 99
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 100 &:= (11 - 1)^{1+1} \\
&:= (2 \times (2 + 2) + 2)^2 \\
&:= 3/3 + 3 \times 33 \\
&:= 4 + 4 \times (4 \times 4 + 4 + 4) \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^6 \\
&:= (7 + 7)/7 + 7 \times (7 + 7) \\
&:= 88 + (88 + 8)/8 \\
&:= 9/9 + 99
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 101 &:= 1 + (11 - 1)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2222/22 \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times 33 - 3/3 \\
&:= 4444/44 \\
&:= 5/5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + 66 - 6/6 \\
&:= 7777/77 \\
&:= 8888/88 \\
&:= 99 + (9 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 102 &:= 1 + 1 + (11 - 1)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 + (2 \times (2 + 2) + 2)^2 \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times 33 \\
&:= (444 - 4)/4 - 4 - 4 \\
&:= (5 + 5)/5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + 66 \\
&:= 7 + 77 + 7 + 77/7 \\
&:= (888 - 8)/8 - 8 \\
&:= 999/9 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 103 &:= 1+1+1+(11-1)^{1+1} \\ &:= 2+2222/22 \\ &:= 3+3 \times 33+3/3 \\ &:= 444/4-4-4 \\ &:= 5+5 \times (5 \times 5-5)-(5+5)/5 \\ &:= 6 \times 6+66+6/6 \\ &:= (777-7)/7-7 \\ &:= 888/8-8 \\ &:= (999+9)/9-9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 104 &:= 1+1+1+1+(11-1)^{1+1} \\ &:= 2 \times 2 \times (22+2+2) \\ &:= 3+3+3 \times 33-3/3 \\ &:= 4 \times 4+44+44 \\ &:= (5^5-5)/(5 \times 5+5) \\ &:= (666-6)/6-6 \\ &:= 777/7-7 \\ &:= 8+(88+8) \\ &:= 99+(9 \times 9+9)/(9+9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 105 &:= 111-(1+1) \times (1+1+1) \\ &:= 222/2-2-2-2 \\ &:= 3+3+3 \times 33 \\ &:= 4+4444/44 \\ &:= 5+5 \times (5 \times 5-5) \\ &:= 666/6-6 \\ &:= 7+7 \times (7+7) \\ &:= 8+8+88+8/8 \\ &:= 9+99-(9+9+9)/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 106 &:= 111-1-1-1-1-1 \\ &:= 2+2 \times 2 \times (22+2+2) \\ &:= 3+3+3 \times 33+3/3 \\ &:= (444-4)/4-4 \\ &:= 555/5-5 \\ &:= (666+6)/6-6 \\ &:= 7+7 \times (7+7)+7/7 \\ &:= 8+8+88+(8+8)/8 \\ &:= 9+99-(9+9)/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 107 &:= 111-1-1-1-1 \\ &:= 222/2-2-2 \\ &:= 3 \times (33+3)-3/3 \\ &:= 444/4-4 \\ &:= (555+5)/5-5 \\ &:= 6 \times (6+6+6)-6/6 \\ &:= 7+(7+7)/7+7 \times (7+7) \\ &:= 8+(88/8+88) \\ &:= 9+99-9/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 108 &:= 111-1-1-1 \\ &:= (222-2)/2-2 \\ &:= 3 \times (33+3) \\ &:= 44+4 \times 4 \times 4 \\ &:= 55+55-(5+5)/5 \\ &:= 6 \times (6+6+6) \\ &:= 7+7777/77 \\ &:= 8+88+(88+8)/8 \\ &:= 9+99 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 109 &:= 111-1-1 \\ &:= 222/2-2 \\ &:= 3/3+3 \times (33+3) \\ &:= 44+(4^4+4)/4 \\ &:= 55+55-5/5 \\ &:= 6/6+6 \times (6+6+6) \\ &:= 77/7+7 \times (7+7) \\ &:= (888-8-8)/8 \\ &:= 9+99+9/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 110 &:= 111-1 \\ &:= (222-2)/2 \\ &:= (333-3)/3 \\ &:= (444-4)/4 \\ &:= 55+55 \\ &:= (666-6)/6 \\ &:= (777-7)/7 \\ &:= (888-8)/8 \\ &:= 99+99/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 111 &:= 111 \\ &:= 222/2 \\ &:= 333/3 \\ &:= 444/4 \\ &:= 555/5 \\ &:= 666/6 \\ &:= 777/7 \\ &:= 888/8 \\ &:= 999/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 112 &:= 1+111 \\ &:= (222+2)/2 \\ &:= (333+3)/3 \\ &:= (444+4)/4 \\ &:= (555+5)/5 \\ &:= (666+6)/6 \\ &:= (777+7)/7 \\ &:= (888+8)/8 \\ &:= (999+9)/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 113 &:= 1+1+111 \\ &:= 2+222/2 \\ &:= (333+3+3)/3 \\ &:= (444+4+4)/4 \\ &:= (555+5+5)/5 \\ &:= (666+6+6)/6 \\ &:= (777+7+7)/7 \\ &:= (888+8+8)/8 \\ &:= (999+9+9)/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 114 &:= 1+1+1+111 \\ &:= 2+(222+2)/2 \\ &:= 3+333/3 \\ &:= 4+(444-4)/4 \\ &:= 5 \times 5 \times 5-55/5 \\ &:= 6+6 \times (6+6+6) \\ &:= ((7+7)/7)^7-7-7 \\ &:= (888+88)/8-8 \\ &:= (999+9+9+9)/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 115 &:= 1+1+1+1+111 \\ &:= 2+2+222/2 \\ &:= 3+(333+3)/3 \\ &:= 4+444/4 \\ &:= 5+55+55 \\ &:= 6+6 \times (6+6+6)+6/6 \\ &:= 77+7 \times 7-77/7 \\ &:= 8+88+8+88/8 \\ &:= 9+9+99-(9+9)/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 116 &:= 1+1+1+1+1+111 \\ &:= 2+2+(222+2)/2 \\ &:= 3+3+(333-3)/3 \\ &:= 4+4 \times (44-4 \times 4) \\ &:= 5+555/5 \\ &:= 6+(666-6)/6 \\ &:= 7+7 \times (7+7)+77/7 \\ &:= 8 \times (8+8)-(88+8)/8 \\ &:= 9+9+99-9/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 117 &:= 111+(1+1) \times (1+1+1) \\ &:= (22/2)^2-2-2 \\ &:= 3 \times (33+3+3) \\ &:= 4+((444+4+4)/4) \\ &:= 5+(555+5)/5 \\ &:= 6+666/6 \\ &:= 7+(777-7)/7 \\ &:= 8 \times (8+8)-88/8 \\ &:= 9+(99+9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 118 &:= 11^{1+1} - 1 - 1 - 1 \\ &:= 22 + 2 \times 2 \times (22 + 2) \\ &:= 3 + 3 + (333 + 3)/3 \\ &:= 4 + 4 + (444 - 4)/4 \\ &:= 5 + (555 + 5 + 5)/5 \\ &:= 6 + (666 + 6)/6 \\ &:= 7 + 777/7 \\ &:= 8 + (888 - 8)/8 \\ &:= 9 + 99 + 9 + 9/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 119 &:= 11^{1+1} - 1 - 1 \\ &:= (22/2)^2 - 2 \\ &:= 3 \times 3 + (333 - 3)/3 \\ &:= 4 + 4 + 444/4 \\ &:= 5 \times 5 \times 5 - 5 - 5/5 \\ &:= 6 + (666 + 6 + 6)/6 \\ &:= 77 + 7 \times 7 - 7 \\ &:= 8 + 888/8 \\ &:= 9 + (99/9 + 99) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 120 &:= 11^{1+1} - 1 \\ &:= (2 + 2 + 2) \times (22 - 2) \\ &:= 3 + 3 \times (33 + 3 + 3) \\ &:= (4 + 4) \times (44/4 + 4) \\ &:= 5 \times 5 \times 5 - 5 \\ &:= 6 + 6 + 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6) \\ &:= 7 + (777 + 7 + 7)/7 \\ &:= 8 \times (8 + 8) - 8 \\ &:= 9 + 999/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 121 &:= 11 \times 11 \\ &:= (22/2)^2 \\ &:= (33/3)^{3-3/3} \\ &:= (44/4)^{(4+4)/4} \\ &:= 5 + 5 + 555/5 \\ &:= 66 \times 66/(6 \times 6) \\ &:= ((7 + 7)/7)^7 - 7 \\ &:= 8 \times (8 + 8) - 8 + 8/8 \\ &:= 9 + (999 + 9)/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 122 &:= 111 + 11 \\ &:= (222 + 22)/2 \\ &:= (333 + 33)/3 \\ &:= (444 + 44)/4 \\ &:= (555 + 55)/5 \\ &:= (666 + 66)/6 \\ &:= (777 + 77)/7 \\ &:= (888 + 88)/8 \\ &:= (999 + 99)/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 123 &:= 1 + 1 + 11 \times 11 \\ &:= 2 + (22/2)^2 \\ &:= 3^3 - 3 + 3 \times 33 \\ &:= 4 + 4 + 4 + 444/4 \\ &:= 5 \times 5 \times 5 - (5 + 5)/5 \\ &:= 6 + 6 + 666/6 \\ &:= (777 + 77 + 7)/7 \\ &:= (888 + 88 + 8)/8 \\ &:= (999 + 99 + 9)/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 124 &:= 1 + 1 + 1 + 11 \times 11 \\ &:= 2 \times (2^{2+2+2} - 2) \\ &:= 3 + (33/3)^{3-3/3} \\ &:= 4 \times 4 \times (4 + 4) - 4 \\ &:= 5 \times 5 \times 5 - 5/5 \\ &:= 6 + 6 + (666 + 6)/6 \\ &:= 7 + 7 + (777 - 7)/7 \\ &:= 8 \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8/(8 + 8) \\ &:= 9 + 9 + 9 + 99 - (9 + 9)/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 125 &:= 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 11 \times 11 \\ &:= 2 + (22/2)^2 + 2 \\ &:= (3 - 3/3 + 3)^3 \\ &:= 44 + (4 - 4/4)^4 \\ &:= 5 \times 5 \times 5 \\ &:= 66 + 66 - 6 - 6/6 \\ &:= 7 + 7 + 777/7 \\ &:= 8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) - 88/8 \\ &:= 9 + 99 + 9 + 9 - 9/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 126 &:= 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 11 \times 11 \\ &:= 2 \times 2^{2+2+2} - 2 \\ &:= 3 \times (3 \times 3 + 33) \\ &:= (4^4 - 4) \times 4/(4 + 4) \\ &:= 5/5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5 \\ &:= 66 + 66 - 6 \\ &:= 77 + 7 \times 7 \\ &:= 8 \times (8 + 8) - (8 + 8)/8 \\ &:= 9 + (99 + 9 + 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 127 &:= 111 + (1 + 1)^{1+1+1+1} \\ &:= (2^{2 \times (2+2)} - 2)/2 \\ &:= 3^3 + (3 \times 33 + 3/3) \\ &:= 4 \times 4 + 444/4 \\ &:= 5 \times 5 \times 5 + (5 + 5)/5 \\ &:= 6 + 66 \times 66/(6 \times 6) \\ &:= 7/7 + (77 + 7 \times 7) \\ &:= 8 \times (8 + 8) - 8/8 \\ &:= 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 128 &:= (1 + 1)^{1+(1+1) \times (1+1+1)} \\ &:= 2 \times 2^{2+2+2} \\ &:= 3 + (3 - 3/3 + 3)^3 \\ &:= 4 \times 4 \times (4 + 4) \\ &:= 5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5 - (5 + 5)/5 \\ &:= ((6 + 6)/6)^{6+6/6} \\ &:= ((7 + 7)/7)^7 \\ &:= 8 \times (8 + 8) \\ &:= 99 + 9 + 9 + 99/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 129 &:= 11 \times (1 + 11) - 1 - 1 - 1 \\ &:= (2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2)/2 \\ &:= 3 + (3 \times 33 + 3^3) \\ &:= 4/4 + 4 \times 4 \times (4 + 4) \\ &:= 5 + (5 \times 5 \times 5 - 5/5) \\ &:= 6 + 6 + 6 + 666/6 \\ &:= 7/7 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7 \\ &:= 8/8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) \\ &:= 9 + 9 + 999/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 130 &:= (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11) \\ &:= 2 + 2 \times 2^{2+2+2} \\ &:= 3 + 3 \times 33 + 3^3 + 3/3 \\ &:= (4^4 + 4)/((4 + 4)/4) \\ &:= 5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5 \\ &:= 66 + ((6 + 6)/6)^6 \\ &:= (7 + 7)/7 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7 \\ &:= 8 \times (8 + 8) + (8 + 8)/8 \\ &:= 9 + 9 + (999 + 9)/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 131 &:= 11 \times (1 + 11) - 1 \\ &:= 2 + (2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2)/2 \\ &:= 3 + 3 + (3 + 3 - 3/3)^3 \\ &:= 4 + 444/4 + 4 \times 4 \\ &:= 5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5 + 5/5 \\ &:= 66 + 66 - 6/6 \\ &:= 7 + 7 + 7 + (777 - 7)/7 \\ &:= 8 \times (8 + 8) + 88/8 - 8 \\ &:= 9 + (999 + 99)/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 132 &:= 11 \times (1 + 11) \\ &:= 22 \times (2 + 2 + 2) \\ &:= 33 + 3 \times 33 \\ &:= 4 + 4 \times 4 \times (4 + 4) \\ &:= 5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5 + (5 + 5)/5 \\ &:= 66 + 66 \\ &:= 7 + 7 + 7 + 777/7 \\ &:= 88 + 88 \times 8/(8 + 8) \\ &:= 99 \times (99 + 9)/(9 \times 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 133 &:= 1 + 11 \times (1 + 11) \\
&:= 22 + 222/2 \\
&:= 33 + 3 \times 33 + 3/3 \\
&:= 4 + 4 \times 4 \times (4 + 4) + 4/4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5 - (5 + 5)/5 \\
&:= 66 + 66 + 6/6 \\
&:= 7 + 77 + 7 \times 7 \\
&:= (8 - 8/8) \times (88/8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 + 9) - 9 - 9 - 99/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 134 &:= 1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 11) \\
&:= 2 + 22 \times (2 + 2 + 2) \\
&:= 3 \times 3 + (3 - 3/3 + 3)^3 \\
&:= 4 + (4^4 + 4) \times 4/(4 + 4) \\
&:= 5 + 5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5 - 5/5 \\
&:= 6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^{6/6+6} \\
&:= 7 + 77 + 7 \times 7 + 7/7 \\
&:= 8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) - (8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 99 - 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 135 &:= 1 + 1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 11) \\
&:= 2 + 22 + 222/2 \\
&:= 3 + 33 + 33 \times 3 \\
&:= (4 - 4/4) \times (44 + 4/4) \\
&:= 5 + 5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5 \\
&:= 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 666/6 \\
&:= 7 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7 \\
&:= 8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) - 8/8 \\
&:= 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 99
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 136 &:= 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 11) \\
&:= 2 + 2 + 22 \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \\
&:= (3/3 + 3) \times (3/3 + 33) \\
&:= 4 + 4 + 4 \times 4 \times (4 + 4) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + 555/5 \\
&:= 6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^6 + 66 \\
&:= 7 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7/7 \\
&:= 8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) \\
&:= (9 - 9/9) \times (9 + 9 - 9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 137 &:= 111 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11) \\
&:= 2^{2+2} + (22/2)^2 \\
&:= 3^3 + (333 - 3)/3 \\
&:= 4 + 4 \times 4 \times (4 + 4) + 4/4 + 4 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + (555 + 5)/5 \\
&:= 6 + 66 + 66 - 6/6 \\
&:= 77 + 77/7 + 7 \times 7 \\
&:= 8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) + 8/8 \\
&:= 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 99/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 138 &:= 111 + (1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1} \\
&:= (2/2 + 2) \times (2 \times 22 + 2) \\
&:= 3^3 + 333/3 \\
&:= 4 + (4^4 + 4) \times 4/(4 + 4) + 4 \\
&:= (5 \times 5 \times 55 + 5)/(5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 + 66 + 66 \\
&:= 77 + 7 \times 7 + (77 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) + (8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= 9 + 9 + 9 + 999/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 139 &:= (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 11) - 1 \\
&:= (2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 22)/2 \\
&:= 3^3 + (333 + 3)/3 \\
&:= 44/4 + 4 \times 4 \times (4 + 4) \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) - 55/5 \\
&:= 6 + 66 + 66 + 6/6 \\
&:= 77/7 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7 \\
&:= 8 \times (8 + 8) + 88/8 \\
&:= 9 + 9 + 9 + (999 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 140 &:= (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 11) \\
&:= 2 \times (2 \times (22 + 2) + 22) \\
&:= 3 + (333 - 3)/3 + 3^3 \\
&:= 4 \times (4 \times (4 + 4) + 4) - 4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5 \\
&:= 6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^{6/6+6} + 6 \\
&:= 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \\
&:= 8 \times (8 + 8) + (88 + 8)/8 \\
&:= 9 + 9 + (999 + 99)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 141 &:= (1 + 11)^{1+1} - 1 - 1 - 1 \\
&:= 22 + (22/2)^2 - 2 \\
&:= 33 + 3 \times (33 + 3) \\
&:= 4^4 - 4 - 444/4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 \times 5 + 555/5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + 666/6 - 6 \\
&:= 7/7 + 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 + 88 - 88/8 \\
&:= 9 + 99 \times (99 + 9)/(9 \times 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 142 &:= (1 + 11)^{1+1} - 1 - 1 \\
&:= (2 \times (2 + 2 + 2))^2 - 2 \\
&:= 3 + (333 + 3)/3 + 3^3 \\
&:= 4 \times 4 + (4^4 - 4) \times 4/(4 + 4) \\
&:= 5 + 5 \times 5 + (555 + 5)/5 \\
&:= (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) - (6 + 6)/6 \\
&:= 7 + 7 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7 \\
&:= 8 + 8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) - (8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9 + 9) - 9 - 99/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 143 &:= 11 \times (1 + 1 + 11) \\
&:= 22 + (22/2)^2 \\
&:= 33 + (333 - 3)/3 \\
&:= 4 \times (4 + 4) + 444/4 \\
&:= 5 + (5 \times 5 \times 55 + 5)/(5 + 5) \\
&:= (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) - 6/6 \\
&:= 77 + 77 - 77/7 \\
&:= 8 + 8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) - 8/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9 + 9) - 9 - 9 - 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 144 &:= (1 + 11)^{1+1} \\
&:= (2 \times (2 + 2 + 2))^2 \\
&:= (3 + 3) \times (3^3 - 3) \\
&:= 4 \times (4 \times (4 + 4) + 4) \\
&:= (5/5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5/5) \\
&:= (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) \\
&:= (7/7 + 7) \times (77/7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) + 8 \\
&:= (9 + 9) \times (9 - 9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 145 &:= 1 + (1 + 11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 + (22/2)^2 + 22 \\
&:= 3/3 + (3 + 3) \times (3^3 - 3) \\
&:= 4^4 - 444/4 \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) - 5 \\
&:= 6/6 + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7) - (7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + 8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) + 8/8 \\
&:= 9/9 + (9 + 9) \times (9 - 9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 146 &:= 1 + 1 + (1 + 11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 + (2 \times (2 + 2 + 2))^2 \\
&:= 3 + (333 - 3)/3 + 33 \\
&:= 4^4 + (4 - 444)/4 \\
&:= 5/5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) - 5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + (666 - 6)/6 \\
&:= 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7/7 \\
&:= 8 + 8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) + (8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= (9 + 9)/9 + (9 + 9) \times (9 - 9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 147 &:= 1 + 1 + 1 + (1 + 11)^{1+1} \\
&:= (22/2 + 2)^2 - 22 \\
&:= 3 + (3 + 3) \times (3^3 - 3) \\
&:= 4 + 444/4 + 4 \times (4 + 4) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + (555 + 5)/5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + 666/6 \\
&:= 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) + 88/8 \\
&:= 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 999/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 148 &:= 1+1+1+1+(1+11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2+2+(2 \times (2+2+2))^2 \\
&:= (33 \times 3^3 - 3)/(3+3) \\
&:= 4+4 \times (4 \times (4+4)+4) \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times 5+5) - (5+5)/5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + (666+6)/6 \\
&:= 7/7+7 \times (7+7+7) \\
&:= 888/(8-(8+8)/8) \\
&:= 99+(9 \times 99-9)/(9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 149 &:= 1+1+1+1+1+(1+11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2+(22/2+2)^2-22 \\
&:= (33 \times 3^3+3)/(3+3) \\
&:= 4+4^4-444/4 \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times 5+5)-5/5 \\
&:= 6+(6+6) \times (6+6)-6/6 \\
&:= 7+((7+7)/7)^7+7+7 \\
&:= 8+8 \times 8+88-88/8 \\
&:= 99+(9 \times 99+9)/(9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 150 &:= (11-1) \times (1+1+1+1+11) \\
&:= 22+2 \times 2^{2+2+2} \\
&:= 3+(3+3) \times (3^3-3)+3 \\
&:= (44+4^4)/((4+4)/4) \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times 5+5) \\
&:= 6+(6+6) \times (6+6) \\
&:= 7+77+77-77/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8+88-(8+8)/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9)-(99+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 151 &:= 1+(11-1) \times (1+1+1+1+11) \\
&:= 22+(2^{2 \times (2+2)}+2)/2 \\
&:= (3+3) \times 3^3-33/3 \\
&:= 44+444/4-4 \\
&:= 5/5+5 \times (5 \times 5+5) \\
&:= 6+(6+6) \times (6+6)+6/6 \\
&:= 7+(7/7+7) \times (77/7+7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8+(88-8)/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9)-99/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 152 &:= 11 \times (1+1+1+11)-1-1 \\
&:= 2 \times 2 \times ((2+2+2)^2+2) \\
&:= 3^3+(3-3/3+3)^3 \\
&:= 4 \times (44-4)-4-4 \\
&:= (5+5)/5+5 \times (5 \times 5+5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6-((6+6)/6)^6 \\
&:= 77+77-(7+7)/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8+88 \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9)-9/9-9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 153 &:= 11 \times (1+1+1+11)-1 \\
&:= 2 \times 22+222/2-2 \\
&:= 3 \times (3^3-3+3^3) \\
&:= 4+4+4^4-444/4 \\
&:= 5+5 \times (5 \times 5+5)-(5+5)/5 \\
&:= 6+666/6+6 \times 6 \\
&:= 77+77-7/7 \\
&:= 8/8+8 \times 8+88 \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9)-9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 154 &:= 11 \times (1+1+1+11) \\
&:= 22+22 \times (2+2+2) \\
&:= 33/3 \times (33/3+3) \\
&:= 44+(444-4)/4 \\
&:= 5+5 \times (5 \times 5+5)-5/5 \\
&:= 6+(666+6)/6+6 \times 6 \\
&:= 77+77 \\
&:= 8 \times 8+(8+8)/8+88 \\
&:= 9/9+9 \times (9+9)-9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 155 &:= 11+(1+11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 \times 22+222/2 \\
&:= 3+(3-3/3+3)^3+3^3 \\
&:= 44+444/4 \\
&:= 5+5 \times (5 \times 5+5) \\
&:= 66/6+(6+6) \times (6+6) \\
&:= 7/7+77+77 \\
&:= 8+8+8 \times (8+8)+88/8 \\
&:= (9+9)/9+9 \times (9+9)-9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 156 &:= (1+11) \times (1+1+11) \\
&:= 2 \times (2 \times 2 \times (22-2)-2) \\
&:= (3+3) \times (3^3-3/3) \\
&:= 4 \times (44-4)-4 \\
&:= (5^5-5)/(5 \times 5-5) \\
&:= 6+(6+6) \times (6+6)+6 \\
&:= 77+77+(7+7)/7 \\
&:= 8+888/(8-(8+8)/8) \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9)+(9+9+9)/9-9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 157 &:= 1+(1+11) \times (1+1+11) \\
&:= 2+222/2+2 \times 22 \\
&:= 3+33/3 \times (33/3+3) \\
&:= 4/4+4 \times (44-4)-4 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 \times 5+((5+5)/5)^5 \\
&:= 6+6+(6+6) \times (6+6)+6/6 \\
&:= 77+(7+7+7)/7+77 \\
&:= 88+88-8-88/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9)+(9-99)/(9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 158 &:= (1+1+11)^{1+1}-11 \\
&:= 2 \times ((2/2+2)^{2+2}-2) \\
&:= 33+(3-3/3+3)^3 \\
&:= 4 \times (44-4)-(4+4)/4 \\
&:= 5 \times ((5+5)/5)^5-(5+5)/5 \\
&:= 6+6 \times 6 \times 6-((6+6)/6)^6 \\
&:= 77/7+7 \times (7+7+7) \\
&:= 8+88-(8+8)/8+8 \times 8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9)+(9-9 \times 9)/(9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 159 &:= 1+(1+1+11)^{1+1}-11 \\
&:= 222/2+2 \times (22+2) \\
&:= (3+3) \times 3^3-3 \\
&:= 4 \times (44-4)-4/4 \\
&:= (55+5^5)/(5 \times 5-5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6+6+6+666/6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7+(777-7)/7 \\
&:= 8+8 \times 8+88-8/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9)-(9+9+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 160 &:= (1+1) \times ((11-1-1)^{1+1}-1) \\
&:= 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times (22-2) \\
&:= 3/3+(3+3) \times 3^3-3 \\
&:= 4 \times (44-4) \\
&:= 5 \times ((5+5)/5)^5 \\
&:= 6+(666+6)/6+6 \times 6+6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7+777/7 \\
&:= 8+8 \times 8+88 \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9)-(9+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 161 &:= (1+1) \times (11-1-1)^{1+1}-1 \\
&:= ((2^{2+2}+2)^2-2)/2 \\
&:= (3+3) \times 3^3-3/3 \\
&:= 4/4+4 \times (44-4) \\
&:= 5+(5^5-5)/(5 \times 5-5) \\
&:= 6+(6+6) \times (6+6)+66/6 \\
&:= 7+77+77 \\
&:= 8+8 \times 8+88+8/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9)-9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 162 &:= (1+1) \times (11-1-1)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 \times (2/2+2)^{2+2} \\
&:= (3+3) \times 3^3 \\
&:= (4+4)/4+4 \times (44-4) \\
&:= 5+5 \times 5 \times 5+((5+5)/5)^5 \\
&:= 6+(6+6) \times (6+6)+6+6 \\
&:= 7+77+77+7/7 \\
&:= 8+88+8 \times 8+(8+8)/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 163 &:= 1 + (1+1) \times (11-1-1)^{1+1} \\
&:= ((2^{2+2} + 2)^2 + 2)/2 \\
&:= 3/3 + (3+3) \times 3^3 \\
&:= 4+4 \times (44-4) - 4/4 \\
&:= 5 \times 55 - (555+5)/5 \\
&:= 6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6) - 66/6 - 6 \\
&:= 7 + 77 + 77 + (7+7)/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 + 88 + 88/8 \\
&:= 9/9 + 9 \times (9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 164 &:= (1+1) \times (1 + (11-1-1)^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 + 2 \times (2/2 + 2)^{2+2} \\
&:= 3 + (3+3) \times 3^3 - 3/3 \\
&:= 4 + 4 \times (44-4) \\
&:= 5 \times 55 - 555/5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + ((6+6)/6)^{6/6+6} \\
&:= 77 + 77 + (77-7)/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 + 88 + (88+8)/8 \\
&:= (9+9)/9 + 9 \times (9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 165 &:= 11 \times (1+1+1+1+11) \\
&:= 2 \times 22 + (22/2)^2 \\
&:= 3 + (3+3) \times 3^3 \\
&:= 4 \times 44 - 44/4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 \times ((5+5)/5)^5 \\
&:= 66 \times (6 \times 6 - 6)/(6+6) \\
&:= 77 + 77 + 77/7 \\
&:= 88 + 88 - 88/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9) + (9+9+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 166 &:= 1 + 11 \times (1+1+1+1+11) \\
&:= 2 \times ((2/2 + 2)^{2+2} + 2) \\
&:= 3 + (3+3) \times 3^3 + 3/3 \\
&:= 4 \times 44 + (4-44)/4 \\
&:= 55 + 555/5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + 66 + ((6+6)/6)^6 \\
&:= 7 + (777-7)/7 + 7 \times 7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 - 8 + (888-8)/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9) + (9 \times 9 - 9)/(9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 167 &:= (1+1+11)^{1+1} - 1 - 1 \\
&:= (22/2 + 2)^2 - 2 \\
&:= (3 \times 333 + 3)/(3+3) \\
&:= 4 \times 44 - 4 - 4 - 4/4 \\
&:= 55 + (555+5)/5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + 66 + 66 - 6/6 \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times 7 + 777/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 - 8 + 888/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9) + (9 \times 9 + 9)/(9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 168 &:= (1+1+11)^{1+1} - 1 \\
&:= 2 \times 2 \times (2 \times 22 - 2) \\
&:= 3 + (3+3) \times 3^3 + 3 \\
&:= 4 \times 44 - 4 - 4 \\
&:= 55 + (555+5+5)/5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + (66+66) \\
&:= 7 + ((77+77) + 7) \\
&:= 88 + (88-8) \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times (9+9) - ((9+9+9)/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 169 &:= (1+1+11)^{1+1} \\
&:= (22/2 + 2)^2 \\
&:= 3 + 3 + (3+3) \times 3^3 + 3/3 \\
&:= 4 + 4 \times 44 - 44/4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 \times 55 - 555/5 \\
&:= (6/6 + 6 + 6)^{(6+6)/6} \\
&:= (7-7/7 + 7)^{(7+7)/7} \\
&:= 8/8 + 88 + 88 - 8 \\
&:= 9 + 9 \times (9+9) - (9+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 170 &:= 1 + (1+1+11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 + 2 \times (2 \times (2 \times 22 - 2)) \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times 333 + 3)/(3+3) \\
&:= 4 \times 44 - 4 - (4+4)/4 \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \\
&:= 66 + (666-6)/6 - 6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7 + ((7+7)/7)^7 - 7 \\
&:= 88 + (8+8)/8 - 8 + 88 \\
&:= 9 + 9 \times (9+9) - 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 171 &:= 1 + 1 + (1+1+11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 + (22/2 + 2)^2 \\
&:= 3 \times (3^3 + 3^3 + 3) \\
&:= 4 \times 44 - 4 - 4/4 \\
&:= 5 + 55 + 555/5 \\
&:= 66 + 666/6 - 6 \\
&:= (7 \times 7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7)/(7+7) \\
&:= (8/8 + 8) \times (88/8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 + 9 \times (9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 172 &:= 1 + 1 + 1 + (1+1+11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 \times (2 \times 2 \times 22 - 2) \\
&:= 3 \times 3 + (3+3) \times 3^3 + 3/3 \\
&:= 4 \times 44 - 4 \\
&:= 5 + 55 + (555+5)/5 \\
&:= 66 - 6 + (666+6)/6 \\
&:= (7 \times 7 \times 7 \times 7 + 7)/(7+7) \\
&:= 88 + 88 - 8 \times 8/(8+8) \\
&:= 9 + 9 \times (9+9) + 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 173 &:= 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + (1+1+11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 + (22/2 + 2)^2 + 2 \\
&:= (3+3) \times 3^3 + 33/3 \\
&:= 4 \times 44 - 4 + 4/4 \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5 + 5) - (5+5)/5 \\
&:= 6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6) - 6/6 - 6 \\
&:= 77 + 7 \times (7+7) - (7+7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + 88 + 88 - 88/8 \\
&:= 99/9 + 9 \times (9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 174 &:= (1+1) \times (111 - (1+1) \times (1+11)) \\
&:= 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 22 - 2 \\
&:= 3 + (3+3) \times 3^3 + 3 \times 3 \\
&:= 4 \times 44 - (4+4)/4 \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5 + 5) - 5/5 \\
&:= 6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6) - 6 \\
&:= 77 + 7 \times (7+7) - 7/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 + (888-8)/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9) + (99+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 175 &:= 11 \times (1+1)^{1+1+1+1} - 1 \\
&:= 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 22 - 2/2 \\
&:= 333/3 + (3/3 + 3)^3 \\
&:= 4 \times 44 - 4/4 \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5 + 5) \\
&:= 6/6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6) - 6 \\
&:= 77 + 7 \times (7+7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 + 888/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9) + (99+9+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 176 &:= 11 \times (1+1)^{1+1+1+1} \\
&:= 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 22 \\
&:= 3 + (3+3) \times 3^3 + 33/3 \\
&:= 4 \times 44 \\
&:= 5/5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5 + 5) \\
&:= 66 + (666-6)/6 \\
&:= 7/7 + 7 \times (7+7) + 77 \\
&:= 88 + 88 \\
&:= (9-9/9) \times (99+99)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 177 &:= 1 + 11 \times (1+1)^{1+1+1+1} \\
&:= 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 22 + 2/2 \\
&:= 3 \times (3^3 + 33) - 3 \\
&:= 4 \times 44 + 4/4 \\
&:= 55 + (555+55)/5 \\
&:= 66 + 666/6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7 + ((7+7)/7)^7 \\
&:= 88 + 88 + 8/8 \\
&:= 99 + 9 \times 9 - (9+9+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 178 &:= (1+1) \times (111-11-11) \\
 &:= 2+2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 2 \\
 &:= 3/3+3 \times (3^3+33)-3 \\
 &:= 4 \times 44+(4+4)/4 \\
 &:= 55+5 \times 5 \times 5-(5+5)/5 \\
 &:= 66+(666+6)/6 \\
 &:= 7+(7 \times 7 \times 7 \times 7-7)/(7+7) \\
 &:= 88+88+8+8/8 \\
 &:= 99+9 \times 9-(9+9)/9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 179 &:= 11+(1+1+11)^{1+1}-1 \\
 &:= 2+(2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 22)+2/2 \\
 &:= 3 \times (3^3+33)-3/3 \\
 &:= 4+4 \times 44-4/4 \\
 &:= 55+5 \times 5 \times 5-5/5 \\
 &:= 6 \times (6 \times 6-6)-6/6 \\
 &:= 7+(7 \times 7 \times 7 \times 7+7)/(7+7) \\
 &:= 8+(8/8+8) \times (88/8+8) \\
 &:= 99+9 \times 9-9/9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 180 &:= 11+(1+1+11)^{1+1} \\
 &:= 2 \times (2 \times 2 \times 22+2) \\
 &:= 3 \times (3^3+33) \\
 &:= 4+4 \times 44 \\
 &:= 55+5 \times 5 \times 5 \\
 &:= 6 \times (6 \times 6-6) \\
 &:= 77+(777-7)/7-7 \\
 &:= 88+88+8 \times 8/(8+8) \\
 &:= 99+9 \times 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 181 &:= 1+11+(1+1+11)^{1+1} \\
 &:= 2/2+2 \times (2 \times 2 \times 22+2) \\
 &:= 3/3+3 \times (3^3+33) \\
 &:= 4+4 \times 44+4/4 \\
 &:= 55+5 \times 5 \times 5+5/5 \\
 &:= 6/6+6 \times (6 \times 6-6) \\
 &:= 77-7+777/7 \\
 &:= 8 \times (8+8+8)+88/8 \\
 &:= 9/9+99+9 \times 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 182 &:= (1+1+11) \times (1+1+1+11) \\
 &:= 2+2 \times (2 \times 2 \times 22+2) \\
 &:= (3+3)^3-33-3/3 \\
 &:= 4+4 \times 44+(4+4)/4 \\
 &:= 55+5 \times 5 \times 5+(5+5)/5 \\
 &:= 6 \times (6 \times 6-6)+(6+6)/6 \\
 &:= 7+77+7 \times (7+7) \\
 &:= 8+8 \times 8+(888-8)/8 \\
 &:= 9+9 \times (9+9)+99/9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 183 &:= 1+(1+1+11) \times (1+1+1+11) \\
 &:= 2 \times 2 \times (2 \times 22+2)-2/2 \\
 &:= (3+3)^3-33 \\
 &:= 4+4+4 \times 44-4/4 \\
 &:= (5-(5+5)/5)^5-55-5 \\
 &:= 6+66+666/6 \\
 &:= 7+77+7 \times (7+7)+7/7 \\
 &:= 8+8 \times 8+888/8 \\
 &:= 9 \times 9-9+999/9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 184 &:= (1+1) \times (11+(11-1-1)^{1+1}) \\
 &:= 2 \times 2 \times (2 \times 22+2) \\
 &:= 3/3+(3+3)^3-33 \\
 &:= 4+4+4 \times 44 \\
 &:= 5+55+5 \times 5 \times 5-5/5 \\
 &:= 6+66+(666+6)/6 \\
 &:= 7+7 \times 7+((7+7)/7)^7 \\
 &:= 8+88+88 \\
 &:= 9 \times 9-9+(999+9)/9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 185 &:= (1+1+1+11)^{1+1}-11 \\
 &:= 2 \times 2 \times (2 \times 22+2)+2/2 \\
 &:= 3+(3+3)^3-33-3/3 \\
 &:= 4+4+4 \times 44+4/4 \\
 &:= 5+55+5 \times 5 \times 5 \\
 &:= 6+6 \times (6 \times 6-6)-6/6 \\
 &:= (7+7) \times (7+7)-77/7 \\
 &:= 8+88+88+8/8 \\
 &:= 9+(9-9/9) \times (99+99)/9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 186 &:= ((1+1)^{11}-1-1)/11 \\
 &:= 2+2 \times 2 \times (2 \times 22+2) \\
 &:= 3+(3+3)^3-33 \\
 &:= 4 \times 44+(44-4)/4 \\
 &:= 5+5 \times 5 \times 5+55+5/5 \\
 &:= 6+6 \times (6 \times 6-6) \\
 &:= 77+7 \times (7+7)+77/7 \\
 &:= 8+88+88+(8+8)/8 \\
 &:= 99+99-(99+9)/9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 187 &:= 1+((1+1)^{11}-1-1)/11 \\
 &:= 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 22+22/2 \\
 &:= 33 \times (3+3)-33/3 \\
 &:= 4 \times 44+44/4 \\
 &:= 55/5 \times ((55+5)/5+5) \\
 &:= 6+6 \times (6 \times 6-6)+6/6 \\
 &:= 77+(777-7)/7 \\
 &:= 88+88+88/8 \\
 &:= 99+99-99/9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 188 &:= 1+1+((1+1)^{11}-1-1)/11 \\
 &:= 2 \times (2 \times (2 \times 22+2)+2) \\
 &:= (3+3)^3-3^3-3/3 \\
 &:= 444-4^4 \\
 &:= (5-(5+5)/5)^5-55 \\
 &:= 6+6 \times (6 \times 6-6)+(6+6)/6 \\
 &:= 77+777/7 \\
 &:= 88+88+(88+8)/8 \\
 &:= 9+99+9 \times 9-9/9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 189 &:= (11-1-1) \times (11+11-1) \\
 &:= ((22-2)^2-22)/2 \\
 &:= (3+3)^3-3^3 \\
 &:= 4/4+444-4^4 \\
 &:= 5 \times (55+5)-555/5 \\
 &:= 66+6+6+666/6 \\
 &:= (7+7) \times (7+7)-7 \\
 &:= 8+8 \times (8+8+8)-88/8 \\
 &:= 9+99+9 \times 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 190 &:= (11-1) \times ((1+1) \times (11-1)-1) \\
 &:= 222-2 \times 2^{2+2} \\
 &:= 3/3+(3+3)^3-3^3 \\
 &:= 4^4-(4^4+4+4)/4 \\
 &:= 5+5 \times 5 \times 5+55+5 \\
 &:= (6-6/6) \times ((6+6)/6+6 \times 6) \\
 &:= 7/7+(7+7) \times (7+7)-7 \\
 &:= 8 \times (8+8+8)-(8+8)/8 \\
 &:= 9+99+9 \times 9+9/9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 191 &:= 1+(11-1) \times ((1+1) \times (11-1)-1) \\
 &:= 22+(22/2+2)^2 \\
 &:= 3 \times (3/3+3)^3-3/3 \\
 &:= 4^4-(4^4+4)/4 \\
 &:= 5 \times 5+55+555/5 \\
 &:= 6 \times (6 \times 6-6)+66/6 \\
 &:= 7+((7+7)/7)^7+7 \times 7+7 \\
 &:= 8 \times (8+8+8)-8/8 \\
 &:= 99+9 \times 9+99/9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 192 &:= 111+(11-1-1)^{1+1} \\
 &:= 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times (22+2) \\
 &:= 3 \times (3/3+3)^3 \\
 &:= 4 \times (44+4) \\
 &:= (5/5+5) \times ((5+5)/5)^5 \\
 &:= 6+6 \times (6 \times 6-6)+6 \\
 &:= 7+(7+7) \times (7+7)-77/7 \\
 &:= 8 \times (8+8+8) \\
 &:= 9 \times 9+999/9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 193 &:= 1 + 111 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 + (22/2 + 2)^2 + 22 \\
&:= 3/3 + 3 \times (3/3 + 3)^3 \\
&:= 4 \times (44 + 4) + 4/4 \\
&:= 5 + (5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5 - 55 \\
&:= 6 + 6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6) + 6/6 \\
&:= (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) - (7 + 7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8/8 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + (999 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 194 &:= (1 + 1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1} - 1 - 1 \\
&:= (2^{2+2} - 2)^2 - 2 \\
&:= 33 \times (3 + 3) - 3 - 3/3 \\
&:= 4^4 + (4 - 4^4 + 4)/4 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5) - 55 - 5/5 \\
&:= 66 + ((6 + 6)/6)^{6/6+6} \\
&:= (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) - (7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= (8 + 8)/8 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + (999 + 9 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 195 &:= (1 + 1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1} - 1 \\
&:= (2^{2+2} - 2)^2 - 2/2 \\
&:= 33 \times (3 + 3) - 3 \\
&:= 4 + 4^4 - (4^4 + 4)/4 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5) - 55 \\
&:= (6 \times 66 - 6) \times 6/(6 + 6) \\
&:= (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) - 7/7 \\
&:= 8 + 88 + 88 + 88/8 \\
&:= 99 + 99 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 196 &:= (1 + 1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1} \\
&:= (2^{2+2} - 2)^2 \\
&:= 3/3 + 33 \times (3 + 3) - 3 \\
&:= 4 + 4 \times (44 + 4) \\
&:= 5/5 + 5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5) - 55 \\
&:= 66 + 66 + ((6 + 6)/6)^6 \\
&:= (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8/(8 + 8) \\
&:= 99 + 99 - (9 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 197 &:= 1 + (1 + 1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2/2 + (2^{2+2} - 2)^2 \\
&:= 33 \times (3 + 3) - 3/3 \\
&:= 4 + 4^4 + (4 - 4^4)/4 \\
&:= 5 + (5/5 + 5) \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5 \\
&:= (66 \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6)/6 \\
&:= 7/7 + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) \\
&:= 88 + (888 - 8 - 8)/8 \\
&:= 99 + 99 - 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 198 &:= (1 + 1) \times 11 \times (11 - 1 - 1) \\
&:= 2 + (2^{2+2} - 2)^2 \\
&:= 33 \times (3 + 3) \\
&:= 4 + 4^4 + (4 - 4^4 + 4)/4 \\
&:= (5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - (5 + 5)/5 \\
&:= 6 \times 66 \times 6/(6 + 6) \\
&:= 77 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7 - 7 \\
&:= 88 + (888 - 8)/8 \\
&:= 99 + 99
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 199 &:= (1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)^{1+1} - 1 \\
&:= ((22 - 2)^2 - 2)/2 \\
&:= 3/3 + 33 \times (3 + 3) \\
&:= 4 + 4 + 4^4 - (4^4 + 4)/4 \\
&:= (5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5/5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6 - 66/6 \\
&:= 77 + (777 + 77)/7 \\
&:= 88 + 888/8 \\
&:= 99 + 99 + 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 200 &:= (1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)^{1+1} \\
&:= 222 - 22 \\
&:= 3 + 33 \times (3 + 3) - 3/3 \\
&:= 4 + 4 + 4 \times (44 + 4) \\
&:= (5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6 + (6 - 66)/6 \\
&:= (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) - 7 + 77/7 \\
&:= 8 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8) \\
&:= 99 + 99 + (9 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 201 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)^{1+1} \\
&:= ((22 - 2)^2 + 2)/2 \\
&:= 3 + 33 \times (3 + 3) \\
&:= 4^4 - 44 - 44/4 \\
&:= 5/5 + (5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5) \\
&:= (6 \times 66 + 6) \times 6/(6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) - (7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8/8 \\
&:= 9 + 9 \times 9 + 999/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 202 &:= (1 + 1) \times (1 + (11 - 1)^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 + 222 - 22 \\
&:= 3 + 33 \times (3 + 3) + 3/3 \\
&:= 4^4 + (4 - 44)/4 - 44 \\
&:= (5 + 5)/5 + (5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6 - 6 - (6 + 6)/6 \\
&:= 7 + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) - 7/7 \\
&:= 8 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8) + (8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= 9 + 9 \times 9 + (999 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 203 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + (11 - 1)^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 + ((22 - 2)^2 + 2)/2 \\
&:= 3 + 3 + 33 \times (3 + 3) - 3/3 \\
&:= 4^4 + (44 - 4^4)/4 \\
&:= (5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6 - 6 - 6/6 \\
&:= 7 + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 88/8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + (999 + 99)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 204 &:= (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + (11 - 1)^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 + 2 + 222 - 22 \\
&:= 3 + 33 \times (3 + 3) + 3 \\
&:= 44 + 4 \times (44 - 4) \\
&:= 5 + (5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5/5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6 - 6 \\
&:= 7 + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7/7 \\
&:= (88 + 8)/8 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8) \\
&:= (999/9 - 9) \times (9 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 205 &:= (1 + 1 + (1 + 1)^{11})/(11 - 1) \\
&:= 2 + 2 + ((22 - 2)^2 + 2)/2 \\
&:= (3 + 3)^3 - 33/3 \\
&:= ((4 + 4)^4 + 4)/(4 \times 4 + 4) \\
&:= 5 + (5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 - 66/6 \\
&:= 77 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7 \\
&:= 88 + 8 \times (8 + 8) - 88/8 \\
&:= 9 + 99 + 99 - (9 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 206 &:= 1 + (1 + 1 + (1 + 1)^{11})/(11 - 1) \\
&:= 222 - 2^{2+2} \\
&:= (3 + 3)^3 + (3 - 33)/3 \\
&:= 4^4 + 44 + 4 - (4 + 4)/4 \\
&:= 5 + (5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5) + 5/5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 + (6 - 66)/6 \\
&:= 77 + 7/7 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7 \\
&:= 8 + 88 + (888 - 8)/8 \\
&:= 9 + 99 + 99 - 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 207 &:= 11 + (1 + 1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2/2 + 222 - 2^{2+2} \\
&:= (3 + 3)^3 - 3 \times 3 \\
&:= 4^4 - 4 - 44 - 4/4 \\
&:= (5^5 - 5 \times 5 + 5)/(5 + 5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 + (6 \times 66 + 6) \times 6/(6 + 6) \\
&:= (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 77/7 \\
&:= 8 + 88 + 888/8 \\
&:= 9 + 99 + 99
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 208 &:= (1+1) \times (111-1) - 1 - 11 \\
&:= 2 + 222 - 2^{2+2} \\
&:= 3 + (3+3)^3 - 33/3 \\
&:= 4 \times (44+4+4) \\
&:= (5^5 - 5)/(5+5+5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6 - (6+6)/6 \\
&:= 7 \times (7+7) + (777-7)/7 \\
&:= 8+8+8 \times (8+8+8) \\
&:= 9+99+99+9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 209 &:= 11 \times ((1+1) \times (11-1) - 1) \\
&:= 222 - 22/2 - 2 \\
&:= 33/3 + 33 \times (3+3) \\
&:= 4/4 + 4 \times (44+4+4) \\
&:= (5^5 + 5+5)/(5+5+5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6/6 - 6 \\
&:= 7 \times (7+7) + 777/7 \\
&:= 88/8 \times (88/8+8) \\
&:= 99+99+99/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 210 &:= (11-1) \times (11+11-1) \\
&:= 222 - 2 \times (2+2+2) \\
&:= (3+3)^3 - 3 - 3 \\
&:= 4^4 - 44 - (4+4)/4 \\
&:= 5 + (5+5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5) + 5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6 \\
&:= 7+7+(7+7) \times (7+7) \\
&:= 88 + (888+88)/8 \\
&:= 99+999/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 211 &:= (1+1) \times 111 - 11 \\
&:= 222 - 22/2 \\
&:= 3/3 + (3+3)^3 - 3 - 3 \\
&:= 4^4 - 44 - 4/4 \\
&:= 55 + (5^5 - 5)/(5 \times 5 - 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6 + 6/6 \\
&:= 7+7+(7+7) \times (7+7) + 7/7 \\
&:= 8+8 \times (8+8+8) + 88/8 \\
&:= 99 + (999+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 212 &:= 1 + (1+1) \times 111 - 11 \\
&:= 222 + ((2-22)/2) \\
&:= (3+3)^3 - (3/3+3) \\
&:= 4^4 - 44 \\
&:= (55+5^5)/(5+5+5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6 + (6+6)/6 \\
&:= 77+7+((7+7)/7)^7 \\
&:= (8 \times 8 \times 8 - 88) \times 8/(8+8) \\
&:= 99 + (999+9+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 213 &:= (1+1) \times (1+111) - 11 \\
&:= 2 + 222 - 22/2 \\
&:= (3+3)^3 - 3 \\
&:= 4^4 - 44 + 4/4 \\
&:= 5 + (5^5 - 5)/(5+5+5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6 \times 6/(6+6) \\
&:= 7+77+((7+7)/7)^7 + 7/7 \\
&:= 8+88+8 \times (8+8) - 88/8 \\
&:= (9+9) \times (9+9) - 999/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 214 &:= 1 + (1+1) \times (1+111) - 11 \\
&:= 222 - 2 \times (2+2) \\
&:= 3/3 + (3+3)^3 - 3 \\
&:= 4^4 - 44 + (4+4)/4 \\
&:= 5 + (5^5 + 5+5)/(5+5+5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 - (6+6)/6 \\
&:= 7 + (7+7) \times (7+7) + 77/7 \\
&:= 88+8 \times (8+8) - (8+8)/8 \\
&:= (9+9)/9 \times (99+9-9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 215 &:= (1+1) \times (1+1+111) - 11 \\
&:= 2+2+222 - 22/2 \\
&:= (3+3)^3 - 3/3 \\
&:= 4+4^4 - 44 - 4/4 \\
&:= 5 \times 55 - 55 - 5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6/6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 - ((7+7)/7)^7 \\
&:= 88+8 \times (8+8) - 8/8 \\
&:= ((9+9) \times (99+9) - 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 216 &:= (1+1) \times (111 - (1+1+1)) \\
&:= (2+2+2)^{2/2+2} \\
&:= (3+3)^3 \\
&:= 4+4^4 - 44 \\
&:= (5-5/5) \times (55-5/5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 \\
&:= (7-7/7)^{(7+7+7)/7} \\
&:= 88+8 \times (8+8) \\
&:= 9+9+99+99
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 217 &:= (1+1) \times (111-1-1) - 1 \\
&:= 222 - 2 - 2 - 2/2 \\
&:= (3+3)^3 + 3/3 \\
&:= 4+4^4 - 44 + 4/4 \\
&:= 5 + (55+5^5)/(5+5+5) \\
&:= 6/6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 77 \\
&:= 8/8 + 8 \times (8+8) + 88 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((9+9)/9)^9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 218 &:= (1+1) \times (111-1-1) \\
&:= 222 - 2 - 2 \\
&:= 3 + (3+3)^3 - 3/3 \\
&:= 444 \times 4/(4+4) - 4 \\
&:= (5 - (5+5)/5)^5 - 5 \times 5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 + (6+6)/6 \\
&:= 7/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 77 \\
&:= 88+8 \times (8+8) + (8+8)/8 \\
&:= 9+99+99+99/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 219 &:= (1+1) \times (111-1) - 1 \\
&:= 222 - 2/2 - 2 \\
&:= 3 + (3+3)^3 \\
&:= 44+4 \times 44 - 4/4 \\
&:= 5 \times 55 - 55 - 5/5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 + 6 \times 6/(6+6) \\
&:= 77+7+7+((7+7)/7)^7 \\
&:= 8+8+8 \times (8+8+8) + 88/8 \\
&:= 9+99+999/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 220 &:= (1+1) \times (111-1) \\
&:= 222 - 2 \\
&:= 3 + (3+3)^3 + 3/3 \\
&:= 44+4 \times 44 \\
&:= 55 \times (5-5/5) \\
&:= 6+6 \times 6 \times 6 - (6+6)/6 \\
&:= 77/7 \times (7-7/7+7+7) \\
&:= (8+8) \times (888-8)/(8 \times 8) \\
&:= 99/9 \times (99/9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 221 &:= (1+1) \times 111 - 1 \\
&:= 222 - 2/2 \\
&:= 3 + (3+3)^3 - 3/3 + 3 \\
&:= 44+4 \times 44 + 4/4 \\
&:= 55 \times (5-5/5) + 5/5 \\
&:= 6 + (6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6/6) \\
&:= (777+777-7)/7 \\
&:= (888-8+888)/8 \\
&:= 99 + (999+99)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 222 &:= (1+1) \times 111 \\
&:= 222 \\
&:= 3 + (3+3)^3 + 3 \\
&:= 444 \times 4/(4+4) \\
&:= (5+5) \times 555/(5 \times 5) \\
&:= 6+6 \times 6 \times 6 \\
&:= ((7+7)/7) \times 777/7 \\
&:= (8+8) \times 888/(8 \times 8) \\
&:= (9+9) \times 999/(9 \times 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 223 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times 111 \\
&:= 2/2 + 222 \\
&:= 3 + (3 + 3)^3 + 3/3 + 3 \\
&:= 4^4 + 44/4 - 44 \\
&:= 5 + (5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5 - 5 \times 5 \\
&:= 6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 + 6/6 \\
&:= 7 + (7 - 7/7)^{(7+7+7)/7} \\
&:= 8 + 88 + 8 \times (8 + 8) - 8/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 99/9 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 224 &:= (1 + 1) \times (1 + 111) \\
&:= 2 + 222 \\
&:= 3 \times 3 + ((3 + 3)^3 - 3/3) \\
&:= 4^4 - 4 \times (4 + 4) \\
&:= (5 - 5/5) \times (55 + 5/5) \\
&:= 6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6 \\
&:= 77 + 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) + 88 \\
&:= 9 + ((9 + 9) \times (99 + 9) - 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 225 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 111) \\
&:= 2 + 222 + 2/2 \\
&:= 3 \times 3 + (3 + 3)^3 \\
&:= 4/4 + 4^4 - 4 \times (4 + 4) \\
&:= 5 \times (55 - 5 - 5) \\
&:= 6 + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6) + 6 \times 6 \times 6 \\
&:= (7/7 + 7 + 7)^{(7+7)/7} \\
&:= (8 - 8/8 + 8)^{(8+8)/8} \\
&:= (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - 99
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 226 &:= (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 111) \\
&:= 2 + 222 + 2 \\
&:= 3 \times 3 + (3 + 3)^3 + 3/3 \\
&:= 4 + 444 \times 4/(4 + 4) \\
&:= 5/5 + 5 \times (55 - 5 - 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 + (66 - 6)/6 \\
&:= 7 \times (7 + 7) + ((7 + 7)/7)^7 \\
&:= 8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) + (8 + 8)/8 + 88 \\
&:= 9 + 9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((9 + 9)/9)^9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 227 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 111) \\
&:= 2 + 2 + 222 + 2/2 \\
&:= (3 + 3)^3 + 33/3 \\
&:= 4 - 44 + 4^4 + 44/4 \\
&:= 5 + (5 + 5) \times 555/(5 \times 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 + 66/6 \\
&:= 7 + 77/7 \times (7 - 7/7 + 7 + 7) \\
&:= 88 + 8 \times (8 + 8) + 88/8 \\
&:= ((9 + 9) \times (99 + 9) + 99)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 228 &:= (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 111) \\
&:= 2 + 222 + 2 + 2 \\
&:= 3 + (3 + 3)^3 + 3 \times 3 \\
&:= 4 + 4^4 - 4 \times (4 + 4) \\
&:= (5 - 5/5) \times ((5 + 5)/5 + 55) \\
&:= 6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 \\
&:= (7 - 7/7) \times (7 \times 7 - 77/7) \\
&:= (88/8 + 8) \times (88 + 8)/8 \\
&:= 9 + 99 + 9 + 999/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 229 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 111) \\
&:= (22^2 - 22)/2 - 2 \\
&:= (3^{3+3} - 33)/3 - 3 \\
&:= 4^4 - 44/4 - 4 \times 4 \\
&:= 5 + (5 - 5/5) \times (55 + 5/5) \\
&:= 6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 + 6/6 + 6 \\
&:= 7 + (7 + 7) \times 777/(7 \times 7) \\
&:= 8 + (888 + 888 - 8)/8 \\
&:= 9 + 99/9 \times (9 + 99/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 230 &:= (11 - 1) \times (1 + 11 + 11) \\
&:= 222 + 2 \times (2 + 2) \\
&:= 3 + (3 + 3)^3 + 33/3 \\
&:= 4 + 4 + 444 \times 4/(4 + 4) \\
&:= 5 + 5 \times (55 - 5 - 5) \\
&:= 6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6 \\
&:= (77 \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + (8 + 8) \times 888/(8 \times 8) \\
&:= 9 + 99 + (999 + 99)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 231 &:= 11 \times (11 + 11 - 1) \\
&:= (22^2 - 22)/2 \\
&:= 33 + 33 \times (3 + 3) \\
&:= 44 + 4 \times 44 + 44/4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 5/5 \\
&:= 66 \times (6 \times 6 + 6)/(6 + 6) \\
&:= 77 + 77 + 77 \\
&:= 8 \times (8 + 8) + 888/8 - 8 \\
&:= 9 + (9 + 9) \times 999/(9 \times 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 232 &:= 111 + 11^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 + 222 + 2 \times (2 + 2) \\
&:= (3^{3+3} - 33)/3 \\
&:= 4^4 - 4 \times 4 - 4 - 4 \\
&:= (5 + 5)/5 \times (555/5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 + (66 - 6)/6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 - 777/7 \\
&:= 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 99/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 233 &:= 11 + (1 + 1) \times 111 \\
&:= 222 + 22/2 \\
&:= 3 \times (3 \times 3^3 - 3) - 3/3 \\
&:= 4 + 4^4 - 4 \times 4 - 44/4 \\
&:= (5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5 - 5 - 5 \\
&:= 6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 + 66/6 \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times (7 + 7) + ((7 + 7)/7)^7 \\
&:= 8 + (8 + 8 - 8/8)^{(8+8)/8} \\
&:= 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9/9 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 234 &:= 1 + 11 + (1 + 1) \times 111 \\
&:= 2^{2 \times (2+2)} - 22 \\
&:= 3 \times (3 \times 3^3 - 3) \\
&:= 4^4 - 44 \times 4/(4 + 4) \\
&:= (5 - 5/5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 + 5/5) \\
&:= 6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 + 6 + 6 \\
&:= (77 + 7/7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= (8 \times (8 + 8) - 88/8) \times (8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 235 &:= 11 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 111) \\
&:= 2 + 222 + 22/2 \\
&:= 3 + (3^{3+3} - 33)/3 \\
&:= 4^4 - 4 - 4 \times 4 - 4/4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 + 5 \times (55 - 5 - 5) \\
&:= 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 + 6/6 \\
&:= 7 + (7 - 7/7) \times (7 \times 7 - 77/7) \\
&:= (8 \times 8 \times 88 + 8)/(8 + 8 + 8) \\
&:= 9/9 + (9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 236 &:= 1 + 11 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 111) \\
&:= 2 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)} - 22 \\
&:= (3^{3+3} - 3)/3 - 3 - 3 \\
&:= 4^4 - 4 \times 4 - 4 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 \times 5 + 555/5 \\
&:= 66 \times 66/(6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \\
&:= (7 + 777/7) \times (7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + (88/8 + 8) \times (88 + 8)/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 + (9 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 237 &:= 11 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 111) \\
&:= (22^2 - 2)/2 - 2 - 2 \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times (3 \times 3^3 - 3) \\
&:= 4/4 + 4^4 - (4 \times 4 + 4) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 \times 5 + (555 + 5)/5 \\
&:= 6 + 66 \times (6 \times 6 + 6)/(6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + (77 \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7)/7 \\
&:= (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) - 88/8 - 8 \\
&:= 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 999/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 238 &:= (1+1) \times (11^{1+1} - 1 - 1) \\
&:= 2 \times ((22/2)^2 - 2) \\
&:= (3^{3+3} + 3)/3 - 3 - 3 \\
&:= 4^4 - 4 \times 4 - (4+4)/4 \\
&:= (5 - (5+5)/5)^5 - 5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 + (66+66)/6 \\
&:= 777 - 7 \times 77 \\
&:= 8 \times (8+8) + (888 - 8)/8 \\
&:= ((9+9)/9)^{9-9/9} - 9 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 239 &:= (1+1) \times (11^{1+1} - 1) - 1 \\
&:= (22^2 - 2)/2 - 2 \\
&:= (3^{3+3} - 3)/3 - 3 \\
&:= 4^4 - 4 \times 4 - 4/4 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 \times (5+5) - 55/5 \\
&:= 6+6+6 \times 6 \times 6 + 66/6 \\
&:= 7+7 \times 7 \times 7 - 777/7 \\
&:= 8 \times (8+8) + 888/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9+9) + ((9-9 \times 9)/(9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 240 &:= (1+1) \times (11^{1+1} - 1) \\
&:= 22^2/2 - 2 \\
&:= 3 \times 3 \times 3^3 - 3 \\
&:= 4^4 - 4 \times 4 \\
&:= (5+5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5/5) \\
&:= 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) - 6 - 6 \\
&:= (7 - (7+7)/7) \times (7 \times 7 - 7/7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 + 88 + 88 \\
&:= (999/9+9) \times (9+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 241 &:= (1+1) \times 11^{1+1} - 1 \\
&:= (22^2 - 2)/2 \\
&:= (3^{3+3} + 3)/3 - 3 \\
&:= 4/4 + 4^4 - 4 \times 4 \\
&:= 5 + 555/5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5 \\
&:= 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) - 66/6 \\
&:= 7 + (7/7 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8/8 + 8 \times 8 + 88 + 88 \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9+9) - (9+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 242 &:= (1+1) \times 11^{1+1} \\
&:= 22^2/2 \\
&:= (3^{3+3} - 3)/3 \\
&:= 44 \times 44/(4+4) \\
&:= (5 - (5+5)/5)^5 - 5/5 \\
&:= 66 \times 66/(6+6+6) \\
&:= 77/7 \times (7+7+7+7/7) \\
&:= 88 \times (88+88)/(8 \times 8) \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9+9) - 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 243 &:= 1 + (1+1) \times 11^{1+1} \\
&:= (22^2 + 2)/2 \\
&:= 3 \times 3 \times 3^3 \\
&:= (4 - 4/4)^{4/4+4} \\
&:= (5 - (5+5)/5)^5 \\
&:= (6 \times 6/(6+6))^{6-6/6} \\
&:= ((7+7+7)/7)^{7-(7+7)/7} \\
&:= (8+8/8) \times (8+8+88/8) \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 244 &:= (1+1) \times (1+11^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 + 22^2/2 \\
&:= (3^{3+3} + 3)/3 \\
&:= 4 + 4^4 - 4 \times 4 \\
&:= 5/5 + (5 - (5+5)/5)^5 \\
&:= ((6+6)/6)^6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6) \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7 - 7) - 7/7 \\
&:= (8+8) \times (8+8) - (88+8)/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9+9) + 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 245 &:= 1 + (1+1) \times (1+11^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 + (22^2 + 2)/2 \\
&:= 3 + (3^{3+3} - 3)/3 \\
&:= 4^4 - 44/4 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 \times (5+5) - 5 \\
&:= (6+6/6) \times (6 \times 6 - 6/6) \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7 - 7) \\
&:= (8+8) \times (8+8) - 88/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9+9) + (9+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 246 &:= (1+1) \times (1+1+11^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 + 22^2/2 + 2 \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times 3 \times 3^3 \\
&:= 4^4 + (4 - 44)/4 \\
&:= 5/5 + 5 \times 5 \times (5+5) - 5 \\
&:= 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) - 6 \\
&:= 7/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7 - 7) \\
&:= (8+8) \times (8+8) + (8 - 88)/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9+9) + (9+9+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 247 &:= 1 + (1+1) \times (1+1+11^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 + (22^2 + 2)/2 + 2 \\
&:= 3 + (3^{3+3} + 3)/3 \\
&:= 4^4 - 4/4 - 4 - 4 \\
&:= 5 + (5 - (5+5)/5)^5 - 5/5 \\
&:= 6/6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) - 6 \\
&:= (7+7)/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7 - 7) \\
&:= (8+8) \times (8+8) - 8 - 8/8 \\
&:= ((9+9)/9)^{9-9/9} - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 248 &:= (1+1) \times (1+1+1+11^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 + 22^2/2 + 2 + 2 \\
&:= 3 + (3^{3+3} - 3)/3 + 3 \\
&:= 4^4 - 4 - 4 \\
&:= 5 + (5 - (5+5)/5)^5 \\
&:= 6 + 66 \times 66/(6+6+6) \\
&:= 77 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7)/(7+7) \\
&:= (8+8) \times (8+8) - 8 \\
&:= 9/9 + ((9+9)/9)^{9-9/9} - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 249 &:= 1 + (1+1) \times (1+1+1+11^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 + (22^2 + 2)/2 + 2 + 2 \\
&:= 33 + (3+3)^3 \\
&:= 4 + 4^4 - 44/4 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 \times (5+5) - 5/5 \\
&:= 6 + (6 \times 6/(6+6))^{6-6/6} \\
&:= ((7+7)/7)^{7/7+7} - 7 \\
&:= 8/8 + (8+8) \times (8+8) - 8 \\
&:= 9 + (999/9+9) \times (9+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 250 &:= (11 - 1) \times (1 + (1+1) \times (1+11)) \\
&:= 2 \times ((22/2)^2 + 2 + 2) \\
&:= 3 + 3 + (3^{3+3} + 3)/3 \\
&:= 4^4 - 4 - (4+4)/4 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 \times (5+5) \\
&:= 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) - (6+6)/6 \\
&:= (7 - (7+7)/7) \times (7 \times 7 + 7/7) \\
&:= (8+8) \times (8+8) + (8+8)/8 - 8 \\
&:= 9 + 9 \times (9+9+9) - (9+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 251 &:= 11 + (1+1) \times (11^{1+1} - 1) \\
&:= (22^2 + 22)/2 - 2 \\
&:= 3 \times 3 + (3^{3+3} - 3)/3 \\
&:= 4^4 - 4/4 - 4 \\
&:= 5/5 + 5 \times 5 \times (5+5) \\
&:= 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) - 6/6 \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7 - 7) - 7/7 \\
&:= 8 + (8/8 + 8) \times (88/8 + 8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 + 9 \times (9+9+9) - 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 252 &:= (1+11) \times (11+11-1) \\
&:= 2^{2 \times (2+2)} - 2 - 2 \\
&:= 3 \times (3 \times 3^3 + 3) \\
&:= 4^4 - 4 \\
&:= (5+5)/5 + 5 \times 5 \times (5+5) \\
&:= 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7 - 7) \\
&:= (8 \times 8 \times 8 - 8) \times 8/(8+8) \\
&:= 9 + 9 \times (9+9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 253 &:= 11 \times (1 + 11 + 11) \\
&:= (22^2 + 22)/2 \\
&:= 3 \times 3 + (3^{3+3} + 3)/3 \\
&:= 4/4 + 4^4 - 4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 + (5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5 \\
&:= 6/6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7 - 7) + 7/7 \\
&:= 8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) - 88/8 \\
&:= 9 + 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 254 &:= 1 + 11 \times (1 + 11 + 11) \\
&:= 2^{2 \times (2+2)} - 2 \\
&:= (3^{3+3} + 33)/3 \\
&:= 4^4 - (4 + 4)/4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5) - 5/5 \\
&:= (6 + 6)/6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) \\
&:= 77 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7 \times 7 \\
&:= (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) - (8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= 99/9 + 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 255 &:= 111 + (1 + 11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2^{2 \times (2+2)} - 2/2 \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times (3 \times 3^3 + 3) \\
&:= 4^4 - 4/4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 - 77/7 - 77 \\
&:= (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) - 8/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + (99 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 256 &:= (1 + 1)^{(1+1)^{1+1+1}} \\
&:= 2^{2 \times (2+2)} \\
&:= (3/3 + 3)^{3/3+3} \\
&:= 4^4 \\
&:= (5 - 5/5)^{5-5/5} \\
&:= ((6 + 6)/6)^{(6+6)/6+6} \\
&:= ((7 + 7)/7)^{7/7+7} \\
&:= (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) \\
&:= ((9 + 9)/9)^{9-9/9}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 257 &:= 1 + (1 + 1)^{(1+1)^{1+1+1}} \\
&:= 2/2 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)} \\
&:= 3 + (3^{3+3} + 33)/3 \\
&:= 4/4 + 4^4 \\
&:= (5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5) - 55 \\
&:= 6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) - 6/6 \\
&:= 7/7 + ((7 + 7)/7)^{7/7+7} \\
&:= 8/8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) \\
&:= 9/9 + ((9 + 9)/9)^{9-9/9}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 258 &:= 1 + 1 + (1 + 1)^{(1+1)^{1+1+1}} \\
&:= 2 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)} \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times (3 \times 3^3 + 3) + 3 \\
&:= 4^4 + (4 + 4)/4 \\
&:= (5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) - 55 \\
&:= 6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) \\
&:= (7 - 7/7) \times ((7/7 - 7) + 7 \times 7) \\
&:= (8 + 8)/8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) \\
&:= 99 + 9 \times (9 + 9) - (9 + 9 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 259 &:= 1 + 1 + 1 + (1 + 1)^{(1+1)^{1+1+1}} \\
&:= 2 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2/2 \\
&:= 3 + (3/3 + 3)^{3/3+3} \\
&:= 4 + 4^4 - 4/4 \\
&:= 5 \times 55 - 55/5 - 5 \\
&:= 6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) + 6/6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 - 77 - 7 \\
&:= 88/8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \\
&:= 99 + 9 \times (9 + 9) - (9 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 260 &:= (1 + 1) \times (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11) \\
&:= 2 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2 \\
&:= 3 + (3^{3+3} + 33)/3 + 3 \\
&:= 4 + 4^4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5) + 5 \\
&:= 6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) + (6 + 6)/6 \\
&:= 7/7 + 7 \times 7 \times 7 - 77 - 7 \\
&:= (8 \times 8 \times 8 + 8) \times 8/(8 + 8) \\
&:= 99 + 9 \times (9 + 9) - 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 261 &:= (1 + 1) \times (11 \times (1 + 11) - 1) - 1 \\
&:= 2 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2/2 + 2 \\
&:= 3 \times (3 \times 3^3 + 3 + 3) \\
&:= 4 + 4/4 + 4^4 \\
&:= 5 + (5 - 5/5)^{5-5/5} \\
&:= 6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 77 + 7 \times 7 \\
&:= (88/8 - 8) \times (88 - 8/8) \\
&:= 99 + 9 \times (9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 262 &:= (1 + 1) \times (11 \times (1 + 11) - 1) \\
&:= 22^2 - 222 \\
&:= 3 + (3/3 + 3)^{3/3+3} + 3 \\
&:= 4 + (4 + 4)/4 + 4^4 \\
&:= 5 + (5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5) - 55 \\
&:= 6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^{(6+6)/6+6} \\
&:= (7 \times 7 \times 77 - 7)/(7 + 7) - 7 \\
&:= 8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) - (8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= 9/9 + 9 \times (9 + 9) + 99
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 263 &:= (1 + 1) \times 11 \times (1 + 11) - 1 \\
&:= 22 + (22^2 - 2)/2 \\
&:= (33 \times (3^3 - 3) - 3)/3 \\
&:= 4 + 4^4 - 4/4 + 4 \\
&:= 5 \times 55 - (55 + 5)/5 \\
&:= 66/6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 + 7)/7)^{7/7+7} \\
&:= 8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) - 8/8 \\
&:= 9 + 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 99/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 264 &:= (1 + 1) \times 11 \times (1 + 11) \\
&:= 2 \times 22 \times (2 + 2 + 2) \\
&:= 33 \times (3 \times 3 - 3/3) \\
&:= 4 + 4^4 + 4 \\
&:= 5 \times 55 - 55/5 \\
&:= 6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) + 6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 - (7 + 7)/7 - 77 \\
&:= 8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 + 9) + 999/9 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 265 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times 11 \times (1 + 11) \\
&:= 22 + (22^2 + 2)/2 \\
&:= (33 \times (3^3 - 3) + 3)/3 \\
&:= 4 + 4/4 + 4^4 + 4 \\
&:= 5 \times 55 - 5 - 5 \\
&:= 6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) + 6/6 + 6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7/7 - 77 \\
&:= 8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8/8 \\
&:= 9 + ((9 + 9)/9)^{9-9/9}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 266 &:= (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11 \times (1 + 11)) \\
&:= 222 + 2 \times 22 \\
&:= 3 + (33 \times (3^3 - 3) - 3)/3 \\
&:= 4^4 + (44 - 4)/4 \\
&:= 5/5 + 5 \times 55 - (5 + 5) \\
&:= (6/6 + 6) \times ((6 + 6)/6 + 6 \times 6) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 - 77 \\
&:= 8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + (8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= 9 + ((9 + 9)/9)^{9-9/9} + 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 267 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11 \times (1 + 11)) \\
&:= 22/2 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)} \\
&:= 3 \times 3 \times (3^3 + 3) - 3 \\
&:= 4^4 + 44/4 \\
&:= 5 \times 55 + ((5 + 5)/5 - 5 - 5) \\
&:= 666 \times 6/(6 + 6) - 66 \\
&:= 7/7 + 7 \times 7 \times 7 - 77 \\
&:= 88/8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) \\
&:= 99/9 + ((9 + 9)/9)^{9-9/9}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 268 &:= (1+1) \times (1+1+11 \times (1+11)) \\
&:= 2+222+2 \times 22 \\
&:= 3+(33 \times (3^3-3)+3)/3 \\
&:= 4+4^4+4+4 \\
&:= 5 \times 5+(5-(5+5)/5)^5 \\
&:= (6-(6+6)/6) \times (66+6/6) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7+(7+7)/7-77 \\
&:= 8+(8 \times 8 \times 8+8) \times 8/(8+8) \\
&:= 9+9 \times (9+9)-(9+9)/9+99
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 269 &:= 1+(1+1) \times (1+1+11 \times (1+11)) \\
&:= 2+2^{2 \times (2+2)}+22/2 \\
&:= 3^3+(3^{3+3}-3)/3 \\
&:= 4+4/4+4^4+4+4 \\
&:= 5 \times 55-(5/5+5) \\
&:= 6+6 \times (6 \times 6+6)+66/6 \\
&:= (7 \times 7 \times 77-7)/(7+7) \\
&:= 8+(88/8-8) \times (88-8)/8 \\
&:= 9+9 \times (9+9)-9/9+99
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 270 &:= (11-1) \times (1+1+1)^{1+1+1} \\
&:= 222+2 \times (22+2) \\
&:= 3 \times 3 \times (3^3+3) \\
&:= 4+(44-4)/4+4^4 \\
&:= 5 \times 55-5 \\
&:= 666-6 \times 66 \\
&:= (7 \times 7 \times 77+7)/(7+7) \\
&:= 8+8+(8+8) \times (8+8)-(8+8)/8 \\
&:= 9+9 \times (9+9)+99
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 271 &:= 1+(11-1) \times (1+1+1)^{1+1+1} \\
&:= 2+2^{2 \times (2+2)}+22/2+2 \\
&:= 3^3+(3^{3+3}+3)/3 \\
&:= 4+44/4+4^4 \\
&:= 5/5+5 \times 55-5 \\
&:= 66+6 \times 6 \times 6-66/6 \\
&:= 7+7 \times 7 \times 7-(7+7)/7-77 \\
&:= 8+(8+8) \times (8+8)-8/8+8 \\
&:= 9+9 \times (9+9)+99+9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 272 &:= (1+1+11) \times (11+11-1)-1 \\
&:= 2^{2+2}+2^{2 \times (2+2)} \\
&:= 3+(3^{3+3}-3)/3+3^3 \\
&:= 4 \times 4+4^4 \\
&:= 5 \times 55+(5+5)/5-5 \\
&:= 6+(6/6+6) \times ((6+6)/6+6 \times 6) \\
&:= 7+7 \times 7 \times 7-7/7-77 \\
&:= 8+(8+8) \times (8+8)+8 \\
&:= 99+99/9+9 \times (9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 273 &:= (1+1+11) \times (11+11-1) \\
&:= (22/2+2) \times (22-2/2) \\
&:= 3+3 \times 3 \times (3^3+3) \\
&:= 4 \times 4+4/4+4^4 \\
&:= 5 \times 55-(5+5)/5 \\
&:= 6+666 \times 6/(6+6)-66 \\
&:= 7+7 \times 7 \times 7-77 \\
&:= 8+(8+8) \times (8+8)+8/8+8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9)+999/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 274 &:= 11 \times (1+(1+1) \times (1+11))-1 \\
&:= 2+2^{2 \times (2+2)}+2^{2+2} \\
&:= 3+3 \times 3 \times (3^3+3)+3/3 \\
&:= 4 \times 4+((4+4)/4+4^4) \\
&:= 5 \times 55-5/5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6+((6+6)/6)^6-6 \\
&:= 7+7 \times 7 \times 7-77+7/7 \\
&:= 8+(8+8) \times (8+8)+(8+8)/8+8 \\
&:= 9+((9+9)/9)^{9-9/9}+9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 275 &:= 11 \times (1+(1+1) \times (1+11)) \\
&:= 22+(22^2+22)/2 \\
&:= 33+(3^{3+3}-3)/3 \\
&:= 4+44/4+4^4+4 \\
&:= 5 \times 55 \\
&:= 66+6 \times 6 \times 6-6/6-6 \\
&:= 77/7 \times (77/7+7+7) \\
&:= 8+(8+8) \times (8+8)+88/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9)+(999+9+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 276 &:= (1+11) \times (1+11+11) \\
&:= 22+2^{2 \times (2+2)}-2 \\
&:= 33+3 \times 3 \times 3^3 \\
&:= 4+4 \times 4+4^4 \\
&:= 5 \times 55+5/5 \\
&:= 66+6 \times 6 \times 6-6 \\
&:= 7+(7 \times 7 \times 77-7)/(7+7) \\
&:= 8+(8 \times 8 \times 8+8) \times 8/(8+8)+8 \\
&:= (99/9+9 \times 9) \times (9+9+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 277 &:= 1+(1+11) \times (1+11+11) \\
&:= ((22+2)^2-22)/2 \\
&:= 33+(3^{3+3}+3)/3 \\
&:= 4+4 \times 4+4^4+4/4 \\
&:= 5 \times 55+(5+5)/5 \\
&:= 66+6 \times 6 \times 6-6+6/6 \\
&:= 7+(7 \times 7 \times 77+7)/(7+7) \\
&:= (8-8/8+8) \times (88/8+8)-8 \\
&:= 99+99-(9+9)/9+9 \times 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 278 &:= (1+1111)/(1+1+1+1) \\
&:= 22+2^{2 \times (2+2)} \\
&:= 3+(3^{3+3}-3)/3+33 \\
&:= 4^4+44 \times 4/(4+4) \\
&:= 5+5 \times 55-(5+5)/5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6+66 \times 66/(6+6+6) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7+(77+7)/7-77 \\
&:= 88+8 \times (8+8+8)-(8+8)/8 \\
&:= 99+9 \times 9-9/9+99
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 279 &:= 1+(1+1111)/(1+1+1+1) \\
&:= 2+((22+2)^2-22)/2 \\
&:= 3 \times (3 \times (3^3+3)+3) \\
&:= 4+44/4+4^4+4+4 \\
&:= 5+5 \times 55-5/5 \\
&:= 6 \times 66-666/6-6 \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7-7)-7/7-7-7 \\
&:= 88+8 \times (8+8+8)-8/8 \\
&:= 99+99+9 \times 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 280 &:= 111+(1+1+11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2+2^{2 \times (2+2)}+22 \\
&:= (3+3)^3+(3/3+3)^3 \\
&:= 4+4 \times 4+4^4+4 \\
&:= 5+5 \times 55 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6+((6+6)/6)^6 \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7-7)-7-7 \\
&:= 88+8 \times (8+8+8) \\
&:= 9/9+99+99+9 \times 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 281 &:= 1+111+(1+1+11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2+((22+2)^2-22)/2+2 \\
&:= 3^3+(3^{3+3}+33)/3 \\
&:= 4+4 \times 4+4^4+4/4+4 \\
&:= 5+5 \times 55+5/5 \\
&:= 66+6 \times 6 \times 6-6/6 \\
&:= 7/7+7 \times (7 \times 7-7)-7-7 \\
&:= 8/8+8 \times (8+8+8)+88 \\
&:= 9+99/9+9 \times (9+9)+99
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 282 &:= (1+1) \times ((1+11)^{1+1}-1-1-1) \\
&:= 2+2^{2 \times (2+2)}+22+2 \\
&:= 3+3 \times (3 \times (3^3+3)+3) \\
&:= 4+44 \times 4/(4+4)+4^4 \\
&:= 5+5 \times 55+(5+5)/5 \\
&:= 66+6 \times 6 \times 6 \\
&:= 77+((7+7)/7)^7+77 \\
&:= 88+8 \times (8+8+8)+(8+8)/8 \\
&:= 9+999/9+9 \times (9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 283 &:= (1+1) \times ((1+11)^{1+1} - 1 - 1) - 1 \\
&:= ((22+2)^2 - 2)/2 - 2 - 2 \\
&:= 3 + (3/3+3)^3 + (3+3)^3 \\
&:= 4 \times 4 + 44/4 + 4^4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 \times 55 - (5+5)/5 + 5 \\
&:= 66 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 + 6/6 \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 77/7 \\
&:= 8 + 8 + (8+8) \times (8+8) + 88/8 \\
&:= 9 + ((9+9)/9)^{9-9/9} + 9 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 284 &:= (1+1) \times ((1+11)^{1+1} - 1 - 1) \\
&:= 2 \times ((2 \times (2+2+2))^2 - 2) \\
&:= (3/3+3) \times ((3+3)^3 - 3)/3 \\
&:= 44 + 4^4 - 4 \times 4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 \times 55 - 5/5 + 5 \\
&:= 66 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 + (6+6)/6 \\
&:= (7-77)/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) \\
&:= (8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - 8) \times 8/(8+8) \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9) + (999+99)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 285 &:= (1+1) \times 11 \times (1+1+11) - 1 \\
&:= ((22+2)^2 - 2)/2 - 2 \\
&:= 3 \times (3 \times 33 - 3) - 3 \\
&:= 44 + 4/4 - 4 \times 4 + 4^4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 \times 55 + 5 \\
&:= 6 \times 66 - 666/6 \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - (7+7)/7 - 7 \\
&:= (8-8/8+8) \times (88/8+8) \\
&:= (99-9/9) \times (9+9+9)/9 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 286 &:= (1+1) \times 11 \times (1+1+11) \\
&:= 22 \times (22/2+2) \\
&:= 33/3 \times (3^3 - 3/3) \\
&:= 44 + 44 \times 44/(4+4) \\
&:= 5 \times 55 + 55/5 \\
&:= 6 + ((6+6)/6)^6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 7/7 - 7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 + (8+8) \times 888/(8 \times 8) \\
&:= 99 \times (9-9/9+9+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 287 &:= (1+1) \times (1+11)^{1+1} - 1 \\
&:= ((22+2)^2 - 2)/2 \\
&:= 3 \times (3 \times 33 - 3) - 3/3 \\
&:= 4^4 + 4 \times (4+4) - 4/4 \\
&:= 5 \times 55 + (55+5)/5 \\
&:= 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6 + 6) - 6/6 \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 7 \\
&:= 88 + 88 + 888/8 \\
&:= (99 \times (9+9+9) - 9)/9 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 288 &:= (1+1) \times (1+11)^{1+1} \\
&:= (22+2)^2/2 \\
&:= 3 \times (3 \times 33 - 3) \\
&:= 4^4 + 4 \times (4+4) \\
&:= (5^5 + 5)/(5+5) - 5 \times 5 \\
&:= 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6 + 6) \\
&:= 7/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 7 \\
&:= 8 + 8 \times (8+8+8) + 88 \\
&:= 9 + (99+99) + 9 \times 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 289 &:= 1 + (1+1) \times (1+11)^{1+1} \\
&:= (2^{2+2} + 2/2)^2 \\
&:= 3/3 + 3 \times (3 \times 33 - 3) \\
&:= 44 + 4^4 - 44/4 \\
&:= 5 \times (55 + 5) - 55/5 \\
&:= 6/6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6 + 6) \\
&:= (7+7)/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 7 \\
&:= (8/8 + 8 + 8)^{(8+8)/8} \\
&:= (9+9-9/9)^{(9+9)/9}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 290 &:= (1+1) \times (1 + (1+11)^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 + (22+2)^2/2 \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times (3 \times 33 - 3) - 3/3 \\
&:= 44 + (4-44)/4 + 4^4 \\
&:= 5 + (5 \times 55 + 5) + 5 \\
&:= (6+6)/6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 77/7 \\
&:= 8/8 + (8/8 + 8 + 8)^{(8+8)/8} \\
&:= (9/9+9) \times (99/9+9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 291 &:= 1 + (1+1) \times (1 + (1+11)^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 + (2^{2+2} + 2/2)^2 \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times (3 \times 33 - 3) \\
&:= 4 + 4 \times (4+4) - 4/4 + 4^4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 \times 55 + 55/5 \\
&:= 6 + 6 \times 66 - 666/6 \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - (7+7+7)/7 \\
&:= 88 + 8 \times (8+8+8) + 88/8 \\
&:= 99 + 9 \times 9 + 999/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 292 &:= (1+1) \times (1+1+(1+11)^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 + (22+2)^2/2 + 2 \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times (3 \times 33 - 3) + 3/3 \\
&:= 4 + 4 \times (4+4) + 4^4 \\
&:= 5 + (55+5)/5 + 5 \times 55 \\
&:= 6 + ((6+6)/6)^6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 + 6 \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - (7+7)/7 \\
&:= (8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) + 8) \times 8/(8+8) \\
&:= 99 + 9 \times 9 + (999+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 293 &:= 1 + (1+1) \times (1+1+1+11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 + (2^{2+2} + 2/2)^2 + 2 \\
&:= 3 \times 3 \times 33 - 3/3 - 3 \\
&:= 4 + 4 \times (4+4) + 4^4 + 4/4 \\
&:= 5 + (5^5 + 5)/(5+5) - 5 \times 5 \\
&:= 6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6 + 6) - 6/6 \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 7/7 \\
&:= 8 + (8-8/8+8) \times (88/8+8) \\
&:= ((9+9+9) \times (99-9/9) - 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 294 &:= (1+1) \times (1+1+1+(1+11)^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 + (22+2)^2/2 + 2 + 2 \\
&:= 3 \times 3 \times 33 - 3 \\
&:= 44 + 4^4 - (4+4)/4 - 4 \\
&:= 5 \times (55 + 5) - 5/5 - 5 \\
&:= 6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) \\
&:= 8 + 8 \times 8 + (8+8) \times 888/(8 \times 8) \\
&:= ((9+9+9)/9) \times (99-9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 295 &:= 11 \times (1+1+1)^{1+1+1} - 1 - 1 \\
&:= 2 + (2^{2+2} + 2/2)^2 + 2 + 2 \\
&:= 3/3 + 3 \times 3 \times 33 - 3 \\
&:= 44 + 4^4 - 4/4 - 4 \\
&:= 5 \times (55 + 5) - 5 \\
&:= 6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6 + 6) + 6/6 \\
&:= 7/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) \\
&:= 8 + 88 + 88 + 888/8 \\
&:= (99 \times (9+9+9) - (9+9))/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 296 &:= 11 \times (1+1+1)^{1+1+1} - 1 \\
&:= 2 \times ((2 \times (2+2+2))^2 + 2 + 2) \\
&:= 3 \times 3 \times 33 - 3/3 \\
&:= 44 + 4^4 - 4 \\
&:= 5/5 + 5 \times (55 + 5) - 5 \\
&:= ((6+6)/6+6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6/6) \\
&:= (7+7)/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 888/(8+8+8) \\
&:= (99 \times (9+9+9) - 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 297 &:= 11 \times (1+1+1)^{1+1+1} \\
&:= ((22+2)^2 + 22)/2 - 2 \\
&:= 3 \times 3 \times 33 \\
&:= 44 + 4^4 + 4/4 - 4 \\
&:= 5 \times 55 + (55+5)/5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 66/(6+(6+6)/6) \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) + (7+7+7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + (8/8 + 8 + 8)^{(8+8)/8} \\
&:= 99 + 99 + 99
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 298 &:= 1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1} \\
&:= 2 \times 22 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)} - 2 \\
&:= 3/3 + 3 \times 3 \times 33 \\
&:= 44 + 4^4 - (4+4)/4 \\
&:= 55 + (5 - (5+5)/5)^5 \\
&:= (66 - 6)/6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6 + 6) \\
&:= 77/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 7 \\
&:= (88 \times (88/8 + 8 + 8) + 8)/8 \\
&:= (99 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 299 &:= 11 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)^{1+1} \\
&:= ((22 + 2)^2 + 22)/2 \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times 3 \times 33 - 3/3) \\
&:= 44 + 4^4 - 4/4 \\
&:= 5 \times (55 + 5) - 5/5 \\
&:= 66/6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - (7 + 7)/7) \\
&:= (8 \times (888 + 8) + 8)/(8 + 8 + 8) \\
&:= (99 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 300 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 \times 22 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)} \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times 3 \times 33 \\
&:= 44 + 4^4 \\
&:= 5 \times (55 + 5) \\
&:= (6 - 66) \times (6/6 - 6) \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 7/7 \\
&:= (8 \times 8 \times 8 + 88) \times 8/(8 + 8) \\
&:= (9/9 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 301 &:= 1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 + ((22 + 2)^2 + 22)/2 \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times 3 \times 33 + 3/3 \\
&:= 44 + 4/4 + 4^4 \\
&:= 5/5 + 5 \times (55 + 5) \\
&:= 6/6 + (6 - 66) \times (6/6 - 6) \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) \\
&:= 8 + (8 - 8/8 + 8) \times (88/8 + 8) + 8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + (99/9 + 9) \times 99/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 302 &:= 1 + 1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)^{1+1} \\
&:= (2^{2+2} + 2)^2 - 22 \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times 3 \times 33 - 3/3 + 3 \\
&:= 44 + (4 + 4)/4 + 4^4 \\
&:= (5 + 5)/5 + 5 \times (55 + 5) \\
&:= 6 + ((6 + 6)/6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6/6) \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) + 7/7 \\
&:= (88 - 8/8 + 8 \times 8) \times (8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= (9 \times (9 + 9) - 99/9) \times (9 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 303 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + (11 - 1)^{1+1}) \\
&:= 222 + (2/2 + 2)^{2+2} \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times 3 \times 33 + 3) \\
&:= 4 + 44 - 4/4 + 4^4 \\
&:= (5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) - 5 - 5 \\
&:= 6 + 6 \times 6 \times 66/(6 + (6 + 6)/6) \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) + (7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 888/8 \\
&:= 9 + (99 - 9/9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 304 &:= 1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + (11 - 1)^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 + (2^{2+2} + 2)^2 - 22 \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times 3 \times 33 + 3/3 + 3 \\
&:= 4 + 44 + 4^4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 \times (55 + 5) - 5/5 \\
&:= ((6 + 6)/6 + 6) \times ((6 + 6)/6 + 6 \times 6) \\
&:= (7/7 + 7) \times (7 \times 7 - 77/7) \\
&:= (8 + 8) \times (88/8 + 8) \\
&:= (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - 99/9 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 305 &:= (11 \times 111 - 1)/(1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \\
&:= 2 + (2/2 + 2)^{2+2} + 222 \\
&:= 333 - 3^3 - 3/3 \\
&:= 4 + 44 + 4^4 + 4/4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 \times (55 + 5) \\
&:= (6 - 6/6) \times (66 - 6 + 6/6) \\
&:= 77/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) \\
&:= 8/8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 88/8) \\
&:= 9 + (99 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 306 &:= (1 + 1) \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 11) - 1) \\
&:= 22 \times (2^{2+2} - 2) - 2 \\
&:= 3 \times (3 \times 33 + 3) \\
&:= 4 + 44 + 4^4 + (4 + 4)/4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 \times (55 + 5) + 5/5 \\
&:= 6 + (6 - 66) \times (6/6 - 6) \\
&:= (7 - 7/7) \times (7 \times 7 + (7 + 7)/7) \\
&:= (8 + 8)/8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 88/8) \\
&:= (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 - 9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 307 &:= 111 + (1 + 1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1} \\
&:= (22 + 2/2)^2 - 222 \\
&:= 3/3 + 3 \times (3 \times 33 + 3) \\
&:= 4 + 44 - 4/4 + 4^4 + 4 \\
&:= (5^5 - 55)/(5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 + (6 - 66) \times (6/6 - 6) + 6/6 \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 7/7 + 7 \\
&:= 88 \times (8 \times 8 - 8)/(8 + 8) - 8/8 \\
&:= 9 + (99 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 308 &:= (1 + 1) \times 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 11) \\
&:= 22 \times (2^{2+2} - 2) \\
&:= 33/3 + 3 \times 3 \times 33 \\
&:= 4 + 44 + 4^4 + 4 \\
&:= (5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) - 5 \\
&:= 66 + 66 \times 66/(6 + 6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) + 7 \\
&:= 88 \times (8 \times 8 - 8)/(8 + 8) \\
&:= 99/9 \times (9/9 + 9 + 9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 309 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 11) \\
&:= 22 + ((22 + 2)^2 - 2)/2 \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times (3 \times 33 + 3) \\
&:= 4^4 + (4^4 - 44)/4 \\
&:= 5 + (5 \times (55 + 5) - 5/5) + 5 \\
&:= 66 + (6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^{6-6/6} \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) + 7/7 + 7 \\
&:= 8/8 + 88 \times (8 \times 8 - 8)/(8 + 8) \\
&:= 99 + 999/9 + 99
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 310 &:= (1 + 1) \times (11 + (1 + 11)^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 + 22 \times (2^{2+2} - 2) \\
&:= ((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3 - 33 \\
&:= 44 + (44 - 4)/4 + 4^4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 \times (55 + 5) + 5 \\
&:= (6 - 6/6) \times ((6 + 6)/6 - 6 + 66) \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) + (7 + 7)/7 + 7 \\
&:= 88 + (8 + 8) \times 888/(8 \times 8) \\
&:= 99 + 99 + (999 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 311 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times (11 + (1 + 11)^{1+1}) \\
&:= 22 + (2^{2+2} + 2/2)^2 \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times 3 \times 33 + 33/3 \\
&:= 44 + 44/4 + 4^4 \\
&:= 55/5 + 5 \times (55 + 5) \\
&:= 6 + (6 - 6/6) \times (66 - 6 + 6/6) \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) + (77 - 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + 888/8 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8) \\
&:= (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - (99 + 9 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 312 &:= (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 11) \\
&:= (22 + 2) \times (22/2 + 2) \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times (3 \times 33 + 3) + 3 \\
&:= 4 + 4 + 4 + 44 + 4^4 \\
&:= (5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 \times ((6 + 6)/6)^6 - 6 - 6 \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) + 77/7 \\
&:= 8 + (8 + 8) \times (88/8 + 8) \\
&:= (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - (99 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 313 &:= 1 + (1+1) \times (1+11) \times (1+1+11) \\
&:= (2^{2+2} + 2)^2 - 22/2 \\
&:= 3 + (3/3 + 3 + 3)^3 - 33 \\
&:= 4 + (4^4 - 44)/4 + 4^4 \\
&:= (5^5 + 5)/(5+5) \\
&:= 6 \times (66 - 6 - 6) - 66/6 \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) + (77 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + (8+8) \times (88/8 + 8) + 8/8 \\
&:= (9+9) \times (9+9) - 99/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 314 &:= (1+1) \times (1 + (1+11) \times (1+1+11)) \\
&:= 2 + (22+2) \times (22/2 + 2) \\
&:= 3 \times 33 + (3+3)^3 - 3/3 \\
&:= 4^4 + (4^4 - 4 - 4)/4 - 4 \\
&:= 5/5 + (5^5 + 5)/(5+5) \\
&:= (6 - 6/6) \times ((6+6)/6)^6 - 6 \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - (7/7 + 77) \\
&:= 8 + (8+8) \times (88/8 + 8) + (8+8)/8 \\
&:= (9+9) \times (9+9) - 9/9 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 315 &:= ((1+1)^{1+11} - 1)/(1+1+11) \\
&:= 22^2 - (22/2 + 2)^2 \\
&:= 3 \times (3 \times 33 + 3 + 3) \\
&:= 4^4 + (4^4 - 4)/4 - 4 \\
&:= (5 \times 5 + 5^5)/(5+5) \\
&:= (666 - 6 \times 6) \times 6/(6+6) \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - 77 \\
&:= 88/8 + (8+8) \times (88/8 + 8) \\
&:= (9+9) \times (9+9) - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 316 &:= (1+1) \times ((1+1+11)^{1+1} - 11) \\
&:= 2 \times (2 \times ((2/2) + 2)^{2+2} - 2) \\
&:= (3/3 + 3 + 3)^3 - 3^3 \\
&:= 4 \times 4 + 44 + 4^4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 \times (55 + 5) + 55/5 \\
&:= 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) + ((6+6)/6)^6 \\
&:= 7/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - 77 \\
&:= 8 + 88 \times (8 \times 8 - 8)/(8+8) \\
&:= 9/9 + (9+9) \times (9+9) - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 317 &:= 1 + (1+1) \times ((1+1+11)^{1+1} - 11) \\
&:= 2 + 22^2 - (22/2 + 2)^2 \\
&:= 333 + 33/3 - 3^3 \\
&:= 4^4 + (4^4 + 4)/4 - 4 \\
&:= 5 + (5^5 - 5)/(5+5) \\
&:= 66 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) - 6/6 \\
&:= (77/7 + 7)^{(7+7)/7} - 7 \\
&:= 8 + 88 \times (8 \times 8 - 8)/(8+8) + 8/8 \\
&:= (9+9)/9 + (9+9) \times (9+9) - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 318 &:= (1+1+1) \times (111 - 1) - 1 - 11 \\
&:= 2^{2+2} \times (22 - 2) - 2 \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times 33 + (3+3)^3 \\
&:= 4^4 + (4^4 - 4 - 4)/4 \\
&:= 5 + (5^5 + 5)/(5+5) \\
&:= 66 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 - 77/7 - 7 - 7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 + (8+8) \times (8+8) - (8+8)/8 \\
&:= 9 + 999/9 + 99 + 99
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 319 &:= 11 \times ((11 - 1) \times (1+1+1) - 1) \\
&:= 2^{2+2} \times (22 - 2) - 2/2 \\
&:= 333 - 33/3 - 3 \\
&:= 4^4 + (4^4 - 4)/4 \\
&:= 5 + (5^5 + 5)/(5+5) + 5/5 \\
&:= 66 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) + 6/6 \\
&:= 7 + 7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) + 77/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 + (8+8) \times (8+8) - 8/8 \\
&:= 99/9 \times (99/9 + 9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 320 &:= (11 - 1) \times (11 \times (1+1+1) - 1) \\
&:= 2^{2+2} \times (22 - 2) \\
&:= 333 + (3 - 33)/3 - 3 \\
&:= 4 \times 4 \times (4 \times 4 + 4) \\
&:= (5+5) \times ((5+5)/5)^5 \\
&:= (6 - 6/6) \times ((6+6)/6)^6 \\
&:= (7/7 + 7) \times (7 \times 7 - (7+7)/7 - 7) \\
&:= 8 \times (8+8+8+8+8) \\
&:= (9 - 9/9) \times (9 \times 9 \times 9 - 9)/(9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 321 &:= (1+1+1) \times 111 - 1 - 11 \\
&:= 2/2 + (2^{2+2} \times (22 - 2)) \\
&:= 333 - (3 \times 3 + 3) \\
&:= 4^4 + (4^4 + 4)/4 \\
&:= 5/5 + ((5+5) \times ((5+5)/5)^5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 + (666/6 - 6) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 - (7/7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \\
&:= 8/8 + (((8+8) \times (8+8)) + 8 \times 8) \\
&:= (9+9) \times (9+9) - (9+9+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 322 &:= (1+1+1) \times 111 - 11 \\
&:= ((2^{2+2} + 2)^2) - 2 \\
&:= 333 - 33/3 \\
&:= 4^4 + (((4^4 + 4) + 4)/4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 - 5)/(5+5) + 5) \\
&:= (6 \times (66 - (6+6))) - (6+6)/6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 - (7+7+7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 + (((8+8) \times (8+8)) + ((8+8)/8)) \\
&:= (9+9) \times (9+9) - (9+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 323 &:= 1 + (1+1+1) \times 111 - 11 \\
&:= ((2^{2+2} + 2)^2) - 2/2 \\
&:= 333 + ((3 - 33)/3) \\
&:= 4 + (((4^4 - 4)/4) + 4^4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 + 5)/(5+5) + 5) \\
&:= (6 \times (66 - (6+6))) - 6/6 \\
&:= 7/7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 - (7+7+7)) \\
&:= (8/8 + 8 + 8) \times (88/8 + 8) \\
&:= (9+9) \times (9+9) - 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 324 &:= ((1+1) \times (11 - 1 - 1))^{1+1} \\
&:= (2^{2+2} + 2)^2 \\
&:= 3 \times (3 \times (33 + 3)) \\
&:= 4 \times (4 - 4/4)^4 \\
&:= (5/5 + 5) \times (55 - 5/5) \\
&:= 6 \times (66 - (6+6)) \\
&:= (77/7 + 7)^{(7+7)/7} \\
&:= (((8+8)/8) + 8) + 8)^{(8+8)/8} \\
&:= (9+9) \times (9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 325 &:= 1 + ((1+1) \times (11 - 1 - 1))^{1+1} \\
&:= 2/2 + ((2^{2+2} + 2)^2) \\
&:= 3 + (333 - 33/3) \\
&:= 4 + ((4^4 + 4)/4 + 4^4) \\
&:= 5 \times (55 + 5 + 5) \\
&:= 6/6 + (6 \times (66 - (6+6))) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 - (77/7 + 7) \\
&:= (8/8 + 8 \times 8) \times ((8 - 88/8) + 8) \\
&:= 9/9 + (9+9) \times (9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 326 &:= (1+1+1) \times (111 - 1 - 1) - 1 \\
&:= 2 + ((2^{2+2} + 2)^2) \\
&:= 333 - ((3/3 + 3) + 3) \\
&:= 4 + (((4^4 + 4) + 4)/4) + 4^4 \\
&:= 5/5 + (5 \times (55 + 5 + 5)) \\
&:= 6 + ((6 - 6/6) \times ((6+6)/6)^6) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 + (((7 - 77)/7) - 7) \\
&:= 8 + (((8+8) \times (8+8)) - ((8+8)/8)) + 8 \times 8 \\
&:= (9+9)/9 + (9+9) \times (9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 327 &:= (1+1+1) \times (111 - 1 - 1) \\
&:= 2 + (((2^{2+2} + 2)^2) + 2/2) \\
&:= 333 - (3 + 3) \\
&:= 4 + (((4^4 - 4)/4) + 4^4) + 4 \\
&:= 5 + (((5^5 - 5)/(5+5) + 5) + 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 + 666/6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 - (((7+7)/7 + 7) + 7) \\
&:= 8 + (((8+8) \times (8+8)) - 8/8) + 8 \times 8 \\
&:= (9+9) \times (9+9) + ((9+9+9)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 328 &:= 1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (111 - 1 - 1) \\
&:= 2 + (((2^{2+2} + 2)^2) + 2) \\
&:= 3/3 + (333 - (3 + 3)) \\
&:= 4 + (4 \times (4 - 4/4)^4) \\
&:= 5 + (((5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) + 5) + 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 + (666 + 6)/6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 - (7/7 + 7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 + (((8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)) + 8 \times 8) \\
&:= 9 + ((99/9) \times (99/9 + 9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 329 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (111 - 1) - 1 \\
&:= 2 + (((2^{2+2} + 2)^2) + 2/2) + 2) \\
&:= 333 - (3/3 + 3) \\
&:= 4 + (((4^4 + 4)/4 + 4^4) + 4) \\
&:= 55 + (5 \times 55 - 5/5) \\
&:= 6 \times 66 - (66 + 6/6) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 - (7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 + (((8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)) + 8/8) + 8 \times 8) \\
&:= (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + ((9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 330 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (111 - 1) \\
&:= 22 \times ((22/2 + 2) + 2) \\
&:= 333 - 3 \\
&:= 4^4 + (((4^4 - 4) + 44)/4) \\
&:= 55 + 5 \times 55 \\
&:= 66 \times (6 - 6/6) \\
&:= 7/7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 - (7 + 7)) \\
&:= 88/8 \times ((88 + 88)/8 + 8) \\
&:= (999 - 9)/(9 + 9 + 9)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 331 &:= 1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (111 - 1) \\
&:= 222 + (222/2 - 2) \\
&:= 3/3 + (333 - 3) \\
&:= 4^4 + ((44 + 4^4)/4) \\
&:= 55 + (5 \times 55 + 5/5) \\
&:= 6/6 + 66 \times (6 - 6/6) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 - (77 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + ((8/8 + 8 + 8) \times (88/8 + 8)) \\
&:= 9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - ((9 + 9)/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 332 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times 111 - 1 \\
&:= 2 + (22 \times ((22/2 + 2) + 2)) \\
&:= 333 - 3/3 \\
&:= 4 + ((4 \times (4 - 4/4)^4) + 4) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + (5^5 - 55)/(5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 66 - ((6 + 6)/6)^6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 - 77/7 \\
&:= 8 + (((8 + 8)/8) + 8) + 8)^{(8+8)/8)} \\
&:= 9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - 9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 333 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times 111 \\
&:= 222 + 222/2 \\
&:= 333 \\
&:= 4^4 + ((4 - 4/4)^4 - 4) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + ((5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) - 5) \\
&:= 666 \times 6/(6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 + (7 - 77)/7 \\
&:= (88/8 - 8) \times 888/8 \\
&:= 9 + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 334 &:= 1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 111 \\
&:= 2 \times (((22/2 + 2)^2) - 2) \\
&:= 3/3 + 333 \\
&:= 444 + ((4 - 444)/4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5 \times 55 - 5/5) + 55) \\
&:= 6/6 + 666 \times 6/(6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 - ((7 + 7)/7 + 7) \\
&:= (((8 + 8 + 8) \times 888/8) + 8)/8 \\
&:= 9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 335 &:= 1 + 1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 111 \\
&:= 2 + (222/2 + 222) \\
&:= 3 + (333 - 3/3) \\
&:= 4 + (((44 + 4^4)/4) + 4^4) \\
&:= 5 + (5 \times 55 + 55) \\
&:= (6 - 6/6) \times (66 + 6/6) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 - (7/7 + 7) \\
&:= ((8 - 8/8)^{88/8-8}) - 8 \\
&:= 99/9 + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 336 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 111) \\
&:= 2 \times (2 \times (2 \times ((2 \times 22) - 2))) \\
&:= 3 + 333 \\
&:= 4 \times ((4 \times (4 \times 4 + 4)) + 4) \\
&:= (5/5 + 5) \times (55 + 5/5) \\
&:= 6 + 66 \times (6 - 6/6) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7 \\
&:= 88 + (((8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)) - 8) \\
&:= (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + (99 + 9)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 337 &:= 1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 111) \\
&:= (((22 + 2 + 2)^2) - 2)/2 \\
&:= 3 + (333 + 3/3) \\
&:= 4^4 + (4 - 4/4)^4 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + (5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 + (66 \times (6 - 6/6) + 6/6) \\
&:= 7/7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7) \\
&:= 8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - 888/8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^{9-9/9})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 338 &:= (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 \times ((22/2 + 2)^2) \\
&:= 3 + ((333 - 3/3) + 3) \\
&:= 4/4 + (((4 - 4/4)^4 + 4^4) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + (5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 + (6 \times 66 - ((6 + 6)/6)^6) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 + ((7 + 7)/7 - 7) \\
&:= 8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) + ((8 - 888)/8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)) + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 339 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 111) \\
&:= (((22 + 2 + 2)^2) + 2)/2 \\
&:= 3 + (333 + 3) \\
&:= (4 \times ((4 - 4/4)^4 + 4)) - 4/4 \\
&:= ((5^5 - 55)/5) - 5 \times 55 \\
&:= 6 + 666 \times 6/(6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 - (77/7)) \\
&:= 8 + (((8/8 + 8 + 8) \times (88/8 + 8)) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + ((999 - 9)/(9 + 9 + 9)/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 340 &:= 1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 111) \\
&:= 2 + (2 \times ((22/2 + 2)^2)) \\
&:= ((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3 - 3 \\
&:= 4 \times ((4 - 4/4)^4 + 4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5 \times 55 + 55) + 5) \\
&:= (6 - 6/6) \times (((6 + 6)/6) + 66) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 - (7 + 7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= ((8 \times 88 - 8)/(8 + 8)/8) - 8 \\
&:= ((9 - 9/9) + 9) \times (99/9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 341 &:= 11 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (111 - 1) \\
&:= 2 + (((22 + 2 + 2)^2) + 2)/2) \\
&:= 3 \times 3 + (333 - 3/3) \\
&:= 4 + ((4 - 4/4)^4 + 4^4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5/5 + 5) \times (55 + 5/5)) \\
&:= 6 + ((6 - 6/6) \times (66 + 6/6)) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 - (7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + ((88/8 - 8) \times 888/8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - 9/9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 342 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 1 + 111)) \\
&:= 2 \times (((22/2 + 2)^2) + 2) \\
&:= 3 \times 3 + 333 \\
&:= (4 - 44)/4 + ((4 + 4) \times 44) \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5) + 5 \times 5) \\
&:= 6 + (66 \times (6 - 6/6) + 6) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7/7 \\
&:= 88 + (((8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)) - ((8 + 8)/8)) \\
&:= 9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 343 &:= 11 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 111 - 1 \\
&:= 222 + (22/2)^2 \\
&:= ((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3 \\
&:= ((4 - 4/4) + 4)^{4-4/4} \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) + 5 \times 5) \\
&:= (6/6 + 6)^{6 \times 6/(6+6)} \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 \\
&:= (8 - 8/8)^{88/8-8} \\
&:= 9 + (((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9/9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 344 &:= 11 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 111 \\
&:= 2 \times (2 \times (2 \times 2 \times 22 - 2)) \\
&:= 333 + 33/3 \\
&:= 44 + (44 + 4^4) \\
&:= (5^5 - 5)/5 - (5 \times 55 + 5) \\
&:= 6 + ((6 \times 66 - ((6 + 6)/6)^6) + 6) \\
&:= 7/7 + 7 \times 7 \times 7 \\
&:= 88 + ((8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)) \\
&:= 9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + (99/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 345 &:= 1 + 11 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 111 \\
&:= 2 + ((22/2)^2 + 222) \\
&:= 3 + (333 + 3 \times 3) \\
&:= 4 + (((4 - 4/4)^4 + 4^4) + 4) \\
&:= 5^5 - (5 \times 555 + 5) \\
&:= 6 + (666 \times 6/(6 + 6) + 6) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 + (7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8/8 + (((8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)) + 88) \\
&:= 9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + ((99 + 9)/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 346 &:= 1 + 1 + 11 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 111 \\
&:= 22 + ((2^{2+2} + 2)^2) \\
&:= 3 + (((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3) \\
&:= ((4 + 4) \times 44) - ((4 + 4)/4 + 4) \\
&:= (5^5 + 5)/5 - (5 \times 55 + 5) \\
&:= 6 + ((6 - 6/6) \times (((6 + 6)/6) + 66)) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 + (7 + 7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 88 + (((8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)) + ((8 + 8)/8)) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^{9-9/9} + 9 \times 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 347 &:= 11 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 111) \\
&:= 2 + (((22/2)^2 + 222) + 2) \\
&:= 3 + (333 + 33/3) \\
&:= ((4 + 4) \times 44) - (4/4 + 4) \\
&:= (55/5 \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5) - 5 \\
&:= 6 \times (66 - 6) - (6/6 + 6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 + (77/7 - 7) \\
&:= ((8 \times 88 - 8)/(8 + 8)/8) - 8/8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times (9 + 9) - 9999/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 348 &:= 1 + 11 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 111) \\
&:= 2 \times ((2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 22) - 2) \\
&:= 3 + ((333 + 3 \times 3) + 3) \\
&:= ((4 + 4) \times 44) - 4 \\
&:= (5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 - 5 \times 55 \\
&:= 6 \times (((6 + 6)/6)^6 - 6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 - ((7 + 7)/7)) \\
&:= (8 \times 88 - 8)/((8 + 8)/8) \\
&:= ((99 + 9)/9) \times (99/9 + 9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 349 &:= 11 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1} \\
&:= (22 \times 2^{2+2}) - 2/2 - 2 \\
&:= 3 + (((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3) + 3) \\
&:= 4/4 + (((4 + 4) \times 44) - 4) \\
&:= (5^5 - 5)/5 - 5 \times 55 \\
&:= 6 \times (66 - 6) - 66/6 \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7/7) \\
&:= 8/8 + ((8 \times 88 - 8)/(8 + 8)/8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 - 9/9) + 9) \times (99/9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 350 &:= 11 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 111) \\
&:= (22 \times 2^{2+2}) - 2 \\
&:= 3 + ((333 + 33/3) + 3) \\
&:= ((4 + 4) \times 44) - (4 + 4)/4 \\
&:= 5 \times ((55 + 5 + 5) + 5) \\
&:= (6 - 6/6) \times (((6 + 6)/6)^6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times 7 \times 7 \\
&:= ((8 + 8)/8) \times (888/8 + 8 \times 8) \\
&:= (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 9 \times (9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 351 &:= 11 \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1) - 1 \\
&:= (22 \times 2^{2+2}) - 2/2 \\
&:= 3 \times (3 \times (33 + 3 + 3)) \\
&:= ((4 + 4) \times 44) - 4/4 \\
&:= (5^5 + 5)/5 - 5 \times 55 \\
&:= (666 + 6 \times 6)/((6 + 6)/6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 + 7/7) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 - 8/8)^{88/8-8}) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 352 &:= 11 \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1) \\
&:= 22 \times 2^{2+2} \\
&:= 3 \times 3 + (((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3) \\
&:= (4 + 4) \times 44 \\
&:= 55/5 \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5 \\
&:= 6 \times (66 - 6) - ((6 + 6)/6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 + ((7 + 7)/7)) \\
&:= 8 \times (88/(8 + 8)/8) \\
&:= ((9/9 + 9 + 9)^{(9+9)/9}) - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 353 &:= 1 + 11 \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1) \\
&:= 2/2 + (22 \times 2^{2+2}) \\
&:= 3 \times 3 + (333 + 33/3) \\
&:= 4/4 + ((4 + 4) \times 44) \\
&:= ((55 \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5) + 5)/5 \\
&:= 6 \times (66 - 6) - 6/6 - 6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 + (77 - 7)/7 \\
&:= 8/8 + (8 \times (88/(8 + 8)/8)) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + (99/9)) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 354 &:= 1 + 1 + 11 \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1) \\
&:= 2 + (22 \times 2^{2+2}) \\
&:= 3 + (333 + (3 \times (3 + 3))) \\
&:= (4 + 4)/4 + ((4 + 4) \times 44) \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 - 5)/5 - 5 \times 55) \\
&:= 6 \times (66 - 6) - 6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 + 77/7 \\
&:= (8 + 8)/8 + (8 \times (88/(8 + 8)/8)) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 999/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 355 &:= 11 + 11 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 111 \\
&:= 2 + ((22 \times 2^{2+2}) + 2/2) \\
&:= 3 + (((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3) + 3 \times 3) \\
&:= 4 + (((4 + 4) \times 44) - 4/4) \\
&:= 55 + (5 \times (55 + 5)) \\
&:= 6/6 + (6 \times (66 - 6) - 6) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 + (77 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 88 + (((8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)) + (88/8)) \\
&:= 99 + (((9 + 9)/9)^{9-9/9})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 356 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (11^{1+1} - (1 + 1)) - 1 \\
&:= 2 + ((22 \times 2^{2+2}) + 2) \\
&:= 3^3 + (333 - (3/3 + 3)) \\
&:= 4 + ((4 + 4) \times 44) \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 + 5)/5 - 5 \times 55) \\
&:= (6 + 6)/6 + (6 \times (66 - 6) - 6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7/7) + 7) \\
&:= (8 \times 88 + 8)/(8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= (((9 \times 9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)) - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 357 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (11^{1+1} - 1 - 1) \\
&:= (2/2 + 2) \times ((22/2)^2 - 2) \\
&:= 3^3 + (333 - 3) \\
&:= 4 + (((4 + 4) \times 44) + 4/4) \\
&:= 5 + (55/5 \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5) \\
&:= 66 \times 66/(6 + 6) - 6 \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 + 7) \\
&:= 8/8 + ((8 \times 88 + 8)/(8 + 8)/8) \\
&:= ((9 - 9/9) + 9) \times (((99 + 9)/9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 358 &:= 1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (11^{1+1} - (1 + 1)) \\
&:= 2 + (((22 \times 2^{2+2}) + 2) + 2) \\
&:= 3^3 + ((333 - 3) + 3/3) \\
&:= 4 + (((4 + 4) \times 44) + (4 + 4)/4) \\
&:= 5 + (((55 \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5) + 5)/5) \\
&:= 6 \times (66 - 6) - (6 + 6)/6 \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times 7 \times 7 + 7/7) + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - ((8 + 8)/8 + 88) \\
&:= (9 + 9)/9 \times ((9 \times 9 - 9/9) + 99)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 359 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (11^{1+1} - 1) - 1 \\
&:= ((22 - (2/2 + 2))^2) - 2 \\
&:= 3^3 + (333 - 3/3) \\
&:= 4 + (((4 + 4) \times 44) - 4/4) + 4 \\
&:= (5/5 + 5) \times (55 + 5) - 5/5 \\
&:= 6 \times (66 - 6) - 6/6 \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times 7 \times 7 + ((7 + 7)/7)) + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - (8/8 + 88) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 9 \times (9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 360 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (11^{1+1} - 1) \\
&:= 2 \times (2 \times (2 \times 2 \times 22 + 2)) \\
&:= 3^3 + 333 \\
&:= 4 + (((4 + 4) \times 44) + 4) \\
&:= (5/5 + 5) \times (55 + 5) \\
&:= 6 \times (66 - 6) \\
&:= 7 + (((77 - 7)/7) + 7 \times 7 \times 7) \\
&:= 8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - 88 \\
&:= (9 + 9) \times (99/9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 361 &:= (((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)) - 1)^{1+1} \\
&:= (22 - (2/2 + 2))^2 \\
&:= 3^3 + (333 + 3/3) \\
&:= 4 + (((4 + 4) \times 44) + 4/4) + 4 \\
&:= 5/5 + (5/5 + 5) \times (55 + 5) \\
&:= 6/6 + 6 \times (66 - 6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 + (77/7)) \\
&:= (88/8 + 8)^{(8+8)/8} \\
&:= (9/9 + 9 + 9)^{(9+9)/9}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 362 &:= 11 \times 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \\
&:= 2 + (2 \times (2 \times (2 \times 2 \times 22 + 2))) \\
&:= (33 \times 33 - 3)/3 \\
&:= 4^4 + ((444 - 4)/4 - 4) \\
&:= 55 + (5^5 - 55)/(5 + 5) \\
&:= (6 + 6)/6 + 6 \times (66 - 6) \\
&:= 7 + ((77 + 7)/7 + 7 \times 7 \times 7) \\
&:= 8/8 + ((88/8 + 8)^{(8+8)/8}) \\
&:= 9/9 + ((9/9 + 9 + 9)^{(9+9)/9})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 363 &:= 11 \times 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) \\
&:= 2 + ((22 - (2/2 + 2))^2) \\
&:= 33 \times 33/3 \\
&:= 4^4 + (444/4 - 4) \\
&:= 55 + ((5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) - 5) \\
&:= 66 \times 66/(6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + (((7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7/7) + 7) + 7) \\
&:= 88/8 + (8 \times (88/((8 + 8)/8))) \\
&:= (99 \times 99)/(9 + 9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 364 &:= 1 + 11 \times 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) \\
&:= 2 \times ((2 \times (2 \times 2 \times 22 + 2)) + 2) \\
&:= (33 \times 33 + 3)/3 \\
&:= 4 + (((4 + 4) \times 44) + 4) + 4 \\
&:= (5 \times (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5))) - 55/5 \\
&:= 6 + (6 \times (66 - 6) - ((6 + 6)/6)) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 + 7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times 88 + 8)/((8 + 8)/8)) \\
&:= ((9 \times 9 \times 9 \times 9) - 9)/(9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 365 &:= 1 + 1 + 11 \times 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) \\
&:= 2 + (((22 - (2/2 + 2))^2) + 2) \\
&:= 3 + ((33 \times 33 - 3)/3) \\
&:= (4/4 + 4)^4 - (4^4 + 4) \\
&:= 5 + (5/5 + 5) \times (55 + 5) \\
&:= 6 + (6 \times (66 - 6) - 6/6) \\
&:= 7 + (((7 \times 7 \times 7 + 7/7) + 7) + 7) \\
&:= 888 - (8 \times 8 \times 8 + 88/8) \\
&:= ((9 \times 9 \times 9 \times 9) + 9)/(9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 366 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11^{1+1}) \\
&:= 222 + ((2 \times (2 + 2 + 2))^2) \\
&:= 33 + 333 \\
&:= 4^4 + (444 - 4)/4 \\
&:= (5/5 + 5) \times ((55 + 5/5) + 5) \\
&:= 6 + 6 \times (66 - 6) \\
&:= 7 + (((7 \times 7 \times 7 + ((7 + 7)/7)) + 7) + 7) \\
&:= ((8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)) + ((888 - 8)/8) \\
&:= 9/9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 9 \times 9) + 9)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 367 &:= 1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11^{1+1}) \\
&:= 222/2 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)} \\
&:= 3 + ((33 \times 33 + 3)/3) \\
&:= 4^4 + 444/4 \\
&:= 55 + (5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 + (6 \times (66 - 6) + 6/6) \\
&:= 7 + (((77 - 7)/7) + 7 \times 7 \times 7) + 7) \\
&:= 888/8 + ((8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 + 9)/9) \times ((9 \times 9 - 9/9) + 99))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 368 &:= 1 + 1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 \times (2 \times (2 \times ((2 \times 22) + 2))) \\
&:= 3 + (((33 \times 33 - 3)/3) + 3) \\
&:= 4 \times (44 + 44 + 4) \\
&:= 55 + (5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 + (6 \times (66 - 6) + ((6 + 6)/6)) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times 7 \times 7 + (77/7)) + 7) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - 88) \\
&:= 9 + (((((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 9 \times (9 + 9)) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 369 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 11^{1+1})) \\
&:= (2/2 + 2) \times ((22/2)^2 + 2) \\
&:= 3 + (333 + 33) \\
&:= (4/4 + 4)^4 - 4^4 \\
&:= (5 \times (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5))) - (5/5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 + 66 \times 66/(6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + (((77 + 7)/7 + 7 \times 7 \times 7) + 7) \\
&:= 8 + ((88/8 + 8)^{(8+8)/8}) \\
&:= 9 + (9 + 9) \times (99/9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 370 &:= (1111 - 1)/(1 + 1 + 1) \\
&:= 2 + (2 \times (2 \times (2 \times ((2 \times 22) + 2)))) \\
&:= 3^3 + (((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3) \\
&:= 4 + ((444 - 4)/4 + 4^4) \\
&:= (5 \times (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5))) - 5 \\
&:= 6 \times (66 - 6) + (66 - 6)/6 \\
&:= 77 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 7/7) \\
&:= (8888 - 8)/(8 + 8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 + ((9/9 + 9 + 9)^{(9+9)/9})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 371 &:= 1 + (1111 - 1)/(1 + 1 + 1) \\
&:= 22^2 - (222/2 + 2) \\
&:= 3^3 + (333 + 33/3) \\
&:= 4 + (444/4 + 4^4) \\
&:= 5/5 + ((5 \times (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5))) - 5) \\
&:= 66/6 + 6 \times (66 - 6) \\
&:= 77 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) \\
&:= (8 - 8/8) \times (8 \times 8 - 88/8) \\
&:= 99/9 + ((9 + 9) \times (99/9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 372 &:= 1 + 1 + (1111 - 1)/(1 + 1 + 1) \\
&:= 2 \times ((2 \times (2 \times ((2 \times 22) + 2))) + 2) \\
&:= 3 + ((333 + 33) + 3) \\
&:= 4 + (((4 + 4) \times 44) + 4 \times 4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5) + 55) \\
&:= 6 + (6 \times (66 - 6) + 6) \\
&:= 7/7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) + 77) \\
&:= 8 + (((8 \times 88 + 8)/((8 + 8)/8)) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + ((99 \times 99)/(9 + 9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 373 &:= (11 + 11)^{1+1} - 111 \\
&:= 22^2 - 222/2 \\
&:= 3 + (((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3) + 3^3 \\
&:= 4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 4^4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) + 55) \\
&:= 6 + ((6 \times (66 - 6) + 6/6) + 6) \\
&:= 77 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) + ((7 + 7)/7)) \\
&:= (8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8 + 8))) - 88/8 \\
&:= 9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 9 \times 9) - 9)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 374 &:= 11 \times (1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)) \\
&:= 22 + (22 \times 2^{2+2}) \\
&:= 33/3 \times (3/3 + 33) \\
&:= (44 \times (4 \times 4 \times 4 + 4))/(4 + 4) \\
&:= (5 \times (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5))) - 5/5 \\
&:= (66/6) \times (6 \times 6 - ((6 + 6)/6)) \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - (77/7 + 7) \\
&:= 888 - (8 \times 8 \times 8 + (8 + 8)/8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 9 \times 9) + 9)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 375 &:= 1 + 11 \times (1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)) \\
&:= 2 + (22^2 - 222/2) \\
&:= 3 \times ((3 - 3/3 + 3)^3) \\
&:= 4 + ((444/4 + 4^4) + 4) \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)) \\
&:= 6 + (66 \times 66/(6 + 6) + 6) \\
&:= 7 + (((7 \times 7 \times 7 + (77/7)) + 7) + 7) \\
&:= 888 - (8 \times 8 \times 8 + 8/8) \\
&:= ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)) - 999/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 376 &:= 1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)) \\
&:= (22 - 2)^2 - (22 + 2) \\
&:= 33 + (((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3) \\
&:= (4 + 4) \times (44 - 4/4 + 4) \\
&:= 5/5 + (5 \times (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5))) \\
&:= 6 + (6 \times (66 - 6) + ((66 - 6)/6)) \\
&:= (7/7 + 7) \times 7 \times 7 - (7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 888 - 8 \times 8 \times 8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + ((99 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - (9 + 9))/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 377 &:= 11 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11^{1+1}) \\
&:= (22/2)^2 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)} \\
&:= 3 + (33/3 \times (3/3 + 33)) \\
&:= 4 + (((4/4 + 4)^4 - 4^4) + 4) \\
&:= (5 + 5)/5 + (5 \times (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5))) \\
&:= 6 + (6 \times (66 - 6) + (66/6)) \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - (7/7 + 7 + 7) \\
&:= 8/8 + (888 - 8 \times 8 \times 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + ((99 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 378 &:= 1 + 11 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11^{1+1}) \\
&:= (22 - 2)^2 - 22 \\
&:= 3 \times (3 \times 33 + 3^3) \\
&:= 4^4 + ((444 + 44)/4) \\
&:= ((5 + 5)/5 + 5) \times (55 - 5/5) \\
&:= 6 \times 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - (7 + 7) \\
&:= (8 - (8 + 8)/8) \times (8 \times 8 - 8/8) \\
&:= (9 + 9) \times (((99 + 9)/9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 379 &:= (11 - 1) \times (1 + 111/(1 + 1 + 1)) - 1 \\
&:= 2/2 + ((22 - 2)^2 - 22) \\
&:= 3 + (((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3) + 33 \\
&:= 444 - (4^4 + 4)/4 \\
&:= 5 + ((5 \times (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5))) - 5/5) \\
&:= 6 \times 66 - ((66/6) + 6) \\
&:= 7/7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - (7 + 7)) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 - 8/8) \times (8 \times 8 - 88/8)) \\
&:= 9 \times 99 - (((9 + 9)/9)^9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 380 &:= (11 - 1) \times (1 + 111/(1 + 1 + 1)) \\
&:= 2 + ((22 - 2)^2 - 22) \\
&:= 3 + ((33/3 \times (3/3 + 33)) + 3) \\
&:= 444 - 4 \times 4 \times 4 \\
&:= 5 + (5 \times (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5))) \\
&:= 6 \times 66 + (((6 - 66)/6) - 6) \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - (77 + 7)/7 \\
&:= (8 \times (88 + 8) - 8)/((8 + 8)/8) \\
&:= (9/9 + 9 + 9) \times (99/9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 381 &:= 11 + (1111 - 1)/(1 + 1 + 1) \\
&:= 2 + (((22 - 2)^2 - 22) + 2/2) \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times (3 \times 33 + 3^3)) \\
&:= 444 + ((4 - 4^4)/4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5 \times (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5))) + 5/5) \\
&:= 6 + ((66 \times 66/(6 + 6) + 6) + 6) \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - 77/7 \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8 + 8))) - (88/8)) \\
&:= 9 + (((99 \times 99)/(9 + 9 + 9)) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 382 &:= 1 + 11 + (1111 - 1)/(1 + 1 + 1) \\
&:= (2^{2+2} \times (22 + 2)) - 2 \\
&:= 3333/3 - 3^{3+3} \\
&:= 4^4 + ((4^4 - 4)/((4 + 4)/4)) \\
&:= 5^5/5 - ((5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5) \\
&:= 6 \times 66 - ((6 + 6)/6 + 6 + 6) \\
&:= ((7 - 77)/7) + 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) \\
&:= (8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8 + 8))) - (8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= 9999/9 - 9 \times 9 \times 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 383 &:= (1 + 11) \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1) - 1 \\
&:= 22 + ((22 - (2/2 + 2))^2) \\
&:= ((3 + 3) \times ((3/3 + 3)^3)) - 3/3 \\
&:= ((4 + 4) \times (44 + 4)) - 4/4 \\
&:= 5 + (((5 + 5)/5 + 5) \times (55 - 5/5)) \\
&:= 6 \times 66 - (6/6 + 6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - ((7 + 7)/7 + 7) \\
&:= (8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8 + 8))) - 8/8 \\
&:= 9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 9 \times 9) + 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 384 &:= (1 + 11) \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1) \\
&:= 2^{2+2} \times (22 + 2) \\
&:= (3 + 3) \times ((3/3 + 3)^3) \\
&:= (4 + 4) \times (44 + 4) \\
&:= ((55 + 5)/5) \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5 \\
&:= 6 \times ((6 + 6)/6)^6 \\
&:= (7/7 + 7) \times (7 \times 7 - 7/7) \\
&:= 8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8 + 8)) \\
&:= ((9 + 9)/9) \times (999/9 + 9 \times 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 385 &:= 11 \times (1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)) \\
&:= 2/2 + (2^{2+2} \times (22 + 2)) \\
&:= 3/3 + ((3 + 3) \times ((3/3 + 3)^3)) \\
&:= 4/4 + ((4 + 4) \times (44 + 4)) \\
&:= 55 \times ((5 + 5)/5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 66 - 66/6 \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - 7 \\
&:= 8/8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8 + 8))) \\
&:= 99/9 \times (((9 - 9/9) + 9) + 9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 386 &:= 1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)) \\
&:= 2 + (2^{2+2} \times (22 + 2)) \\
&:= 3^{3+3} - (((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3) \\
&:= 4^4 + ((4^4 + 4)/((4 + 4)/4)) \\
&:= 5 \times 55 + 555/5 \\
&:= 6 \times 66 + (6 - 66)/6 \\
&:= 7/7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - 7) \\
&:= (8 + 8)/8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8 + 8))) \\
&:= (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - ((99 + 9 + 9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 387 &:= 1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)) \\
&:= (22 - 2)^2 - (22/2 + 2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3 + 3) \times ((3/3 + 3)^3)) \\
&:= 4 + (((4 + 4) \times (44 + 4)) - 4/4) \\
&:= 5 \times 55 + (555 + 5)/5 \\
&:= 6 \times 66 + (((6 - 66) + 6)/6) \\
&:= ((7 + 7)/7) + (7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - 7) \\
&:= 888 + (88/8 - 8 \times 8 \times 8) \\
&:= ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)) - 99
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 388 &:= ((1+1) \times (11-1))^{1+1} - 1 - 11 \\
&:= 2 \times (((2^{2+2} - 2)^2) - 2) \\
&:= 3 + (((3+3) \times ((3/3+3)^3)) + 3/3) \\
&:= 4 + (((4+4) \times (44+4)) \\
&:= 5 \times 55 + (555+5+5)/5 \\
&:= 6 \times 66 - ((6+6)/6+6) \\
&:= ((7 \times 777) - 7)/(7+7) \\
&:= (8 \times (88+8) + 8)/((8+8)/8) \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times 99 - ((9+9)/9)^9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 389 &:= ((1+1) \times (11-1))^{1+1} - 11 \\
&:= (22-2)^2 - 22/2 \\
&:= 3^3 + ((33 \times 33 - 3)/3) \\
&:= 4 + (((4+4) \times (44+4)) + 4/4) \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55) - 55/5 \\
&:= 6 \times 66 - 6/6 - 6 \\
&:= ((7 \times 777) + 7)/(7+7) \\
&:= (((8-8/8) \times 888) + 8)/(8+8) \\
&:= 9 + ((9/9+9+9) \times (99/9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 390 &:= 1 + ((1+1) \times (11-1))^{1+1} - 11 \\
&:= (2 \times ((2^{2+2} - 2)^2)) - 2 \\
&:= 3^3 + (33 \times 33/3) \\
&:= ((4+4)/4+4) \times (4^4+4)/4 \\
&:= 5 + (55 \times ((5+5)/5+5)) \\
&:= 6 \times 66 - 6 \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - (7+7)/7 \\
&:= (8 - (8+8)/8) \times (8/8+8 \times 8) \\
&:= ((9 \times 9 \times 99) - 999)/(9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 391 &:= (1+1)^{11-1-1} - 11^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 + ((22-2)^2 - 22/2) \\
&:= 3^3 + ((33 \times 33 + 3)/3) \\
&:= 444 + ((44-4^4)/4) \\
&:= 5 + (555/5 + 5 \times 55) \\
&:= 6/6 + (6 \times 66 - 6) \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - 7/7 \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8+8))) - 8/8) \\
&:= ((99/9+9) \times (9+9)^9) - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 392 &:= (1+1) \times (1+1+1+11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 \times ((2^{2+2} - 2)^2) \\
&:= (3/3+3) \times (3 \times 33 - 3/3) \\
&:= 4 + (((4+4) \times (44+4)) + 4) \\
&:= ((5+5)/5+5) \times (55+5/5) \\
&:= (6+6)/6 + (6 \times 66 - 6) \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8+8))) \\
&:= (9-9/9) \times ((9 \times 99 - 9)/(9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 393 &:= (1+1+1) \times (11 \times (1+11) - 1) \\
&:= 2/2 + (2 \times ((2^{2+2} - 2)^2)) \\
&:= (33 \times (3 \times 3 + 3)) - 3 \\
&:= 4 + (((4+4) \times (44+4)) + 4/4 + 4) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + ((5^5+5)/(5+5) + 55) \\
&:= 6 \times 66 - 6 \times 6/(6+6) \\
&:= 7/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8+8))) + 8/8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9+9)/9) \times (999/9+9 \times 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 394 &:= 1 + (1+1+1) \times (11 \times (1+11) - 1) \\
&:= 2 + (2 \times ((2^{2+2} - 2)^2)) \\
&:= 3/3 + ((33 \times (3 \times 3 + 3)) - 3) \\
&:= 4 + (((4+4)/4+4) \times (4^4+4)/4) \\
&:= (5-5/5)^5 - (5^5/5+5) \\
&:= 6 \times 66 - (6+6)/6 \\
&:= ((7+7)/7) + 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8+8))) + ((8+8)/8)) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + ((9+9) \times (9+9) - (99/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 395 &:= 11 \times (1+1+1) \times (1+11) - 1 \\
&:= (22-2)^2 - (2/2+2+2) \\
&:= (33 \times (3 \times 3 + 3)) - 3/3 \\
&:= 44 + (((4+4) \times 44) - 4/4) \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55) - 5 \\
&:= 6 \times 66 - 6/6 \\
&:= 7 + (((7 \times 777) - 7)/(7+7)) \\
&:= 88/8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8+8))) \\
&:= (((9+9)/9)^9) - (99+9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 396 &:= 11 \times (1+1+1) \times (1+11) \\
&:= 22 \times (2^{2+2} + 2) \\
&:= 33 \times (3 \times 3 + 3) \\
&:= 44 + ((4+4) \times 44) \\
&:= 5/5 + (5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55) - 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 66 \\
&:= 7 + (((7 \times 777) + 7)/(7+7)) \\
&:= (88 \times (8 \times 8 + 8))/(8+8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + ((9+9) \times (9+9) - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 397 &:= 1 + 11 \times (1+1+1) \times (1+11) \\
&:= (22-2)^2 - 2/2 - 2 \\
&:= 3/3 + (33 \times (3 \times 3 + 3)) \\
&:= 44 + (((4+4) \times 44) + 4/4) \\
&:= 5 + (((5+5)/5+5) \times (55+5/5)) \\
&:= 6/6 + 6 \times 66 \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - ((7+7)/7)) \\
&:= 8/8 + ((88 \times (8 \times 8 + 8))/(8+8)) \\
&:= (((9+9) \times (99+99)) + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 398 &:= ((1+1) \times (11-1))^{1+1} - 1 - 1 \\
&:= (22-2)^2 - 2 \\
&:= 3 + ((33 \times (3 \times 3 + 3)) - 3/3) \\
&:= 444 - ((4+4)/4+44) \\
&:= (5-5/5)^5 - (5^5+5)/5 \\
&:= (6+6)/6+6 \times 66 \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - 7/7) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 - (8+8)/8) \times (8/8+8 \times 8)) \\
&:= ((9+9)/9) \times ((9/9+99) + 99)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 399 &:= ((1+1) \times (11-1))^{1+1} - 1 \\
&:= (22-2)^2 - 2/2 \\
&:= 3 + (33 \times (3 \times 3 + 3)) \\
&:= 4 \times 4^4 - (4/4+4)^4 \\
&:= (5-5/5)^5 - 5^5/5 \\
&:= 6 \times 66 + (6 \times 6/(6+6)) \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) \\
&:= (8-8/8) \times ((8/8-8) + 8 \times 8) \\
&:= (9/9+9+9) \times (((99+9)/9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 400 &:= ((1+1) \times (11-1))^{1+1} \\
&:= (22-2)^2 \\
&:= 3 + ((33 \times (3 \times 3 + 3)) + 3/3) \\
&:= 444 - 44 \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55) \\
&:= 6 + (6 \times 66 - ((6+6)/6)) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) + 7/7) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8+8))) + 8) \\
&:= (99/9+9) \times (9+9)^9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 401 &:= 1 + ((1+1) \times (11-1))^{1+1} \\
&:= 2/2 + (22-2)^2 \\
&:= 3 + (((33 \times (3 \times 3 + 3)) - 3/3) + 3) \\
&:= 4/4 + (444 - 44) \\
&:= 5/5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55) \\
&:= 6 + (6 \times 66 - 6/6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) + ((7+7)/7)) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - 888/8 \\
&:= (((9+9)/9)^9) - 999/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 402 &:= 1 + 1 + ((1+1) \times (11-1))^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 + (22-2)^2 \\
&:= 3 + ((33 \times (3 \times 3 + 3)) + 3) \\
&:= 444 + ((4+4)/4 - 44) \\
&:= (5+5)/5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55) \\
&:= 6 + 6 \times 66 \\
&:= ((77-7)/7) + 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + ((8-888)/8) \\
&:= (((9+9)/9)^9) + ((9-999)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 403 &:= 1 + 1 + 1 + ((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 + (22 - 2)^2 + 2/2 \\
&:= 3 + (((33 \times (3 \times 3 + 3)) + 3/3) + 3) \\
&:= 4 + (4 \times 4^4 - (4/4 + 4)^4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5 - 5/5)^5 - (5^5 + 5)/5) \\
&:= 6 + (6 \times 66 + 6/6) \\
&:= 77/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8 + 8))) + (88/8)) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - ((9 + 9)/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 404 &:= (1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1) \times (1 + (11 - 1)^{1+1})) \\
&:= 2 + (22 - 2)^2 + 2 \\
&:= 333 + (((3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3) \\
&:= 4 + (444 - 44) \\
&:= 5 + ((5 - 5/5)^5 - 5^5/5) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 + 6)/6) + 6 \times 66) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 - (((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 + ((88 \times (8 \times 8 + 8))/(8 + 8)) \\
&:= (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - (99 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 405 &:= 11 \times 111/(1 + 1 + 1) - 1 - 1 \\
&:= 2 + (22 - 2)^2 + 2/2 + 2 \\
&:= 3^3 \times ((3 \times 3 + 3) + 3) \\
&:= (4/4 + 4) \times (4 - 4/4)^4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 \times 6)/(6 + 6)) + 6 \times 66) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - 7/7) + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - ((88/8 + 88) + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times (((9 + 9 + 9) + 9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 406 &:= 11 \times 111/(1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \\
&:= 2 + (22 - 2)^2 + 2 + 2 \\
&:= 3/3 + (3^3 \times ((3 \times 3 + 3) + 3)) \\
&:= 4 + (((4 + 4)/4 - 44) + 444) \\
&:= 5 + (5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55) + 5/5) \\
&:= 6 \times 66 + (66 - 6)/6 \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) + 7) \\
&:= (8 - 8/8) \times (((8 + 8)/8) - 8) + 8 \times 8 \\
&:= 9/9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 407 &:= 11 \times 111/(1 + 1 + 1) \\
&:= 2 + (22 - 2)^2 + 2/2 + 2 + 2 \\
&:= 33 \times 333/3^3 \\
&:= 4 + ((4 \times 4^4 - (4/4 + 4)^4) + 4) \\
&:= 55/5 \times (((5 + 5)/5)^5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 66 + 66/6 \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) + 7/7) + 7) \\
&:= 8888/8 - 8 \times 88 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + ((9 + 9)/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 408 &:= 1 + 11 \times 111/(1 + 1 + 1) \\
&:= 2 \times (2 + 2) + (22 - 2)^2 \\
&:= 3 + (3^3 \times ((3 \times 3 + 3) + 3)) \\
&:= 4 + ((444 - 44) + 4) \\
&:= (5 \times 5 - 5/5) \times (((55 + 5)/5) + 5) \\
&:= 6 + (6 \times 66 + 6) \\
&:= (7/7 + 7) \times ((7 + 7)/7 + 7 \times 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - (88 + 8 + 8) \\
&:= (99 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 999)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 409 &:= 1 + 1 + 11 \times 111/(1 + 1 + 1) \\
&:= 22/2 + (22 - 2)^2 - 2 \\
&:= 3 + ((3^3 \times ((3 \times 3 + 3) + 3)) + 3/3) \\
&:= 4 + ((4/4 + 4) \times (4 - 4/4)^4) \\
&:= 5 + (((5 - 5/5)^5 - 5^5/5) + 5) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 \times 66 + 6/6) + 6) + 6) \\
&:= 77 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 - (77/7)) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - 888/8) \\
&:= 9 + ((99/9 + 9)^{(9+9)/9})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 410 &:= 11 + ((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1} - 1 \\
&:= 2 + (22 - 2)^2 + 2 \times (2 + 2) \\
&:= 3 + 33 \times 333/3^3 \\
&:= (((4 + 4)^4) + 4)/((44 - 4)/4) \\
&:= 5 + (5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55) + 5) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 + 6)/6) + 6 \times 66) + 6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) + (77/7)) \\
&:= 8 + (((8 - 888)/8) + 8 \times 8 \times 8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 999/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 411 &:= 11 + ((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1} \\
&:= 22/2 + (22 - 2)^2 \\
&:= 3 \times 3^3 + (333 - 3) \\
&:= 44 + (444/4 + 4^4) \\
&:= 55/5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 \times 6)/(6 + 6)) + 6 \times 66) + 6) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 - ((7 + 7)/7)^7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - (8888/88) \\
&:= (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - ((9 + 9)/9 + 99)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 412 &:= 1 + 11 + ((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 \times (222 - 2^{2+2}) \\
&:= 3/3 + ((3 \times 3^3 - 3) + 333) \\
&:= 444 - 4 \times (4 + 4) \\
&:= 5 + (55/5 \times (((5 + 5)/5)^5 + 5)) \\
&:= 6 + (((66 - 6)/6) + 6 \times 66) \\
&:= 77 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 - (7/7 + 7)) \\
&:= (888 - 8 \times 8)/(8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - (9/9 + 99)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 413 &:= 1 + 1 + 11 + ((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 + (22 - 2)^2 + 22/2 \\
&:= 3 \times 3^3 + (333 - 3/3) \\
&:= 44 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 4^4) \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) + (5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 + (6 \times 66 + (66/6)) \\
&:= 77 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - (88/8 + 88) \\
&:= (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 99
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 414 &:= (1 + 1) \times (11 + (1 + 1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 + 2 \times (222 - 2^{2+2}) \\
&:= 3 \times 3^3 + 333 \\
&:= 4 + ((4 + 4)^4 + 4)/((44 - 4)/4) \\
&:= (5 - 5/5)^5 - (555 + 55) \\
&:= 6 + ((6 \times 66 + 6) + 6) \\
&:= 7/7 + ((7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7) + 77) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + ((8 - 88)/8 - 88) \\
&:= 9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 415 &:= (1 + 1 + 11) \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1) - 1 \\
&:= 2 + (22 - 2)^2 + 22/2 + 2 \\
&:= 3/3 + (3 \times 3^3 + 333) \\
&:= 4^4 + (4 \times (44 - 4) - 4/4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55) + 5) + 5) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 \times 66 + 6/6) + 6) + 6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7/7 + 7) \times ((7 + 7)/7 + 7 \times 7)) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - ((8/8 + 88) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9) + 9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 416 &:= (1 + 1 + 11) \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1) \\
&:= 2^{2+2} + (22 - 2)^2 \\
&:= 3 + ((333 - 3/3) + 3 \times 3^3) \\
&:= 4^4 + (4 \times (44 - 4)) \\
&:= (55/5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 + 5/5) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 + 6)/6) + 6 \times 66) + 6) + 6) \\
&:= ((77 \times 77 - 7)/(7 + 7)) - 7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - (88 + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + (99/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 417 &:= 11 \times (1 + 111/(1 + 1 + 1)) - 1 \\
&:= (22 - 2/2)^2 - 22 - 2 \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times 3^3 + 333) \\
&:= 4/4 + (4 \times (44 - 4) + 4^4) \\
&:= ((5^5 + 5^5) + 5)/(5 + 5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 66 + ((6 \times 6 + 6)/((6 + 6)/6)) \\
&:= ((77 \times 77 + 7)/(7 + 7)) - 7 \\
&:= 8/8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - (88 + 8)) \\
&:= 9 + ((99 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 999)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 418 &:= 11 \times (1 + 111 / (1 + 1 + 1)) \\
&:= 22 \times (22 - 2 / 2 - 2) \\
&:= 33 / 3 \times (33 / 3 + 3^3) \\
&:= 4^4 + (4 \times (44 - 4) + (4 + 4) / 4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 + 5) / (5 + 5) + 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5)) \\
&:= 6 \times 66 + ((66 + 66) / 6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times 77 - ((7 + 7) / 7)^7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + (((8 + 8) / 8) - (88 + 8)) \\
&:= 9 + (((99 / 9 + 9)^{(9+9) / 9} + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 419 &:= 1 + 11 \times (1 + 111 / (1 + 1 + 1)) \\
&:= (22 - 2 / 2)^2 - 22 \\
&:= ((3^3 + 3) \times (33 / 3 + 3)) - 3 / 3 \\
&:= (44 \times 44 - (4^4 + 4)) / 4 \\
&:= 555 - (555 / 5 + 5 \times 5) \\
&:= 6 + ((6 \times 66 + (66 / 6)) + 6) \\
&:= 77 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7 / 7) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - (8888 / 88)) \\
&:= (((9 \times 999) + 9) / (9 + 9)) - 9 \times 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 420 &:= (1 + 1) \times (11 - 1) \times (11 + 11 - 1) \\
&:= 22 + (22 - 2)^2 - 2 \\
&:= (3^3 + 3) \times (33 / 3 + 3) \\
&:= 4 + (4 \times (44 - 4) + 4^4) \\
&:= (55 + 5) \times ((5 + 5) / 5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 \times (((6 + 6) / 6)^6 + 6) \\
&:= 77 + 7 \times 7 \times 7 \\
&:= 88 \times 88 / (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8 \\
&:= ((9 + 9) / 9) \times (999 / 9 + 99)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 421 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)^{1+1} - 11 \\
&:= 2 + (((22 - 2 / 2)^2) - 22) \\
&:= (((3 + 3)^{3/3+3}) - 3) / 3 \\
&:= 4^4 + ((4 \times 44) - 44 / 4) \\
&:= 5 + ((55 / 5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 + 5 / 5)) \\
&:= (6 \times (66 + 6)) - 66 / 6 \\
&:= 7 / 7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 + 77) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - (88 / 8 + 88)) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 + 9) / 9)^9) - (9 / 9 + 99)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 422 &:= (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times 111 - 11 \\
&:= 22 + (22 - 2)^2 \\
&:= 3^3 + ((33 \times (3 \times 3 + 3)) - 3 / 3) \\
&:= 444 - (44 / ((4 + 4) / 4)) \\
&:= 5 + (((5^5 + 5^5) + 5) / (5 + 5 + 5)) \\
&:= ((6 - 66) / 6) + (6 \times (66 + 6)) \\
&:= 77 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 + ((7 + 7) / 7)) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - ((8 + 8) / 8 + 88) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 + 9) / 9)^9) - 99
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 423 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1) \times 111 - 11) \\
&:= 22 + ((22 - 2)^2 + 2 / 2) \\
&:= 3 \times (3 \times (33 + 3)) + 33 \\
&:= 444 - ((4 \times 4 + 4 / 4) + 4) \\
&:= 55 + ((5^5 + 5) / (5 + 5) + 55) \\
&:= 66 + (66 \times 66 / (6 + 6) - 6) \\
&:= (77 \times 77 - 7) / (7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - (8 / 8 + 88) \\
&:= 99 + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 424 &:= (1 + 1) \times (1 + ((1 + 1) \times 111 - 11)) \\
&:= 2 + ((22 - 2)^2 + 22) \\
&:= 3 \times 3^3 + (((3 / 3 + 3) + 3)^3) \\
&:= 444 - (4 \times 4 + 4) \\
&:= (5 - 5 / 5) \times (555 / 5 - 5) \\
&:= 6 \times (66 - 6) + ((6 + 6) / 6)^6 \\
&:= (77 \times 77 + 7) / (7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - 88 \\
&:= 9 / 9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 99)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 425 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + ((1 + 1) \times 111 - 11)) \\
&:= ((22 - 2 / 2)^2) - 2^{2+2} \\
&:= (((3 + 3) \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3)) - 3) / 3 \\
&:= 4 / 4 + (444 - (4 \times 4 + 4)) \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55 + 5) \\
&:= (6 \times (66 + 6)) - 6 / 6 - 6 \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times 77 - ((7 + 7) / 7)^7) + 7) \\
&:= 8 / 8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - 88) \\
&:= 99 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + ((9 + 9) / 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 426 &:= (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times (1 + 111) - 11 \\
&:= (2 \times (222 + 2)) - 22 \\
&:= (3 + 3) \times (((3 + 3)^3 - 3) / 3) \\
&:= 444 - ((4 + 4) / 4 + 4 \times 4) \\
&:= 5 / 5 + (5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55 + 5)) \\
&:= (6 \times (66 + 6)) - 6 \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7 / 7) + 77) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + (((8 + 8) / 8) - 88) \\
&:= (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + (999 / 9 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 427 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 111) - 11) \\
&:= 2 + (((22 - 2 / 2)^2) - 2^{2+2}) \\
&:= (((3 + 3) \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3)) + 3) / 3 \\
&:= 444 - (4 \times 4 + 4 / 4) \\
&:= (5 + 5) / 5 + (5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55 + 5)) \\
&:= 6 / 6 + ((6 \times (66 + 6)) - 6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 + 77) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + (88 / 8 - (88 + 8)) \\
&:= (((9 \times 9 \times 99) - 9) / (9 + 9)) - (9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 428 &:= (11 \times ((1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11))) - 1 \\
&:= 2 \times (222 - 2 \times (2 + 2)) \\
&:= (((3 + 3)^{3/3+3}) - 3) / 3 - 3 \\
&:= 444 - 4 \times 4 \\
&:= (5 - 5 / 5) \times ((555 + 5) / 5 - 5) \\
&:= (6 + 6) / 6 + ((6 \times (66 + 6)) - 6) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 - 777 / 7 \\
&:= 888 / ((8 + 8) / 8) - 8 - 8 \\
&:= (((9 \times 9 \times 99) + 9) / (9 + 9)) - (9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 429 &:= 11 \times ((1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11)) \\
&:= (2 \times (222 - 2)) - 22 / 2 \\
&:= 33 + (33 \times (3 \times 3 + 3)) \\
&:= 4 / 4 + (444 - 4 \times 4) \\
&:= 555 - (5 \times 5 \times 5 + 5 / 5) \\
&:= 66 + 66 \times 66 / (6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 + ((7 - 777) / 7) \\
&:= 8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - (88 / 8 + 8) \\
&:= (((9 + 9) / 9)^9) - ((9 + 9) / 9) + 9 \times 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 430 &:= ((11 + 11 - 1)^{1+1}) - 11 \\
&:= 2 + (2 \times (222 - 2 \times (2 + 2))) \\
&:= (3 - 3 / 3) \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3 / 3) \\
&:= 4^4 + ((4 \times 44) - (4 + 4) / 4) \\
&:= 555 - 5 \times 5 \times 5 \\
&:= (6 \times (66 + 6)) - (6 + 6) / 6 \\
&:= 7 + ((77 \times 77 - 7) / (7 + 7)) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - ((8 + 8) / 8 + 88)) \\
&:= (((9 + 9) / 9)^9) - (9 / 9 + 9 \times 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 431 &:= ((1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)^{1+1}) - 1 \\
&:= 2 \times 222 - (22 / 2 + 2) \\
&:= (((3 + 3)^{3/3+3}) - 3) / 3 \\
&:= 4^4 + ((4 \times 44) - 4 / 4) \\
&:= 5 / 5 + (555 - 5 \times 5 \times 5) \\
&:= (6 \times (66 + 6)) - 6 / 6 \\
&:= 7 + ((77 \times 77 + 7) / (7 + 7)) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - (8 / 8 + 88)) \\
&:= (((9 + 9) / 9)^9) - 9 \times 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 432 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 \times ((2 + 2 + 2)^{2/2+2}) \\
&:= 3 \times ((3 + 3) \times (3^3 - 3)) \\
&:= 4^4 + (4 \times 44) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 \times 5 + (5^5 - 55) / (5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 \times (66 + 6) \\
&:= ((7 + 7) / 7 + 7) \times (7 \times 7 - 7 / 7) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - 88) \\
&:= 9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 99)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 433 &:= 1 + ((1+1+1) \times (1+11))^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 \times 222 - 22/2 \\
&:= (((3+3)^{3/3+3} + 3)/3) \\
&:= 444 - 44/4 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 \times 5 + ((5^5 + 5)/(5+5) - 5) \\
&:= 6/6 + (6 \times (66+6)) \\
&:= 777 - (7 \times 7 \times 7 + 7/7) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times 8 \times 8 - 88) + 8/8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9+9) \times (9+9) + 99) + 9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 434 &:= 1 + (1 + ((1+1+1) \times (1+11))^{1+1}) \\
&:= (2 \times (222 - (2+2))) - 2 \\
&:= 3 + (((3+3)^{3/3+3} - 3)/3) \\
&:= 444 + (4 - 44)/4 \\
&:= 5 + (555 - (5 \times 5 \times 5 + 5/5)) \\
&:= (6+6)/6 + (6 \times (66+6)) \\
&:= 777 - 7 \times 7 \times 7 \\
&:= (8 - 8/8) \times (8 \times 8 - ((8+8)/8)) \\
&:= 99 + ((9+9) \times (9+9) + (99/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 435 &:= (1+1+1) \times (1 + (1+11))^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 + (2 \times 222 - 22/2) \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times 33 + 333) \\
&:= 444 - ((4/4 + 4) + 4) \\
&:= 5 + (555 - 5 \times 5 \times 5) \\
&:= (6 \times (66+6)) + (6 \times 6/(6+6)) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times 77 - 777/7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + (88/8 - 88) \\
&:= (9+9) \times (9+9) + 999/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 436 &:= (1+1) \times (1+1) \times (111-1-1) \\
&:= 2 \times (222 - (2+2)) \\
&:= 3 + (((3+3)^{3/3+3} + 3)/3) \\
&:= 444 - 4 - 4 \\
&:= 5 + ((555 - 5 \times 5 \times 5) + 5/5) \\
&:= 6 + ((6 \times (66+6)) - ((6+6)/6)) \\
&:= 7 + (((7 - 777)/7) + 7 \times 77) \\
&:= 888 / ((8+8)/8) - 8 \\
&:= (((9 \times 9 \times 99) - 9)/(9+9)) - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 437 &:= 1 + ((1+1) \times (1+1) \times (111-1-1)) \\
&:= ((22 - 2/2)^2) - 2 - 2 \\
&:= (((3+3) \times ((3+3)^3 + 3)) - 3)/3 \\
&:= 4 + (444 - 44/4) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 \times 5 + (5^5 - 5)/(5+5) \\
&:= 6 + ((6 \times (66+6)) - 6/6) \\
&:= 7 + (((77 \times 77 - 7)/(7+7)) + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - 88/8 \\
&:= (((9 \times 9 \times 99) + 9)/(9+9)) - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 438 &:= (1+1) \times ((1+1) \times (111-1) - 1) \\
&:= (2 \times (222 - 2)) - 2 \\
&:= (3+3) \times (((3+3)^3 + 3)/3) \\
&:= 444 - ((4+4)/4 + 4) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 \times 5 + (5^5 + 5)/(5+5) \\
&:= 6 + (6 \times (66+6)) \\
&:= 7 + (((77 \times 77 + 7)/(7+7)) + 7) \\
&:= (8 - 88)/8 + 8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9+9)/9)^9) - (((9+9)/9) + 9 \times 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 439 &:= ((11+11-1))^{1+1} - 1 - 1 \\
&:= ((22 - 2/2)^2) - 2 \\
&:= (((3+3) \times ((3+3)^3 + 3)) + 3)/3 \\
&:= 444 - (4/4 + 4) \\
&:= 555 - (555/5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 + ((6 \times (66+6)) + 6/6) \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7 + 7) - (7+7)/7 \\
&:= 8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - (8/8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9+9)/9)^9) - (9/9 + 9 \times 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 440 &:= (1+1) \times (1+1) \times (111-1) \\
&:= 2 \times (222 - 2) \\
&:= (3/3 + 3) \times ((333 - 3)/3) \\
&:= 444 - 4 \\
&:= (5+5) \times (55 - (55/5)) \\
&:= 6 + ((6 \times (66+6)) + ((6+6)/6)) \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7 + 7) - 7/7 \\
&:= 8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - 8 \\
&:= 9 + (((9+9)/9)^9) - 9 \times 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 441 &:= (11+11-1))^{1+1} \\
&:= (22 - 2/2)^2 \\
&:= 3 \times (((3+3) \times (3^3 - 3)) + 3) \\
&:= 4/4 + (444 - 4) \\
&:= ((55/5 + 5) + 5)^{(5+5)/5} \\
&:= 6 + ((6 \times (66+6)) + (6 \times 6/(6+6))) \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7 + 7) \\
&:= 8/8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - 8) \\
&:= 9 \times ((9 \times 99 - 9)/(9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 442 &:= 1 + ((11+11-1))^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 \times 222 - 2 \\
&:= 3 \times 33 + (((3/3+3) + 3)^3) \\
&:= 444 - (4+4)/4 \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 - 5)/(5+5) + 5 \times 5 \times 5) \\
&:= ((66 - 6)/6) + (6 \times (66+6)) \\
&:= 7/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7 + 7) \\
&:= (8+8)/8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - 8) \\
&:= 9/9 + (9 \times ((9 \times 99 - 9)/(9+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 443 &:= ((1+1) \times (1+1) \times 111) - 1 \\
&:= 2 + ((22 - 2/2)^2) \\
&:= 333 + ((333 - 3)/3) \\
&:= 444 - 4/4 \\
&:= 555 - (555 + 5)/5 \\
&:= 66/6 + (6 \times (66+6)) \\
&:= ((7+7)/7) + 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7 + 7) \\
&:= 888 / ((8+8)/8) - 8/8 \\
&:= 9 + (((9+9) \times (9+9) + (99/9)) + 99)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 444 &:= (1+1) \times (1+1) \times 111 \\
&:= 2 \times 222 \\
&:= 333 + 333/3 \\
&:= 444 \\
&:= (5 - 5/5) \times 555/5 \\
&:= 6 + ((6 \times (66+6)) + 6) \\
&:= (77/7 - 7) \times 777/7 \\
&:= 888 / ((8+8)/8) \\
&:= (999 \times (9 - 9/9)) / (9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 445 &:= 1 + ((1+1) \times (1+1) \times 111) \\
&:= 2/2 + 2 \times 222 \\
&:= 333 + ((333 + 3)/3) \\
&:= 4/4 + 444 \\
&:= 555 - (55 + 55) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 \times (66+6)) + 6/6) + 6) \\
&:= 77/7 + (777 - 7 \times 7 \times 7) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - (88/8)) \\
&:= ((9 \times 9 \times 99) - 9) / (9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 446 &:= (1+1) \times (1 + (1+1) \times 111) \\
&:= 2 + 2 \times 222 \\
&:= ((3 \times (33 \times 3^3)) + 3) / (3+3) \\
&:= 444 + (4+4)/4 \\
&:= 5 + (((55/5 + 5) + 5)^{(5+5)/5}) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 \times (66+6)) + ((6+6)/6)) + 6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7 + 7) - ((7+7)/7)) \\
&:= 8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - (8+8)/8 \\
&:= ((9 \times 9 \times 99) + 9) / (9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 447 &:= 1 + ((1+1) \times (1 + (1+1) \times 111)) \\
&:= 2 + (2 \times 222 + 2/2) \\
&:= 3 + (333/3 + 333) \\
&:= 4 + (444 - 4/4) \\
&:= ((5^5 - 5/5) + 5) / ((5+5)/5 + 5) \\
&:= ((6/6 + 6) \times ((6+6)/6)^6) - 6/6 \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7 + 7) - 7/7) \\
&:= 8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - 8/8 \\
&:= 9/9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 99) + 9) / (9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 448 &:= (1+1) \times (1+1) \times (1+111) \\
&:= 2 \times (222+2) \\
&:= (3/3+3) \times ((333+3)/3) \\
&:= 4+444 \\
&:= (5-5/5) \times (555+5)/5 \\
&:= (6/6+6) \times ((6+6)/6)^6 \\
&:= 7+7 \times (7 \times 7+7+7) \\
&:= 8 \times (8 \times 8-8) \\
&:= (9-9/9) \times ((999+9)/(9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 449 &:= 1 + ((1+1) \times (1+1) \times (1+111)) \\
&:= 2/2 + (2 \times (222+2)) \\
&:= 3 + (((3 \times (33 \times 3^3)) + 3)/(3+3)) \\
&:= 4 + (444+4/4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5-5/5) \times 555/5) \\
&:= 6 + ((6 \times (66+6)) + (66/6)) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7+7+7) + 7/7) \\
&:= 8/8 + 8 \times (8 \times 8-8) \\
&:= 9 + (((((9+9)/9)^9) - 9 \times 9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 450 &:= (1+1) \times (1+(1+1) \times (1+111)) \\
&:= 2 + (2 \times (222+2)) \\
&:= (3+3) \times ((3 \times (3^3-3)) + 3) \\
&:= 4 + (444 + (4+4)/4) \\
&:= (5+5) \times (55-5-5) \\
&:= 666 - 6 \times 6 \times 6 \\
&:= (7-7/7) \times (77 - (7+7)/7) \\
&:= (8+8)/8 + 8 \times (8 \times 8-8) \\
&:= 9 \times ((9 \times 99+9)/(9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 451 &:= 1 + ((1+1) \times (1+(1+1) \times (1+111))) \\
&:= 2 + ((2 \times (222+2)) + 2/2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3/3+3) \times ((333+3)/3)) \\
&:= 4 + ((444-4/4) + 4) \\
&:= 5/5 + ((5+5) \times (55-5-5)) \\
&:= 66 + (6 \times 66 - (66/6)) \\
&:= 77/7 \times (7 \times 7 - (7/7+7)) \\
&:= 88/8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8-8) - 8) \\
&:= ((9 \times 9 \times 99) + 99)/(9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 452 &:= 11 + ((11+11-1)^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 \times ((222+2) + 2) \\
&:= (3/3+3) \times (((333-3)/3) + 3) \\
&:= 4 + (444+4) \\
&:= (5+5)/5 + ((5+5) \times (55-5-5)) \\
&:= 66 + (((6-66)/6) + 6 \times 66) \\
&:= 77/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7+7+7) \\
&:= 8 + 888/((8+8)/8) \\
&:= 9/9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 99) + 99)/(9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 453 &:= 1 + (11 + ((11+11-1)^{1+1})) \\
&:= 2/2 + (2 \times ((222+2) + 2)) \\
&:= (3 \times (3+3) \times 3^3) - 33 \\
&:= 4 + ((444+4/4) + 4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5-5/5) \times (555+5)/5) \\
&:= 6 + (((6/6+6) \times ((6+6)/6)^6) - 6/6) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 + (777-7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8-8) - (88/8)) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + ((999 \times (9-9/9))/(9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 454 &:= 11 + (((1+1) \times (1+1) \times 111) - 1) \\
&:= 2 + (2 \times ((222+2) + 2)) \\
&:= 3/3 + ((3 \times (3+3) \times 3^3) - 33) \\
&:= 444 + (44-4)/4 \\
&:= 5 + (((5-5/5) \times 555/5) + 5) \\
&:= 6 + ((6/6+6) \times ((6+6)/6)^6) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 + 777/7 \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8-8) - ((8+8)/8)) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 99) - 9)/(9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 455 &:= 11 + ((1+1) \times (1+1) \times 111) \\
&:= 22/2 + 2 \times 222 \\
&:= (3+3)^3 + (((3^{3+3} - 3)/3) - 3) \\
&:= 444 + 44/4 \\
&:= 5 + ((5+5) \times (55-5-5)) \\
&:= (6/6+6) \times (66-6/6) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 - (77+7) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8-8) - 8/8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 99) + 9)/(9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 456 &:= 1 + (11 + ((1+1) \times (1+1) \times 111)) \\
&:= 2 \times (((222+2) + 2) + 2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3 \times (3+3) \times 3^3) - 33) \\
&:= 4 + (444+4+4) \\
&:= 5 + (((5+5) \times (55-5-5)) + 5/5) \\
&:= 66 + (6 \times 66 - 6) \\
&:= (7-7/7) \times (77-7/7) \\
&:= 8+8 \times (8 \times 8-8) \\
&:= (9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9+9))) - 999/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 457 &:= 11 + ((1+1) \times (1+(1+1) \times 111)) \\
&:= 2 + (2 \times 222 + 22/2) \\
&:= (3+3)^3 + (((3^{3+3} + 3)/3) - 3) \\
&:= 4 + (((444+4/4) + 4) + 4) \\
&:= (((5+5)/5)^{5-5/5+5}) - 55 \\
&:= 66 + ((6 \times 66 - 6) + 6/6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7-7/7) \times (77 - (7+7)/7)) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8-8) + 8/8) \\
&:= ((9999+9)/(9+9)) - 99
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 458 &:= 1 + (11 + ((1+1) \times (1+(1+1) \times 111))) \\
&:= 22^2 - (22+2+2) \\
&:= (3+3)^3 + ((3^{3+3} - 3)/3) \\
&:= 4 + ((44-4)/4 + 444) \\
&:= (5 \times 5 \times 5 \times 55 - 5)/(5+5+5) \\
&:= 66 + (((6+6)/6 - 6) + 6 \times 66) \\
&:= 7 + (77/7 \times (7 \times 7 - (7/7+7))) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8-8) + ((8+8)/8)) \\
&:= 9 + ((((((9+9)/9)^9) - 9 \times 9) + 9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 459 &:= 11 + ((1+1) \times (1+1) \times (1+111)) \\
&:= 22/2 + (2 \times (222+2)) \\
&:= 3 \times (3 \times ((3^3-3) + 3^3)) \\
&:= 4 + (444 + 44/4) \\
&:= (5^5 - 555)/5 - 55 \\
&:= 66 + (6 \times 66 - (6 \times 6/(6+6))) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7+7+7) + (77/7)) \\
&:= 88/8 + 8 \times (8 \times 8-8) \\
&:= (9+9+9) \times ((9-9/9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 460 &:= (1+1) \times ((11-1) \times (1+11+11)) \\
&:= 22^2 - (22+2) \\
&:= (3+3)^3 + ((3^{3+3} + 3)/3) \\
&:= 4 \times 4 + 444 \\
&:= 5 + (((5+5) \times (55-5-5)) + 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 66 + ((6+6)/6)^6 \\
&:= 7 \times 77 - ((7+7)/7 + 77) \\
&:= 8 + (888/((8+8)/8) + 8) \\
&:= (9 \times (99+9)) - (((9+9)/9)^9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 461 &:= ((1+1) \times (11 \times (11+11-1))) - 1 \\
&:= 22^2 - (22+2/2) \\
&:= (33 \times (33/3+3)) - 3/3 \\
&:= 4 \times 4 + (444+4/4) \\
&:= 55/5 + ((5+5) \times (55-5-5)) \\
&:= 66 + (6 \times 66 - 6/6) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 - (7/7+77) \\
&:= 8 \times (8 \times 8-8) + (88+8+8)/8 \\
&:= 9/9 + ((9 \times (99+9)) - (((9+9)/9)^9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 462 &:= (1+1) \times (11 \times (11+11-1)) \\
&:= 22^2 - 22 \\
&:= 33 \times (33/3+3) \\
&:= 4 \times 4 + (444 + (4+4)/4) \\
&:= 55/5 \times (((5+5)/5)^5 + 5) + 5 \\
&:= 66 + 6 \times 66 \\
&:= 77 \times (7-7/7) \\
&:= (8-8/8) \times (((8+8)/8) + 8 \times 8) \\
&:= 99 + ((99 \times 99)/(9+9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 463 &:= 1 + ((1 + 1) \times (11 \times (11 + 11 - 1))) \\
&:= 22 + ((22 - 2/2)^2) \\
&:= 3/3 + (33 \times (33/3 + 3)) \\
&:= 4 + ((444 + 44/4) + 4) \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) + (5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) \\
&:= 66 + (6 \times 66 + 6/6) \\
&:= 7/7 + (77 \times (7 - 7/7)) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - 8/8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 99) - 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 464 &:= (1 + 1) \times (111 + 11^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 + (22^2 - 22) \\
&:= 3 + ((33 \times (33/3 + 3)) - 3/3) \\
&:= 4 + (444 + 4 \times 4) \\
&:= (5 - 5/5) \times (555/5 + 5) \\
&:= 66 + (((6 + 6)/6) + 6 \times 66) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 + ((7 + 7)/7 - 77) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 99) + 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 465 &:= 1 + ((1 + 1) \times (111 + 11^{1+1})) \\
&:= 2 + ((22^2 - 22) + 2/2) \\
&:= 3 + (33 \times (33/3 + 3)) \\
&:= 4 + ((444 + 4 \times 4) + 4/4) \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times 5 \times 5 - ((5 + 5)/5)^5) \\
&:= 66 + ((6 \times 6/(6 + 6)) + 6 \times 66) \\
&:= 77 + (((7 \times 777) - 7)/(7 + 7)) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) + 8/8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + ((9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9))) - 999/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 466 &:= (1 + 1) \times (11 + (1 + 1) \times 111) \\
&:= 22 + 2 \times 222 \\
&:= 3 + ((33 \times (33/3 + 3)) + 3/3) \\
&:= 444 + (44/((4 + 4)/4)) \\
&:= (5^5 + 5)/5 - (5 \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 + 6)/6)^6 + 6 \times 66) \\
&:= 77 + (((7 \times 777) + 7)/(7 + 7)) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) + ((8 + 8)/8)) + 8) \\
&:= ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)) - (99/9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 467 &:= 1 + ((1 + 1) \times (11 + (1 + 1) \times 111)) \\
&:= 22 + (2 \times 222 + 2/2) \\
&:= ((3 + 3) \times (3 \times 3^3 - 3)) - 3/3 \\
&:= 4^4 + (4^4 - (44 + 4/4)) \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5) + 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5)) \\
&:= (6 \times (66 + 6 + 6)) - 6/6 \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times 77 - ((7 + 7)/7 + 77)) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) + (88/8)) \\
&:= (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - (((9 + 9 + 9) + 9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 468 &:= (1 + 1) \times (1 + (11 + (1 + 1) \times 111)) \\
&:= 22^2 - 2^{2+2} \\
&:= (3 + 3) \times (3 \times 3^3 - 3) \\
&:= 4^4 + (4^4 - 44) \\
&:= (5 - 5/5) \times ((555 + 5)/5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 \times (66 + 6 + 6) \\
&:= (7 - 7/7) \times (7/7 + 77) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - (88/((8 + 8)/8)) \\
&:= (9 + 9) \times (((9 - 9/9) + 9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 469 &:= 1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + (11 + (1 + 1) \times 111))) \\
&:= 2/2 + (22^2 - 2^{2+2}) \\
&:= 3/3 + ((3 + 3) \times (3 \times 3^3 - 3)) \\
&:= 4/4 + ((4^4 - 44) + 4^4) \\
&:= (5 - 5/5)^5 - 555 \\
&:= 6/6 + (6 \times (66 + 6 + 6)) \\
&:= 7 + (77 \times (7 - 7/7)) \\
&:= (8 - 8/8) \times ((88/8 - 8) + 8 \times 8) \\
&:= 9 + ((9 \times (99 + 9)) - (((9 + 9)/9)^9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 470 &:= (1 + 1) \times (11 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 111)) \\
&:= 2 + (22^2 - 2^{2+2}) \\
&:= 3 + (((3 + 3) \times (3 \times 3^3 - 3)) - 3/3) \\
&:= 4 + ((44/((4 + 4)/4)) + 444) \\
&:= (5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5)) - 5 \\
&:= (6 + 6)/6 + (6 \times (66 + 6 + 6)) \\
&:= 7 + ((77 \times (7 - 7/7)) + 7/7) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 - 8/8) \times (((8 + 8)/8) + 8 \times 8)) \\
&:= (9 + 9)/9 + ((9 + 9) \times (((9 - 9/9) + 9) + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 471 &:= (11 + 11)^{1+1} - (1 + 1 + 11) \\
&:= 22^2 - (22/2 + 2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3 + 3) \times (3 \times 3^3 - 3)) \\
&:= 4 \times 4 + (444 + 44/4) \\
&:= 5/5 + ((5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5)) - 5) \\
&:= 6 \times (66 - 6) + 666/6 \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times 7 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7 \\
&:= 8 + (((8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - 8/8) + 8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (((99 \times 99)/(9 + 9 + 9)) + 99)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 472 &:= (11 + 11)^{1+1} - 1 - 11 \\
&:= 22^2 - (2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)) \\
&:= 3 + (((3 + 3) \times (3 \times 3^3 - 3)) + 3/3) \\
&:= 4 + ((4^4 - 44) + 4^4) \\
&:= 55 + (((5^5 + 5^5) + 5)/(5 + 5 + 5)) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 + 6)/6)^6 + 6 \times 66) + 6 \\
&:= 7 \times (77 - 7) - (77/7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) + 8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 99) - 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 473 &:= (11 + 11)^{1+1} - 11 \\
&:= 22^2 - 22/2 \\
&:= 33/3 + (33 \times (33/3 + 3)) \\
&:= 44/4 \times (44 - 4/4) \\
&:= 55/5 \times (55 - ((55 + 5)/5)) \\
&:= 6 + ((6 \times (66 + 6 + 6)) - 6/6) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 + (77/7 - 77) \\
&:= 8 + (((8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) + 8/8) + 8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - (((9 + 9)/9)^{9-9/9})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 474 &:= 1 + ((11 + 11)^{1+1} - 11) \\
&:= 22^2 + ((2 - 22)/2) \\
&:= (3 \times ((3 + 3) \times 3^3 - 3)) - 3 \\
&:= ((44 \times (44 - 4/4)) + 4)/4 \\
&:= 5 + ((5 - 5/5)^5 - 555) \\
&:= 6 + (6 \times (66 + 6 + 6)) \\
&:= (7 - 7/7) \times ((7 + 7)/7 + 77) \\
&:= (8 - (8 + 8)/8) \times (88 - (8/8 + 8)) \\
&:= ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)) - (99 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 475 &:= 1 + (1 + ((11 + 11)^{1+1} - 11)) \\
&:= 2 + (22^2 - 22/2) \\
&:= (3 \times (3 + 3) \times 3^3) - 33/3 \\
&:= 444 + (4 \times (4 + 4) - 4/4) \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5) \\
&:= 6 + ((6 \times (66 + 6 + 6)) + 6/6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 - 7/7) \times (7/7 + 77)) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) + (88/8)) + 8) \\
&:= ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)) - 99/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 476 &:= (1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1) \times (11^{1+1} - (1 + 1))) \\
&:= 22^2 - 2 \times (2 + 2) \\
&:= (33/3 + 3) \times (3/3 + 33) \\
&:= 444 + 4 \times (4 + 4) \\
&:= 5/5 + (5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5)) \\
&:= (6/6 + 6) \times (((6 + 6)/6) + 66) \\
&:= 7 \times (77 - 7) - (7 + 7) \\
&:= 88 \times 88/(8 + 8) - 8 \\
&:= (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - ((9 + 9 + 9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 477 &:= 1 + ((1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1) \times (11^{1+1} - (1 + 1)))) \\
&:= 2 + ((22^2 - 22/2) + 2) \\
&:= 3 \times ((3 + 3) \times 3^3 - 3) \\
&:= 4 + (44/4 \times (44 - 4/4)) \\
&:= (5 + 5)/5 + (5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5)) \\
&:= 6 + (6 \times (66 - 6) + 666/6) \\
&:= 7/7 + (7 \times (77 - 7) - (7 + 7)) \\
&:= (8/8 + 8) \times (8 \times 8 - 88/8) \\
&:= ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)) - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 478 &:= (1+1) \times ((1+1) \times (11^{1+1} - 1) - 1) \\
&:= 22^2 - (2+2+2) \\
&:= 3/3 + (3 \times ((3+3) \times 3^3 - 3)) \\
&:= 4^4 + (444/((4+4)/4)) \\
&:= 5 + (55/5 \times (55 - ((55+5)/5))) \\
&:= ((66-6)/6) + (6 \times (66+6+6)) \\
&:= 7 + (((7+7)/7)^7 + 7 \times 7 \times 7) \\
&:= (88 \times 88 - (88+8))/(8+8) \\
&:= 9/9 + (((9+9) \times (9+9+9)) - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 479 &:= ((1+1) \times (1+1) \times (11^{1+1} - 1)) - 1 \\
&:= 22^2 - (2/2 + 2 + 2) \\
&:= ((3-3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - 33 \\
&:= ((44 \times 44 - 4)/4) - 4 \\
&:= 5 + (((5-5/5)^5 - 555) + 5) \\
&:= 66/6 + (6 \times (66+6+6)) \\
&:= 7 \times (77-7) - 77/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - ((8/8+8+8+8) + 8) \\
&:= (9+9)/9 + (((9+9) \times (9+9+9)) - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 480 &:= (1+1) \times (1+1) \times (11^{1+1} - 1) \\
&:= 22^2 - 2 - 2 \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times ((3+3) \times 3^3 - 3)) \\
&:= (4+4) \times (4 \times 4 + 44) \\
&:= 5 + (5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5)) \\
&:= 6 + ((6 \times (66+6+6)) + 6) \\
&:= (7/7 + 7) \times (77/7 + 7 \times 7) \\
&:= 8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8/((8+8)/8))) \\
&:= (9/9 - 9 \times 9) \times (((9+9+9)/9) - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 481 &:= (11+11)^{1+1} - 1 - 1 - 1 \\
&:= 22^2 - 2/2 - 2 \\
&:= 3 + ((3 \times ((3+3) \times 3^3 - 3)) + 3/3) \\
&:= ((44 \times 44 + 4)/4) - 4 \\
&:= (5555 - 5^5)/5 - 5 \\
&:= (6/6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6/6) \\
&:= 7 \times (77-7) - ((7+7)/7 + 7) \\
&:= 8/8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8/((8+8)/8)))) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + ((99/9 + 9)^{(9+9)/9})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 482 &:= (11+11)^{1+1} - 1 - 1 \\
&:= 22^2 - 2 \\
&:= 3 + (((3-3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - 33) \\
&:= (44 \times 44 - (4+4))/4 \\
&:= ((5555 - 5^5 + 5)/5) - 5 \\
&:= 6 + ((6/6 + 6) \times (((6+6)/6) + 66)) \\
&:= 7 \times (77-7) - (7/7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - ((88+88)/8 + 8) \\
&:= ((9 \times ((9 \times (99+9)) - 9)) + 9)/(9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 483 &:= (11+11)^{1+1} - 1 \\
&:= 22^2 - 2/2 \\
&:= (3 \times (3+3) \times 3^3) - 3 \\
&:= (44 \times 44 - 4)/4 \\
&:= 5 \times 55 + ((5^5 - 5)/(5+5+5)) \\
&:= (6/6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6/(6+6) + 66) \\
&:= 7 \times (77-7) - 7 \\
&:= 88 \times 88/(8+8) - 8/8 \\
&:= ((9+9+9)/9) \times (9 \times (9+9) - 9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 484 &:= (11+11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 22^2 \\
&:= 3/3 + ((3 \times (3+3) \times 3^3) - 3) \\
&:= 44 \times 44/4 \\
&:= 55/5 \times (55 - (55/5)) \\
&:= ((66+66)/6)^{(6+6)/6} \\
&:= 7/7 + (7 \times (77-7) - 7) \\
&:= 88 \times 88/(8+8) \\
&:= ((99+99)/9)^{(9+9)/9}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 485 &:= 1 + (11+11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2/2 + 22^2 \\
&:= ((3-3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - 3^3 \\
&:= (44 \times 44 + 4)/4 \\
&:= 5 + ((5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5)) + 5) \\
&:= 6 + ((6 \times (66+6+6)) + (66/6)) \\
&:= ((7+7)/7) + (7 \times (77-7) - 7) \\
&:= 8/8 + 88 \times 88/(8+8) \\
&:= (((9+9)/9)^9) - (9+9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 486 &:= 1 + (1 + (11+11)^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 + 22^2 \\
&:= 3 \times (3+3) \times 3^3 \\
&:= ((44 \times 44 + 4) + 4)/4 \\
&:= (5555 - 5^5)/5 \\
&:= 666 + (6 \times (6 - 6 \times 6)) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (77-7) - (77/7)) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + ((8-88)/8 - (8+8)) \\
&:= (9+9) \times (9+9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 487 &:= 1 + (1 + (1 + (11+11)^{1+1})) \\
&:= 2 + 22^2 + 2/2 \\
&:= 3/3 + (3 \times (3+3) \times 3^3) \\
&:= 4 + ((44 \times 44 - 4)/4) \\
&:= (5555 - 5^5 + 5)/5 \\
&:= 6 + ((6/6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6/6)) \\
&:= 7 \times (77-7) - (7+7+7)/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - (8/8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \\
&:= 9/9 + ((9+9) \times (9+9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 488 &:= (1+1) \times ((1+1) \times (1+11^{1+1})) \\
&:= 2 + 22^2 + 2 \\
&:= 3 + (((3-3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - 3^3) \\
&:= 44 + 444 \\
&:= (5-5/5) \times ((555+55)/5) \\
&:= ((6+6)/6 + 6) \times ((66-6) + 6/6) \\
&:= 7 \times (77-7) - (7+7)/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 \\
&:= (9+9)/9 + ((9+9) \times (9+9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 489 &:= 1 + ((1+1) \times ((1+1) \times (1+11^{1+1}))) \\
&:= 2 + 22^2 + 2/2 + 2 \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times (3+3) \times 3^3) \\
&:= 4 + ((44 \times 44 + 4)/4) \\
&:= 555 - (55/5 + 55) \\
&:= 666 - (666/6 + 66) \\
&:= 7 \times (77-7) - 7/7 \\
&:= 8/8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - (8+8+8)) \\
&:= ((9+9+9)/9) + ((9+9) \times (9+9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 490 &:= (1+1) \times (1 + ((1+1) \times (1+11^{1+1}))) \\
&:= 2 + 22^2 + 2 + 2 \\
&:= 3 + ((3 \times (3+3) \times 3^3) + 3/3) \\
&:= 4 + (((44 \times 44 + 4) + 4)/4) \\
&:= (5+5) \times (55 - (5/5 + 5)) \\
&:= (6/6 + 6) \times (((6+6)/6)^6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 \times (77-7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - (88+88)/8 \\
&:= (((9 \times 999) - 9)/(9+9)) - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 491 &:= 1 + ((1+1) \times (1 + ((1+1) \times (1+11^{1+1})))) \\
&:= 2 + 22^2 + 2/2 + 2 + 2 \\
&:= 3 + (((((3-3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - 3^3) + 3)) \\
&:= 4 + (((44 \times 44 - 4)/4) + 4) \\
&:= 5 + (5555 - 5^5)/5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + ((6/6 + 6) \times (66 - 6/6)) \\
&:= 7/7 + 7 \times (77-7) \\
&:= 8 + (88 \times 88/(8+8) - 8/8) \\
&:= (((9 \times 999) + 9)/(9+9)) - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 492 &:= (1+1) \times ((1+1) \times (1 + (1+11^{1+1}))) \\
&:= 2 \times (2+2) + 22^2 \\
&:= 3 + ((3 \times (3+3) \times 3^3) + 3) \\
&:= 4 + (444 + 44) \\
&:= 5 + ((5555 - 5^5 + 5)/5) \\
&:= 66 + ((6 \times (66+6)) - 6) \\
&:= ((7+7)/7) + 7 \times (77-7) \\
&:= 8 + 88 \times 88/(8+8) \\
&:= (((9+9)/9)^9) - (99/9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 493 &:= 11 + ((11 + 11)^{1+1} - (1 + 1)) \\
&:= 22/2 + (22^2 - 2) \\
&:= 3 + (((3 \times (3 + 3) \times 3^3) + 3/3) + 3) \\
&:= 4 + (((44 \times 44 + 4)/4) + 4) \\
&:= 555 + ((5 - 5^5/5)/(5 + 5)) \\
&:= ((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6)) - 66/6 \\
&:= 7 \times (77 - 7) + (7 + 7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - (88/8 + 8) \\
&:= (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - (9/9 + 9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 494 &:= 11 + ((11 + 11)^{1+1} - 1) \\
&:= 2 + 2 \times (2 + 2) + 22^2 \\
&:= ((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - (3 \times (3 + 3)) \\
&:= ((44 \times 44 - 4) + 44)/4 \\
&:= 555 - ((55 + 5/5) + 5) \\
&:= ((6 - 66)/6) + ((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6)) \\
&:= 77/7 + (7 \times (77 - 7) - 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + ((8 - 88)/8 - 8) \\
&:= (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - (9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 495 &:= 11 + (11 + 11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 22/2 + 22^2 \\
&:= 3 \times ((3 + 3) \times 3^3 + 3) \\
&:= 44/4 \times (44 + 4/4) \\
&:= 55 \times (5 - 5/5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 66 + (666/6 - (6 + 6)) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (77 - 7) - ((7 + 7)/7)) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - (8/8 + 8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 496 &:= 1 + (11 + (11 + 11)^{1+1}) \\
&:= 22^2 + (2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)) \\
&:= 3/3 + (3 \times ((3 + 3) \times 3^3 + 3)) \\
&:= 4 \times (4 \times 4 \times (4 + 4) - 4) \\
&:= 5/5 + (55 \times (5 - 5/5 + 5)) \\
&:= ((6 + 6)/6)^6 + (6 \times (66 + 6)) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (77 - 7) - 7/7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - 8 - 8 \\
&:= 9 + (((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)) + 9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 497 &:= 1 + (1 + (11 + (11 + 11)^{1+1})) \\
&:= 2 + (22/2 + 22^2) \\
&:= 33/3 + (3 \times (3 + 3) \times 3^3) \\
&:= 4/4 + ((4^4 - 4 \times 4) + 4^4) \\
&:= 555 + ((5 + 5)/5 - (55 + 5)) \\
&:= 66 + ((6 \times (66 + 6)) - 6/6) \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times (77 - 7) \\
&:= 8/8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - (8 + 8)) \\
&:= 99/9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 498 &:= (11 - 1)^{1+1+1}/(1 + 1) - 1 - 1 \\
&:= 2^{2+2} + (22^2 - 2) \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times ((3 + 3) \times 3^3 + 3)) \\
&:= 4^4 + (44 \times 44/(4 + 4)) \\
&:= 555 - ((5 + 5)/5 + 55) \\
&:= 66 + (6 \times (66 + 6)) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (77 - 7) + 7/7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + (((8 + 8)/8) - (8 + 8)) \\
&:= ((99 + 9)/9) + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 499 &:= (11 - 1)^{1+1+1}/(1 + 1) - 1 \\
&:= 2 + 22/2 + 22^2 + 2 \\
&:= ((3 \times (3 \times 333)) - 3)/(3 + 3) \\
&:= 4 + 44/4 \times (44 + 4/4) \\
&:= 555 - (55 + 5/5) \\
&:= 66 + ((6 \times (66 + 6)) + 6/6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (77 - 7) + ((7 + 7)/7)) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - (88 + 8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= ((9 \times 999) - 9)/(9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 500 &:= (11 - 1)^{1+1+1}/(1 + 1) \\
&:= 2^{2+2} + 22^2 \\
&:= (3/3 + 3) \times ((3 - 3/3 + 3)^3) \\
&:= 4 + ((4^4 - 4 \times 4) + 4^4) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) \\
&:= 66 + ((6 \times (66 + 6)) + ((6 + 6)/6)) \\
&:= 7 \times (77 - 7) + (77 - 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - (88 + 8)/8 \\
&:= ((9 \times 999) + 9)/(9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 501 &:= (1 + 1)^{11-1-1} - 11 \\
&:= 2/2 + 2^{2+2} + 22^2 \\
&:= ((3 + 3) \times (3 \times 3^3 + 3)) - 3 \\
&:= 4^4 + (4^4 - 44/4) \\
&:= 5/5 + (5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5)) \\
&:= 6 \times 66 + (666/6 - 6) \\
&:= 77/7 + 7 \times (77 - 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - 88/8 \\
&:= (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 99/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 502 &:= 1 + (1 + 1)^{11-1-1} - 11 \\
&:= 2 + 2^{2+2} + 22^2 \\
&:= 3 + ((3 \times 3 \times 333 - 3)/(3 + 3)) \\
&:= 4^4 + ((4 - 44)/4 + 4^4) \\
&:= 555 + ((5 + 5)/5 - 55) \\
&:= ((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6)) - (6 + 6)/6 \\
&:= 7 \times (77 - 7) + (77 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + (8 - 88)/8 \\
&:= (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 9/9 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 503 &:= 1 + 1 + (1 + 1)^{11-1-1} - 11 \\
&:= 22 + 22^2 - (2/2 + 2) \\
&:= ((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - 3 \times 3 \\
&:= (((4 + 4) \times (4^4 - 4)) - 4)/4 \\
&:= (5^5 - (555 + 55))/5 \\
&:= ((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6)) - 6/6 \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times (77 - 7) - 7/7) + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - (8/8 + 8) \\
&:= (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 504 &:= (1 + 1) \times ((1 + 11) \times (11 + 11 - 1)) \\
&:= 22 + 22^2 - 2 \\
&:= (3 + 3) \times (3 \times 3^3 + 3) \\
&:= 4^4 + (4^4 - 4 - 4) \\
&:= 5 + (555 - (55 + 5/5)) \\
&:= (6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (77 - 7) + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - 8 \\
&:= 9 + (((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 505 &:= (11111 - 1)/(11 + 11) \\
&:= 22 + 22^2 - 2/2 \\
&:= 3/3 + ((3 + 3) \times (3 \times 3^3 + 3)) \\
&:= (((4 + 4) \times (4^4 - 4)) + 4)/4 \\
&:= 5 + (5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5)) \\
&:= 6/6 + ((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6)) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times (77 - 7) + 7/7) + 7) \\
&:= 8/8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - 8) \\
&:= (9 + 9)/9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 506 &:= (1 + 1) \times 11 \times (1 + 11 + 11) \\
&:= 22 + 22^2 \\
&:= ((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - (3 + 3) \\
&:= 4^4 + (4^4 - ((4 + 4)/4 + 4)) \\
&:= 5 + ((5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5)) + 5/5) \\
&:= (6 + 6)/6 + ((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6)) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times (77 - 7) + ((7 + 7)/7)) + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + (((8 + 8)/8) - 8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)) + (99/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 507 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 22 + 22^2 + 2/2 \\
&:= 3 + ((3 + 3) \times (3 \times 3^3 + 3)) \\
&:= 4^4 + (4^4 - (4/4 + 4)) \\
&:= (((5 + 5)/5)^{5-5/5+5}) - 5 \\
&:= 6 \times 66 + 666/6 \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (77 - 7) + ((77 - 7)/7)) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + (88/8 - (8 + 8)) \\
&:= (((9 + 9)/9)^9) + ((9 - 99)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 508 &:= 1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 + 22^2 + 22 \\
&:= ((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - (3/3 + 3) \\
&:= 4^4 + (4^4 - 4) \\
&:= ((5^5 - (555 + 5))/5) - 5 \\
&:= 6 \times 66 + (666 + 6)/6 \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (77 - 7) + (77/7)) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - (8/(8 + 8)/8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 \times 999) - 9)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 509 &:= (1 + 1)^{11-1-1} - 1 - 1 - 1 \\
&:= 2 + 22^2 + 2/2 + 22 \\
&:= ((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - 3 \\
&:= 4/4 + ((4^4 - 4) + 4^4) \\
&:= (5^5 - 555)/5 - 5 \\
&:= 6 + (((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6)) - 6/6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (77 - 7) + (77 + 7)/7) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - 88/8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 \times 999) + 9)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 510 &:= (1 + 1)^{11-1-1} - 1 - 1 \\
&:= 2^{(2/2+2)^2} - 2 \\
&:= 3^{3+3} - ((3 + 3)^3 + 3) \\
&:= 4^4 + (4^4 - (4 + 4)/4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5)) + 5) \\
&:= 6 + ((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6)) \\
&:= (7 - 7/7) \times (7/7 + 77 + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - (8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - (9 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 511 &:= (1 + 1)^{11-1-1} - 1 \\
&:= 2^{(2/2+2)^2} - 2/2 \\
&:= ((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - 3/3 \\
&:= 4^4 + (4^4 - 4/4) \\
&:= 555 + (55/5 - 55) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6)) + 6/6) \\
&:= 7 \times (77 + 7) - 77 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - 8/8 \\
&:= (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 512 &:= (1 + 1)^{11-1-1} \\
&:= 2^{(2/2+2)^2} \\
&:= (3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3} \\
&:= 4^4 + 4^4 \\
&:= ((5 + 5)/5)^{5-5/5+5} \\
&:= ((6 + 6)/6)^{6 \times 6/(6+6)+6} \\
&:= (7/7 + 7)^{(7+7+7)/7} \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 \\
&:= ((9 + 9)/9)^9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 513 &:= 1 + (1 + 1)^{11-1-1} \\
&:= 2/2 + 2^{(2/2+2)^2} \\
&:= 3^{3+3} - (3 + 3)^3 \\
&:= 4/4 + (4^4 + 4^4) \\
&:= (5^5 - (555 + 5))/5 \\
&:= 6 + (666/6 + 6 \times 66) \\
&:= 7/7 + ((7/7 + 7)^{(7+7+7)/7}) \\
&:= 8/8 + 8 \times 8 \times 8 \\
&:= 9/9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 514 &:= 1 + 1 + (1 + 1)^{11-1-1} \\
&:= 2 + 2^{(2/2+2)^2} \\
&:= 3 + (((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - 3/3) \\
&:= 4^4 + ((4 + 4)/4 + 4^4) \\
&:= (5^5 - 555)/5 \\
&:= 6 + ((666 + 6)/6 + 6 \times 66) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 - (77/7 + 7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + (8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= (9 + 9)/9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 515 &:= 1 + 1 + 1 + (1 + 1)^{11-1-1} \\
&:= 2 + ((2^{(2/2+2)^2}) + 2/2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) \\
&:= 4 + ((4^4 - 4/4) + 4^4) \\
&:= 5^5/5 - (55 + 55) \\
&:= 66/6 + ((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6)) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times (77 - 7) + (77/7)) + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + (88/8 - 8) \\
&:= (((9 + 9)/9)^9) + ((9 + 9 + 9)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 516 &:= 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + (1 + 1)^{11-1-1} \\
&:= 2 \times (2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2) \\
&:= 3 + (3^{3+3} - (3 + 3)^3) \\
&:= 4 + (4^4 + 4^4) \\
&:= (5^5 + 5)/5 - (55 + 55) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6)) + 6) \\
&:= (7 - 7/7) \times (((7 + 7)/7 + 77) + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + (8/(8 + 8)/8) \\
&:= (((9 + 9)/9)^9) + ((9 \times 9 - 9)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 517 &:= 11 \times (1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11 + 11)) \\
&:= 22 + (22/2 + 22^2) \\
&:= 3 + (((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - 3/3) + 3) \\
&:= 4 + ((4/4 + 4^4) + 4^4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^{5-5/5+5} \\
&:= (66/6) \times (66/6 + 6 \times 6) \\
&:= 77/7 \times 7 \times 7 - (7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times 8 \times 8 - 88/8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 \times 999) - 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 518 &:= (1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1} - 11 \\
&:= 2 + (2 \times (2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2)) \\
&:= 3 + (((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) + 3) \\
&:= 4 + (((4 + 4)/4 + 4^4) + 4^4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 - (555 + 5))/5) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 + 6)/6)^{6 \times 6/(6+6)+6}) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 - (7 + 7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - ((8 + 8)/8)) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 \times 999) + 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 519 &:= 1 + (1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1} - 11 \\
&:= 2 + ((2 \times (2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2)) + 2/2) \\
&:= 33 + (3 \times (3 + 3) \times 3^3) \\
&:= (((4 + 4) \times (4^4 + 4)) - 4)/4 \\
&:= 5 + (5^5 - 555)/5 \\
&:= 6 + ((666/6 + 6 \times 66) + 6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7/7 + 7)^{(7+7+7)/7}) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - 8/8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - ((9 + 9)/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 520 &:= 1 + 1 + (1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1} - 11 \\
&:= 2 \times ((2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2) + 2) \\
&:= 3 \times 3 + (((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - 3/3) \\
&:= 4 + ((4^4 + 4^4) + 4) \\
&:= (5^5 - 5)/5 + 5) \\
&:= ((6 + 6)/6 + 6) \times (66 - 6/6) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 - ((77 + 7)/7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 + 8 \times 8 \times 8 \\
&:= 9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 521 &:= 11 + (1 + 1)^{11-1-1} - (1 + 1) \\
&:= (22/2)^2 + (22 - 2)^2 \\
&:= 3 \times 3 + ((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) \\
&:= (((4 + 4) \times (4^4 + 4)) + 4)/4 \\
&:= (5^5 + 5/5)/(5/5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6)) + (66/6)) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 - (77/7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 + 8/8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 522 &:= 11 + (1 + 1)^{11-1-1} - 1 \\
&:= 2 + ((2 + 2 + 2)^2 + 22^2) \\
&:= (3 + 3) \times (3 \times 3^3 + 3 + 3) \\
&:= 4^4 + ((44 - 4)/4 + 4^4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^{5-5/5+5} + 5 \\
&:= 666 - (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 + (((7 - 77)/7) - 7) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 + (8 + 8)/8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) + 9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 523 &:= 11 + (1+1)^{11-1-1} \\
&:= 22/2 + (2^{(2/2+2)^2}) \\
&:= 33/3 + ((3-3/3)^{3 \times 3}) \\
&:= 4^4 + (44/4 + 4^4) \\
&:= 555 - ((5+5)/5)^5 \\
&:= 6 + ((66/6) \times (66/6 + 6 \times 6)) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 - ((7+7)/7 + 7) + 7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + 88/8 \\
&:= 99/9 + (((9+9)/9)^9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 524 &:= 1 + 11 + (1+1)^{11-1-1} \\
&:= 2 \times (22^2 - 222) \\
&:= 3 + (((3-3/3)^{3 \times 3}) + 3 \times 3) \\
&:= (44 \times ((4+4) + 4)) - 4 \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 - 555)/5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 66 + (((6+6)/6)^{6/6+6}) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 - (7/7 + 7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + (88 + 8)/8 \\
&:= (((9+9)/9)^9) + (99 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 525 &:= 1 + 1 + 11 + (1+1)^{11-1-1} \\
&:= ((22 + 2/2)^2) - 2 - 2 \\
&:= 3 + ((3+3) \times (3 \times 3^3 + 3 + 3)) \\
&:= 444 + (4 - 4/4)^4 \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) + 5) \\
&:= (6 - 6/6) \times (666/6 - 6) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 - (7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + (88 + 8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= (((9+9)/9)^9) + ((99 + 9 + 9)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 526 &:= (1+1) \times ((1+1) \times 11 \times (1+11) - 1) \\
&:= (22 \times (22 + 2)) - 2 \\
&:= 3 + (((3-3/3)^{3 \times 3}) + 33/3) \\
&:= (44 \times ((4+4) + 4)) - (4 + 4)/4 \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 + 5/5)/(5/5 + 5)) \\
&:= 6 + (((6+6)/6 + 6) \times (66 - 6/6)) \\
&:= 7/7 + (7 \times 77 - (7 + 7)) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times 8 \times 8 - ((8+8)/8)) + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 99) - 9)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 527 &:= (1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1} - 1 - 1 \\
&:= ((22 + 2/2)^2) - 2 \\
&:= 3 + (((3-3/3)^{3 \times 3}) + 3 \times 3 + 3) \\
&:= (44 \times ((4+4) + 4)) - 4/4 \\
&:= 555 + ((5+5)/5 - (5 \times 5 + 5)) \\
&:= (66 \times ((6+6)/6 + 6)) - 6/6 \\
&:= 7 \times 77 - (77 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times 8 \times 8 - 8/8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 99) + 9)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 528 &:= (1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1} - 1 \\
&:= 22 \times (22 + 2) \\
&:= 33 \times (3^3 - 33/3) \\
&:= 44 \times ((4+4) + 4) \\
&:= 5 + (555 - ((5+5)/5)^5) \\
&:= 66 \times ((6+6)/6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 - 77/7 \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (((((9+9)/9)^9) - ((9+9)/9)) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 529 &:= (1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1} \\
&:= (22 + 2/2)^2 \\
&:= (3^3 - 3/3 - 3)^{3-3/3} \\
&:= 4/4 + (44 \times ((4+4) + 4)) \\
&:= 555 - (5 \times 5 + 5/5) \\
&:= 6/6 + (66 \times ((6+6)/6 + 6)) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 + (7 - 77)/7 \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times 8 \times 8 + 8/8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (((((9+9)/9)^9) - 9/9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 530 &:= 1 + (1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 + (22 \times (22 + 2)) \\
&:= (3 \times (3 + 3)) + ((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) \\
&:= (4 + 4)/4 + (44 \times ((4+4) + 4)) \\
&:= 555 - 5 \times 5 \\
&:= (6 + 6)/6 + (66 \times ((6+6)/6 + 6)) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 - ((7+7)/7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times 8 \times 8 + (8+8)/8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9+9)/9)^9) + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 531 &:= 1 + 1 + (1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 + ((22 + 2/2)^2) \\
&:= 3 \times ((3 \times (3^3 + 33)) - 3) \\
&:= 4 + ((44 \times ((4+4) + 4)) - 4/4) \\
&:= 5/5 + (555 - 5 \times 5) \\
&:= 6 + ((6 - 6/6) \times (666/6 - 6)) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 - (7/7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 + 88/8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - (99 + 99)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 532 &:= 1 + 1 + 1 + (1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 + ((22 \times (22 + 2)) + 2) \\
&:= 3 + (((3-3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - 3 - 3/3) \\
&:= 4 + (44 \times ((4+4) + 4)) \\
&:= 555 + ((5+5)/5 - 5 \times 5) \\
&:= (6/6 + 6) \times (((6+6)/6)^6 + 6) + 6 \\
&:= 7 \times 77 - 7 \\
&:= 8 + (((88 + 8)/8) + 8 \times 8 \times 8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9+9)/9)^9) + (99/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 533 &:= 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + (1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 + (((22 + 2/2)^2) + 2) \\
&:= 3 + (((3-3/3)^{3 \times 3}) + (3 \times (3 + 3))) \\
&:= 4 + ((44 \times ((4+4) + 4)) + 4/4) \\
&:= 555 - (55 + 55)/5 \\
&:= 6 + ((66 \times ((6+6)/6 + 6)) - 6/6) \\
&:= 7/7 + (7 \times 77 - 7) \\
&:= 8 + ((88 + 8 + 8)/8 + 8 \times 8 \times 8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9+9)/9)^9) + ((99 + 9)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 534 &:= 11 + 11 + (1 + 1)^{11-1-1} \\
&:= 22 + (2^{(2/2+2)^2}) \\
&:= 3 + (33 \times (3 + 3) + 333) \\
&:= (4 + 4)/4 \times (44/4 + 4^4) \\
&:= 5 + (555 - (5 \times 5 + 5/5)) \\
&:= 6 + (66 \times ((6+6)/6 + 6)) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 + ((7+7)/7 - 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + (88 + 88)/8 \\
&:= (((9+9)/9)^9) + ((99 + 99)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 535 &:= 1 + 11 + 11 + (1 + 1)^{11-1-1} \\
&:= 2 + (((22 + 2/2)^2) + 2) + 2 \\
&:= (3333 - (3 \times 3 + 3)^3)/3 \\
&:= (4/4 + 4) \times (444/4 - 4) \\
&:= 5 + (555 - 5 \times 5) \\
&:= 6 + ((66 \times ((6+6)/6 + 6)) + 6/6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times 77 - (77/7)) \\
&:= 8 + (((8 \times 8 \times 8 - 8/8) + 8) + 8) \\
&:= (((99 \times 99) - 9)/(9 + 9)) - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 536 &:= (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 11)) \\
&:= 2 + ((2^{(2/2+2)^2}) + 22) \\
&:= 3^3 + (((3-3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - 3) \\
&:= 4 + ((44 \times ((4+4) + 4)) + 4) \\
&:= 5 + ((555 - 5 \times 5) + 5/5) \\
&:= ((6+6)/6 + 6) \times (66 + 6/6) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 - (7 + 7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 + 8 + 8) \\
&:= (((99 \times 99) + 9)/(9 + 9)) - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 537 &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 11)) \\
&:= 2 \times (2 + 2) + ((22 + 2/2)^2) \\
&:= (3 \times (3 \times (3^3 + 33))) - 3 \\
&:= (4/4 + 4)^4 - (44 + 44) \\
&:= 5 + (((5+5)/5 - 5 \times 5) + 555) \\
&:= 666/6 + ((6 \times (66 + 6)) - 6) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 - (7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + (((8 \times 8 \times 8 + 8/8) + 8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) - 999/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 538 &:= 11 + ((1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1} - (1 + 1)) \\
&:= 22 + (2 \times (2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2)) \\
&:= 3^3 + (((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3} - 3/3)) \\
&:= 4 + ((4 + 4)/4 \times (44/4 + 4^4)) \\
&:= 555 - (((55 + 5)/5) + 5) \\
&:= 666 - (((6 + 6)/6)^{6/6+6}) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 - 7/7 \\
&:= 8 + (((8 \times 8 \times 8 + (8 + 8)/8) + 8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + ((((((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 9/9) + 9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 539 &:= 11 + ((1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1} - 1) \\
&:= 22/2 + (22 \times (22 + 2)) \\
&:= 3^3 + ((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) \\
&:= 44/4 + (44 \times ((4 + 4) + 4)) \\
&:= 555 - (55/5 + 5) \\
&:= (6/6 + 6) \times (66/6 + 66) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times 8 \times 8 + 88/8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (((((9 + 9)/9)^9) + 9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 540 &:= 11 + (1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 \times ((2 \times (22 + 2)) + 222) \\
&:= 3 \times (3 \times (3^3 + 33)) \\
&:= (4 - 4/4) \times ((4 \times 44) + 4) \\
&:= (5 + 5) \times (55 - 5/5) \\
&:= (6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 - 6) \\
&:= 7/7 + 7 \times 77 \\
&:= 8 + (((88 + 8)/8) + 8 \times 8 \times 8) + 8) \\
&:= (9 + 9 + 9) \times (99/9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 541 &:= 1 + (11 + (1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 + ((22 \times (22 + 2)) + 22/2) \\
&:= 3/3 + (3 \times (3 \times (3^3 + 33))) \\
&:= 4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - (44 + 44)) \\
&:= 5/5 + ((5 + 5) \times (55 - 5/5)) \\
&:= 6/6 + ((6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 - 6)) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 + (7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 \times (88 - 8) - (88/8 + 88) \\
&:= 9 + (((((9 + 9)/9)^9) + (99/9)) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 542 &:= 1 + (1 + (11 + (1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1})) \\
&:= 2 + (((22 + 2/2)^2) + 22/2) \\
&:= 3 + (((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) + 3^3) \\
&:= (4 + 4)/4 \times ((44/4 + 4^4) + 4) \\
&:= 555 - (55 + 5 + 5)/5 \\
&:= 6 + (((6 + 6)/6 + 6) \times (66 + 6/6)) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 + (7 + 7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + ((88 + 88)/8 + 8 \times 8 \times 8) \\
&:= ((9999 - 9 \times 9)/(9 + 9)) - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 543 &:= (1111 - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1 - 11 \\
&:= 2^{2+2} + (((22 + 2/2)^2) - 2) \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times (3 \times (3^3 + 33))) \\
&:= ((4 + 4) \times (4 \times 4 \times 4 + 4)) - 4/4 \\
&:= 555 - (55 + 5)/5 \\
&:= 666/6 + (6 \times (66 + 6)) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 + (77/7 - 7) \\
&:= 8 + (((8 \times 8 \times 8 - 8/8) + 8) + 8) + 8) \\
&:= (((99 \times 99) - 9)/(9 + 9)) - 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 544 &:= (1111 - 1)/(1 + 1) - 11 \\
&:= 2 \times (2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2^{2+2}) \\
&:= (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3) - 33 \\
&:= (4 + 4) \times (4 \times 4 \times 4 + 4) \\
&:= 555 - 55/5 \\
&:= 666 - ((666 + 66)/6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times 77 - ((7 + 7)/7)) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times 8 \times 8 + 8 + 8) + 8) \\
&:= ((99 \times 99) - 9)/(9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 545 &:= (1 + 1111)/(1 + 1) - 11 \\
&:= 2^{2+2} + ((22 + 2/2)^2) \\
&:= 33 + ((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) \\
&:= 4/4 + ((4 + 4) \times (4 \times 4 \times 4 + 4)) \\
&:= 555 - 5 - 5 \\
&:= 6 + ((6/6 + 6) \times (66/6 + 66)) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times 77 - 7/7) \\
&:= 8 + (((8 \times 8 \times 8 + 8/8) + 8) + 8) + 8) \\
&:= ((99 \times 99) + 9)/(9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 546 &:= 1 + ((1 + 1111)/(1 + 1) - 11) \\
&:= 222 + ((2^{2+2} + 2)^2) \\
&:= (3 + 3)^3 + (333 - 3) \\
&:= (4 + 4)/4 + ((4 + 4) \times (4 \times 4 \times 4 + 4)) \\
&:= 5/5 + (555 - 5 - 5) \\
&:= 6 + ((6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 - 6)) \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times 77 \\
&:= (8 - 8/8) \times ((8 - 88)/8 + 88) \\
&:= ((9999 - 9)/(9 + 9)) - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 547 &:= 1 + (1 + ((1 + 1111)/(1 + 1) - 11)) \\
&:= 2 + (((22 + 2/2)^2) + 2^{2+2}) \\
&:= 3 + (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3) - 33 \\
&:= ((44 \times 44 - 4) + 4^4)/4 \\
&:= 555 + ((5 + 5)/5 - 5 - 5) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 - 6)) + 6/6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times 77 + 7/7) \\
&:= (8888 - 8)/(8 + 8) - 8 \\
&:= ((9999 + 9)/(9 + 9)) - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 548 &:= (1111 - 11)/(1 + 1) - 1 - 1 \\
&:= 22^2 + 2^{2+2+2} \\
&:= 3 + (((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) + 33) \\
&:= 4 + ((4 + 4) \times (4 \times 4 \times 4 + 4)) \\
&:= 555 - ((5 + 5)/5 + 5) \\
&:= 666 - ((666 + 6)/6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times 77 + ((7 + 7)/7)) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 + 88 \times 88/(8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 + ((((((9 + 9)/9)^9) + 9) + 9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 549 &:= (1111 - 11)/(1 + 1) - 1 \\
&:= 22 + (((22 + 2/2)^2) - 2) \\
&:= 3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 33) \\
&:= ((44 \times 44 + 4^4) + 4)/4 \\
&:= 555 - (5/5 + 5) \\
&:= 666 - (666/6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 + (77 - 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + 888/(8 + 8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) - 99
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 550 &:= (1111 - 11)/(1 + 1) \\
&:= 22 + (22 \times (22 + 2)) \\
&:= 3/3 + ((3 + 3)^3 + 333) \\
&:= (4/4 + 4) \times (444 - 4)/4 \\
&:= (5 + 5) \times 55 \\
&:= (6 - 6/6) \times ((666 - 6)/6) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 + 77/7 \\
&:= (8888 - 88)/(8 + 8) \\
&:= 9/9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) - 99)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 551 &:= 1 + (1111 - 11)/(1 + 1) \\
&:= 22 + ((22 + 2/2)^2) \\
&:= (3333 - 3^3)/(3 + 3) \\
&:= 444 + (444/4 - 4) \\
&:= 5/5 + (5 + 5) \times 55 \\
&:= 66/6 + ((6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 - 6)) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 + (77 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 \times (88 - 8) - (8/8 + 88) \\
&:= (9999 - 9 \times 9)/(9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 552 &:= 1 + (1 + (1111 - 11)/(1 + 1)) \\
&:= (22 + 2) \times (22 + 2/2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3 + 3)^3 + 333) \\
&:= 44 + ((4^4 - 4) + 4^4) \\
&:= 555 + ((5 + 5)/5 - 5) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 - 6)) + 6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times 77 - 7/7) + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times (88 - 8) - 88 \\
&:= (9 - 9/9) \times (9 \times 9 - ((99 + 9)/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 553 &:= (1111 - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1 - 1 \\
&:= 2 + (((22 + 2/2)^2) + 22) \\
&:= ((3333 + 3)/(3 + 3)) - 3 \\
&:= 4 + (((44 \times 44 + 4^4) + 4)/4) \\
&:= 555 - (5 + 5)/5 \\
&:= (6/6 + 6) \times (66 + 6/6 + 6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times 77 + 7) \\
&:= 8/8 + (8 \times (88 - 8) - 88) \\
&:= 9 + (((99 \times 99) - 9)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 554 &:= (1111 - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1 \\
&:= ((22 + 2)^2) - 22 \\
&:= (3333 - 3 \times 3)/(3 + 3) \\
&:= 444 + (444 - 4)/4 \\
&:= 555 - 5/5 \\
&:= 666 - (666 + 6)/6 \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times 77 + 7/7) + 7) \\
&:= (8 + 8)/8 + (8 \times (88 - 8) - 88) \\
&:= 9 + (((99 \times 99) + 9)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 555 &:= (1111 - 1)/(1 + 1) \\
&:= (2222 - 2)/(2 + 2) \\
&:= (3333 - 3)/(3 + 3) \\
&:= 444 + 444/4 \\
&:= 555 \\
&:= (6 - 6/6) \times 666/6 \\
&:= (7777 - 7)/(7 + 7) \\
&:= (8888 - 8)/(8 + 8) \\
&:= (9999 - 9)/(9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 556 &:= (1 + 1111)/(1 + 1) \\
&:= 2 + (((22 + 2)^2) - 22) \\
&:= (3333 + 3)/(3 + 3) \\
&:= 44 + (4^4 + 4^4) \\
&:= 5/5 + 555 \\
&:= (6666 + 6)/(6 + 6) \\
&:= (7777 + 7)/(7 + 7) \\
&:= (8888 + 8)/(8 + 8) \\
&:= (9999 + 9)/(9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 557 &:= 1 + (1 + 1111)/(1 + 1) \\
&:= 2 + ((2222 - 2)/(2 + 2)) \\
&:= (3333 + 3 \times 3)/(3 + 3) \\
&:= 44 + ((4/4 + 4^4) + 4^4) \\
&:= 555 + (5 + 5)/5 \\
&:= 6/6 + (6666 + 6)/(6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times 77 + (77/7)) \\
&:= 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - (88/8 + 8) \\
&:= (9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9))) - 9/9 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 558 &:= 1 + (1 + (1 + 1111)/(1 + 1)) \\
&:= 2 + (((22 + 2)^2) - 22) + 2) \\
&:= 3 \times (((3 + 3)^3 - 33) + 3) \\
&:= 4 + ((444 - 4)/4 + 444) \\
&:= 5 + (555 - (5 + 5)/5) \\
&:= 666 - 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + ((77 + 7)/7 + 7 \times 77) \\
&:= (8/8 + 8) \times (8 \times 8 - ((8 + 8)/8)) \\
&:= (9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9))) - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 559 &:= 1 + (1 + (1 + (1 + 1111)/(1 + 1))) \\
&:= 2 + (((2222 - 2)/(2 + 2)) + 2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3333 + 3)/(3 + 3)) \\
&:= 4 + (444/4 + 444) \\
&:= 5 + (555 - 5/5) \\
&:= 6/6 + (666 - 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)) \\
&:= 7 + (((7 \times 77 - 7/7) + 7) + 7) \\
&:= 888/8 + 8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) \\
&:= 9/9 + ((9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9))) - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 560 &:= (11 - 1) \times (1 + 111)/(1 + 1) \\
&:= ((22 + 2)^2) - 2^{2+2} \\
&:= (3333 + 3^3)/(3 + 3) \\
&:= 4 + ((44 + 4^4) + 4^4) \\
&:= 5 + 555 \\
&:= (6 - 6/6) \times (666 + 6)/6 \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times 77 + 7) + 7) \\
&:= (8 - 8/8) \times (88 - 8) \\
&:= (9 - 9/9) \times (9 \times 9 - 99/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 561 &:= (11 + 1111)/(1 + 1) \\
&:= (2222 + 22)/(2 + 2) \\
&:= 33 \times ((33/3 + 3) + 3) \\
&:= (4/4 + 4^4) - 4 \times 4 \times 4 \\
&:= 5 + (555 + 5/5) \\
&:= 6 + ((6 - 6/6) \times 666/6) \\
&:= 7 + (((7 \times 77 + 7/7) + 7) + 7) \\
&:= 8/8 + ((8 - 8/8) \times (88 - 8)) \\
&:= (9999 + 99)/(9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 562 &:= 1 + ((11 + 1111)/(1 + 1)) \\
&:= 2 + (((22 + 2)^2) - 2^{2+2}) \\
&:= ((3 \times 3 + 3 + 3)^3 - 3)/(3 + 3) \\
&:= ((4 - 4^4)/4) + (4/4 + 4^4) \\
&:= 5 + (555 + (5 + 5)/5) \\
&:= 6 + (6666 + 6)/(6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7777 - 7)/(7 + 7)) \\
&:= (8 + 8)/8 + ((8 - 8/8) \times (88 - 8)) \\
&:= 9 + (((99 \times 99) - 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 563 &:= 1 + (1 + ((11 + 1111)/(1 + 1))) \\
&:= ((22 + 2)^2) - (22/2 + 2) \\
&:= ((3 \times 3 + 3 + 3)^3 + 3)/(3 + 3) \\
&:= 4 + ((444/4 + 444) + 4) \\
&:= 5 + ((555 - (5 + 5)/5) + 5) \\
&:= 666 - ((6 \times 6 + 66) + 6/6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7777 + 7)/(7 + 7)) \\
&:= 8 + (8888 - 8)/(8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (((99 \times 99) + 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 564 &:= ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1} - 1 - 11 \\
&:= 22^2 + (2 \times 2 \times (22 - 2)) \\
&:= (3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3^3)) - 3 \\
&:= (4 \times (4^4 - 4)) - 444 \\
&:= 5 + (555 - 5/5 + 5) \\
&:= (6 + 6) \times (66/6 + 6 \times 6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times 77 + (77/7)) + 7) \\
&:= 8 + ((8888 + 8)/(8 + 8)) \\
&:= 9 + ((9999 - 9)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 565 &:= ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1} - 11 \\
&:= ((22 + 2)^2) - 22/2 \\
&:= ((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 - 33)/3 \\
&:= 4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 4 \times 4 \times 4) \\
&:= 5 + 555 + 5 \\
&:= 6/6 + ((6 + 6) \times (66/6 + 6 \times 6)) \\
&:= 7 + (((77 + 7)/7 + 7 \times 77) + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - 88/8 \\
&:= 9 + ((9999 + 9)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 566 &:= 11 + (1111 - 1)/(1 + 1) \\
&:= ((2 - 22)/2) + ((22 + 2)^2) \\
&:= (3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3^3)) - 3/3 \\
&:= 4 + (((4 - 4^4)/4) + (4/4 + 4^4)) \\
&:= 555 + 55/5 \\
&:= 6 + ((6 - 6/6) \times (666 + 6)/6) \\
&:= 77 + (7 \times (77 - 7) - 7/7) \\
&:= (8 - 88)/8 + 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) \\
&:= (9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9))) - 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 567 &:= 11 + (1 + 1111)/(1 + 1) \\
&:= 2 + (((22 + 2)^2) - 22/2) \\
&:= 3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3^3) \\
&:= ((4/4 + 4) + 4) \times ((4^4 - 4)/4) \\
&:= 555 + (55 + 5)/5 \\
&:= 6 + (((6 - 6/6) \times 666/6) + 6) \\
&:= 77 + 7 \times (77 - 7) \\
&:= (8/8 + 8) \times (8 \times 8 - 8/8) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 568 &:= 1 + (11 + (1 + 1111)/(1 + 1)) \\
&:= ((22 + 2)^2) - 2 \times (2 + 2) \\
&:= 3 + (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 - 33)/3) \\
&:= 4 + ((4 \times (4^4 - 4)) - 444) \\
&:= (5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 - 55 \\
&:= 6 + ((6666 + 6)/(6 + 6) + 6) \\
&:= 7/7 + (7 \times (77 - 7) + 77) \\
&:= 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - 8 \\
&:= 9/9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 569 &:= 1 + (1 + (11 + (1 + 1111)/(1 + 1))) \\
&:= 2 + (((22 + 2)^2) - 22/2) + 2) \\
&:= (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3) - (3 + 3) \\
&:= 4 + (((4/4 + 4)^4 - 4 \times 4 \times 4) + 4) \\
&:= (5^5 - 5)/5 - 55 \\
&:= 66 + (((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6)) - 6/6) \\
&:= 7 + (((7777 - 7)/(7 + 7)) + 7) \\
&:= 8/8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - 8) \\
&:= (9 + 9)/9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 570 &:= (11 - 1) \times (1 + (1 + 111)/(1 + 1)) \\
&:= ((22 + 2)^2) - (2 + 2 + 2) \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3^3)) \\
&:= 444 + ((4^4 - 4)/(4 + 4)/4) \\
&:= 5^5/5 - 55 \\
&:= 66 + ((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6)) \\
&:= 7 \times (77 + 7) - (77/7 + 7) \\
&:= (8 + 8)/8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - 8) \\
&:= 9 + ((9999 + 99)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 571 &:= 1 + (11 - 1) \times (1 + (1 + 111)/(1 + 1)) \\
&:= ((22 + 2)^2) - (2/2 + 2 + 2) \\
&:= (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3) - (3 + 3) \\
&:= ((44 \times (44 + 4 + 4)) - 4)/4 \\
&:= (5^5 + 5)/5 - 55 \\
&:= 66 + (((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6)) + 6/6) \\
&:= 7 + (((7 \times 77 + (77/7)) + 7) + 7) \\
&:= 8 + ((8888 - 8)/(8 + 8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (((99 \times 99) - 9)/(9 + 9) + 9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 572 &:= 11 + ((11 + 1111)/(1 + 1)) \\
&:= 22 \times (22 + 2 + 2) \\
&:= (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3) - 3 \\
&:= 44 + (44 \times ((4 + 4) + 4)) \\
&:= (5^5 + 5 + 5)/5 - 55 \\
&:= (66/6) \times (((6 + 6)/6)^6 - (6 + 6)) \\
&:= 7777/7 - 7 \times 77 \\
&:= 88 + 88 \times 88/(8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (((99 \times 99) + 9)/(9 + 9) + 9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 573 &:= ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1} - 1 - 1 - 1 \\
&:= ((22 + 2)^2) - 2/2 - 2 \\
&:= ((3 \times 3 + 3)^3/3) - 3 \\
&:= (4/4 + 4)^4 - (44 + 4 + 4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 - 55) \\
&:= 66 + (666/6 + 6 \times 66) \\
&:= 7 \times (77 + 7) - (7/7 + 7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - 88/8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9999 - 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 574 &:= ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1} - 1 - 1 \\
&:= ((22 + 2)^2) - 2 \\
&:= (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3) - 3 \\
&:= 4^4 + (((4^4 - 4 - 4)/4) + 4^4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 - 5)/5 - 55) \\
&:= (6 \times ((6 \times 6 - 6) + 66)) - (6 + 6)/6 \\
&:= 7 \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - (8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= (9 - ((9 + 9)/9)) \times (9/9 + 9 \times 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 575 &:= ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1} - 1 \\
&:= ((22 + 2)^2) - 2/2 \\
&:= ((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3 \\
&:= 4^4 + (((4^4 - 4)/4) + 4^4) \\
&:= 5 + (5^5/5 - 55) \\
&:= (6 \times ((6 \times 6 - 6) + 66)) - 6/6 \\
&:= 7/7 + (7 \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7)) \\
&:= 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - 8/8 \\
&:= 9 + ((9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9))) - 9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 576 &:= ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1} \\
&:= (22 + 2)^2 \\
&:= (3 \times 3 + 3)^3/3 \\
&:= 4 \times (4 \times (4 \times (4 + 4) + 4)) \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 + 5)/5 - 55) \\
&:= 6 \times ((6 \times 6 - 6) + 66) \\
&:= (77 + 7)/7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7/7) \\
&:= 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 577 &:= 1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1} \\
&:= 2/2 + ((22 + 2)^2) \\
&:= ((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3 \\
&:= (4/4 + 4)^4 - (44 + 4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 + 5 + 5)/5 - 55) \\
&:= 6/6 + (6 \times ((6 \times 6 - 6) + 66)) \\
&:= 7 \times (77 + 7) - 77/7 \\
&:= 8/8 + 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 + ((9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9))) + 9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 578 &:= 1 + (1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 + ((22 + 2)^2) \\
&:= 3 + (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3) \\
&:= 4/4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - (44 + 4)) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + (555 - (5 + 5)/5) \\
&:= (6 + 6)/6 + (6 \times ((6 \times 6 - 6) + 66)) \\
&:= ((7 - 77)/7) + 7 \times (77 + 7) \\
&:= (8 + 8)/8 + 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) \\
&:= 99/9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 579 &:= 1 + (1 + (1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1})) \\
&:= 2 + (((22 + 2)^2) + 2/2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3 \times 3 + 3)^3/3) \\
&:= 4 \times 4^4 - (444 + 4/4) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + (555 - 5/5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 + 66 \times 66/(6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 \times (77 + 7) - ((7 + 7)/7 + 7) \\
&:= 88/8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - 8) \\
&:= ((99 + 9)/9) + (9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 580 &:= (1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 11)^{1+1})) \\
&:= 2 + (((22 + 2)^2) + 2) \\
&:= 3 + (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3) \\
&:= 4 \times 4^4 - 444 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + 555 \\
&:= (6 - 6/6) \times (((666 - 6)/6) + 6) \\
&:= 7 \times (77 + 7) - (7/7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) + (8/(8 + 8)/8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + (((9 \times 999) - 9)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 581 &:= 1 + ((1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 11)^{1+1}))) \\
&:= 2 + (((22 + 2)^2) + 2/2) + 2) \\
&:= 3 + (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3) + 3) \\
&:= (4/4 + 4)^4 - 44 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + (555 + 5/5) \\
&:= 6 + ((6 \times ((6 \times 6 - 6) + 66)) - 6/6) \\
&:= 7 \times (77 + 7) - 7 \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - 88/8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + (((9 \times 999) + 9)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 582 &:= (1 + 1) \times (1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 11)^{1+1}))) \\
&:= 2 + (((22 + 2)^2) + 2) + 2) \\
&:= 3 + (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3/3) + 3) \\
&:= 4/4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 44) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + (555 + (5 + 5)/5) \\
&:= 6 + (6 \times ((6 \times 6 - 6) + 66)) \\
&:= 7/7 + (7 \times (77 + 7) - 7) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - (8 + 8)/8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - (99/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 583 &:= 11 \times ((111 - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1 - 1) \\
&:= 2 + (((22 + 2)^2) + 2/2) + 2) + 2) \\
&:= 3 + (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3) + 3) \\
&:= 44/4 \times ((4^4 - 44)/4) \\
&:= 55/5 \times (55 - (5 + 5)/5) \\
&:= 6 + ((6 \times ((6 \times 6 - 6) + 66)) + 6/6) \\
&:= ((7 + 7)/7) + (7 \times (77 + 7) - 7) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - 8/8) \\
&:= 9 + ((9 - ((9 + 9)/9)) \times (9/9 + 9 \times 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 584 &:= 1 + 11 \times ((111 - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1 - 1) \\
&:= 2 \times (2 + 2) + ((22 + 2)^2) \\
&:= 3 \times 3 + (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3) \\
&:= 4 + (4 \times 4^4 - 444) \\
&:= 5 + ((555 - 5/5) + 5 \times 5) \\
&:= ((6 + 6)/6 + 6) \times (66 + 6/6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (77 + 7) - (77/7)) \\
&:= 8 + 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 585 &:= 11 + (((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1} - (1 + 1)) \\
&:= 22/2 + (((22 + 2)^2) - 2) \\
&:= 3 \times (33 \times (3 + 3) - 3) \\
&:= 4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 44) \\
&:= 5 + (555 + 5 \times 5) \\
&:= (6 - 6/6) \times (666/6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) + 8/8) \\
&:= 9 + ((9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9))) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 586 &:= 11 + (((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1} - 1) \\
&:= 2 + (((22 + 2)^2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)) \\
&:= 3 \times 3 + (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3) \\
&:= 4 + (((4/4 + 4)^4 - 44) + 4/4) \\
&:= 5 + (555 + 5 \times 5 + 5/5) \\
&:= (((6 + 6)/6)^{6+6} + 6)/(6/6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) + ((8 + 8)/8)) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9))) + 9/9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 587 &:= 11 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1} \\
&:= 22/2 + ((22 + 2)^2) \\
&:= ((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 + 33)/3 \\
&:= 4 + (44/4 \times ((4^4 - 44)/4)) \\
&:= 555 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5 \\
&:= 66/6 + (6 \times ((6 \times 6 - 6) + 66)) \\
&:= 7 \times (77 + 7) - 7/7 \\
&:= 88/8 + 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 + ((9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9))) + (99/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 588 &:= 1 + (11 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1}) \\
&:= (2/2 + 2) \times ((2^{2+2} - 2)^2) \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times (33 \times (3 + 3) - 3)) \\
&:= 4 + ((4 \times 4^4 - 444) + 4) \\
&:= 5 \times 55 + (5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) \\
&:= 666 - (66 + 6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 \times (77 + 7) \\
&:= ((88 + 8)/8) + 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) \\
&:= (99 - 9/9) \times (9 - ((9 + 9 + 9)/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 589 &:= 1 + (1 + (11 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1})) \\
&:= 2 + (((22 + 2)^2) + 22/2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3 \times (33 \times (3 + 3) - 3)) + 3/3) \\
&:= 4 + (((4/4 + 4)^4 - 44) + 4) \\
&:= ((5^5 - 55)/5) - 5 \times 5 \\
&:= 666 - (66/6 + 66) \\
&:= 7/7 + 7 \times (77 + 7) \\
&:= 88 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - 88/8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 \times 999) - 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9 \times 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 590 &:= (11 - 1) \times ((11^{1+1} - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1) \\
&:= 2^{2+2} + (((22 + 2)^2) - 2) \\
&:= 3 + (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 + 33)/3) \\
&:= (44 - 4)/4 \times (((4^4 - 4)/4) - 4) \\
&:= 5 + (555 + 5 \times 5) + 5) \\
&:= 666 + (((6 - 66)/6) - 66) \\
&:= ((7 + 7)/7) + 7 \times (77 + 7) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - (8 + 8)/8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 \times 999) + 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9 \times 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 591 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 1 + 1 + 11))^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 + (((22 + 2)^2) + 22/2) + 2) \\
&:= 3 \times 33 \times (3 + 3) - 3 \\
&:= 44/4 + (4 \times 4^4 - 444) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + (555 + (55/5)) \\
&:= 6 + ((6 - 6/6) \times (666/6 + 6)) \\
&:= 7 \times (77 + 7) + (7 + 7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - 8/8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - ((9 + 9)/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 592 &:= (1 + 1) \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1))^{1+1+1} - 1) \\
&:= 2^{2+2} + ((22 + 2)^2) \\
&:= 3/3 + (3 \times 33 \times (3 + 3) - 3) \\
&:= 4 \times ((4 \times (4 \times (4 + 4) + 4)) + 4) \\
&:= 5 + (((5 + 5)/5)^5 + 555) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + (6666 + 6)/(6 + 6) \\
&:= 77/7 + (7 \times (77 + 7) - 7) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 593 &:= 11 \times ((111 - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1) - 1 \\
&:= 22^2 + (222/2 - 2) \\
&:= 3 \times 33 \times (3 + 3) - 3/3 \\
&:= (4/4 + 4)^4 - 4 \times (4 + 4) \\
&:= 5^5/5 - ((5 + 5)/5)^5 \\
&:= 666 - (66 + 6/6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (77 + 7) - ((7 + 7)/7)) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 - 888/8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 594 &:= 11 \times ((111 - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1) \\
&:= 2 + (((22 + 2)^2) + 2^{2+2}) \\
&:= 3 \times 33 \times (3 + 3) \\
&:= 4/4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 4 \times (4 + 4)) \\
&:= 55/5 \times (55 - 5/5) \\
&:= 666 - (66 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (77 + 7) - 7/7) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 + ((8 - 888)/8) \\
&:= 99 \times (9 - ((9 + 9 + 9)/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 595 &:= 111 + (11 + 11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 22^2 + 222/2 \\
&:= 3/3 + 3 \times 33 \times (3 + 3) \\
&:= (44 \times 44 + 444)/4 \\
&:= 5^5/5 - (5 \times 5 + 5) \\
&:= 6/6 + (666 - (66 + 6)) \\
&:= 7 + 7 \times (77 + 7) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) + (88/8)) \\
&:= 9/9 + (99 \times (9 - ((9 + 9 + 9)/9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 596 &:= 1 + (111 + (11 + 11))^{1+1}) \\
&:= 22 + (((22 + 2)^2) - 2) \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times 33 \times (3 + 3) - 3/3) \\
&:= (4 \times (4^4 + 4)) - 444 \\
&:= (5^5 + 5)/5 - (5 \times 5 + 5) \\
&:= 666 - (((6 + 6)/6)^6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (77 + 7) + 7/7) \\
&:= 8 + (((88 + 8)/8) + 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8)) \\
&:= (9999 + 9 \times 9 \times 9)/(9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 597 &:= 1 + (1 + (111 + (11 + 11))^{1+1})) \\
&:= 2 + (222/2 + 22^2) \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times 33 \times (3 + 3) \\
&:= 4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 4 \times (4 + 4)) \\
&:= (5^5 + 5 + 5)/5 - (5 \times 5 + 5) \\
&:= 666 - (6 \times 6/(6 + 6) + 66) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (77 + 7) + ((7 + 7)/7)) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times 8 \times 8 - 88/8) + 88) \\
&:= 999/9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 598 &:= 11 + (11 + ((1+1) \times (1+11))^{1+1}) \\
&:= 22 + ((22+2)^2) \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times 33 \times (3+3) + 3/3) \\
&:= (4+4)/4 \times ((44-4/4) + 4^4) \\
&:= (5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 - 5 \times 5 \\
&:= 666 - (((6+6)/6) + 66) \\
&:= 7 \times (77+7) + (77-7)/7 \\
&:= 88 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - ((8+8)/8)) \\
&:= 99 + (((9 \times 999) - 9)/(9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 599 &:= 1111 - (1+1)^{11-1-1} \\
&:= 22 + (((22+2)^2) + 2/2) \\
&:= ((33/3)^3) - (3^{3+3} + 3) \\
&:= (((4+4) \times (44+4^4)) - 4)/4 \\
&:= (5^5 - 5)/5 - 5 \times 5 \\
&:= 666 - (66 + 6/6) \\
&:= 77/7 + 7 \times (77+7) \\
&:= 88 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - 8/8) \\
&:= 99 + (((9 \times 999) + 9)/(9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 600 &:= (1+1) \times (1+1+1) \times (11-1)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 + (((22+2)^2) + 22) \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times 33 \times (3+3) + 3) \\
&:= (4+4) \times ((44+4^4)/4) \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times 5 \times 5 - 5) \\
&:= 666 - 66 \\
&:= (7/7 + 7) \times (77 - (7+7)/7) \\
&:= 88 + 8 \times 8 \times 8 \\
&:= 99 + (((9+9)/9)^9) - (99/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 601 &:= 1 + (1+1) \times (1+1+1) \times (11-1)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 + (((22+2)^2) + 22) + 2/2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3 \times 33 \times (3+3) + 3/3) + 3) \\
&:= (4/4 + 4)^4 - ((4 \times 4 + 4) + 4) \\
&:= (5^5 + 5)/5 - 5 \times 5 \\
&:= 6/6 + (666 - 66) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times (77+7) - 7/7) + 7) \\
&:= 8/8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 + 88) \\
&:= 9 + (((9+9)/9)^9) - 9/9 + 9 \times 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 602 &:= (1+1) \times (1 + (1+1+1) \times (11-1)^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 + (((22+2)^2) + 22) + 2) \\
&:= ((33/3)^3) - 3^{3+3} \\
&:= (4+4)/4 \times ((44+4^4) + 4/4) \\
&:= (5^5 + 5 + 5)/5 - 5 \times 5 \\
&:= 666 - ((6+6)/6)^6 \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (77+7) + 7) \\
&:= 88 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 + (8+8)/8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9+9)/9)^9) + 9 \times 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 603 &:= 11 \times (111-1)/(1+1) - 1 - 1 \\
&:= 22^2 + ((22/2)^2 - 2) \\
&:= 3 \times (33 \times (3+3) + 3) \\
&:= 4 + (((4+4) \times (44+4^4)) - 4)/4 \\
&:= (5^5 - (55+55))/5 \\
&:= 6/6 + (666 - ((6+6)/6)^6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times (77+7) + 7/7) + 7) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) + (88/8)) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (99 \times (9 - ((9+9+9)/9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 604 &:= 11 \times (111-1)/(1+1) - 1 \\
&:= 2 \times (((2^{2+2} + 2)^2) - 22) \\
&:= 3^3 + (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3) \\
&:= 4^4 + (((4+4) \times 44) - 4) \\
&:= (55 \times 55 - 5)/5 \\
&:= 6 + (666 - (((6+6)/6) + 66)) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times (77+7) + ((7+7)/7)) + 7) \\
&:= 88 + ((8/((8+8)/8)) + 8 \times 8 \times 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + (((9+9)/9)^9) + (99/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 605 &:= 11 \times (111-1)/(1+1) \\
&:= 22^2 + (22/2)^2 \\
&:= 3 + (((33/3)^3) - 3^{3+3}) \\
&:= (4/4 + 4)^4 - (4 \times 4 + 4) \\
&:= 55 \times (55/5) \\
&:= 6 + (666 - 66 - 6/6) \\
&:= 77 + (7 \times 77 - (77/7)) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 - (88/8 + 88) \\
&:= 99/9 \times ((999-9)/(9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 606 &:= 1 + 11 \times (111-1)/(1+1) \\
&:= 2 + (2 \times (((2^{2+2} + 2)^2) - 22)) \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times (33 \times (3+3) + 3)) \\
&:= 4/4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - (4 \times 4 + 4)) \\
&:= (55 \times 55 + 5)/5 \\
&:= 6 + (666 - 66) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (77+7) + (77/7)) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times 8 \times 8 - ((8+8)/8)) + 88) \\
&:= 9 + (((9+9) \times (9+9+9)) + 999/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 607 &:= 1 + 1 + 11 \times (111-1)/(1+1) \\
&:= 2 + ((22/2)^2 + 22^2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3 \times (33 \times (3+3) + 3)) + 3/3) \\
&:= 4^4 + (((4+4) \times 44) - 4/4) \\
&:= ((55 \times 55 + 5) + 5)/5 \\
&:= 6 + ((666 - 66) + 6/6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (77+7) + (77+7)/7) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times 8 \times 8 - 8/8) + 88) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - (999+99)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 608 &:= (11 \times 111 - 1)/(1+1) - 1 - 1 \\
&:= 2^{2+2} \times ((2+2+2)^2 + 2) \\
&:= 33 + (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3) \\
&:= 4^4 + ((4+4) \times 44) \\
&:= ((5^5 - (55+55))/5) - 5 \\
&:= 6 + (666 - ((6+6)/6)^6) \\
&:= (7/7 + 7) \times (77 - 7/7) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 + 88) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - (((999+9)/9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 609 &:= (11 \times 111 - 1)/(1+1) - 1 \\
&:= 2 + (((22/2)^2 + 22^2) + 2) \\
&:= 33 + ((3 \times 3 + 3)^3/3) \\
&:= (4/4 + 4)^4 - 4 \times 4 \\
&:= ((5^5 - 55)/5) - 5 \\
&:= 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 66) - 6 \times 6/(6+6) \\
&:= 77 + (7 \times 77 - 7) \\
&:= (8 - 8/8) \times (88 - 8/8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - (999/9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 610 &:= (11 \times 111 - 1)/(1+1) \\
&:= 2 + ((2 \times 2^{2+2}) + ((22+2)^2)) \\
&:= 33 + (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3) \\
&:= 4/4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 4 \times 4) \\
&:= 55 + 555 \\
&:= 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 66) - (6+6)/6 \\
&:= 7/7 + (7 \times 77 - 7 + 77) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times 8 \times 8 + (8+8)/8) + 88) \\
&:= 99 + (((9+9)/9)^9) - 9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 611 &:= (1 + 11 \times 111)/(1+1) \\
&:= 22^2 + ((2^{2 \times (2+2)} - 2)/2) \\
&:= 3 \times 33 + ((3-3/3)^{3 \times 3}) \\
&:= 4 + (((4+4) \times 44) - 4/4) + 4^4) \\
&:= 5 + ((55 \times 55 + 5)/5) \\
&:= 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 66) - 6/6 \\
&:= 77 + (((7+7)/7 - 7) + 7 \times 77) \\
&:= 88 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 + 88/8) \\
&:= 99 + (((9+9)/9)^9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 612 &:= 1 + (1 + 11 \times 111)/(1+1) \\
&:= 2 \times ((22 \times (2^{2+2} - 2)) - 2) \\
&:= (3+3) \times (3 \times 33 + 3) \\
&:= 4 + (((4+4) \times 44) + 4^4) \\
&:= (5^5 - (55+5+5))/5 \\
&:= 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 66) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times 77 - (77/7)) + 77) \\
&:= 88 + (((88+8)/8) + 8 \times 8 \times 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - (99+9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 613 &:= 1 + 1 + (1 + 11 \times 111)/(1 + 1) \\
&:= 22^2 + ((2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2)/2) \\
&:= 3/3 + ((3 + 3) \times (3 \times 33 + 3)) \\
&:= 4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 4 \times 4) \\
&:= (5^5 - (55 + 5))/5 \\
&:= 6/6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 66) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times (77 + 7) + (77/7)) + 7) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times 88 - (88/8 + 88)) \\
&:= 9/9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - (99 + 9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 614 &:= (1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1} - 11 \\
&:= (2 \times (22 \times (2^{2+2} - 2))) - 2 \\
&:= 3 \times (3 + 3)^3 - (3/3 + 33) \\
&:= (4/4 + 4)^4 - 44/4 \\
&:= (5^5 - 55)/5 \\
&:= (6 + 6)/6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 66) \\
&:= 77 + (7 \times 77 - ((7 + 7)/7)) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 - ((8 + 8)/8 + 88) \\
&:= 999/9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 615 &:= 11 \times (1 + 111)/(1 + 1) - 1 \\
&:= (2/2 + 2 + 2) \times ((22/2)^2 + 2) \\
&:= 3 \times (3 + 3)^3 - 33 \\
&:= (4 - 44)/4 + (4/4 + 4)^4 \\
&:= 5^5/5 - 5 - 5 \\
&:= (66 \times 66 - 666)/6 \\
&:= 77 + (7 \times 77 - 7/7) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 - (8/8 + 88) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - (((999 + 9 + 9) + 9)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 616 &:= 11 \times ((1 + 111)/(1 + 1)) \\
&:= 2 \times (22 \times (2^{2+2} - 2)) \\
&:= 3/3 + (3 \times (3 + 3)^3 - 33) \\
&:= (4 + 4) \times ((4 - 4/4)^4 - 4) \\
&:= (5^5 + 5)/5 - 5 - 5 \\
&:= 6 + (6 \times (6 \times 6 + 66) - ((6 + 6)/6)) \\
&:= 77 + 7 \times 77 \\
&:= 88 \times (8 - 8/8) \\
&:= 99/9 \times ((999 + 9)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 617 &:= 1 + 11 \times (1 + 111)/(1 + 1) \\
&:= 22 + (222/2 + 22^2) \\
&:= 3^{3+3} - ((333 + 3)/3) \\
&:= (4/4 + 4)^4 - 4 - 4 \\
&:= (5^5 + 5 + 5)/5 - 5 - 5 \\
&:= 6 + (6 \times (6 \times 6 + 66) - 6/6) \\
&:= 7/7 + (7 \times 77 + 77) \\
&:= 8/8 + 88 \times (8 - 8/8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((999 + 9)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 618 &:= 1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 111)/(1 + 1) \\
&:= 2 + (2 \times (22 \times (2^{2+2} - 2))) \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times (3 + 3)^3 - 33) \\
&:= 4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 44/4) \\
&:= (5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 - 5 \\
&:= 6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 66) \\
&:= 77 + (7 \times 77 + ((7 + 7)/7)) \\
&:= (8 + 8)/8 + 88 \times (8 - 8/8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - 999/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 619 &:= 1 + 1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 111)/(1 + 1) \\
&:= (2 \times 22) + (((22 + 2)^2) - 2/2) \\
&:= 3^{3+3} + ((3 - 333)/3) \\
&:= 444 + ((4 \times 44) - 4/4) \\
&:= (5^5 - 5)/5 - 5 \\
&:= 6 + (6 \times (6 \times 6 + 66) + 6/6) \\
&:= 77 + (((7 + 7 + 7)/7) + 7 \times 77) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times 8 \times 8 + 88/8) + 88) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((9 - 999)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 620 &:= 11 + (11 \times 111 - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1 \\
&:= (2 \times 22) + ((22 + 2)^2) \\
&:= 3 \times (3 + 3)^3 - (3^3 + 3/3) \\
&:= 444 + (4 \times 44) \\
&:= 5^5/5 - 5 \\
&:= 6 + (6 \times (6 \times 6 + 66) + ((6 + 6)/6)) \\
&:= 77 + ((7 \times 77 - 7) + (77/7)) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 + ((8888 + 8)/(8 + 8)) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) + 99
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 621 &:= 11 + (11 \times 111 - 1)/(1 + 1) \\
&:= ((2/2 + 2 + 2)^{2+2}) - 2 - 2 \\
&:= 3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3 \times 3) \\
&:= (4/4 + 4)^4 - 4 \\
&:= (5^5 + 5)/5 - 5 \\
&:= 6 + ((66 \times 66 - 666)/6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times 77 - ((7 + 7)/7)) + 77) \\
&:= 8 \times (88 - 8) - (88/8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - (99 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 622 &:= 11 + (1 + 11 \times 111)/(1 + 1) \\
&:= 222 + (22 - 2)^2 \\
&:= 3/3 + (3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3 \times 3)) \\
&:= 4/4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 4) \\
&:= (5^5 + 5 + 5)/5 - 5 \\
&:= 66 + (6666 + 6)/(6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times 77 - 7/7) + 77) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + ((888 - 8)/8) \\
&:= 9/9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - (99 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 623 &:= 111 + (1 + 1)^{11-1-1} \\
&:= ((2/2 + 2 + 2)^{2+2}) - 2 \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times (3 + 3)^3 - (3^3 + 3/3)) \\
&:= (4/4 + 4)^4 - (4 + 4)/4 \\
&:= (5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 \\
&:= 66/6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 66) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times 77 + 77) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + 888/8 \\
&:= 999/9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 624 &:= (1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1} - 1 \\
&:= (22 + 2) \times (22 + 2 + 2) \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3 \times 3)) \\
&:= 4 \times (4 \times (44 - 4) - 4) \\
&:= (5^5 - 5)/5 \\
&:= 666 - (6 \times 6 + 6) \\
&:= (7/7 + 7) \times (7/7 + 77) \\
&:= 8 + 88 \times (8 - 8/8) \\
&:= (9 - 9/9) \times (9 \times 9 - ((9 + 9 + 9)/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 625 &:= (1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1} \\
&:= (2/2 + 2 + 2)^{2+2} \\
&:= (3 - 3/3 + 3)^{3/3+3} \\
&:= (4/4 + 4)^4 \\
&:= 5^5/5 \\
&:= (6 - 6/6)^{6-(6+6)/6} \\
&:= (7 - ((7 + 7)/7))^{7/7-7} \\
&:= 8 + (88 \times (8 - 8/8) + 8/8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 + (((99 \times 99) - 9)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 626 &:= 1 + (1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 + ((22 + 2) \times (22 + 2 + 2)) \\
&:= 3/3 + ((3 - 3/3 + 3)^{3/3+3}) \\
&:= 4/4 + (4/4 + 4)^4 \\
&:= (5^5 + 5)/5 \\
&:= 6/6 + (((6 - 6/6)^{6-(6+6)/6}) \\
&:= (7 \times (77 + 7 + 7)) - 77/7 \\
&:= 8 + (((8 + 8)/8) - 88) + 8 \times 88 \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((999 + 9)/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 627 &:= 11 \times (1 + ((1 + 111)/(1 + 1))) \\
&:= 2 + ((2/2 + 2 + 2)^{2+2}) \\
&:= 33 + 3 \times 33 \times (3 + 3) \\
&:= (4 + 4)/4 + (4/4 + 4)^4 \\
&:= (5^5 + 5 + 5)/5 \\
&:= 666 - ((66 \times 6)/(6 + 6) + 6) \\
&:= 77 + (7 \times 77 + (77/7)) \\
&:= 88/8 + 88 \times (8 - 8/8) \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - 999/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 628 &:= 1 + (11 \times (1 + ((1 + 111)/(1 + 1)))) \\
&:= 22^2 + ((2 \times (2 + 2 + 2))^2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3 - 3/3 + 3)^{3/3+3}) \\
&:= 4 + (4 \times (4 \times (44 - 4) - 4)) \\
&:= 5 + (5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 \\
&:= 666 - (((6 + 6)/6) + 6 \times 6) \\
&:= 77 + ((77 + 7)/7 + 7 \times 77) \\
&:= 8 \times (88 - 8) - (88 + 8)/8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((9 + 9)/9 + 99)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 629 &:= 1 + (1 + (11 \times (1 + ((1 + 111)/(1 + 1)))))) \\
&:= 2 + (((2/2 + 2 + 2)^{2+2}) + 2) \\
&:= 3^{3+3} - (3 \times 33 + 3/3) \\
&:= 4 + (4/4 + 4)^4 \\
&:= 5 + (5^5 - 5)/5 \\
&:= 666 - (6 \times 6 + 6/6) \\
&:= (7 \times (77 + 7 + 7)) - (7/7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times (88 - 8) - 88/8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - (9/9 + 99)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 630 &:= (11 - 1) \times ((1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 + (11 - 1))) \\
&:= 2 + (((2 \times (2 + 2 + 2))^2) + 22^2) \\
&:= 3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - (3 + 3)) \\
&:= 4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 + 4/4) \\
&:= 5 + 5^5/5 \\
&:= 666 - 6 \times 6 \\
&:= (7 \times (77 + 7 + 7)) - 7 \\
&:= (8 - 8/8) \times ((8 + 8)/8 + 88) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - 99
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 631 &:= 1 + ((11 - 1) \times ((1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 + (11 - 1)))) \\
&:= 2 + (((2/2 + 2 + 2)^{2+2}) + 2) + 2) \\
&:= 3/3 + (3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - (3 + 3))) \\
&:= 4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 + (4 + 4)/4) \\
&:= 5 + (5^5 + 5)/5 \\
&:= 6/6 + (666 - 6 \times 6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7/7 + 7) \times (7/7 + 77)) \\
&:= 8 \times (88 - 8) - (8/8 + 8) \\
&:= 9/9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - 99)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 632 &:= 11^{1+1} + ((1 + 1)^{11-1-1} - 1) \\
&:= (22 + 2 + 2)^2 - 2 \times 22 \\
&:= 3 + (3^{3+3} - (3 \times 33 + 3/3)) \\
&:= (4 \times (4 \times (44 - 4))) - 4 - 4 \\
&:= 5 + (5^5 + 5 + 5)/5 \\
&:= 666 + (((6 + 6)/6) - 6 \times 6) \\
&:= (7/7 + 7) \times ((7 + 7)/7 + 77) \\
&:= 8 \times (88 - 8) - 8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + (((9 + 9)/9) - 99)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 633 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1) \times 111 - 11) \\
&:= 2 \times (2 + 2) + ((2/2 + 2 + 2)^{2+2}) \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - (3 + 3))) \\
&:= 4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 + 4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 + 5) \\
&:= 666 - (66 \times 6/(6 + 6)) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times (77 + 7 + 7)) - (77/7)) \\
&:= 8/8 + (8 \times (88 - 8) - 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + (((9 + 9 + 9)/9) - 99)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 634 &:= 1 + ((1 + 1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1) \times 111 - 11)) \\
&:= 2 + (((22 + 2 + 2)^2) - (2 \times 22)) \\
&:= 3 \times (3 + 3)^3 - (33/3 + 3) \\
&:= 4 + (((4/4 + 4)^4 + 4/4) + 4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 - 5)/5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 + (666 - (((6 + 6)/6) + 6 \times 6)) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times 77 + (77/7)) + 77) \\
&:= (8 + 8)/8 + (8 \times (88 - 8) - 8) \\
&:= 9 + (((99 \times 99) - 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9 \times 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 635 &:= 11 + ((1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1} - 1) \\
&:= (((2 + 2 + 2)^{2+2}) - 22)/2 - 2 \\
&:= (3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3)) - (3/3 + 3) \\
&:= (4/4 + 4)^4 + (44 - 4)/4 \\
&:= 5 + (5^5/5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 + (666 - (6 \times 6 + 6/6)) \\
&:= (7 \times (77 + 7 + 7)) - (7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + (88 \times (8 - 8/8) + (88/8)) \\
&:= 9 \times 99 - (((9 + 9)/9)^{9-9/9})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 636 &:= 11 + (1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 \times ((2^{2+2} \times (22 - 2)) - 2) \\
&:= (3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3)) - 3 \\
&:= (4 \times (4 \times (44 - 4))) - 4 \\
&:= (55 + 5^5)/5 \\
&:= 6 + (666 - 6 \times 6) \\
&:= (7 \times (77 + 7 + 7)) - 7/7 \\
&:= 8 \times (88 - 8) - (8/((8 + 8)/8)) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) - (99 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 637 &:= 1 + (11 + (1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1}) \\
&:= (((2 + 2 + 2)^{2+2}) - 22)/2 \\
&:= 3 \times (3 + 3)^3 - 33/3 \\
&:= 4 + (((4/4 + 4)^4 + 4) + 4) \\
&:= (55 + 5^5 + 5)/5 \\
&:= 6 + ((666 - 6 \times 6) + 6/6) \\
&:= 7 \times (77 + 7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (88 - 8) - (88/8)) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) - 99/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 638 &:= 11 \times (1 + 1 + (1 + 111)/(1 + 1)) \\
&:= (2 \times (2^{2+2} \times (22 - 2))) - 2 \\
&:= (3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3)) - 3/3 \\
&:= (4 \times (4 \times (44 - 4))) - (4 + 4)/4 \\
&:= ((55 + 5^5 + 5) + 5)/5 \\
&:= (66/6) \times (((6 + 6)/6)^6 - 6) \\
&:= 7/7 + (7 \times (77 + 7 + 7)) \\
&:= 8 \times (88 - 8) - (8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) - 9/9 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 639 &:= 1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + (1 + 111)/(1 + 1)) \\
&:= 2 + (((2 + 2 + 2)^{2+2}) - 22)/2) \\
&:= 3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3) \\
&:= (4 \times (4 \times (44 - 4))) - 4/4 \\
&:= 5 + (((5^5 - 5)/5 + 5) + 5) \\
&:= 6 + (666 - (66 \times 6/(6 + 6))) \\
&:= ((7 + 7)/7) + (7 \times (77 + 7 + 7)) \\
&:= 8 \times (88 - 8) - 8/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 640 &:= 111 + (1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 \times (2^{2+2} \times (22 - 2)) \\
&:= 3/3 + (3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3)) \\
&:= 4 \times (4 \times (44 - 4)) \\
&:= 5 + (5^5/5 + 5 + 5) \\
&:= ((66 - 6)/6) \times ((6 + 6)/6)^6 \\
&:= (7 - ((7 + 7)/7)) \times ((7 + 7)/7)^7 \\
&:= 8 \times (88 - 8) \\
&:= 9/9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 641 &:= 1 + 111 + (1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2/2 + (2 \times (2^{2+2} \times (22 - 2))) \\
&:= 3 + ((3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3)) - 3/3) \\
&:= 4 \times 4 + (4/4 + 4)^4 \\
&:= 5 + ((55 + 5^5)/5) \\
&:= 666 + ((66/6) - 6 \times 6) \\
&:= 77/7 + ((7 \times (77 + 7 + 7)) - 7) \\
&:= 8/8 + 8 \times (88 - 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((99/9) - 99)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 642 &:= (1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1 + 1) \times 111 - 1 - 11) \\
&:= 2 + (2 \times (2^{2+2} \times (22 - 2))) \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3)) \\
&:= 4 \times 4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 + 4/4) \\
&:= 5 + ((55 + 5^5 + 5)/5) \\
&:= (6 \times 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)) - 6 \\
&:= 777 - (((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7) \\
&:= (8 + 8)/8 + 8 \times (88 - 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + (((99 + 9)/9) - 99)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 643 &:= (1+1) \times ((1+1+1) \times 111 - 11) - 1 \\
&:= (22-2)^2 + (22^2+2)/2 \\
&:= 3 + ((3 \times (3+3)^3 - 3) + 3/3) \\
&:= 4 + ((4 \times (4 \times (44-4))) - 4/4) \\
&:= 5 + (((55+5^5+5)+5)/5) \\
&:= 6/6 + ((6 \times 6 \times (6+6+6)) - 6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times (77+7+7)) - 7/7) \\
&:= 88/8 + (8 \times (88-8) - 8) \\
&:= 99 + (((99 \times 99) - 9)/(9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 644 &:= (1+1) \times ((1+1+1) \times 111 - 11) \\
&:= 2 \times (((2^{2+2} + 2)^2) - 2) \\
&:= 3 \times (3+3)^3 - (3/3+3) \\
&:= 4 + (4 \times (4 \times (44-4))) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + ((5^5 - 5)/5 - 5) \\
&:= 666 - ((66+66)/6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (77+7+7)) \\
&:= 8 \times (88-8) + (8/((8+8)/8)) \\
&:= 99 + (((99 \times 99) + 9)/(9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 645 &:= 1 + (1+1) \times ((1+1+1) \times 111 - 11) \\
&:= (((2+2+2)^{2+2} - 2)/2) - 2 \\
&:= 3 \times (3+3)^3 - 3 \\
&:= 4 + ((4/4+4)^4 + 4 \times 4) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + (5^5/5 - 5) \\
&:= (6 \times 6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6)/((6+6)/6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times (77+7+7)) + 7/7) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times (88-8) - (88/8)) + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) - (9+9+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 646 &:= (1+1) \times (1 + (1+1+1) \times 111 - 11) \\
&:= (2 \times ((2^{2+2} + 2)^2)) - 2 \\
&:= 3/3 + (3 \times (3+3)^3 - 3) \\
&:= 4 + (((4/4+4)^4 + 4 \times 4) + 4/4) \\
&:= 5 + (((55+5^5)/5) + 5) \\
&:= (6 \times 6 \times (6+6+6)) - (6+6)/6 \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times (77+7+7)) + ((7+7)/7)) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (88-8) - ((8+8)/8)) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) - (9+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 647 &:= (1+1) \times ((1+1) \times (11-1-1))^{1+1} - 1 \\
&:= (((2+2+2)^{2+2} - 2)/2) \\
&:= 3 \times (3+3)^3 - 3/3 \\
&:= ((4+4) \times (4-4/4)^4) - 4/4 \\
&:= ((55+55)+5^5)/5 \\
&:= (6 \times 6 \times (6+6+6)) - 6/6 \\
&:= 7 + ((7 - ((7+7)/7)) \times ((7+7)/7)^7) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (88-8) - 8/8) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) - 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 648 &:= (1+1) \times ((1+1) \times (11-1-1))^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 \times ((2^{2+2} + 2)^2) \\
&:= 3 \times (3+3)^3 \\
&:= (4+4) \times (4-4/4)^4 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + (5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times (6+6+6) \\
&:= 77/7 + (7 \times (77+7+7)) \\
&:= 8 + 8 \times (88-8) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 649 &:= 11 \times ((11^{1+1} - 1)/(1+1) - 1) \\
&:= (((2+2+2)^{2+2} + 2)/2) \\
&:= 3/3 + 3 \times (3+3)^3 \\
&:= 4 + (((4/4+4)^4 + 4 \times 4) + 4) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + (5^5 - 5)/5 \\
&:= 6/6 + (6 \times 6 \times (6+6+6)) \\
&:= 777 - ((7+7)/7)^7 \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (88-8) + 8/8) \\
&:= 9/9 + 9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 650 &:= 1 + 11 \times ((11^{1+1} - 1)/(1+1) - 1) \\
&:= 2 + (2 \times ((2^{2+2} + 2)^2)) \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times (3+3)^3 - 3/3) \\
&:= (44-4)/4 \times (4^4+4)/4 \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times 5 \times 5 + 5) \\
&:= 666 + (((6-66)/6) - 6) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 + 777/7 \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (88-8) + ((8+8)/8)) \\
&:= (9+9)/9 + 9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 651 &:= (1+1+1) \times ((1+1) \times (111-1-1) - 1) \\
&:= 2 + (((2+2+2)^{2+2} + 2)/2) \\
&:= 3 + 3 \times (3+3)^3 \\
&:= 44/4 + (4 \times (4 \times (44-4))) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + (5^5+5)/5 \\
&:= (6 \times 6 \times 6 \times 6 + 6)/((6+6)/6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times (77+7+7)) + 7) \\
&:= 88/8 + 8 \times (88-8) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) + ((9+9+9)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 652 &:= (1+1) \times ((1+1+1) \times (111-1-1) - 1) \\
&:= 2 \times (((2^{2+2} + 2)^2) + 2) \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times (3+3)^3 + 3/3) \\
&:= 4 + ((4+4) \times (4-4/4)^4) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + (5^5+5+5)/5 \\
&:= 666 - ((6+6)/6 + 6+6) \\
&:= 7 + (((7 \times (77+7+7)) + 7/7) + 7) \\
&:= ((88+8)/8) + 8 \times (88-8) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) + ((9 \times 9 - 9)/(9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 653 &:= (11^{1+1+1} - 1)/(1+1) - 1 - 11 \\
&:= 22^2 + ((22/2+2)^2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3 \times (3+3)^3 - 3/3) + 3) \\
&:= 44 + ((4/4+4)^4 - 4 \times 4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 + 5 \times 5) \\
&:= 666 - (6/6+6+6) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 + (((7+7)/7)^7 - (7+7)) \\
&:= 88 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - 88/8) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) + ((9 \times 9 + 9)/(9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 654 &:= (1+1) \times ((1+1+1) \times (111-1-1)) \\
&:= ((22+2+2)^2) - 22 \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times (3+3)^3 + 3) \\
&:= 4 + ((44-4)/4 \times (4^4+4)/4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 - 5)/5 + 5 \times 5) \\
&:= 666 - 6 - 6 \\
&:= 77 + (7 \times (77+7) - (77/7)) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times (88-8) - ((8+8)/8)) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) - ((9+9+9)/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 655 &:= (1+1) \times (1+1+1) \times 111 - 11 \\
&:= 2 + (((22/2+2)^2) + 22^2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3 \times (3+3)^3 + 3/3) + 3) \\
&:= (4 \times (4 \times (44-4) + 4)) - 4/4 \\
&:= 5 + (5^5/5 + 5 \times 5) \\
&:= 666 - 66/6 \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times (77+7+7)) + (77/7)) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times (88-8) - 8/8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) - ((9+9)/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 656 &:= 1 + ((1+1) \times (1+1+1) \times 111 - 11) \\
&:= 2 + (((22+2+2)^2) - 22) \\
&:= (3 \times ((3+3)^3 + 3)) - 3/3 \\
&:= 4 \times (4 \times (44-4) + 4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5+5)/5 + 5 \times 5) \\
&:= 666 + (6-66)/6 \\
&:= 7 + (777 - ((7+7)/7)^7) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (88-8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) - 9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 657 &:= (1+1+1) \times (((1+1) \times (111-1)) - 1) \\
&:= (2/2+2) \times (222 - (2/2+2)) \\
&:= 3 \times ((3+3)^3 + 3) \\
&:= 4 \times (4+4) + (4/4+4)^4 \\
&:= 5^5/5 + ((5+5)/5)^5 \\
&:= 666 + (((6-66)+6)/6) \\
&:= 7 + (777/7 + 7 \times 77) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times (88-8) + 8/8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + 9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 658 &:= (1+1) \times (((1+1+1) \times (111-1)) - 1) \\
&:= (22 \times (2 \times (2+2) + 22)) - 2 \\
&:= 3/3 + (3 \times ((3+3)^3 + 3)) \\
&:= 44 + ((4/4+4)^4 - 44/4) \\
&:= (5^5 + 5)/5 + ((5+5)/5)^5 \\
&:= 666 - ((6+6)/6 + 6) \\
&:= 77 + (7 \times (77+7) - 7) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times (88-8) + ((8+8)/8)) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) + 9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 659 &:= ((1+1) \times ((1+1+1) \times (111-1))) - 1 \\
&:= (((2+2+2)^{2+2}) + 22)/2 \\
&:= 33/3 + 3 \times (3+3)^3 \\
&:= 4 \times 4 \times 44 - (44 + 4/4) \\
&:= ((55 \times (55+5)) - 5)/5 \\
&:= 666 - 6/6 - 6 \\
&:= 777 - (777/7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (88-8) + (88/8)) \\
&:= 99/9 + 9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 660 &:= (1+1) \times ((1+1+1) \times (111-1)) \\
&:= 22 \times (2 \times (2+2) + 22) \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times ((3+3)^3 + 3)) \\
&:= 44 \times (44/4 + 4) \\
&:= 55 \times ((55+5)/5) \\
&:= 666 - 6 \\
&:= 7 \times 77 + (((7+7)/7)^7 - 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 - (88/((8+8)/8)) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) + (99+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 661 &:= 1 + ((1+1) \times ((1+1+1) \times (111-1))) \\
&:= 2 + (((2+2+2)^{2+2}) + 22)/2 \\
&:= 3 + ((3 \times ((3+3)^3 + 3)) + 3/3) \\
&:= 4 + ((4/4+4)^4 + 4 \times (4+4)) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + ((55+5^5)/5) \\
&:= 6/6 + (666-6) \\
&:= 7 \times 77 + (777+77)/7 \\
&:= ((88+8) \times (8-8/8)) - 88/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) + ((99+9+9)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 662 &:= (1+1) \times (1 + ((1+1+1) \times (111-1))) \\
&:= 2 + (22 \times (2 \times (2+2) + 22)) \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times (3+3)^3 + 33/3) \\
&:= (4+4)/4 + (44 \times (44/4 + 4)) \\
&:= 5 + (((5+5)/5)^5 + 5^5/5) \\
&:= 666 + ((6+6)/6 - 6) \\
&:= 7 + (((7 \times (77+7+7)) + (77/7)) + 7) \\
&:= 88 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - (8+8)/8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 \times 9 + 9)/(9+9)) + 9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 663 &:= (1+1+1) \times ((1+1) \times 111 - 1) \\
&:= 222 + ((22-2/2)^2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3 \times ((3+3)^3 + 3)) + 3) \\
&:= 4 + 4 \times 4 \times 44 - (44 + 4/4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 + 5)/5 + ((5+5)/5)^5) \\
&:= 666 - 6 \times 6/(6+6) \\
&:= 7 + ((777 - ((7+7)/7)^7) + 7) \\
&:= 88 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - 8/8) \\
&:= 9 + ((9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) - ((9+9+9)/9)) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 664 &:= (1+1) \times ((1+1+1) \times 111 - 1) \\
&:= ((2/2+2) \times 222) - 2 \\
&:= (3-3/3) \times (333-3/3) \\
&:= 4 + (44 \times (44/4 + 4)) \\
&:= 5 + (((55 \times (55+5)) - 5)/5) \\
&:= 666 - (6+6)/6 \\
&:= 77 + (7 \times (77+7) - 7/7) \\
&:= 88 + 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) \\
&:= (9-9/9) \times (((9+9)/9) + 9 \times 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 665 &:= (11^{1+1+1} - 1)/(1+1) \\
&:= ((22+2+2)^2) - 22/2 \\
&:= 3^{3+3} - ((3/3+3)^3) \\
&:= 44 + ((4/4+4)^4 - 4) \\
&:= 5 + (55 \times ((55+5)/5)) \\
&:= 666 - 6/6 \\
&:= 77 + 7 \times (77+7) \\
&:= 8/8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) + 88) \\
&:= 9 + ((9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) - 9/9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 666 &:= (1+1) \times (1+1+1) \times 111 \\
&:= (2/2+2) \times 222 \\
&:= 3 \times (((3+3)^3 + 3) + 3) \\
&:= ((4+4)/4 + 4) \times 444/4 \\
&:= 555 + 555/5 \\
&:= 666 \\
&:= (7-7/7) \times 777/7 \\
&:= (8-(8+8)/8) \times 888/8 \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 667 &:= 1 + (1+1) \times (1+1+1) \times 111 \\
&:= 2/2 + ((2/2+2) \times 222) \\
&:= (((3+3) \times 333) + 3)/3 \\
&:= 4444/4 - 444 \\
&:= 555 + (555+5)/5 \\
&:= 6/6 + 666 \\
&:= 7 \times 77 + ((7+7)/7)^7 \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times (88-8) + (88/8)) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + ((9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) + 9/9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 668 &:= (1+1) \times (1 + (1+1+1) \times 111) \\
&:= 2 + ((2/2+2) \times 222) \\
&:= 3 + (3^{3+3} - ((3/3+3)^3)) \\
&:= (4 \times ((4 \times 44) - (4+4))) - 4 \\
&:= 55 + ((5^5 - (55+5))/5) \\
&:= 666 + (6+6)/6 \\
&:= (7 \times 7 \times (7+7)) - (77/7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times 88 - (88/((8+8)/8))) \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) + (99/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 669 &:= (1+1+1) \times (1 + (1+1) \times 111) \\
&:= (2/2+2) \times (222+2/2) \\
&:= 3 + (333+333) \\
&:= 44 + (4/4+4)^4 \\
&:= 55 + ((5^5 - 55)/5) \\
&:= 666 + (6 \times 6/(6+6)) \\
&:= ((7-77)/7) + ((7 \times 7 \times (7+7)) - 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 - ((88/8+8+8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) + ((99+9)/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 670 &:= 1 + ((1+1+1) \times (1 + (1+1) \times 111)) \\
&:= 2 + (((2/2+2) \times 222) + 2) \\
&:= 3 + (((3+3) \times 333) + 3)/3 \\
&:= 44 + ((4/4+4)^4 + 4/4) \\
&:= 55 + (5^5/5 - (5+5)) \\
&:= 6 + (666 - ((6+6)/6)) \\
&:= ((7+7)/7) \times (7 \times 7 \times 7 - (7/7+7)) \\
&:= ((88+8) \times (8-8/8)) - (8+8)/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) + ((99+99)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 671 &:= 11 \times ((1+11^{1+1})/(1+1)) \\
&:= 2 + ((2/2+2) \times (222+2/2)) \\
&:= 33/3 \times (((3/3+3)^3) - 3) \\
&:= 44/4 \times ((4^4+4)/4 - 4) \\
&:= 5 + (555/5 + 555) \\
&:= 6 + (666 - 6/6) \\
&:= (7 \times 7 \times (7+7)) - (7/7+7+7) \\
&:= ((88+8) \times (8-8/8)) - 8/8 \\
&:= 99/9 \times (9 \times 9 - (99/9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 672 &:= (1+1) \times ((1+1+1) \times (1+111)) \\
&:= (2/2+2) \times (222+2) \\
&:= 3^3 + (3 \times (3+3)^3 - 3) \\
&:= 4 \times ((4 \times 44) - (4+4)) \\
&:= (5/5+5) \times (555+5)/5 \\
&:= 6 + 666 \\
&:= (7+7) \times (7 \times 7 - 7/7) \\
&:= (88+8) \times (8-8/8) \\
&:= (9-9/9) \times (((9+9+9)/9) + 9 \times 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 673 &:= 1 + ((1+1) \times ((1+1+1) \times (1+111))) \\
&:= ((22+2+2)^2) - 2/2 - 2 \\
&:= (3^3 - 3/3)^{3-3/3} - 3 \\
&:= 4 + ((4/4+4)^4 + 44) \\
&:= 55 + ((5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 - 5) \\
&:= 6 + (666 + 6/6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7-7/7) \times 777/7) \\
&:= 8/8 + ((88+8) \times (8-8/8)) \\
&:= 9 + ((9-9/9) \times ((9+9)/9) + 9 \times 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 674 &:= (1+1) \times (1 + ((1+1+1) \times (1+111))) \\
&:= ((22+2+2)^2) - 2 \\
&:= 3^3 + (3 \times (3+3)^3 - 3/3) \\
&:= 4 + (((4/4+4)^4 + 44) + 4/4) \\
&:= 55 + ((5^5 - 5)/5 - 5) \\
&:= 6 + (666 + ((6+6)/6)) \\
&:= 7 + (((7+7)/7)^7 + 7 \times 77) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 - (8+8)/8) \times 888/8) \\
&:= 9 \times (9+9) + (((9+9)/9)^9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 675 &:= (((1+1) \times (1 + (1+11)))^{1+1}) - 1 \\
&:= ((22+2+2)^2) - 2/2 \\
&:= 3 \times ((3+3)^3 + 3 \times 3) \\
&:= (44/4+4) \times (44+4/4) \\
&:= 5 \times ((5 \times 5 \times 5 + 5) + 5) \\
&:= 6 + ((6 \times 6/(6+6)) + 666) \\
&:= (7 \times 7 \times (7+7)) - 77/7 \\
&:= (8/8+8) \times (88/8+8 \times 8) \\
&:= 9 + ((9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) + 9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 676 &:= ((1+1) \times (1 + (1+11)))^{1+1} \\
&:= (22+2+2)^2 \\
&:= (3^3 - 3/3)^{3-3/3} \\
&:= 4 + (4 \times ((4 \times 44) - (4+4))) \\
&:= 55 + ((5^5 + 5)/5 - 5) \\
&:= 666 + (66 - 6)/6 \\
&:= ((7-77)/7) + (7 \times 7 \times (7+7)) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 + ((8-8 \times 8)/((8+8)/8)) \\
&:= (((9-9/9) + 9) + 9)^{(9+9)/9}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 677 &:= 1 + (((1+1) \times (1 + (1+11)))^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2/2 + ((22+2+2)^2) \\
&:= (((3+3) \times 333) + 33)/3 \\
&:= 4 + (((4/4+4)^4 + 44) + 4) \\
&:= 55 + ((5^5 + 5 + 5)/5 - 5) \\
&:= 666 + 66/6 \\
&:= (7 \times 7 \times (7+7)) - ((7+7)/7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 - (88/8 + 8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 + ((9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) + (99/9)) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 678 &:= 1 + (1 + (((1+1) \times (1 + (1+11)))^{1+1})) \\
&:= 2 + ((22+2+2)^2) \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times (3+3)^3 + 3^3) \\
&:= (4-44)/4 + (4 \times ((4 \times 44) - 4)) \\
&:= 55 + (5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 \\
&:= 6 + (666 + 6) \\
&:= (7 \times 7 \times (7+7)) - (7/7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 + ((8-88)/8 - (8+8)) \\
&:= 999/9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 679 &:= (((1+1)^{11}) - 11)/(1+1+1) \\
&:= 2 + (((22+2+2)^2) + 2/2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3^3 - 3/3)^{3-3/3}) \\
&:= 4 + (44/4+4) \times (44+4/4) \\
&:= 55 + (5^5 - 5)/5 \\
&:= 6 + (666 + 6/6 + 6) \\
&:= (7 \times 7 \times (7+7)) - 7 \\
&:= 8 \times 88 - (8/8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((9 \times 99 + 9)/(9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 680 &:= 1 + (((1+1)^{11}) - 11)/(1+1+1) \\
&:= 2 + (((22+2+2)^2) + 2) \\
&:= 33 + (3 \times (3+3)^3 - 3/3) \\
&:= (4+4) \times ((4-4/4)^4 + 4) \\
&:= 55 + 5^5/5 \\
&:= 6 + ((666 + ((6+6)/6)) + 6) \\
&:= 7/7 + ((7 \times 7 \times (7+7)) - 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((9-9 \times 99)/(9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 681 &:= ((1 + ((1+1)^{11}))/ (1+1+1)) - 1 - 1 \\
&:= 2 + (((22+2+2)^2) + 2/2) + 2) \\
&:= 33 + 3 \times (3+3)^3 \\
&:= 4 + (((4/4+4)^4 + 44) + 4) + 4) \\
&:= 55 + (5^5 + 5)/5 \\
&:= 66 \times (6+6) - 666/6 \\
&:= ((7+7)/7) + ((7 \times 7 \times (7+7)) - 7) \\
&:= 8/8 + (8 \times 88 - (8+8+8)) \\
&:= 9 \times 99 - (999/9 + 99)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 682 &:= (((1+1)^{11}) - (1+1))/(1+1+1) \\
&:= 2 + (((22+2+2)^2) + 2) + 2) \\
&:= 3/3 + (3 \times (3+3)^3 + 33) \\
&:= 44/4 \times ((4^4 - 4 - 4)/4) \\
&:= 55 + (5^5 + 5 + 5)/5 \\
&:= 6 + ((66 - 6)/6 + 666) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times 7 \times (7+7)) - (77/7)) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 - (88/8 + 8 + 8) \\
&:= 99/9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9/9 + 9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 683 &:= (1 + ((1+1)^{11}))/ (1+1+1) \\
&:= 22^2 + (((22-2)^2 - 2)/2) \\
&:= ((33/3)^3) - 3 \times (3+3)^3 \\
&:= (4 \times ((4 \times 44) - 4)) - (4/4 + 4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 + 55) \\
&:= 6 + (666 + (66/6)) \\
&:= (7 \times 7 \times (7+7)) - (7+7+7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + ((8/8+8) \times (88/8+8 \times 8)) \\
&:= 9 + (((9+9)/9)^9) + 9 \times (9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 684 &:= 1 + ((1 + ((1+1)^{11}))/ (1+1+1)) \\
&:= 2 \times (2 \times (((22/2+2)^2) + 2)) \\
&:= 3 + (3 \times (3+3)^3 + 33) \\
&:= (4 \times ((4 \times 44) - 4)) - 4 \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 - 5)/5 + 55) \\
&:= 6 + ((666 + 6) + 6) \\
&:= (7 \times 7 \times (7+7)) - (7+7)/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 88 - (((88+8)/8) + 8) \\
&:= (99 \times (9 - ((9+9)/9))) - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 685 &:= 1 + (1 + ((1 + ((1+1)^{11}))/ (1+1+1))) \\
&:= 22/2 + (((22+2+2)^2) - 2) \\
&:= 3^{3+3} - (33/3 + 33) \\
&:= 4 \times 4 + ((4/4+4)^4 + 44) \\
&:= 5 + (5^5/5 + 55) \\
&:= 6 + ((666 + 6/6 + 6) + 6) \\
&:= (7 \times 7 \times (7+7)) - 7/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 88 - (88/8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9-9/9) + 9) + 9)^{(9+9)/9}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 686 &:= (11 + (((1+1)^{11}) - 11))/ (1+1+1) \\
&:= 2 \times ((22/2)^2 + 222) \\
&:= (3 - 3/3) \times (((3/3+3) + 3)^3) \\
&:= (4 \times ((4 \times 44) - 4)) - (4+4)/4 \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 + 5)/5 + 55) \\
&:= 6 + (((666 + ((6+6)/6)) + 6) + 6) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times (7+7) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 + ((8-88)/8 - 8) \\
&:= (99 - 9/9) \times (9 - ((9+9)/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 687 &:= 11 + (((1+1) \times (1 + (1+11)))^{1+1}) \\
&:= 22/2 + ((22+2+2)^2) \\
&:= 3^{3+3} - (3 \times 3 + 33) \\
&:= (4 \times ((4 \times 44) - 4)) - 4/4 \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 + 5 + 5)/5 + 55) \\
&:= ((6 \times 6/(6+6))^6) - (6 \times 6 + 6) \\
&:= 7/7 + (7 \times 7 \times (7+7)) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 - (8/8 + 8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 + ((9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9+9))) + 999/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 688 &:= (1+1) \times (11 + (1+1+1) \times 111) \\
&:= 2 \times (2 \times (2 \times (2 \times 22 - 2))) \\
&:= 3 + (3^{3+3} - (33/3 + 33)) \\
&:= 4 \times ((4 \times 44) - 4) \\
&:= (5 \times 5 \times 5 \times 55 + 5) / (5 + 5) \\
&:= 666 + ((66 + 66) / 6) \\
&:= ((7 + 7) / 7) + (7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 - 8 - 8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((9 \times 9 \times 9 + 9) / (9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 689 &:= 1 + ((1+1) \times (11 + (1+1+1) \times 111)) \\
&:= 2 + (((22+2+2)^2) + 22/2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3-3/3) \times (((3/3+3) + 3)^3)) \\
&:= 4/4 + (4 \times ((4 \times 44) - 4)) \\
&:= 5 + (((5^5 - 5) / 5 + 55) + 5) \\
&:= 6 + ((666 + (66/6)) + 6) \\
&:= 777 - (77/7 + 77) \\
&:= 8/8 + (8 \times 88 - (8 + 8)) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((9 - 9 \times 9 \times 9) / (9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 690 &:= 11 + (((1+1)^{11}) - 11) / (1+1+1) \\
&:= 2 + (((2/2+2) \times 222) + 22) \\
&:= 33 + (3 \times ((3+3)^3 + 3)) \\
&:= (4+4)/4 + (4 \times ((4 \times 44) - 4)) \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 / 5 + 55) + 5) \\
&:= 6 + (((666 + 6) + 6) + 6) \\
&:= 77/7 + ((7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) - 7) \\
&:= (8 + 8) / 8 + (8 \times 88 - (8 + 8)) \\
&:= (9/9 + 9) \times (9 \times 9 - ((99 + 9) / 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 691 &:= ((1+1)^{11-1}) - (1+1+1) \times 111 \\
&:= 2 + (((22+2+2)^2) + 22/2) + 2 \\
&:= 3^{3+3} - (33/3 + 3^3) \\
&:= 4 + ((4 \times ((4 \times 44) - 4)) - 4/4) \\
&:= 55 + ((55 + 5^5) / 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + (666 - 66/6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) - ((7 + 7) / 7)) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 - (88 + 8 + 8) / 8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((99/9 + 9 + 9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 692 &:= (11 \times ((1+1+1) \times (11 + (11 - 1)))) - 1 \\
&:= 2 \times (((2^{2+2} + 2)^2) + 22) \\
&:= 3^{3+3} - (3/3 + 33 + 3) \\
&:= 4 + (4 \times ((4 \times 44) - 4)) \\
&:= 55 + ((55 + 5^5 + 5) / 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + (((6 - 66) / 6) + 666) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) - 7/7) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 - (88 + 8) / 8 \\
&:= 99 + (((9 + 9) / 9)^9) + 9 \times 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 693 &:= 11 \times ((1+1+1) \times (11 + (11 - 1))) \\
&:= (2/2 + 2) \times ((22^2 - 22) / 2) \\
&:= 33 \times ((3 \times (3 + 3)) + 3) \\
&:= 44/4 \times ((4^4 - 4) / 4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5 \times 5 \times 5 \times 55 + 5) / (5 + 5)) \\
&:= ((6 \times 6 / (6 + 6))^6) - 6 \times 6 \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 - 88/8 \\
&:= 99 \times (9 - ((9 + 9) / 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 694 &:= 11 + ((1 + ((1+1)^{11})) / (1+1+1)) \\
&:= 2 + (((22+2+2)^2) + 2^{2+2}) \\
&:= 3/3 + (33 \times ((3 \times (3 + 3)) + 3)) \\
&:= (4 - 44) / 4 + 4 \times 4 \times 44 \\
&:= 5 + (((5^5 - 5) / 5 + 55) + 5) + 5 \\
&:= 6 + (((66 + 66) / 6) + 666) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) + 7/7) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 + (8 - 88) / 8 \\
&:= 9/9 + (99 \times (9 - ((9 + 9) / 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 695 &:= 1 + 11 + (1 + (1+1)^{11}) / (1+1+1) \\
&:= 222 + (22^2 - 22/2) \\
&:= 3^{3+3} - (3/3 + 33) \\
&:= 4^4 + (444 - (4/4 + 4)) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) - 55 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + (666 - 6/6 - 6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) + ((7 + 7) / 7)) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 - (8/8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 + ((99 - 9/9) \times (9 - ((9 + 9) / 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 696 &:= (1+1+1) \times (111 + 11^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 \times (2 \times ((2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 22) - 2)) \\
&:= 3^{3+3} - 33 \\
&:= 4^4 + (444 - 4) \\
&:= 5 + (((55 + 5^5) / 5) + 55) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + (666 - 6) \\
&:= (7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) + (77 - 7) / 7 \\
&:= 8 \times 88 - 8 \\
&:= (9 - 9/9) \times (99 - ((99 + 9) / 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 697 &:= 1 + (1+1+1) \times (111 + 11^{1+1}) \\
&:= (22/2)^2 + ((22+2)^2) \\
&:= 3/3 + (3^{3+3} - 33) \\
&:= 4 + (44/4 \times ((4^4 - 4) / 4)) \\
&:= 5 + (((55 + 5^5 + 5) / 5) + 55) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + ((666 - 6) + 6/6) \\
&:= 77/7 + (7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) \\
&:= 8/8 + (8 \times 88 - 8) \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((9 \times 9 \times 9 + 9) / (9 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 698 &:= (1+1+1) \times (11 + (1+1) \times 111) - 1 \\
&:= 22 + ((22+2+2)^2) \\
&:= 3 + (3^{3+3} - (3/3 + 33)) \\
&:= 4^4 + (444 - (4+4) / 4) \\
&:= (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)) + (5^5 - 5 - 5) / 5 \\
&:= ((66/6) \times ((6+6) / 6)^6) - 6 \\
&:= 777 - ((7+7) / 7 + 77) \\
&:= (8 + 8) / 8 + (8 \times 88 - 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - (((99 + 99) / 9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 699 &:= (1+1+1) \times (11 + (1+1) \times 111) \\
&:= 2 + ((22/2)^2 + ((22+2)^2)) \\
&:= 3 + (3^{3+3} - 33) \\
&:= 4^4 + (444 - 4/4) \\
&:= (5^5 - 5) / 5 + (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 \times 6 / (6 + 6))^6) - 6 \times 6) \\
&:= 777 - (7/7 + 77) \\
&:= 88/8 + (8 \times 88 - (8 + 8)) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) - 999/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 700 &:= 1 + (1+1+1) \times (11 + (1+1) \times 111) \\
&:= 2 \times ((22 \times 2^{2+2}) - 2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3^{3+3} - 33) + 3/3) \\
&:= 4^4 + 444 \\
&:= 5 \times (((5 \times 5 \times 5 + 5) + 5) + 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + (666 - ((6+6) / 6)) \\
&:= 777 - 77 \\
&:= 8 \times 88 - (8 / ((8 + 8) / 8)) \\
&:= (9/9 + 9) \times (9 \times 9 - 99/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 701 &:= 1 + 1 + (1+1+1) \times (11 + (1+1) \times 111) \\
&:= 2/2 + (2 \times ((22 \times 2^{2+2}) - 2)) \\
&:= 3^{3+3} - (3^3 + 3/3) \\
&:= 4/4 + (444 + 4^4) \\
&:= (5^5 + 5) / 5 + (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + (666 - 6/6) \\
&:= 7/7 + (777 - 77) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times 88 - (88/8)) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((9/9 + 9 + 9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 702 &:= (1+1) \times ((11 \times ((11 \times (1+1+1)) - 1)) - 1) \\
&:= (2 \times (22 \times 2^{2+2})) - 2 \\
&:= 3^{3+3} - 3^3 \\
&:= 4 \times 4 \times 44 - (4 + 4) / 4 \\
&:= 55 + (((55 + 55) + 5^5) / 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + 666 \\
&:= ((7 + 7) / 7) + (777 - 77) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 - (8 + 8) / 8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - (9 + 9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 703 &:= (11 \times ((1+1)^{(1+1) \times (1+1+1)})) - 1 \\
&:= (2 \times (22 \times 2^{2+2})) - 2/2 \\
&:= 3/3 + (3^{3+3} - 3^3) \\
&:= 4 \times 4 \times 44 - 4/4 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + ((5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 + 55) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + (666 + 6/6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times 7 \times (7+7)) + ((77 - 7)/7)) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 - 8/8 \\
&:= 9/9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - (9+9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 704 &:= 11 \times ((1+1)^{(1+1) \times (1+1+1)}) \\
&:= 2 \times (22 \times 2^{2+2}) \\
&:= 33/3 \times ((3/3 + 3)^3) \\
&:= 4 \times (4 \times 44) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + ((5^5 - 5)/5 + 55) \\
&:= (66/6) \times ((6+6)/6)^6 \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times 7 \times (7+7)) + (77/7)) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 \\
&:= (9 - 9/9) \times (99 - (99/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 705 &:= 1 + 11 \times ((1+1)^{(1+1) \times (1+1+1)}) \\
&:= 2/2 + (2 \times (22 \times 2^{2+2})) \\
&:= 3 + (3^{3+3} - 3^3) \\
&:= 4/4 + 4 \times 4 \times 44 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + (5^5/5 + 55) \\
&:= ((66 \times ((6+6)/6)^6) + 6)/6 \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times 7 \times (7+7)) + (77+7)/7) \\
&:= 8/8 + 8 \times 88 \\
&:= 9 + ((9 - 9/9) \times (99 - ((99+9)/9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 706 &:= 1 + 1 + 11 \times ((1+1)^{(1+1) \times (1+1+1)}) \\
&:= 222 + 22^2 \\
&:= 3 + ((3^{3+3} - 3^3) + 3/3) \\
&:= (4+4)/4 + 4 \times 4 \times 44 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + ((5^5 + 5)/5 + 55) \\
&:= 6 + ((666 - ((6+6)/6)) + 6 \times 6) \\
&:= 7 + (777 - (7/7 + 77)) \\
&:= (8+8)/8 + 8 \times 88 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((99+99+9)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 707 &:= (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1} - 11 - 11 \\
&:= 2/2 + (222 + 22^2) \\
&:= 3 + (33/3 \times ((3/3 + 3)^3)) \\
&:= 4 + 4 \times 4 \times 44 - 4/4 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + ((5^5 + 5 + 5)/5 + 55) \\
&:= 6 + ((666 - 6/6) + 6 \times 6) \\
&:= 7 + (777 - 77) \\
&:= 88/8 + (8 \times 88 - 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((99+99)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 708 &:= (1 + 11) \times ((11^{1+1} - 1)/(1+1) - 1) \\
&:= 2 + (222 + 22^2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3^{3+3} - 3^3) + 3) \\
&:= 4 + 4 \times 4 \times 44 \\
&:= ((55 + 5)/5) \times (55 - 5/5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 + (666 + 6 \times 6) \\
&:= 7 + ((777 - 77) + 7/7) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 + (8/((8+8)/8)) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - (((99+9)/9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 709 &:= 11 \times 111 - (1+1)^{11-1-1} \\
&:= 2 + ((222 + 22^2) + 2/2) \\
&:= 3^{3+3} - (33/3 + 3 \times 3) \\
&:= 4 + 4 \times 4 \times 44 + 4/4 \\
&:= 5 + (((5^5 - 5)/5 + 55) + 5 \times 5) \\
&:= 6 + ((666 + 6/6) + 6 \times 6) \\
&:= 7 + (((7+7)/7 - 77) + 777) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times 88 - (88/8)) + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - (99/9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 710 &:= (11 - 1) \times ((1+11)^{1+1}/(1+1) - 1) \\
&:= 2 + ((222 + 22^2) + 2) \\
&:= 3^{3+3} - ((3 \times (3+3)) + 3/3) \\
&:= 4 + 4 \times 4 \times 44 + (4+4)/4 \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5/5 + 55) + 5 \times 5) \\
&:= 6 + ((66/6) \times ((6+6)/6)^6) \\
&:= 777 + (((77 - 7)/7) - 77) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times 88 - ((8+8)/8)) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - (9/9 + 9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 711 &:= 1111 - ((1+1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1} \\
&:= (2222/2) - (22 - 2)^2 \\
&:= 3^{3+3} - (3 \times (3+3)) \\
&:= 4 + (4 \times 4 \times 44 - 4/4) + 4 \\
&:= ((555 + 5^5)/5) - 5 \times 5 \\
&:= ((6 \times 6/(6+6))^6) - 6 - 6 - 6 \\
&:= 77/7 + (777 - 77) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times 88 - 8/8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - (9+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 712 &:= 1 + (1111 - (((1+1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1})) \\
&:= 2 \times (((22 \times 2^{2+2}) + 2) + 2) \\
&:= 3/3 + (3^{3+3} - (3 \times (3+3))) \\
&:= 4 + 4 \times 4 \times 44 + 4 \\
&:= 55 + (((5+5)/5)^5 + 5^5/5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + ((66 - 6)/6 + 666) \\
&:= 777 + ((77+7)/7 - 77) \\
&:= 8 + 8 \times 88 \\
&:= 9/9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - (9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 713 &:= (1 + (11 + 11)) \times (1 + ((11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1))) \\
&:= ((2/2 + 2)^{2+2+2}) - 2^{2+2} \\
&:= 3^{3+3} + (33/3 - 3^3) \\
&:= 4 + (4 \times 4 \times 44 + 4/4) + 4 \\
&:= (55 \times (55 + 5 + 5) - (5 + 5))/5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + (666 + (66/6)) \\
&:= 7 + ((777 - (7/7 + 77)) + 7) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times 88 + 8/8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + (((9+9)/9) - (9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 714 &:= (1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1 + 1) \times (11^{1+1} - (1 + 1))) \\
&:= (2 + 2 + 2) \times ((22/2)^2 - 2) \\
&:= 3 + (3^{3+3} - (3 \times (3 + 3))) \\
&:= 4 \times 4 \times 44 + (44 - 4)/4 \\
&:= (55 \times (55 + 5 + 5) - 5)/5 \\
&:= (6 + 6) \times (66 - 6) - 6 \\
&:= 7 + ((777 - 77) + 7) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 + 8)/8 + 8 \times 88) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + (((9+9+9)/9) - (9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 715 &:= 11 \times (1 + ((1+1)^{(1+1) \times (1+1+1)})) \\
&:= 22/2 + (2 \times (22 \times 2^{2+2})) \\
&:= 3^{3+3} - (33/3 + 3) \\
&:= 44/4 + 4 \times 4 \times 44 \\
&:= 55 \times (55 + 5 + 5)/5 \\
&:= (66/6) \times (66 - 6/6) \\
&:= 7 + (((777 - 77) + 7/7) + 7) \\
&:= 88/8 + 8 \times 88 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + (((9 - 99)/(9+9)) - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 716 &:= ((1+1)^{11}) - (1 + 11^{1+1+1}) \\
&:= 2 + ((2 + 2 + 2) \times ((22/2)^2 - 2)) \\
&:= 3^{3+3} + (((3 - 33)/3) - 3) \\
&:= (4 \times ((4 \times 44) + 4)) - 4 \\
&:= (55 \times (55 + 5 + 5) + 5)/5 \\
&:= ((66 \times (66 - 6/6)) + 6)/6 \\
&:= 7 \times (77 + 7) + ((7+7)/7)^7 \\
&:= 8 \times 88 + (88 + 8)/8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((99+9+9)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 717 &:= ((1+1)^{11}) - 11^{1+1+1} \\
&:= 222 + (22/2 + 22^2) \\
&:= 3^{3+3} - (3 \times 3 + 3) \\
&:= 4/4 + ((4 \times (4 \times 44) + 4)) - 4 \\
&:= ((55 \times (55 + 5 + 5) + 5) + 5)/5 \\
&:= ((6 \times 6/(6+6))^6) - 6 - 6 \\
&:= 777 - (77/7 + 7 \times 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 + (88 + 8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - (99 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 718 &:= (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1} - 11 \\
&:= 2 \times ((22 - (2/2 + 2))^2) - 2 \\
&:= 3^{3+3} - 33/3 \\
&:= (4 \times ((4 \times 44) + 4)) - (4 + 4)/4 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) - ((5 + 5)/5)^5 \\
&:= (6 + 6) \times (66 - 6) - (6 + 6)/6 \\
&:= 7 + ((77/7 - 77) + 777) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times 88 - ((8 + 8)/8)) + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - 99/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 719 &:= 1 + ((11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1} - 11) \\
&:= ((22 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2) - 2/2 \\
&:= 3^{3+3} + ((3 - 33)/3) \\
&:= (4 \times ((4 \times 44) + 4)) - 4/4 \\
&:= (((55 + 5)^{(5+5)/5}) - 5)/5 \\
&:= (6 + 6) \times (66 - 6) - 6/6 \\
&:= 777 - (((7 + 7)/7 + 7 \times 7) + 7) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times 88 - 8/8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - 9/9 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 720 &:= (1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1 + 1) \times (11^{1+1} - 1)) \\
&:= (22 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2 \\
&:= 3^{3+3} - 3 \times 3 \\
&:= 4 \times ((4 \times 44) + 4) \\
&:= (5/5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 \times 5 - 5) \\
&:= (6 + 6) \times (66 - 6) \\
&:= 777 - ((7/7 + 7 \times 7) + 7) \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times 88 + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 721 &:= (111 + 11^{1+1+1})/(1 + 1) \\
&:= (((2 + 2 + 2)^2 + 2)^2) - 2)/2 \\
&:= 3 + (3^{3+3} - 33/3) \\
&:= 4/4 + (4 \times ((4 \times 44) + 4)) \\
&:= (((55 + 5)^{(5+5)/5}) + 5)/5 \\
&:= 6/6 + (6 + 6) \times (66 - 6) \\
&:= 777 - (7 \times 7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times 88 + 8/8) + 8) \\
&:= 9/9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 722 &:= (1 + 1) \times (((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)) - 1)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 \times ((22 - (2/2 + 2))^2) \\
&:= 3^{3+3} - ((3/3 + 3) + 3) \\
&:= (4 + 4)/4 + (4 \times ((4 \times 44) + 4)) \\
&:= (((55 + 5)^{(5+5)/5}) + 5)/5 \\
&:= (6 + 6)/6 + (6 + 6) \times (66 - 6) \\
&:= 7/7 + (777 - (7 \times 7 + 7)) \\
&:= 8 + (((8 + 8)/8) + 8 \times 88) + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + (((9 + 9)/9) - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 723 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (((1 + 1) \times 11^{1+1}) - 1) \\
&:= (2/2 + 2) \times (22^2 - 2)/2 \\
&:= 3^{3+3} - (3 + 3) \\
&:= 4 + ((4 \times ((4 \times 44) + 4)) - 4/4) \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) + (5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 \\
&:= ((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) - 6 \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (77 + 7) + ((7 + 7)/7)^7) \\
&:= 8 + (88/8 + 8 \times 88) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + (((9 + 9 + 9)/9) - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 724 &:= (1 + 1) \times ((11 \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1))) - 1) \\
&:= 2 + (2 \times ((22 - (2/2 + 2))^2)) \\
&:= 3/3 + (3^{3+3} - (3 + 3)) \\
&:= 4 + (4 \times ((4 \times 44) + 4)) \\
&:= (5^5 - 5)/5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) \\
&:= (66 \times 66 - 6 - 6)/6 \\
&:= (7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7)) - 77/7 \\
&:= 8 + (((88 + 8)/8) + 8 \times 88) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((9 - 99)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 725 &:= ((1 + 1) \times (11 \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)))) - 1 \\
&:= 22^2 + (22^2 - 2)/2 \\
&:= 3^{3+3} - (3/3 + 3) \\
&:= 4 + ((4 \times ((4 \times 44) + 4)) + 4/4) \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) - 5) \\
&:= (66 \times 66 - 6)/6 \\
&:= 777 - (((7 + 7 + 7)/7) + 7 \times 7) \\
&:= 8 + ((88 + 8 + 8)/8 + 8 \times 88) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((9 - 9 \times 9)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 726 &:= (1 + 1) \times (11 \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1))) \\
&:= 22 \times (22/2 + 22) \\
&:= 3^{3+3} - 3 \\
&:= 44/4 \times (((4^4 + 4) + 4)/4) \\
&:= 5/5 + (5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) - 5)) \\
&:= 66 \times (66/6) \\
&:= (7 - 7/7) \times (((7 + 7)/7)^7 - 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 + (88 + 88)/8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 727 &:= (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1} - 1 - 1 \\
&:= ((2/2 + 2)^{2+2+2}) - 2 \\
&:= 3/3 + (3^{3+3} - 3) \\
&:= 4 + (((4 \times ((4 \times 44) + 4)) - 4/4) + 4) \\
&:= (5 + 5)/5 + (5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) - 5)) \\
&:= (66 \times 66 + 6)/6 \\
&:= 777 - (7/7 + 7 \times 7) \\
&:= 8 + (((8 \times 88 - 8/8) + 8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - (9 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 728 &:= (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1} - 1 \\
&:= 2 + (22^2/2 + 22^2) \\
&:= 3^{3+3} - 3/3 \\
&:= 4 + ((4 \times ((4 \times 44) + 4)) + 4) \\
&:= (55 + 5/5) \times (55 + 5 + 5)/5 \\
&:= ((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) - 6/6 \\
&:= 777 - 7 \times 7 \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times 88 + 8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 729 &:= (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1} \\
&:= (2/2 + 2)^{2+2+2} \\
&:= 3^{3+3} \\
&:= (4 - 4/4)^{4+(4+4)/4} \\
&:= (5 - (5 + 5)/5)^{5/5+5} \\
&:= (6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6 \\
&:= 7/7 + (777 - 7 \times 7) \\
&:= (8/8 + 8)^{88/8-8} \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 730 &:= 1 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1} \\
&:= 2/2 + ((2/2 + 2)^{2+2+2}) \\
&:= 3/3 + 3^{3+3} \\
&:= 4 + (44/4 \times (((4^4 + 4) + 4)/4)) \\
&:= 5 + (5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) - 5)) \\
&:= 6/6 + ((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) \\
&:= ((7 + 7)/7) + (777 - 7 \times 7) \\
&:= 8 + (((8 + 8)/8) + 8 \times 88) + 8) + 8) \\
&:= 9/9 + 9 \times 9 \times 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 731 &:= 1 + (1 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1}) \\
&:= 2 + ((2/2 + 2)^{2+2+2}) \\
&:= 3 + (3^{3+3} - 3/3) \\
&:= 44/4 + (4 \times ((4 \times 44) + 4)) \\
&:= ((555 + 5^5)/5) - 5 \\
&:= 6 + ((66 \times 66 - 6)/6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7)) - (77/7)) \\
&:= 8 + ((88/8 + 8 \times 88) + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((9 + 9)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 732 &:= 1 + (1 + (1 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1})) \\
&:= (2/2 + 2) \times (22^2/2 + 2) \\
&:= 3 + 3^{3+3} \\
&:= 44 + (4 \times ((4 \times 44) - 4)) \\
&:= (((555 + 5^5) + 5)/5) - 5 \\
&:= 66 + 666 \\
&:= 77/7 + (777 - (7 \times 7 + 7)) \\
&:= 8 + (((88 + 8)/8) + 8 \times 88) + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((9 + 9 + 9)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 733 &:= 1 + (1 + (1 + (1 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1}))) \\
&:= 2 + (((2/2 + 2)^{2+2+2}) + 2) \\
&:= 3 + (3^{3+3} + 3/3) \\
&:= 4 + ((4 - 4/4)^{4+(4+4)/4}) \\
&:= 55 + ((5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 + 55) \\
&:= 6 + ((66 \times 66 + 6)/6) \\
&:= (7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7)) - (7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + (((88 + 8 + 8)/8 + 8 \times 88) + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((9 \times 9 - 9)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 734 &:= (1 + 1) \times (1 + ((1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11^{1+1}))) \\
&:= 222 + (2^{(2/2+2)^2}) \\
&:= 3 + ((3^{3+3} - 3/3) + 3) \\
&:= (4 + 4)/4 \times (444/4 + 4^4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5 - (5 + 5)/5)^{5/5+5}) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) - 6/6) \\
&:= (7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7)) - 7/7 \\
&:= 8 + ((88 + 88)/8 + 8 \times 88) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 735 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11^{1+1}))) \\
&:= 2 + (((2/2 + 2)^{2+2+2}) + 2) + 2) \\
&:= 3 + (3^{3+3} + 3) \\
&:= (4 - 4/4) \times (4^4 - 44/4) \\
&:= 55 + (5^5/5 + 55) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) \\
&:= 7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7) \\
&:= 8 + (((8 \times 88 - 8/8) + 8) + 8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((9 + 9 + 9)/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 736 &:= 111 + (1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1} \\
&:= 2^{2+2} \times ((2 \times 22) + 2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3^{3+3} + 3/3) + 3) \\
&:= 4 \times (((4 \times 44) + 4) + 4) \\
&:= (555 + 5^5)/5 \\
&:= 6 + (((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) + 6/6) \\
&:= 7/7 + (7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7)) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times 88 + 8 + 8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((9 + 9)/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 737 &:= 11 \times (1 + ((1 + 1) \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)))) \\
&:= 2/2 + (2^{2+2} \times ((2 \times 22) + 2)) \\
&:= 3 \times 3 + (3^{3+3} - 3/3) \\
&:= 4/4 + (4 \times (((4 \times 44) + 4) + 4)) \\
&:= ((555 + 5^5) + 5)/5 \\
&:= (66/6) \times (66 + 6/6) \\
&:= ((7 + 7)/7) + (7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7)) \\
&:= 8 + ((8/8 + 8)^{88/8-8}) \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - 9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 738 &:= 1 + (11 \times (1 + ((1 + 1) \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)))))) \\
&:= 2 + (2^{2+2} \times ((2 \times 22) + 2)) \\
&:= 3 \times 3 + 3^{3+3} \\
&:= 4^4 + ((44 \times 44 - (4 + 4))/4) \\
&:= (((555 + 5^5) + 5) + 5)/5 \\
&:= 6 + (666 + 66) \\
&:= 777 + (((77 - 7)/7) - 7 \times 7) \\
&:= (8/8 + 8) \times (((8 + 8)/8) - 8) + 88) \\
&:= 9 + 9 \times 9 \times 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 739 &:= 11 + ((11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1} - 1) \\
&:= 22^2 + (2^{2 \times (2+2)} - 2/2) \\
&:= 3 \times 3 + (3^{3+3} + 3/3) \\
&:= 4^4 + ((44 \times 44 - 4)/4) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 \times 5 + ((5^5 - 55)/5) \\
&:= 6 + (((66 \times 66 + 6)/6) + 6) \\
&:= 77/7 + (777 - 7 \times 7) \\
&:= 8 + (((88/8 + 8 \times 88) + 8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 + 9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 740 &:= 11 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1} \\
&:= 22^2 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)} \\
&:= 3^{3+3} + 33/3 \\
&:= 4 + (4 \times (((4 \times 44) + 4) + 4)) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) - 5 - 5 \\
&:= 66/6 + (((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7)) - ((7 + 7)/7)) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 + ((8 \times 8 + 8)/((8 + 8)/8)) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + (99/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 741 &:= 1 + (11 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1}) \\
&:= 2/2 + (2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 22^2) \\
&:= 3 + (3^{3+3} + 3 \times 3) \\
&:= 4^4 + ((44 \times 44 + 4)/4) \\
&:= 5 + ((555 + 5^5)/5) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) + 6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7)) - 7/7) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 + 888/(8 + 8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + (99 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 742 &:= 1 + (1 + (11 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1})) \\
&:= 2 + (2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 22^2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3^{3+3} + 3/3) + 3 \times 3) \\
&:= 4^4 + (((44 \times 44 + 4) + 4)/4) \\
&:= 5 + (((555 + 5^5) + 5)/5) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) + 6/6) + 6) \\
&:= 7 + (7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7)) \\
&:= 8 + (((88 + 88)/8 + 8 \times 88) + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((99 + 9 + 9)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 743 &:= 1 + (1 + (1 + (11 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1}))) \\
&:= 2 + ((2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 22^2) + 2/2) \\
&:= 3 + (3^{3+3} + 33/3) \\
&:= 4 + (((44 \times 44 - 4)/4) + 4^4) \\
&:= 5 + (((555 + 5^5) + 5) + 5)/5) \\
&:= 6 + ((66/6) \times (66 + 6/6)) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7)) + 7/7) \\
&:= 888/8 + (8 \times (88 - 8) - 8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9 \times 9 \times 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 744 &:= (1 + 11) \times (1 + ((1 + 11^{1+1})/(1 + 1))) \\
&:= (2 \times 22^2) - (222 + 2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3^{3+3} + 3 \times 3) + 3) \\
&:= 44 + (444 + 4^4) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 \times 5 + ((5^5 - 5)/5 - 5) \\
&:= 6 + ((666 + 66) + 6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7)) + ((7 + 7)/7)) \\
&:= 8 \times (88 + 8) - 8 - 8 - 8 \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((9 + 9 + 9)/9)) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 745 &:= (1 + (1 + (1 + ((1 + 1)^{1+1+1}))))/11 \\
&:= 2^{2+2} + ((2/2 + 2)^{2+2+2}) \\
&:= 3^3 + (3^{3+3} - 33/3) \\
&:= 4 + (((44 \times 44 + 4)/4) + 4^4) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) - 5 \\
&:= 6 + (((66 \times 66 + 6)/6) + 6) + 6) \\
&:= 777 - ((77/7 + 7 + 7) + 7) \\
&:= 8 + (((8/8 + 8)^{88/8-8}) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((9 + 9)/9)) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 746 &:= (1 + 1) \times (((11 + 11)^{1+1}) - 111) \\
&:= (2 \times 22^2) - 222 \\
&:= 3 + ((3^{3+3} + 33/3) + 3) \\
&:= 44 + 4 \times 4 \times 44 - (4 + 4)/4) \\
&:= 5 + (((555 + 5^5)/5) + 5) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) + (66/6)) \\
&:= 77/7 + (7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7)) \\
&:= 8 \times (88 + 8) - (88 + 88)/8 \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - 9/9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 747 &:= ((1 + 1) \times (11 \times (1 + (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)))))) - 1 \\
&:= 2/2 + ((2 \times 22^2) - 222) \\
&:= 3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 + 33) \\
&:= 44 + 4 \times 4 \times 44 - 4/4) \\
&:= ((555 + 55) + 5^5)/5) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) + 6) + 6) \\
&:= (77 + 7)/7 + (7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7)) \\
&:= (8/8 + 8) \times ((88/8 + 8 \times 8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 748 &:= (1+1) \times (11 \times (1 + (11 \times (1+1+1)))) \\
&:= 22 \times ((2 \times 2^{2+2}) + 2) \\
&:= 3/3 + (3^{3+3} + (3 \times (3+3))) \\
&:= 44 + 4 \times 4 \times 44 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 \times 5 + (5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 \\
&:= (66/6) \times (((6+6)/6) + 66) \\
&:= 7 + (((7 \times (7 \times (7+7) + 7)) - 7/7) + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 + (88/(8+8)/8) \\
&:= 9 + ((9 \times 9 \times 9 + 9/9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 749 &:= 1 + ((1+1) \times (11 \times (1 + (11 \times (1+1+1)))) \\
&:= 22 + (((2/2+2)^{2+2+2}) - 2) \\
&:= 3 \times 3 + (3^{3+3} + 33/3) \\
&:= 44 + 4 \times 4 \times 44 + 4/4 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 \times 5 + (5^5 - 5)/5 \\
&:= 6 + (((66/6) \times (66+6/6)) + 6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times (7 \times (7+7) + 7)) + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times (88+8) - (88/8+8) \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 + (99/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 750 &:= (1+1) \times (1 + (11 \times (1 + (11 \times (1+1+1)))) \\
&:= 2 + (22 \times ((2 \times 2^{2+2}) + 2)) \\
&:= 3 + (3^{3+3} + (3 \times (3+3))) \\
&:= 44 + 4 \times 4 \times 44 + (4+4)/4 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) \\
&:= 66 \times (6+6) - (6 \times 6 + 6) \\
&:= (7/7 + 7 + 7) \times (7/7 + 7 \times 7) \\
&:= (8 - 88)/8 + (8 \times (88+8) - 8) \\
&:= 9 + (((99+9)/9) + 9 \times 9 \times 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 751 &:= 11 + (11 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1}) \\
&:= 22 + ((2/2+2)^{2+2+2}) \\
&:= 33 + (3^{3+3} - 33/3) \\
&:= (4 \times (4^4 - 4)) - (4/4 + 4^4) \\
&:= 5/5 + 5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + ((66/6) \times (66 - 6/6)) \\
&:= 777 - ((77+7)/7 + 7 + 7) \\
&:= 888/8 + 8 \times (88 - 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((99+99)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 752 &:= 1 + (11 + (11 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1})) \\
&:= 2 \times ((22 - 2)^2 - (22 + 2)) \\
&:= 3^3 + (3^{3+3} - (3/3 + 3)) \\
&:= 4 \times (444 - 4^4) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 \times 5 + (5^5 + 5 + 5)/5 \\
&:= 6 + (((6 \times 6/(6+6))^6) + (66/6) + 6) \\
&:= 777 - (77/7 + 7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times (88+8) - 8 - 8 \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((99+99+9)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 753 &:= (((1+11)^{1+1+1})/(1+1)) - 111 \\
&:= 2 + (((2/2+2)^{2+2+2}) + 22) \\
&:= 3^3 + (3^{3+3} - 3) \\
&:= 4/4 + (4 \times (444 - 4^4)) \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 \times 6/(6+6))^6) + 6) + 6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times (7 \times (7+7) + 7)) + (77/7)) \\
&:= 8/8 + (8 \times (88+8) - (8+8)) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((9+9+9)/9)) + 9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 754 &:= 1 + (((1+11)^{1+1+1})/(1+1)) - 111 \\
&:= (2 \times ((22 - 2)^2 - 22)) - 2 \\
&:= 3^3 + ((3^{3+3} - 3) + 3/3) \\
&:= (4 + 4)/4 + (4 \times (444 - 4^4)) \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 - 5)/5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5) \\
&:= 6 + ((66/6) \times (((6+6)/6) + 66)) \\
&:= 777 - (((7+7)/7 + 7) + 7) + 7) \\
&:= (8+8)/8 + (8 \times (88+8) - (8+8)) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((9+9)/9)) + 9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 755 &:= 11^{1+1+1} - (((1+1) \times (1+11))^{1+1}) \\
&:= (2 \times ((22 - 2)^2 - 22)) - 2/2 \\
&:= 3^3 + (3^{3+3} - 3/3) \\
&:= ((4 - 4/4) \times (4^4 - 4)) - 4/4 \\
&:= 5 + 5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) \\
&:= 66 \times (6+6) - (6 \times 6 + 6/6) \\
&:= 777 - (7/7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times (88+8) - (88+8+8)/8 \\
&:= 9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 9 - 9/9) + 9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 756 &:= (1+1+1) \times ((1+11) \times (11 + (11 - 1))) \\
&:= 2 \times ((22 - 2)^2 - 22) \\
&:= 3^3 + 3^{3+3} \\
&:= (4 - 4/4) \times (4^4 - 4) \\
&:= 5 + (5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) + 5/5) \\
&:= 6 \times ((66 - 6) + 66) \\
&:= 777 - (7 + 7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times (88+8) - (88+8)/8 \\
&:= 9 + ((9 \times 9 \times 9 + 9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 757 &:= 1 + ((1+1+1) \times ((1+11) \times (11 + (11 - 1)))) \\
&:= 2/2 + (2 \times ((22 - 2)^2 - 22)) \\
&:= 3^3 + (3^{3+3} + 3/3) \\
&:= 4/4 + ((4 - 4/4) \times (4^4 - 4)) \\
&:= 5 + (5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) + ((5+5)/5)) \\
&:= 6/6 + (6 \times ((66 - 6) + 66)) \\
&:= 7/7 + (777 - (7 + 7 + 7)) \\
&:= 8 \times (88+8) - 88/8 \\
&:= 9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 9 + 9/9) + 9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 758 &:= (11 \times ((1+1+1) \times (1 + (11 + 11)))) - 1 \\
&:= 2 + (2 \times ((22 - 2)^2 - 22)) \\
&:= 3 + ((3^{3+3} - 3/3) + 3^3) \\
&:= (4 + 4)/4 + ((4 - 4/4) \times (4^4 - 4)) \\
&:= 5 + (((5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5) + 5) \\
&:= (6 + 6)/6 + (6 \times ((66 - 6) + 66)) \\
&:= 777 - ((77+7)/7 + 7) \\
&:= (8 - 88)/8 + 8 \times (88+8) \\
&:= 9 + ((9 \times 9 \times 9 + (99/9)) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 759 &:= 11 \times ((1+1+1) \times (1 + (11 + 11))) \\
&:= (2/2 + 2) \times ((22^2 + 22)/2) \\
&:= 3 + (3^{3+3} + 3^3) \\
&:= (4 - 4/4) \times ((4/4 - 4) + 4^4) \\
&:= 5 + (((5^5 - 5)/5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5) + 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + (((6 \times 6/(6+6))^6) - 6) \\
&:= 777 - (77/7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times (88+8) - (8/8 + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) + 999/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 760 &:= 1 + (11 \times ((1+1+1) \times (1 + (11 + 11)))) \\
&:= 2 \times (((22 - 2)^2 - 22) + 2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3^{3+3} + 3/3) + 3^3) \\
&:= 4 + ((4 - 4/4) \times (4^4 - 4)) \\
&:= 5 + (5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) + 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + ((66 \times 66 - 6 - 6)/6) \\
&:= 777 + (((7 - 77)/7) - 7) \\
&:= 8 \times (88+8) - 8 \\
&:= 9 + (((99+99)/9) + 9 \times 9 \times 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 761 &:= 1 + (1 + (11 \times ((1+1+1) \times (1 + (11 + 11)))) \\
&:= 2 + ((2/2+2) \times ((22^2 + 22)/2)) \\
&:= 33 + (3^{3+3} - 3/3) \\
&:= ((4 - 4/4) \times (4^4 - 4/4)) - 4 \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + ((555 + 5^5)/5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + ((66 \times 66 - 6)/6) \\
&:= 777 - (((7+7)/7 + 7) + 7) \\
&:= 8/8 + (8 \times (88+8) - 8) \\
&:= ((99/9) \times (9 \times 9 - (99/9))) - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 762 &:= (1+1+1) \times (1 + (11 \times (1 + (11 + 11)))) \\
&:= (2/2 + 2) \times (2^{2 \times (2+2)} - 2) \\
&:= 33 + 3^{3+3} \\
&:= (4 - 4/4) \times (4^4 - (4+4)/4) \\
&:= 5 \times 5 + (((555 + 5^5) + 5)/5) \\
&:= 6 + (6 \times ((66 - 6) + 66)) \\
&:= 777 - (7/7 + 7 + 7) \\
&:= (8+8)/8 + (8 \times (88+8) - 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + (99/((9+9+9)/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 763 &:= (111 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1))) \\
&:= 2/2 + ((2/2 + 2) \times (2^{2 \times (2+2)} - 2)) \\
&:= 3/3 + (3^{3+3} + 33) \\
&:= 4 \times 4^4 - ((4/4 + 4^4) + 4) \\
&:= 555 + ((5^5 - 5)/5 + 5 + 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + ((66 \times 66 + 6)/6) \\
&:= 777 - (7 + 7) \\
&:= 88/8 + (8 \times (88 + 8) - (8 + 8)) \\
&:= (9 - ((9 + 9)/9)) \times (9/9 + 99 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 764 &:= 1 + ((111 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)))) \\
&:= 2 \times ((2^{2+2} \times (22 + 2)) - 2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3^{3+3} - 3/3) + 33) \\
&:= 4 \times 4^4 - (4^4 + 4) \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) + ((5^5 - 55)/5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + (((6 \times 6)/(6 + 6))^6) - 6/6 \\
&:= 7/7 + (777 - (7 + 7)) \\
&:= 8 \times (88 + 8) - 8/((8 + 8)/8) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 9 - 9/9) + 9) + 9) + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 765 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (111 + ((1 + 11)^{1+1})) \\
&:= (2/2 + 2) \times (2^{2 \times (2+2)} - 2/2) \\
&:= 3 + (3^{3+3} + 33) \\
&:= (4 - 4/4) \times (4^4 - 4/4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) + 5) + 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + ((6 \times 6)/(6 + 6))^6 \\
&:= 777 - (77 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (88 + 8) - (88/8)) \\
&:= 9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 9 + 9) + 9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 766 &:= (111 \times (1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)))) - 11 \\
&:= (2 \times (2^{2+2} \times (22 + 2))) - 2 \\
&:= 3 + ((3^{3+3} + 3/3) + 33) \\
&:= 4 \times 4^4 - ((4 + 4)/4 + 4^4) \\
&:= 5 + (((555 + 5^5)/5) + 5 \times 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + (((6 \times 6)/(6 + 6))^6) + 6/6 \\
&:= 777 - 77/7 \\
&:= 8 \times (88 + 8) - (8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= 9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 9 + 9/9) + 9) + 9) + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 767 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)^{(1+1)^{1+1+1}} - 1 \\
&:= (2 \times 2 \times 222) - (22/2)^2 \\
&:= 3^3 + (3^{3+3} + 33/3) \\
&:= 4 \times 4^4 - (4/4 + 4^4) \\
&:= 5 + (((555 + 5^5) + 5)/5) + 5 \times 5 \\
&:= ((6 + 6) \times ((6 + 6)/6)^6) - 6/6 \\
&:= 777 + (7 - 77)/7 \\
&:= 8 \times (88 + 8) - 8/8 \\
&:= 9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 9 + (99/9)) + 9) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 768 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)^{(1+1)^{1+1+1}} \\
&:= 2 \times (2^{2+2} \times (22 + 2)) \\
&:= 3 + ((3^{3+3} + 33) + 3) \\
&:= 4 \times (4 \times (44 + 4)) \\
&:= (5 \times 5 - 5/5) \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5 \\
&:= (6 + 6) \times ((6 + 6)/6)^6 \\
&:= (7 - 7/7) \times ((7 + 7)/7)^7 \\
&:= 8 \times (88 + 8) \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) + 999/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 769 &:= 1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)^{(1+1)^{1+1+1}} \\
&:= 2/2 + (2 \times (2^{2+2} \times (22 + 2))) \\
&:= 3 + (((3^{3+3} + 3/3) + 33) + 3) \\
&:= 4/4 + (4 \times (4 \times (44 + 4))) \\
&:= (5 \times (5 - 55)) + ((5 - 5/5)^5 - 5) \\
&:= 6/6 + ((6 + 6) \times ((6 + 6)/6)^6) \\
&:= 777 - (7/7 + 7) \\
&:= 8/8 + 8 \times (88 + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((9 \times 9 \times 9 - 9)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 770 &:= 11 \times ((11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1} - 11) \\
&:= 2 + (2 \times (2^{2+2} \times (22 + 2))) \\
&:= 3 + ((3^{3+3} + 33/3) + 3^3) \\
&:= (4 + 4)/4 + (4 \times (4 \times (44 + 4))) \\
&:= 55 \times ((5 - 5/5 + 5) + 5) \\
&:= (6/6 + 6) \times ((666 - 6)/6) \\
&:= 777 - 7 \\
&:= (8 + 8)/8 + 8 \times (88 + 8) \\
&:= 99/9 \times (9 \times 9 - 99/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 771 &:= 1 + (11 \times ((11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1} - 11)) \\
&:= 22^2 + (((22 + 2)^2) - 2)/2 \\
&:= 3 \times 3 + (3^{3+3} + 33) \\
&:= (4 - 4/4) \times (4/4 + 4^4) \\
&:= 5/5 + (55 \times ((5 - 5/5 + 5) + 5)) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 \times 6)/(6 + 6))^6) + 6 \times 6 \\
&:= 7/7 + (777 - 7) \\
&:= 88/8 + (8 \times (88 + 8) - 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 99 - (999/9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 772 &:= 1 + (1 + (11 \times ((11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1} - 11))) \\
&:= 2 \times ((2^{2+2} \times (22 + 2)) + 2) \\
&:= 3 \times 3 + ((3^{3+3} + 3/3) + 33) \\
&:= 4 + (4 \times (4 \times (44 + 4))) \\
&:= (((5 + 5)/5 + 5) \times 555/5) - 5 \\
&:= 666 + ((666 + 6)/6 - 6) \\
&:= ((7 + 7)/7) + (777 - 7) \\
&:= 8 \times (88 + 8) + 8/((8 + 8)/8) \\
&:= 9 \times 99 + (((9 - 999)/9) - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 773 &:= ((1 + ((1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1}))^{1+1}) - 11 \\
&:= (2 \times 22) + ((2/2 + 2)^{2+2+2}) \\
&:= 33 + (3^{3+3} + 33/3) \\
&:= 4 + ((4 \times (4 \times (44 + 4))) + 4/4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5 \times 5 - 5/5) \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 + 6) \times ((6 + 6)/6)^6) - 6/6) \\
&:= 7 + (777 - (77/7)) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times (88 + 8) - (88/8)) + 8) \\
&:= 99 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 774 &:= 1 + (((1 + ((1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1}))^{1+1}) - 11) \\
&:= (2/2 + 2) \times (2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3^{3+3} + 33) + 3 \times 3) \\
&:= (4 - 4/4) \times ((4 + 4)/4 + 4^4) \\
&:= (5 \times (5 - 55)) + (5 - 5/5)^5 \\
&:= 6 + ((6 + 6) \times ((6 + 6)/6)^6) \\
&:= 777 - (7 + 7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (88 + 8) - ((8 + 8)/8)) \\
&:= 9 \times 99 - (99 + 9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 775 &:= 1111 - ((1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 111)) \\
&:= 2 + (((2^{2+2} + 2/2)^2) + 22^2) \\
&:= 3333/3 - (333 + 3) \\
&:= 4 + ((4 - 4/4) \times (4/4 + 4^4)) \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) + 5) \\
&:= 66 \times (6 + 6) - ((66/6) + 6) \\
&:= 777 - (7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (88 + 8) - 8/8) \\
&:= ((9 - 9/9) \times (99 - 9/9)) - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 776 &:= (111 \times (1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)))) - 1 \\
&:= 2 \times (2 \times (((2^{2+2} - 2)^2) - 2)) \\
&:= 3 + ((3^{3+3} + 33/3) + 33) \\
&:= 4 + ((4 \times (4 \times (44 + 4))) + 4) \\
&:= 5/5 + (5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) + 5)) \\
&:= 666 + (666 - 6)/6 \\
&:= 777 - 7/7 \\
&:= 8 + 8 \times (88 + 8) \\
&:= (9 - 9/9) \times (99 - ((9 + 9)/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 777 &:= 111 \times (1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1))) \\
&:= 222/2 \times ((2/2 + 2 + 2) + 2) \\
&:= (3^3 \times (3^3 + 3)) - 33 \\
&:= (4 - 4/4) \times ((4^4 - 4/4) + 4) \\
&:= ((5 + 5)/5 + 5) \times 555/5 \\
&:= 666 + 666/6 \\
&:= 777 \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (88 + 8) + 8/8) \\
&:= (9 - ((9 + 9)/9)) \times 999/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 778 &:= 1 + (111 \times (1 + ((1+1) \times (1+1+1)))) \\
&:= (2 \times (22 - 2)^2) - 22 \\
&:= 3333/3 - 333 \\
&:= 4 + ((4 - 4/4) \times ((4+4)/4 + 4^4)) \\
&:= ((5^5 - 5)/(5 - 5/5)) - (5 + 5)/5 \\
&:= 666 + (666 + 6)/6 \\
&:= 7/7 + 777 \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (88 + 8) + ((8+8)/8)) \\
&:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((9 \times 99 - 9)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 779 &:= 1 + (1 + (111 \times (1 + ((1+1) \times (1+1+1)))) \\
&:= 2/2 + ((2 \times (22 - 2)^2) - 22) \\
&:= (33 \times 3^3) - ((333 + 3)/3) \\
&:= 44/4 + (4 \times (4 \times (44 + 4))) \\
&:= ((5^5 - 5)/(5 - 5/5)) - 5/5 \\
&:= 66 \times (6 + 6) - (6/6 + 6 + 6) \\
&:= ((7 + 7)/7) + 777 \\
&:= 88/8 + 8 \times (88 + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 99 - ((999 + 9)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 780 &:= (11 - 1) \times (111 - (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1))) \\
&:= 2 + ((2 \times (22 - 2)^2) - 22) \\
&:= (3^3 + 3) \times (3^3 - 3/3) \\
&:= (4 - 4/4) \times (4^4 + 4) \\
&:= (5^5 - 5)/(5 - 5/5) \\
&:= (6 + 6) \times (66 - 6/6) \\
&:= 777 + (7 + 7 + 7)/7 \\
&:= ((88 + 8)/8) + 8 \times (88 + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 99 - 999/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 781 &:= 11 \times (((1 + 11)^{1+1})/(1 + 1)) - 1 \\
&:= ((22 + 2 + 2 + 2)^2) - 2/2 - 2 \\
&:= 33/3 \times (((3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3) \\
&:= 4/4 + ((4 - 4/4) \times (4^4 + 4)) \\
&:= (5^5 - 5/5)/(5 - 5/5) \\
&:= 66 \times (6 + 6) - 66/6 \\
&:= 77/7 + (777 - 7) \\
&:= 88 + (8 \times 88 - (88/8)) \\
&:= 9 \times 99 + ((9 - 999)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 782 &:= 1 + (11 \times (((1 + 11)^{1+1})/(1 + 1)) - 1) \\
&:= ((22 + 2 + 2 + 2)^2) - 2 \\
&:= 3^3 + ((3^3 + 3 - 3/3) + 3^3) \\
&:= (4 + 4)/4 + ((4 - 4/4) \times (4^4 + 4)) \\
&:= 5 + (((5 + 5)/5 + 5) \times 555/5) \\
&:= ((6 - 66)/6) + 66 \times (6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + (777 - ((7 + 7)/7)) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times (88 + 8) - ((8 + 8)/8)) + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 99 - (9/9 + 99 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 783 &:= ((1 + ((1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1}))^{1+1}) - 1 \\
&:= ((22 + 2 + 2 + 2)^2) - 2/2 \\
&:= 3 \times (3 \times (3 \times 3^3 + 3 + 3)) \\
&:= (4 - 4/4) \times ((4/4 + 4^4) + 4) \\
&:= (((5 + 5)/5 + 5^5) + 5)/(5 - 5/5) \\
&:= 6 + (666/6 + 666) \\
&:= 7 + (777 - 7/7) \\
&:= (8/8 + 8) \times (88 - 8/8) \\
&:= 9 \times 99 - (99 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 784 &:= (1 + ((1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1}))^{1+1} \\
&:= (22 + 2 + 2 + 2)^2 \\
&:= (3^3 + 3/3)^{3-3/3} \\
&:= 4 \times ((4 \times (44 + 4)) + 4) \\
&:= (55/5 + 5^5)/(5 - 5/5) \\
&:= (6/6 + 6) \times (666 + 6)/6 \\
&:= 7 + 777 \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (88 + 8) + 8) \\
&:= (9 - 9/9) \times (99 - 9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 785 &:= 1 + ((1 + ((1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1}))^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2/2 + ((22 + 2 + 2 + 2)^2) \\
&:= 3/3 + ((3^3 + 3/3)^{3-3/3}) \\
&:= 4/4 + (4 \times ((4 \times (44 + 4)) + 4)) \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 - 5)/(5 - 5/5)) \\
&:= 66 \times (6 + 6) - 6/6 - 6 \\
&:= 7 + (777 + 7/7) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times (88 + 8) + 8/8) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + ((9 - 9/9) \times (99 - ((9 + 9)/9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 786 &:= 1 + (1 + ((1 + ((1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1}))^{1+1})) \\
&:= 2 + ((22 + 2 + 2 + 2)^2) \\
&:= (33 \times (3^3 - 3)) - (3 + 3) \\
&:= (4 + 4)/4 + (4 \times ((4 \times (44 + 4)) + 4)) \\
&:= 5 + ((5^5 - 5/5)/(5 - 5/5)) \\
&:= 66 \times (6 + 6) - 6 \\
&:= 7 + (((7 + 7)/7) + 777) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times (88 + 8) + ((8 + 8)/8)) + 8) \\
&:= 9 + ((9 - ((9 + 9)/9)) \times 999/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 787 &:= 111 + (((1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 11)))^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 + (((22 + 2 + 2 + 2)^2) + 2/2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3^3 + 3/3)^{3-3/3}) \\
&:= 4 + ((4 - 4/4) \times ((4/4 + 4^4) + 4)) \\
&:= 5 + (((5 + 5)/5 + 5) \times 555/5 + 5) \\
&:= 6/6 + (66 \times (6 + 6) - 6) \\
&:= 777 + (77 - 7)/7 \\
&:= 8 + (8 \times (88 + 8) + (88/8)) \\
&:= 9999/9 - (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 788 &:= 11 + (111 \times (1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)))) \\
&:= 2 + (((22 + 2 + 2 + 2)^2) + 2) \\
&:= (33 \times (3^3 - 3)) - (3/3 + 3) \\
&:= 4 + (4 \times ((4 \times (44 + 4)) + 4)) \\
&:= 5 + (((5 + 5)/5 + 5^5) + 5)/(5 - 5/5) \\
&:= (6 + 6)/6 + (66 \times (6 + 6) - 6) \\
&:= 77/7 + 777 \\
&:= 8 + (((88 + 8)/8) + 8 \times (88 + 8)) \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times 99 - ((999 + 9)/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 789 &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (((1 + 1) \times (11 \times (1 + 11))) - 1) \\
&:= (2 \times (22 - 2)^2) - 22/2 \\
&:= (33 \times (3^3 - 3)) - 3 \\
&:= 4 + ((4 \times ((4 \times (44 + 4)) + 4)) + 4/4) \\
&:= 5 + ((55/5 + 5^5)/(5 - 5/5)) \\
&:= 66 + (((6 \times 6)/(6 + 6))^6) - 6 \\
&:= 777 + (77 + 7)/7 \\
&:= 888 - (88/8 + 88) \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times 99 - 999/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 790 &:= (1 + 1) \times ((11 \times ((1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))) - 1) \\
&:= (22 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2) - 2 \\
&:= 3/3 + ((33 \times (3^3 - 3)) - 3) \\
&:= 4 + ((4 \times ((4 \times (44 + 4)) + 4)) + (4 + 4)/4) \\
&:= 5 + (((5^5 - 5)/(5 - 5/5)) + 5) \\
&:= 66 \times (6 + 6) - (6 + 6)/6 \\
&:= 7 + ((777 - 7/7) + 7) \\
&:= 88 + (8 \times 88 - ((8 + 8)/8)) \\
&:= 9 \times 99 - ((9 + 9)/9 + 99)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 791 &:= (11 \times (((1 + 11)^{1+1})/(1 + 1)) - 1) \\
&:= (22 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2) - 2/2 \\
&:= (33 \times (3^3 - 3)) - 3/3 \\
&:= 44/4 + ((4 - 4/4) \times (4^4 + 4)) \\
&:= 55 + ((555 + 5^5)/5) \\
&:= 66 \times (6 + 6) - 6/6 \\
&:= 7 + (777 + 7) \\
&:= 88 + (8 \times 88 - 8/8) \\
&:= 9 \times 99 - (9/9 + 99)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 792 &:= 11 \times (((1 + 11)^{1+1})/(1 + 1)) \\
&:= 22 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2 \\
&:= 33 \times (3^3 - 3) \\
&:= 44 \times ((4 + 4)/4 + 4 \times 4) \\
&:= 55 + (((555 + 5^5) + 5)/5) \\
&:= 66 \times (6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + ((777 + 7/7) + 7) \\
&:= 88 + 8 \times 88 \\
&:= 99 \times (9 - 9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 793 &:= 1 + (11 \times (((1+11)^{1+1})/(1+1))) \\
&:= 2/2 + (22 \times (2+2+2)^2) \\
&:= 3/3 + (33 \times (3^3 - 3)) \\
&:= 4/4 + (44 \times ((4+4)/4 + 4 \times 4)) \\
&:= 555 + (((5 - (5+5)/5)^5) - 5) \\
&:= 6/6 + 66 \times (6+6) \\
&:= 7 + (((7+7)/7) + 777) + 7 \\
&:= 8/8 + (8 \times 88 + 88) \\
&:= 9/9 + (99 \times (9 - 9/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 794 &:= 1 + (1 + (11 \times (((1+11)^{1+1})/(1+1)))) \\
&:= 2 + (22 \times (2+2+2)^2) \\
&:= 3 + ((33 \times (3^3 - 3)) - 3/3) \\
&:= 444 + (((4+4) \times 44) - (4+4)/4) \\
&:= (5 \times (5 \times ((5+5)/5)^5)) - (5/5+5) \\
&:= (6+6)/6 + 66 \times (6+6) \\
&:= 7 + (((77 - 7)/7) + 777) \\
&:= 88 + ((8+8)/8 + 8 \times 88) \\
&:= (9+9)/9 + (99 \times (9 - 9/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 795 &:= 11 + ((1 + ((1+1+1)^{1+1+1}))^{1+1}) \\
&:= (2 \times ((22 - 2)^2 - 2)) - 2/2 \\
&:= 3 + (33 \times (3^3 - 3)) \\
&:= 444 + (((4+4) \times 44) - 4/4) \\
&:= (55 + 5^5)/(5 - 5/5) \\
&:= 66 + ((6 \times 6)/(6+6))^6 \\
&:= 7 + (77/7 + 777) \\
&:= 8 + ((8 \times (88 + 8) + (88/8)) + 8) \\
&:= 9 \times 99 + (((9+9+9)/9) - 99)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 796 &:= (1+1) \times (((1+1) \times (11-1))^{1+1}) - (1+1) \\
&:= 2 \times ((22 - 2)^2 - 2) \\
&:= 3 + ((33 \times (3^3 - 3)) + 3/3) \\
&:= 444 + ((4+4) \times 44) \\
&:= 5 + (((555 + 5^5)/5) + 55) \\
&:= 6 + (66 \times (6+6) - ((6+6)/6)) \\
&:= 7 + ((77 + 7)/7 + 777) \\
&:= 88 + ((8/((8+8)/8)) + 8 \times 88) \\
&:= 9 + (9999/9 - (9+9) \times (9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 797 &:= ((11 \times (1 + ((1+11)^{1+1}))) - 1)/(1+1) \\
&:= 2/2 + (2 \times ((22 - 2)^2 - 2)) \\
&:= 3 + (((33 \times (3^3 - 3)) - 3/3) + 3) \\
&:= (4 \times 44) + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 4) \\
&:= 5 + (((555 + 5^5) + 5)/5) + 55 \\
&:= 6 + (66 \times (6+6) - 6/6) \\
&:= 7 + (((777 - 7/7) + 7) + 7) \\
&:= 8 + (888 - (88/8 + 88)) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) - ((99 + 9 + 9)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 798 &:= (1+1) \times (((1+1) \times (11-1))^{1+1}) - 1 \\
&:= (2 \times (22 - 2)^2) - 2 \\
&:= 3 + ((33 \times (3^3 - 3)) + 3) \\
&:= (4 - 4/4) \times ((44 - 4)/4 + 4^4) \\
&:= 555 + ((5 - (5+5)/5)^5) \\
&:= 6 + 66 \times (6+6) \\
&:= 7 + (777 + 7 + 7) \\
&:= 888 - ((8+8)/8 + 88) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) - (99 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 799 &:= ((1+1) \times (((1+1) \times (11-1))^{1+1})) - 1 \\
&:= (2 \times (22 - 2)^2) - 2/2 \\
&:= (3^3 \times (3^3 + 3)) - 33/3 \\
&:= ((4 \times 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4)) - 4/4 \\
&:= (5 \times (5 \times ((5+5)/5)^5)) - 5/5 \\
&:= 6 + (66 \times (6+6) + 6/6) \\
&:= 7 + (((777 + 7/7) + 7) + 7) \\
&:= 888 - (8/8 + 88) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) - 99/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 800 &:= (1+1) \times (((1+1) \times (11-1))^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 \times (22 - 2)^2 \\
&:= 3^{3+3} + (((3+3)^3 - 3)/3) \\
&:= (4 \times 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4) \\
&:= 5 \times (5 \times ((5+5)/5)^5) \\
&:= 6 + (66 \times (6+6) + ((6+6)/6)) \\
&:= 7 + (((((7+7)/7) + 777) + 7) + 7) \\
&:= 888 - 88 \\
&:= (9 - 9/9) \times (9/9 + 99)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 801 &:= 1 + ((1+1) \times (((1+1) \times (11-1))^{1+1})) \\
&:= 2/2 + (2 \times (22 - 2)^2) \\
&:= 3 \times ((3 \times (3 \times (3^3 + 3))) - 3) \\
&:= (4 \times 44) + (4/4 + 4)^4 \\
&:= 5/5 + (5 \times (5 \times ((5+5)/5)^5)) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 \times 6)/(6+6))^6) + 66 \\
&:= 7 + (((77 - 7)/7) + 777) + 7 \\
&:= 8/8 + (888 - 88) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 802 &:= (1+1) \times (1 + (((1+1) \times (11-1))^{1+1})) \\
&:= 2 + (2 \times (22 - 2)^2) \\
&:= 3^{3+3} + (((3+3)^3 + 3)/3) \\
&:= 4/4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 + (4 \times 44)) \\
&:= (5+5)/5 + (5 \times (5 \times ((5+5)/5)^5)) \\
&:= 66 \times (6+6) + (66 - 6)/6 \\
&:= 7 + ((77/7 + 777) + 7) \\
&:= 888 + (((8+8)/8) - 88) \\
&:= 9/9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 803 &:= 11 \times (1 + (((1+11)^{1+1})/(1+1))) \\
&:= 2 + ((2 \times (22 - 2)^2) + 2/2) \\
&:= 33/3 + (33 \times (3^3 - 3)) \\
&:= 4 + (((4 \times 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4)) - 4/4) \\
&:= 5 + (((5 - (5+5)/5)^5) + 555) \\
&:= 66/6 + 66 \times (6+6) \\
&:= 7 + (((77 + 7)/7 + 777) + 7) \\
&:= 88 + (88/8 + 8 \times 88) \\
&:= (9+9)/9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 804 &:= 1 + (11 \times (1 + (((1+11)^{1+1})/(1+1)))) \\
&:= 2 \times ((22 - 2)^2 + 2) \\
&:= (3^3 \times (3^3 + 3)) - (3+3) \\
&:= 4 + ((4 \times 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4)) \\
&:= 5 + ((5 \times (5 \times ((5+5)/5)^5)) - 5/5) \\
&:= 6 + (66 \times (6+6) + 6) \\
&:= 7 + (((777 - 7/7) + 7) + 7) + 7 \\
&:= 88 + (((88 + 8)/8) + 8 \times 88) \\
&:= 9 \times 99 + (((99 + 9)/9) - 99)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 805 &:= ((1+1)^{11}) - (11 \times (1 + (1 + 111))) \\
&:= 2/2 + (2 \times ((22 - 2)^2 + 2)) \\
&:= 3 + (((3+3)^3 + 3)/3) + 3^{3+3} \\
&:= 4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 + (4 \times 44)) \\
&:= 5 + (5 \times (5 \times ((5+5)/5)^5)) \\
&:= 6 + ((66 \times (6+6) + 6/6) + 6) \\
&:= 7 + (777 + 7 + 7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 + (8888/88) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) + ((9 - 99)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 806 &:= 1 + (((1+1)^{11}) - (11 \times (1 + (1 + 111)))) \\
&:= 2 + (2 \times ((22 - 2)^2 + 2)) \\
&:= (3^3 \times (3^3 + 3)) - (3/3 + 3) \\
&:= ((44 - 4)/4 \times (4 - 4/4)^4) - 4 \\
&:= 5 + ((5 \times (5 \times ((5+5)/5)^5)) + 5/5) \\
&:= 6 + ((66 \times (6+6) + ((6+6)/6)) + 6) \\
&:= 7 + (((777 + 7/7) + 7) + 7) + 7 \\
&:= 8 + (888 - ((8+8)/8 + 88)) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) + ((9 - 9 \times 9)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 807 &:= (1 + ((1+1) \times (11 \times (111 - 1))))/(1+1+1) \\
&:= 2 + ((2 \times ((22 - 2)^2 + 2)) + 2/2) \\
&:= (3^3 \times (3^3 + 3)) - 3 \\
&:= 4 + (((4 \times 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4)) - 4/4) + 4 \\
&:= 5 + ((5 \times (5 \times ((5+5)/5)^5)) + ((5+5)/5)) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 \times 6)/(6+6))^6) + 66 + 6 \\
&:= (7 \times 7 \times (7+7)) + (((7+7)/7)^7 - 7) \\
&:= 8 + (888 - (8/8 + 88)) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) - (9 + 9 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 808 &:= (1+1)^{1+1+1} \times (1+(11-1)^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 \times (((22-2)^2+2)+2) \\
&:= 3/3 + ((3^3 \times (3^3+3)) - 3) \\
&:= 4 + (((4 \times 4 + 4) \times (44-4)) + 4) \\
&:= 5 + (((5-5+5)/5)^5 + 555) + 5) \\
&:= 6 + (66 \times (6+6) + ((66-6)/6)) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 + (777 - (77/7 + 7)) \\
&:= 8 + (888 - 88) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) - (9+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 809 &:= ((11-1) \times (11-1-1)^{1+1}) - 1 \\
&:= 2/2 + (2 \times (((22-2)^2+2)+2)) \\
&:= (3^3 \times (3^3+3)) - 3/3 \\
&:= 4 + (((4/4+4)^4 + (4 \times 44)) + 4) \\
&:= (55 \times (5+5+5)) - (55/5+5) \\
&:= 6 + (66 \times (6+6) + (66/6)) \\
&:= 7 + (((77/7+777)+7)+7) \\
&:= 8 + ((888-88)+8/8) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) - 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 810 &:= (11-1) \times (11-1-1)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 + (2 \times (((22-2)^2+2)+2)) \\
&:= 3^3 \times (3^3+3) \\
&:= (44-4)/4 \times (4-4/4)^4 \\
&:= (5+5+5) \times (55-5/5) \\
&:= 6 + ((66 \times (6+6)+6)+6) \\
&:= (7-7/7) \times (((7+7)/7)^7 + 7) \\
&:= (8/8+8) \times ((8+8)/8+88) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 811 &:= 1 + (11-1) \times (11-1-1)^{1+1} \\
&:= 22/2 + (2 \times (22-2)^2) \\
&:= 3/3 + (3^3 \times (3^3+3)) \\
&:= 44 + (4 \times 4^4 - (4/4+4^4)) \\
&:= 5/5 + ((5+5+5) \times (55-5/5)) \\
&:= 6 + (((66 \times (6+6)+6/6)+6)+6) \\
&:= 77 + ((7 \times (7 \times (7+7)+7)) - 7/7) \\
&:= 888 + (88/8 - 88) \\
&:= 9/9 + 9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 812 &:= 1 + 1 + (11-1) \times (11-1-1)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 \times (((22-2)^2+2)+2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3^3 \times (3^3+3)) - 3/3) \\
&:= 44 + (4 \times (4 \times (44+4))) \\
&:= ((5+5)/5+5) \times (555/5+5) \\
&:= (6/6+6) \times (((666-6)/6)+6) \\
&:= 77 + (7 \times (7 \times (7+7)+7)) \\
&:= 888 + ((88+8)/8 - 88) \\
&:= (9+9)/9 + 9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 813 &:= ((1+1) \times (11 \times (111/(1+1+1)))) - 1 \\
&:= 2 + ((2 \times (22-2)^2) + 22/2) \\
&:= 3 + (3^3 \times (3^3+3)) \\
&:= 44 + ((4 \times (4 \times (44+4))) + 4/4) \\
&:= (55 \times (5+5+5)) - (55+5)/5 \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + (666/6 + 666) \\
&:= 7/7 + ((777 - (7+7)) + 7 \times 7) \\
&:= 888 - (88/8 + 8 \times 8) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) + ((9+9+9)/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 814 &:= (1+1) \times (11 \times (111/(1+1+1))) \\
&:= 22 + (22 \times (2+2+2)^2) \\
&:= 3 + ((3^3 \times (3^3+3)) + 3/3) \\
&:= 4 + ((44-4)/4 \times (4-4/4)^4) \\
&:= (55 \times (5+5+5)) - 55/5 \\
&:= (66/6) \times (((6+6)/6)+66)+6) \\
&:= (7 \times 7 \times (7+7)) + ((7+7)/7)^7 \\
&:= 8 \times 88 + ((888-8)/8) \\
&:= 99/9 \times (((9+9)/9) - 9) + 9 \times 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 815 &:= 1 + ((1+1) \times (11 \times (111/(1+1+1)))) \\
&:= 22/2 + (2 \times ((22-2)^2+2)) \\
&:= 3 + (((3^3 \times (3^3+3)) - 3/3) + 3) \\
&:= 4 \times 4 \times 44 + 444/4 \\
&:= (55 \times (5+5+5)) - 5-5 \\
&:= 6 + ((66 \times (6+6) + (66/6)) + 6) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 + (777 - (77/7)) \\
&:= 8 \times 88 + 888/8 \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) + ((9 \times 9 + 9)/(9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 816 &:= ((1+1)^{11}) - (11 \times (1+111)) \\
&:= 2 \times ((22-2)^2 + 2 \times (2+2)) \\
&:= 3 + ((3^3 \times (3^3+3)) + 3) \\
&:= 4 \times (4 \times (44-4) + 44) \\
&:= 5/5 + ((55 \times (5+5+5)) - (5+5)) \\
&:= (6+6) \times (((6+6)/6)+66) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 + (((7-77)/7) + 777) \\
&:= 888 - (8 \times 8 + 8) \\
&:= (9-9/9) \times (999/9-9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 817 &:= 1 + (((1+1)^{11}) - (11 \times (1+111))) \\
&:= ((22+2)^2) + (22^2 - 2)/2 \\
&:= 3 + (((3^3 \times (3^3+3)) + 3/3) + 3) \\
&:= (4 \times (44+4)) + (4/4+4)^4 \\
&:= 5 + (((5+5)/5+5) \times (555/5+5)) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + (66 \times (6+6) - (66/6)) \\
&:= 7 + ((7-7/7) \times (((7+7)/7)^7 + 7)) \\
&:= 8/8 + (888 - (8 \times 8 + 8)) \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) - ((9+9)/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 818 &:= 1 + (1 + (((1+1)^{11}) - (11 \times (1+111)))) \\
&:= 22 + (2 \times ((22-2)^2 - 2)) \\
&:= 3^3 + ((33 \times (3^3-3)) - 3/3) \\
&:= 4 + (((44-4)/4 \times (4-4/4)^4) + 4) \\
&:= (55 \times (5+5+5)) - ((5+5)/5+5) \\
&:= (6 - (((6+6)/6)^{6+6}))/((6/6-6)) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 + (777 - (7/7+7)) \\
&:= 8 + ((8/8+8) \times ((8+8)/8+88)) \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) - 9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 819 &:= 11^{1+1+1} - (1+1)^{11-1-1} \\
&:= ((22+2)^2) + (22^2+2)/2 \\
&:= 3 \times ((3 \times (3 \times (3^3+3))) + 3) \\
&:= (((4+4)^4) - 4/4)/(4/4+4) \\
&:= (55 \times (5+5+5)) - (5/5+5) \\
&:= (6/6+6) \times (666/6+6) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 + (777-7) \\
&:= 8 + ((888-88) + (88/8)) \\
&:= 9 + 9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 820 &:= (11-1) \times (1+(11-1-1)^{1+1}) \\
&:= 22 + ((2 \times (22-2)^2) - 2) \\
&:= 3^3 + ((33 \times (3^3-3)) + 3/3) \\
&:= (((4+4)^4) + 4)/(4/4+4) \\
&:= (55 \times (5+5+5)) - 5 \\
&:= 6 + (((66+66)/6) + 66 \times (6+6)) \\
&:= 7/7 + (777 - 7 + 7 \times 7) \\
&:= (((88/8-8)^8) - 8/8)/8 \\
&:= 9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) + 9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 821 &:= 1 + ((11-1) \times (1+(11-1-1)^{1+1})) \\
&:= 22 + ((2 \times (22-2)^2) - 2/2) \\
&:= 33/3 + (3^3 \times (3^3+3)) \\
&:= 4 + ((4 \times (44+4)) + (4/4+4)^4) \\
&:= 5/5 + ((55 \times (5+5+5)) - 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + (66 \times (6+6) - (6/6+6)) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times 7 \times (7+7)) + ((7+7)/7)^7) \\
&:= 8 \times (88+8+8) - 88/8 \\
&:= 99/9 + 9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 822 &:= (1+1) \times (11 + (((1+1) \times (11-1))^{1+1})) \\
&:= 22 + (2 \times (22-2)^2) \\
&:= 3 + ((33 \times (3^3-3)) + 3^3) \\
&:= (4+4)/4 + (((4+4)^4) + 4)/(4/4+4) \\
&:= (5+5)/5 + ((55 \times (5+5+5)) - 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 + (66 \times (6+6) - 6) \\
&:= 7 + ((777 - (77/7)) + 7 \times 7) \\
&:= 888 - (((8+8)/8) + 8 \times 8) \\
&:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) + (99+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 958 &:= 1 + (11 \times (111 - ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)))) \\
&:= (2 \times (22^2 - (2 + 2))) - 2 \\
&:= 3 + ((33 \times 3^3) + ((3/3 + 3)^3)) \\
&:= 4 \times 4^4 - (((4^4 + 4) + 4)/4) \\
&:= (5 - 5/5)^5 - (55/5 + 55) \\
&:= (((6 + 6)/6)^{(66-6)/6}) - 66 \\
&:= (77 \times 77 + 777)/7 \\
&:= (8 \times (8 \times (8 + 8) - 8)) - (8 + 8)/8 \\
&:= 9 + (9999/9 - 9 \times (9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 959 &:= ((1 + 1)^{11}) - ((11 \times (1 + 1 + 1))^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 + ((2 \times 22^2) - 22/2) \\
&:= ((3^3 + 3) \times (33 - 3/3)) - 3/3 \\
&:= 4 \times 4^4 - (4^4 + 4)/4 \\
&:= (5 - 5/5)^5 - (55 + 5 + 5) \\
&:= (6/6 + 6) \times ((66 - 6/6 + 66) + 6) \\
&:= 77 + 7 \times (77 + 7 \times 7) \\
&:= (8 \times (8 \times (8 + 8) - 8)) - 8/8 \\
&:= 999 + ((9 - 9 \times 9 \times 9)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 960 &:= (1 + 11) \times ((11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1} - 1) \\
&:= 2 \times (22^2 - (2 + 2)) \\
&:= (3^3 + 3) \times (33 - 3/3) \\
&:= 4 \times (4^4 - 4 \times 4) \\
&:= (5 \times 5 + 5) \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5 \\
&:= (6 - 66) \times (((6 - 66)/6) - 6) \\
&:= 7/7 + (7 \times (77 + 7 \times 7) + 77) \\
&:= 8 \times (8 \times (8 + 8) - 8) \\
&:= (9 - 9/9) \times (999/9 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 961 &:= (1 + ((11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)))^{1+1} \\
&:= ((2/2 + 2)^2 + 22)^2 \\
&:= ((3^3 + 3/3) + 3)^{3-3/3} \\
&:= 4/4 + (4 \times (4^4 - 4 \times 4)) \\
&:= ((5 \times 5 + 5/5) + 5)^{(5+5)/5} \\
&:= ((6 \times 6 - 6) + 6/6)^{(6+6)/6} \\
&:= (7 \times 7 - (77/7 + 7))^{(7+7)/7} \\
&:= 8/8 + (8 \times (8 \times (8 + 8) - 8)) \\
&:= (9 \times (99 + 9)) - 99/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 962 &:= 1 + ((1 + ((11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)))^{1+1}) \\
&:= (2 \times (22^2 - 2)) - 2 \\
&:= (33 \times 3^3) + (((3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3) \\
&:= (4 + 4)/4 + (4 \times (4^4 - 4 \times 4)) \\
&:= (5 \times 5 + 5/5) \times (((5 + 5)/5)^5 + 5) \\
&:= 6/6 + (((6 \times 6 - 6) + 6/6)^{(6+6)/6}) \\
&:= (7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) - (77/7 + 7) \\
&:= (8 + 8)/8 + (8 \times (8 \times (8 + 8) - 8)) \\
&:= (9 \times (99 + 9)) - 9/9 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 963 &:= 1 + (1 + ((1 + ((11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)))^{1+1})) \\
&:= (2 \times (22^2 - 2)) - 2/2 \\
&:= 3 \times (333 - (3 \times 3 + 3)) \\
&:= 4 + (4 \times 4^4 - (4^4 + 4)/4) \\
&:= (5 - 5/5)^5 - ((55 + 5/5) + 5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 \times 6 - 666 \times 6/(6 + 6) \\
&:= 7 + ((7 \times ((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7) + (77/7)) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 + (888 + 88/8) \\
&:= (9 \times (99 + 9)) - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 964 &:= (1 + 1) \times (((11 + 11)^{1+1}) - (1 + 1)) \\
&:= 2 \times (22^2 - 2) \\
&:= ((3 \times 3 + 3/3)^3) - (33 + 3) \\
&:= 4 + (4 \times (4^4 - 4 \times 4)) \\
&:= (5 - 5/5)^5 - (55 + 5) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 + 6)/6)^{(66-6)/6}) - 66 \\
&:= 7777/7 - 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7) \\
&:= 8 + ((88 \times 88 - (88 + 8))/8) \\
&:= 9/9 + ((9 \times (99 + 9)) - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 965 &:= ((1 + 1) \times (((11 + 11)^{1+1}) - 1)) - 1 \\
&:= 2/2 + (2 \times (22^2 - 2)) \\
&:= (3 \times 333) - (3/3 + 33) \\
&:= 4 + ((4 \times (4^4 - 4 \times 4)) + 4/4) \\
&:= 5 + ((5 \times 5 + 5) \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5) \\
&:= 66 + ((6 \times ((6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6)) - 6/6) \\
&:= 7 + ((77 \times 77 + 777)/7) \\
&:= 8 + (88/8 \times (88 - 8/8)) \\
&:= (9 + 9)/9 + ((9 \times (99 + 9)) - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 966 &:= (1 + 1) \times (((11 + 11)^{1+1}) - 1) \\
&:= (2 \times 22^2) - 2 \\
&:= (3 \times 333) - 33 \\
&:= (44 \times 44 - 4)/((4 + 4)/4) \\
&:= 5 + (((5 \times 5 + 5/5) + 5)^{(5+5)/5}) \\
&:= 66 + (6 \times ((6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6)) \\
&:= (7 + 7) \times (77 - (7/7 + 7)) \\
&:= (88 \times 88 - (8 + 8))/8 \\
&:= 999 - (99/((9 + 9 + 9)/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 967 &:= 1111 - ((1 + 11)^{1+1}) \\
&:= (2 \times 22^2) - 2/2 \\
&:= ((3 \times 3 + 3/3)^3) - 33 \\
&:= ((44 \times (44 + 44)) - 4)/4 \\
&:= (5 - 5/5)^5 - ((5 + 5)/5 + 55) \\
&:= 6 + (((6 \times 6 - 6) + 6/6)^{(6+6)/6}) \\
&:= 77 \times (7 + 7) - 777/7 \\
&:= (88 \times 88 - 8)/8 \\
&:= (9 \times (99 + 9)) + ((9 - 99)/(9 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 968 &:= (1 + 1) \times ((11 + 11)^{1+1}) \\
&:= 2 \times 22^2 \\
&:= (3/3 + 3) \times ((3^{3+3} - 3)/3) \\
&:= 4 + ((4 \times (4^4 - 4 \times 4)) + 4) \\
&:= (5 - 5/5)^5 - (55 + 5/5) \\
&:= (66/6) \times (((66 + 66)/6) + 66) \\
&:= (7/7 + 7) \times (((7 + 7)/7)^7 - 7) \\
&:= 88 \times (88/8) \\
&:= 99/9 \times (99 - (99/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 969 &:= 1 + ((1 + 1) \times ((11 + 11)^{1+1})) \\
&:= 2/2 + (2 \times 22^2) \\
&:= (3^3 \times (33 + 3)) - 3 \\
&:= 4 \times 4^4 - (44/4 + 44) \\
&:= (5 - 5/5)^5 - 55 \\
&:= (6 \times 6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6)) - 666/6 \\
&:= (7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) - 77/7 \\
&:= (88 \times 88 + 8)/8 \\
&:= (9 \times (99 + 9)) - (9 + 9 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 970 &:= (1 + 1) \times (1 + ((11 + 11)^{1+1})) \\
&:= 2 + (2 \times 22^2) \\
&:= 3 + (((3 \times 3 + 3/3)^3) - 33) \\
&:= (44 \times 44 + 4)/((4 + 4)/4) \\
&:= 5/5 + ((5 - 5/5)^5 - 55) \\
&:= ((6 - 666)/6) + (6 \times 6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6)) \\
&:= ((7 - 77)/7) + (7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) \\
&:= ((88 \times 88 + 8) + 8)/8 \\
&:= (9 \times (99 + 9)) - (9 + 9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 971 &:= 1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + ((11 + 11)^{1+1}))) \\
&:= 2 + ((2 \times 22^2) + 2/2) \\
&:= (3^3 \times (33 + 3)) - 3/3 \\
&:= 44/4 + (4 \times (4^4 - 4 \times 4)) \\
&:= ((5 - 5/5)^{5/5+5}) - 5^5 \\
&:= ((6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - (6 + 6))) - 6/6 \\
&:= (7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) - ((7 + 7)/7 + 7) \\
&:= 88/8 + (8 \times (8 \times (8 + 8) - 8)) \\
&:= (9 \times (99 + 9)) - 9/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 972 &:= (1 + 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1} \\
&:= 2 \times (22^2 + 2) \\
&:= 3^3 \times (33 + 3) \\
&:= 4 \times ((4 - 4/4)^{4+4/4}) \\
&:= (5 - 5/5) \times ((5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5) \\
&:= (6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - (6 + 6)) \\
&:= (7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) - (7/7 + 7) \\
&:= 88 + (888 - (8/((8 + 8)/8))) \\
&:= 9 \times (99 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 973 &:= 1 + ((1 + 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1))^{1+1} \\ &:= 2/2 + (2 \times (22^2 + 2)) \\ &:= 3/3 + (3^3 \times (33 + 3)) \\ &:= 4 + (4 \times 4^4 - (44/4 + 44)) \\ &:= 5 + ((5 - 5/5)^5 - (55 + 5/5)) \\ &:= 6/6 + ((6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - (6 + 6))) \\ &:= (7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) - 7 \\ &:= 8 + ((88/8 \times (88 - 8/8)) + 8) \\ &:= 9/9 + (9 \times (99 + 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 974 &:= 1 + (1 + ((1 + 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1))^{1+1}) \\ &:= 2 + (2 \times (22^2 + 2)) \\ &:= 3 + ((3^3 \times (33 + 3)) - 3/3) \\ &:= 4 + ((44 \times 44 + 4)/(4 + 4)/4) \\ &:= 5 + ((5 - 5/5)^5 - 55) \\ &:= (6 + 6)/6 + ((6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - (6 + 6))) \\ &:= 7/7 + ((7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) - 7) \\ &:= 8 + ((88 \times 88 - (8 + 8))/8) \\ &:= (9 + 9)/9 + (9 \times (99 + 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 975 &:= 111 + (((1 + 11))^{1+1+1})/(1 + 1) \\ &:= 2 + ((2 \times (22^2 + 2)) + 2/2) \\ &:= 3 + (3^3 \times (33 + 3)) \\ &:= 4 \times 4^4 - ((44 + 4/4) + 4) \\ &:= 5 \times ((5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5)) - 55) \\ &:= 666/6 + (6 \times (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)) \\ &:= 7 + ((7/7 + 7) \times (((7 + 7)/7)^7 - 7)) \\ &:= 8 + ((88 \times 88 - 8)/8) \\ &:= (9 \times (99 + 9)) + ((9 + 9 + 9)/9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 976 &:= (1 + 1)^{1+1+1} \times (1 + 11)^{1+1} \\ &:= 2 \times (22^2 + 2 + 2) \\ &:= 3 + ((3^3 \times (33 + 3)) + 3/3) \\ &:= 4 \times ((4^4 - 4 \times 4) + 4) \\ &:= 5 + (((5 - 5/5)^{5/5+5}) - 5^5) \\ &:= ((6 + 6)/6 + 6) \times ((666 + 66)/6) \\ &:= 7 + ((7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) - (77/7)) \\ &:= 88 + 888 \\ &:= 999 - ((99 + 99 + 9)/9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 977 &:= 1 + (1 + 1)^{1+1+1} \times (1 + 11)^{1+1} \\ &:= 2/2 + (2 \times (22^2 + 2 + 2)) \\ &:= 3 + (((3^3 \times (33 + 3)) - 3/3) + 3) \\ &:= 4/4 + (4 \times ((4^4 - 4 \times 4) + 4)) \\ &:= 5 + ((5 - 5/5) \times ((5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5)) \\ &:= 6 + (((6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - (6 + 6))) - 6/6) \\ &:= (7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) - (7 + 7 + 7)/7 \\ &:= 8 + ((88 \times 88 + 8)/8) \\ &:= 999 - ((99 + 99)/9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 978 &:= 1111 - (1 + 11 \times (1 + 11)) \\ &:= 2 + (2 \times (22^2 + 2 + 2)) \\ &:= 3 + ((3^3 \times (33 + 3)) + 3) \\ &:= 4 \times 4^4 - ((4 + 4)/4 + 44) \\ &:= 5 + (((5 - 5/5)^5 - (55 + 5/5)) + 5) \\ &:= 6 + ((6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - (6 + 6))) \\ &:= (7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) - (7 + 7)/7 \\ &:= 8 + (((88 \times 88 + 8) + 8)/8) \\ &:= 999 - (((99 + 9)/9) + 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 979 &:= 11 \times (111 - 11 - 11) \\ &:= 22/2 + (2 \times 22^2) \\ &:= (3 \times (333 - 3)) - 33/3 \\ &:= 4 \times 4^4 - (44 + 4/4) \\ &:= 5 + (((5 - 5/5)^5 - 55) + 5) \\ &:= (6666/6) - (66 + 66) \\ &:= (7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) - 7/7 \\ &:= 88/8 \times (8/8 + 88) \\ &:= 999 - (99/9 + 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 980 &:= 1 + 11 \times (111 - 11 - 11) \\ &:= 2 \times ((22^2 + 2 + 2) + 2) \\ &:= (3 \times (333 - (3 + 3))) - 3/3 \\ &:= 4 \times 4^4 - 44 \\ &:= 5 + (5 \times ((5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5)) - 55)) \\ &:= (6 \times 6 - 6/6) \times (((66 + 66)/6) + 6) \\ &:= (7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) \\ &:= ((88 \times 88 + 88) + 8)/8 \\ &:= 9 + ((9 \times (99 + 9)) - 9/9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 981 &:= (11 - 1 - 1) \times (111 - 1 - 1) \\ &:= 2 + ((2 \times 22^2) + 22/2) \\ &:= 3 \times (333 - (3 + 3)) \\ &:= 4/4 + (4 \times 4^4 - 44) \\ &:= (5555/5) - (5 \times 5 \times 5 + 5) \\ &:= 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) + ((6 \times 6)/(6 + 6))^6 \\ &:= 7/7 + (7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) \\ &:= (8/8 + 8) \times ((888 - (8 + 8))/8) \\ &:= 9 + (9 \times (99 + 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 982 &:= 1 + (11 - 1 - 1) \times (111 - 1 - 1) \\ &:= 2 + (2 \times ((22^2 + 2 + 2) + 2)) \\ &:= 3/3 + (3 \times (333 - (3 + 3))) \\ &:= (4 + 4)/4 + (4 \times 4^4 - 44) \\ &:= 5 + (((5 - 5/5) \times ((5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5)) + 5) \\ &:= (((6 + 6)/6)^{(66-6)/6}) - (6 \times 6 + 6) \\ &:= ((7 + 7)/7) + (7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) \\ &:= 8 + (((88 \times 88 - (8 + 8))/8) + 8) \\ &:= 9 + ((9 \times (99 + 9)) + 9/9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 983 &:= 1 + 1 + (11 - 1 - 1) \times (111 - 1 - 1) \\ &:= 22/2 + (2 \times (22^2 + 2)) \\ &:= 33/3 + (3^3 \times (33 + 3)) \\ &:= 4 + 4 \times 4^4 - (44 + 4/4) \\ &:= (5 - 5/5)^5 - ((55/5 + 5 \times 5) + 5) \\ &:= 66/6 + ((6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - (6 + 6))) \\ &:= ((7 + 7 + 7)/7) + (7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) \\ &:= 8 + (((88 \times 88 - 8)/8) + 8) \\ &:= 99/9 + (9 \times (99 + 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 984 &:= (1 + 11) \times (1 + (11 - 1 - 1))^{1+1} \\ &:= 2 \times (2 \times (2 + 2) + 22^2) \\ &:= 3 + (3 \times (333 - (3 + 3))) \\ &:= 4 + (4 \times 4^4 - 44) \\ &:= 5 + (((5 - 5/5)^5 - 55) + 5) + 5) \\ &:= 6 + (((6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - (6 + 6))) + 6) \\ &:= 77/7 + ((7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) - 7) \\ &:= 8 + (888 + 88) \\ &:= (9 \times (99 + 9)) + (99 + 9)/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 985 &:= 1 + (1 + 11) \times (1 + (11 - 1 - 1))^{1+1} \\ &:= 2 + ((2 \times (22^2 + 2)) + 22/2) \\ &:= (3 \times 333) - (33/3 + 3) \\ &:= 4 + ((4 \times 4^4 - 44) + 4/4) \\ &:= 5 + ((5 \times ((5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5)) - 55)) + 5) \\ &:= 6 + ((6666/6) - (66 + 66)) \\ &:= 7 + ((7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) - ((7 + 7)/7)) \\ &:= 8 + (((88 \times 88 + 8)/8) + 8) \\ &:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^{9-9/9}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 986 &:= (11 - 1)^{1+1+1} - 1 - 1 - 1 - 11 \\ &:= 22 + (2 \times (22^2 - 2)) \\ &:= (3 \times (333 - 3)) - (3/3 + 3) \\ &:= 4 + (((4 + 4)/4 - 44) + 4 \times 4^4) \\ &:= (5555/5) - 5 \times 5 \times 5 \\ &:= ((66/6) + 6) \times (((6 + 6)/6)^6 - 6) \\ &:= 7 + ((7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) - 7/7) \\ &:= 8 + (((88 \times 88 + 8)/8) + 8) \\ &:= 999 - ((99 + 9 + 9)/9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 987 &:= (11 - 1)^{1+1+1} - 1 - 1 - 11 \\ &:= 22 + ((2 \times (22^2 - 2)) + 2/2) \\ &:= (3 \times (333 - 3)) - 3 \\ &:= (4 \times (4^4 - 4 - 4)) - (4/4 + 4) \\ &:= (5 - 5/5)^5 - (((5 + 5)/5)^5 + 5) \\ &:= ((66 \times (6 \times 6 - 6)) - 6)/(6 + 6)/6 \\ &:= 7 + (7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) \\ &:= 8 + (88/8 \times (8/8 + 88)) \\ &:= 999 - (99 + 9)/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 988 &:= (11-1)^{1+1+1} - 1 - 11 \\
 &:= 22 + ((2 \times 22^2) - 2) \\
 &:= (3 \times 333) - 33/3 \\
 &:= (4 \times (4^4 - 4 - 4)) - 4 \\
 &:= (5 - 5/5)^5 - (55/5 + 5 \times 5) \\
 &:= (((6+6)/6)^{(66-6)/6}) - 6 \times 6 \\
 &:= 7 + ((7+7) \times (77-7) + 7/7) \\
 &:= 8 + (((88 \times 88 + 88) + 8)/8) \\
 &:= 999 - 99/9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 989 &:= (11-1)^{1+1+1} - 11 \\
 &:= 22 + ((2 \times 22^2) - 2/2) \\
 &:= (3 \times (333 - 3)) - 3/3 \\
 &:= 4/4 + ((4 \times (4^4 - 4 - 4)) - 4) \\
 &:= (5 - 5/5)^5 - ((5 \times 5 + 5) + 5) \\
 &:= 666 + ((6 \times (66 - (6 + 6))) - 6/6) \\
 &:= 7 + ((7+7) \times (77-7) + ((7+7)/7)) \\
 &:= 888 + (8888/88) \\
 &:= 999 - 9/9 - 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 990 &:= (11-1-1) \times (111-1) \\
 &:= 22 + (2 \times 22^2) \\
 &:= 3 \times (333 - 3) \\
 &:= (4 \times (4^4 - 4 - 4)) - (4 + 4)/4 \\
 &:= (5 + 5) \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5/5) \\
 &:= 6 \times ((66 \times (6 \times 6 - 6))/6 + 6) \\
 &:= 77/7 \times ((77 - 7/7 + 7) + 7) \\
 &:= 88/8 \times ((8 + 8)/8 + 88) \\
 &:= 999 - 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 991 &:= 1 + (11-1-1) \times (111-1) \\
 &:= 22 + ((2 \times 22^2) + 2/2) \\
 &:= 3/3 + (3 \times (333 - 3)) \\
 &:= (4 \times (4^4 - 4 - 4)) - 4/4 \\
 &:= 5 + ((5555/5) - 5 \times 5 \times 5) \\
 &:= 6/6 + ((6 \times (66 - (6 + 6))) + 666) \\
 &:= 77/7 + (7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) \\
 &:= 888 + (888/8 - 8) \\
 &:= 9/9 + (999 - 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 992 &:= 1 + 1 + (11-1-1) \times (111-1) \\
 &:= 2 + ((2 \times 22^2) + 22) \\
 &:= 3 + ((3 \times (333 - 3)) - 3/3) \\
 &:= 4 \times (4^4 - 4 - 4) \\
 &:= (5 - 5/5)^5 - ((5 + 5)/5)^5 \\
 &:= 6 + (((66/6) + 6) \times (((6+6)/6)^6 - 6)) \\
 &:= (77 + 7)/7 + (7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) \\
 &:= 8 + ((888 + 88) + 8) \\
 &:= (9 + 9)/9 + (999 - 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 993 &:= 1 + 1 + 1 + (11-1-1) \times (111-1) \\
 &:= 2 + (((2 \times 22^2) + 22) + 2/2) \\
 &:= 3 + (3 \times (333 - 3)) \\
 &:= 4/4 + (4 \times (4^4 - 4 - 4)) \\
 &:= (5 - 5/5)^5 - ((5 \times 5 + 5/5) + 5) \\
 &:= ((66 \times (6 \times 6 - 6)) + 6)/((6+6)/6) \\
 &:= 7 + (((7+7) \times (77-7) - 7/7) + 7) \\
 &:= 8 + (((88 \times 88 + 8)/8) + 8) + 8 \\
 &:= 999 + (((9+9+9)/9) - 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 994 &:= (1+1)^{11-1} - (11-1) \times (1+1+1) \\
 &:= 22 + (2 \times (22^2 + 2)) \\
 &:= ((3 \times 3 + 3/3)^3) - (3 + 3) \\
 &:= (4 + 4)/4 + (4 \times (4^4 - 4 - 4)) \\
 &:= (5 - 5/5)^5 - (5 \times 5 + 5) \\
 &:= (((66 - 6)/6)^{6 \times 6/(6+6)}) - 6 \\
 &:= 7 + ((7+7) \times (77-7) + 7) \\
 &:= 8 + (((88 \times 88 + 8)/8) + 8) + 8 \\
 &:= 999 + ((9 - 99)/(9 + 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 995 &:= (11-1)^{1+1+1} - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 \\
 &:= 22 + ((2 \times (22^2 + 2)) + 2/2) \\
 &:= (3 \times 333) - (3/3 + 3) \\
 &:= 4 + ((4 \times (4^4 - 4 - 4)) - 4/4) \\
 &:= (5 \times (5 + 5)) \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5 \\
 &:= 666 + (6 \times 66 - (66 + 6/6)) \\
 &:= 7 + (((7+7) \times (77-7) + 7/7) + 7) \\
 &:= 8 + ((88/8 \times (8/8 + 88)) + 8) \\
 &:= 999 + ((9 - 9 \times 9)/(9 + 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 996 &:= (1+1+1) \times ((1+1+1) \times 111 - 1) \\
 &:= 2 + ((2 \times (22^2 + 2)) + 22) \\
 &:= (3 \times 333) - 3 \\
 &:= 4 + (4 \times (4^4 - 4 - 4)) \\
 &:= 5/5 + ((5 \times (5 + 5)) \times (5 \times 5 - 5)) - 5 \\
 &:= (6 + 6) \times (66/6 + 66 + 6) \\
 &:= (77 + 7)/7 \times (77 - 7/7 + 7) \\
 &:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + 88 \times 88/(8 + 8) \\
 &:= 999 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 997 &:= (11-1)^{1+1+1} - (1+1+1) \\
 &:= ((2/2 + 2)^2 \times 222/2) - 2 \\
 &:= ((3 \times 3 + 3/3)^3) - 3 \\
 &:= (4 \times (4^4 - 4)) - 44/4 \\
 &:= 5 + ((5 - 5/5)^5 - ((5 + 5)/5)^5) \\
 &:= 6 \times 6 + (((6 \times 6 - 6) + 6/6)^{(6+6)/6}) \\
 &:= (((77 + 7)^{(7+7)/7}) - 77)/7 \\
 &:= 888 + ((888 - (8 + 8))/8) \\
 &:= 999 - (9 + 9)/9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 998 &:= (11-1)^{1+1+1} - 1 - 1 \\
 &:= 22 + (2 \times (22^2 + 2 + 2)) \\
 &:= (3 \times 333) - 3/3 \\
 &:= (4 \times (4^4 - 4)) + (4 - 44)/4 \\
 &:= (5 - 5/5)^5 - (5 \times 5 + 5/5) \\
 &:= 666 + (6 \times 66 - ((6+6)/6)^6) \\
 &:= 7 + ((7+7) \times (77-7) + (77/7)) \\
 &:= 888 + ((888 - 8)/8) \\
 &:= 999 - 9/9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 999 &:= 111 \times (11-1-1) \\
 &:= (2/2 + 2)^2 \times 222/2 \\
 &:= 3 \times 333 \\
 &:= ((4/4 + 4) + 4) \times 444/4 \\
 &:= (5 - 5/5)^5 - 5 \times 5 \\
 &:= (6 \times 666)/(6 - ((6+6)/6)) \\
 &:= ((7+7)/7 + 7) \times 777/7 \\
 &:= 888 + 888/8 \\
 &:= 999
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 1000 &:= (11-1)^{1+1+1} \\
 &:= 2 \times (2^{2+2} + 22^2) \\
 &:= (3 \times 3 + 3/3)^3 \\
 &:= (4 \times (4^4 - 4)) - 4 - 4 \\
 &:= 5 \times (5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5) \\
 &:= ((66 - 6)/6)^{6 \times 6/(6+6)} \\
 &:= ((77 - 7)/7)^{(7+7+7)/7} \\
 &:= 8 \times 8 \times (8 + 8) - 8 - 8 - 8 \\
 &:= 9/9 + 999
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 1001 &:= 1 + (11-1)^{1+1+1} \\
 &:= ((2^{22/2} - 2)/2) - 22 \\
 &:= 3 + (3 \times 333 - 3/3) \\
 &:= 4 + (4 \times (4^4 - 4) - 44/4) \\
 &:= 5/5 + 5 \times (5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5) \\
 &:= (6/6 + 6) \times ((6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) - 6/6) \\
 &:= 77 \times (7 - 7/7 + 7) \\
 &:= 8/8 + (8 \times 8 \times (8 + 8) - (8 + 8 + 8)) \\
 &:= (9 + 9)/9 + 999
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 1002 &:= 1 + 1 + (11-1)^{1+1+1} \\
 &:= 2^{2 \times (2+2)+2} - 22 \\
 &:= 3 + 3 \times 333 \\
 &:= 4 \times 4^4 - (44/((4+4)/4)) \\
 &:= (5 + 5)/5 + 5 \times (5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5) \\
 &:= 66 + ((6 + 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6)) \\
 &:= 7/7 + 77 \times (7 - 7/7 + 7) \\
 &:= ((8 + 8)/8) \times (8 \times 8 \times 8 - 88/8) \\
 &:= 999 + ((9 + 9 + 9)/9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 1003 &:= 1+1+1+(11-1)^{1+1+1} \\
&:= (2^{2^{2/2}}+2)/2-22 \\
&:= 3+(3 \times 3+3/3)^3 \\
&:= 4 \times (4^4-4)-(4/4+4) \\
&:= 5+((5-5/5)^5-(5 \times 5+5/5)) \\
&:= (66/6+6) \times (66-(6/6+6)) \\
&:= ((7+7)/7)+77 \times (7-7/7+7) \\
&:= 8+((88/8 \times (8/8+88)+8)+8) \\
&:= 999+((9 \times 9-9)/(9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 1004 &:= 1+1+1+1+(11-1)^{1+1+1} \\
&:= 2+2^{2 \times (2+2)+2}-22 \\
&:= 3+(3 \times 333-3/3)+3 \\
&:= 4 \times (4^4-4)-4 \\
&:= 5+((5-5/5)^5-5 \times 5) \\
&:= (6-((6+6)/6)) \times (6 \times (6 \times 6+6)-6/6) \\
&:= 7+(((77+7)^{(7+7)/7})-77)/7 \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times (8+8)-((88+8)/8+8) \\
&:= 999+((9 \times 9+9)/(9+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 1005 &:= 1+1+1+1+1+(11-1)^{1+1+1} \\
&:= (2+2^{2^{2/2}}+2)/2-22 \\
&:= 3+(3 \times 333+3) \\
&:= 4/4+(4 \times (4^4-4)-4) \\
&:= 5+5 \times (5+5) \times (5 \times 5-5) \\
&:= 6+(((66-6)/6)/(6-((6+6)/6))) \\
&:= 7+(((7+7) \times (77-7)+(77/7))+7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times (8+8)-(88/8+8) \\
&:= 9+(999-((9+9+9)/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 1006 &:= (11-1-1) \times (1+111)-1-1 \\
&:= (2 \times ((22^2-2)+22))-2 \\
&:= 3+(((3 \times 3+3/3)^3)+3) \\
&:= 4 \times (4^4-4)-(4+4)/4 \\
&:= 5+(5 \times (5+5) \times (5 \times 5-5)+5/5) \\
&:= 6+(((66-6)/6)^{6 \times 6/(6+6)}) \\
&:= 7+(((7+7)/7+7) \times 777/7) \\
&:= 8+((888-8)/8+888) \\
&:= 9+(999-((9+9)/9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 1007 &:= (11-1-1) \times (1+111)-1 \\
&:= (2^{2^{2/2}}-2)/2-2^{2+2} \\
&:= (3 \times (333+3))-3/3 \\
&:= 4 \times (4^4-4)-4/4 \\
&:= (5-5/5)^5-(((55+5)/5)+5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6+(66 \times (6+6)-6/6) \\
&:= (((77+7)^{(7+7)/7})-7)/7 \\
&:= 8+(888/8+888) \\
&:= 9+(999-9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 1008 &:= (11-1-1) \times (1+111) \\
&:= 2 \times (22^2-2+22) \\
&:= 3 \times (333+3) \\
&:= 4 \times (4^4-4) \\
&:= (5-5/5)^5-(55/5+5) \\
&:= 6 \times ((6 \times 6+66)+66) \\
&:= 7+77 \times (7-7/7+7) \\
&:= (8+8) \times (8 \times 8-8/8) \\
&:= 9+999
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 1009 &:= 1+(11-1-1) \times (1+111) \\
&:= 2/2+2 \times (22^2-2+22) \\
&:= 3 \times 3+((3 \times 3+3/3)^3) \\
&:= 4/4+4 \times (4^4-4) \\
&:= (5-5/5)^5-(5+5+5) \\
&:= 6/6+(66 \times (6+6)+6 \times 6 \times 6) \\
&:= (((77+7)^{(7+7)/7})+7)/7 \\
&:= 8/8+((8+8) \times (8 \times 8-8/8)) \\
&:= 9+(999+9/9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 1010 &:= (11111-1)/11 \\
&:= 2 \times (22^2+22)-2 \\
&:= 33/3+3 \times 333 \\
&:= (4+4)/4+4 \times (4^4-4) \\
&:= 5+(5 \times (5+5) \times (5 \times 5-5)+5) \\
&:= 6 \times 6 \times 6+(66 \times (6+6)+((6+6)/6)) \\
&:= ((7+7)/7)^7+7 \times (77+7 \times 7) \\
&:= 888+((888+88)/8) \\
&:= 99/9+999
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 1011 &:= 11+(11-1)^{1+1+1} \\
&:= 2 \times (22^2+22)-2/2 \\
&:= 3+(3 \times (333+3)) \\
&:= 4+(4 \times (4^4-4)-4/4) \\
&:= 5 \times 55+(555+5^5)/5 \\
&:= 6+(((66-6)/6)/(6-((6+6)/6)))+6) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times (7+7+7)-(77/7+7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times (8+8)-(88+8+8)/8 \\
&:= 999+(99+9)/9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 1012 &:= (1+1)^{11-1}-1-11 \\
&:= 2 \times (22^2+22) \\
&:= 3+(3 \times (333+3)+3/3) \\
&:= 4+4 \times (4^4-4) \\
&:= (5-5/5)^5-(55+5)/5 \\
&:= (((6+6)/6)^{(66-6)/6})-6-6 \\
&:= 77/7+77 \times (7-7/7+7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times (8+8)-(88+8)/8 \\
&:= 9999/9-99
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 1013 &:= (1+1)^{11-1}-11 \\
&:= (2^{2^{2/2}}-22)/2 \\
&:= 3+(3 \times 333+33/3) \\
&:= 4 \times 4^4-44/4 \\
&:= (5-5/5)^5-55/5 \\
&:= (6 \times 6 \times (6 \times 6-6))-(66+6/6) \\
&:= 7777/7-7 \times (7+7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times (8+8)-88/8 \\
&:= (9999+9)/9-99
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 1014 &:= 1+(1+1)^{11-1}-11 \\
&:= 2+2 \times (22^2+22) \\
&:= 3+(3 \times (333+3)+3) \\
&:= 4 \times 4^4+(4-44)/4 \\
&:= (5-5/5)^5-5-5 \\
&:= (6 \times 6 \times (6 \times 6-6))-66 \\
&:= (7-7/7+7) \times (7/7+77) \\
&:= (8-88)/8+8 \times 8 \times (8+8) \\
&:= 9+((999-((9+9+9)/9))+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 1015 &:= 1+1+(1+1)^{11-1}-11 \\
&:= 2+(2^{2^{2/2}}-22)/2 \\
&:= 3+((3 \times (333+3)+3/3)+3) \\
&:= 4 \times 4^4-((4/4+4)+4) \\
&:= 5 \times (((5^5-5)/(5+5+5))-5) \\
&:= 6/6+((6 \times 6 \times (6 \times 6-6))-66) \\
&:= 7 \times 7 \times (7+7+7)-(7+7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times (8+8)-(8/8+8) \\
&:= (((9+9)/9)^{9/9+9})-9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 1016 &:= 1+1+1+(1+1)^{11-1}-11 \\
&:= 2 \times (22^2+22+2) \\
&:= (3 \times ((333+3)+3))-3/3 \\
&:= 4 \times 4^4-4-4 \\
&:= (5+5)/5+((5-5/5)^5-(5+5)) \\
&:= (6 \times 6 \times (6 \times 6-6))-((6+6)/6)^6 \\
&:= 7+(((77+7)^{(7+7)/7})+7)/7) \\
&:= 8 \times 8 \times (8+8)-8 \\
&:= 9+(999-9/9)+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright 1017 &:= (11-1-1) \times (1+1+111) \\
&:= 2+(2^{2^{2/2}}-22)/2+2 \\
&:= 3 \times ((333+3)+3) \\
&:= 4+(4 \times 4^4-44/4) \\
&:= (5-5/5)^5-((5+5)/5+5) \\
&:= 6 \times (6 \times 6+6+6)+((6 \times 6)/(6+6))^6) \\
&:= (((7/7+7) \times ((7+7)/7)^7)-7) \\
&:= 8/8+(8 \times 8 \times (8+8)-8) \\
&:= 9+(999+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 1018 &:= ((1+1)^{11} - (1+11))/(1+1) \\
 &:= 2 + (2 \times ((2^{2^2} + 22) + 2)) \\
 &:= 3/3 + (3 \times ((333+3) + 3)) \\
 &:= 4 \times 4^4 - ((4+4)/4+4) \\
 &:= (5-5/5)^5 - (5/5+5) \\
 &:= (((6+6)/6)^{(66-6)/6} - 6) \\
 &:= 7 \times 7 \times (7+7+7) - 77/7 \\
 &:= (8+8)/8 + (8 \times 8 \times (8+8) - 8) \\
 &:= 9 + ((999+9/9) + 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 1019 &:= (1 + (1+1)^{11} - 11)/(1+1) \\
 &:= ((2^{2^2/2} - 2)/2) - 2 - 2 \\
 &:= 33/3 + (3 \times (333+3)) \\
 &:= 4 \times 4^4 - (4/4+4) \\
 &:= (5-5/5)^5 - 5 \\
 &:= ((66-6) \times (66/6+6)) - 6/6 \\
 &:= ((7-77)/7) + 7 \times 7 \times (7+7+7) \\
 &:= 88/8 + ((8+8) \times (8 \times 8 - 8/8)) \\
 &:= 9 + (99/9 + 999)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 1020 &:= (1+1)^{11-1} - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 \\
 &:= 2 \times ((2^{(2/2+2)^2}) - 2) \\
 &:= 3 + (3 \times ((333+3) + 3)) \\
 &:= 4 \times 4^4 - 4 \\
 &:= 5/5 + ((5-5/5)^5 - 5) \\
 &:= (66-6) \times (66/6+6) \\
 &:= 7 + (7777/7 - 7 \times (7+7)) \\
 &:= 8 \times 8 \times (8+8) - (8/((8+8)/8)) \\
 &:= 9 + (((99+9)/9) + 999)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 1021 &:= (1+1)^{11-1} - 1 - 1 - 1 \\
 &:= ((2^{2^2/2} - 2)/2) - 2 \\
 &:= ((3-3/3)^{3 \times 3 + 3/3}) - 3 \\
 &:= 4/4 + (4 \times 4^4 - 4) \\
 &:= (5+5)/5 + ((5-5/5)^5 - 5) \\
 &:= 6/6 + ((66-6) \times (66/6+6)) \\
 &:= 7 \times 7 \times (7+7+7) - (7/7+7) \\
 &:= 8 + (8 \times 8 \times (8+8) - (88/8)) \\
 &:= 9 + (9999/9 - 99)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 1022 &:= (1+1)^{11-1} - 1 - 1 \\
 &:= (2^{2 \times (2+2)+2}) - 2 \\
 &:= 3 + (3 \times (333+3) + 33/3) \\
 &:= 4 \times 4^4 - (4+4)/4 \\
 &:= (5-5/5)^5 - (5+5)/5 \\
 &:= 6 + ((6 \times 6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6)) - ((6+6)/6)^6) \\
 &:= 7 \times 7 \times (7+7+7) - 7 \\
 &:= 8 \times 8 \times (8+8) - (8+8)/8 \\
 &:= 9 + ((9999+9)/9 - 99)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 1023 &:= (1+1)^{11-1} - 1 \\
 &:= (2^{2^2/2} - 2)/2 \\
 &:= 3^3 + (3 \times 333 - 3) \\
 &:= 4 \times 4^4 - 4/4 \\
 &:= (5-5/5)^5 - 5/5 \\
 &:= (((6+6)/6)^{(66-6)/6} - 6/6) \\
 &:= 7/7 + (7 \times 7 \times (7+7+7) - 7) \\
 &:= 8 \times 8 \times (8+8) - 8/8 \\
 &:= (((9+9)/9)^{9/9+9}) - 9/9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 1024 &:= (1+1)^{11-1} \\
 &:= 2^{2 \times (2+2)+2} \\
 &:= (3-3/3)^{3 \times 3 + 3/3} \\
 &:= 4 \times 4^4 \\
 &:= (5-5/5)^5 \\
 &:= ((6+6)/6)^{(66-6)/6} \\
 &:= (7/7+7) \times ((7+7)/7)^7 \\
 &:= 8 \times 8 \times (8+8) \\
 &:= ((9+9)/9)^{9/9+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 1025 &:= 1 + (1+1)^{11-1} \\
 &:= (2^{2^2/2} + 2)/2 \\
 &:= 3^3 + (3 \times 333 - 3/3) \\
 &:= 4/4 + 4 \times 4^4 \\
 &:= 5/5 + (5-5/5)^5 \\
 &:= 6/6 + (((6+6)/6)^{(66-6)/6}) \\
 &:= 7 + (7 \times 7 \times (7+7+7) - (77/7)) \\
 &:= 8/8 + 8 \times 8 \times (8+8) \\
 &:= 9 + (((999-9/9) + 9) + 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 1026 &:= 1 + 1 + (1+1)^{11-1} \\
 &:= 2 + (2^{2 \times (2+2)+2}) \\
 &:= 3 \times (333+3 \times 3) \\
 &:= (4+4)/4 + 4 \times 4^4 \\
 &:= (5+5)/5 + (5-5/5)^5 \\
 &:= 666 + 6 \times (66-6) \\
 &:= ((7+7+7)/7) \times (7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7/7) \\
 &:= (8+8)/8 + 8 \times 8 \times (8+8) \\
 &:= 9 + (999+9+9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 1027 &:= 1 + 1 + 1 + (1+1)^{11-1} \\
 &:= 2 + ((2^{2^2/2} + 2)/2) \\
 &:= 3^3 + ((3 \times 3 + 3/3)^3) \\
 &:= 4 + (4 \times 4^4 - 4/4) \\
 &:= 5 + ((5-5/5)^5 - ((5+5)/5)) \\
 &:= 6/6 + (6 \times (66-6) + 666) \\
 &:= 7 \times 7 \times (7+7+7) - (7+7)/7 \\
 &:= 88/8 + (8 \times 8 \times (8+8) - 8) \\
 &:= 9 + (((999+9/9) + 9) + 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 1028 &:= 1 + (1+1+1+(1+1)^{11-1}) \\
 &:= 2 + ((2^{2 \times (2+2)+2}) + 2) \\
 &:= (3 \times (((3/3+3) + 3)^3)) - 3/3 \\
 &:= 4 + 4 \times 4^4 \\
 &:= 5 + ((5-5/5)^5 - 5/5) \\
 &:= 666 + (6 \times (66-6) + ((6+6)/6)) \\
 &:= 7 \times 7 \times (7+7+7) - 7/7 \\
 &:= 8 \times 8 \times (8+8) + (8/((8+8)/8)) \\
 &:= 9 + ((99/9+999) + 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 1029 &:= (11 + (1+1)^{11} - 1)/(1+1) \\
 &:= 2 + (((2^{2^2/2} + 2)/2) + 2) \\
 &:= 3 \times (((3/3+3) + 3)^3) \\
 &:= 4 + (4 \times 4^4 + 4/4) \\
 &:= 5 + (5-5/5)^5 \\
 &:= 666 + 66 \times 66/(6+6) \\
 &:= 7 \times 7 \times (7+7+7) \\
 &:= 8 + ((8 \times 8 \times (8+8) - (88/8)) + 8) \\
 &:= ((9999-9)/9) - 9 \times 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 1030 &:= (1+11+(1+1)^{11})/(1+1) \\
 &:= 2 + (((2^{2 \times (2+2)+2}) + 2) + 2) \\
 &:= 3 + (((3 \times 3 + 3/3)^3) + 3^3) \\
 &:= 4 + ((4+4)/4 + 4 \times 4^4) \\
 &:= 5 + ((5-5/5)^5 + 5/5) \\
 &:= 6 + (((6+6)/6)^{(66-6)/6}) \\
 &:= 7/7 + 7 \times 7 \times (7+7+7) \\
 &:= 8 + (8 \times 8 \times (8+8) - ((8+8)/8)) \\
 &:= 9999/9 - 9 \times 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 1031 &:= 1 + (1+11+(1+1)^{11})/(1+1) \\
 &:= 2 + (((2^{2^2/2} + 2)/2) + 2) + 2) \\
 &:= 33 + (3 \times 333 - 3/3) \\
 &:= 4 + ((4 \times 4^4 - 4/4) + 4) \\
 &:= 5 + ((5-5/5)^5 + ((5+5)/5)) \\
 &:= 6 + (((6+6)/6)^{(66-6)/6} + 6/6) \\
 &:= 7 + ((7/7+7) \times ((7+7)/7)^7) \\
 &:= 8 + (8 \times 8 \times (8+8) - 8/8) \\
 &:= (9999+9)/9 - 9 \times 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 1032 &:= 11 + (1+1)^{11-1} - 1 - 1 - 1 \\
 &:= 2 \times (2 \times (2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2)) \\
 &:= 33 + 3 \times 333 \\
 &:= 4 + (4 \times 4^4 + 4) \\
 &:= 5 + (5-5/5)^5 - (5+5)/5 + 5 \\
 &:= 6 + (6 \times (66-6) + 666) \\
 &:= (7/7+7) \times (((7+7)/7)^7 + 7/7) \\
 &:= 8 + 8 \times 8 \times (8+8) \\
 &:= 9 + (((9+9)/9)^{9/9+9}) - 9/9)
 \end{aligned}$$

